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MAVZUSIDAGI RESPUBLIKA
ILMIY-AMALIY ANJUMANI

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TIL BILGAN EL BILADI

Ibroxim G'ULOMOV,
ISFT rektori v.b.

Hurmatli mehmonlar! "International school of finance technology and science" instituti filologiya kafedrasida tomonidan "Tillarni o'qitishda zamonaviy yondashuvlar" mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumaniga xush kelibsiz!

Keyingi yillarda mamlakatimizda xorijiy tillarni o'rgatishni ommalashtirishni yangi bosqichga olib chiqish va sohani rivojlantirish uchun tizimli ishlarni tashkil etish, ulg'ayib kelayotgan yosh avlodni har tomonlama barkamol qilib tarbiyalash, buning uchun barcha shart-sharoitlarni yaratish maqsadida boshqa sohalarda bo'lganidek, oliy ta'lim tizimida ham keng miqyosdagi ishlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Jumladan, dunyo bo'yicha samarali natija bergan o'qitish metodikalari, dastur va darsliklarni oliy ta'lim muassasalarida joriy etish yuzasidan boshqa oliy o'quv yurtlari qatorida institutimizda ham xorijiy davlatlar ta'lim muassasalari bilan hamkorlikning yo'lga qo'yilishi buning yorqin misolidir. Shu yilning fevral oyida ustozlarimiz Turkiya kabi davlatlarning ta'lim tizimi, ulardagi ilg'or pedagogik texnologiyalarni o'rganib qaytgan bo'lsalar, ayni kunlarda bir guruh ustozlar Belarus oliy ta'lim tizimidagi metodika, dastur va darsliklar bilan tanishmoqdalar. Bu ustozlarning katta qismi til mutaxassisleri ekanligi alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi. Chunki bugungi kun yoshlari nafaqat bir, balki kamida 2-3 xorijiy tilni bilishlarini davr taqozo etmoqda.

Bundan bir asrdan ziyod vaqt ilgari ma'rifatparvar shoir Avaz O'tar:

Har tilni biluv emdi bani odama jondur,

Til vositai robitayi olamiyondur,

deb yozgan bo'lsa, Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiyning ***"...Bugun bizlarga to'rt tilga tahrir va taqrir etguvchilar kerak"***, deya murojaat qilishi til o'rganish hamisha xalqimiz ma'naviyatida eng ahamiyatli jihatlardan biri ekaniga ishoradir.

Yurtimiz Buyuk ipak yo'lining markaziy nuqtalaridan biri bo'lgani, otabobolarimizning arabiy, forsiy tillarini turkiy til kabi mukammal egallagani til o'rganish biz uchun nafaqat bugungi kun talabi, balki zarurat ekanligini ko'rsatadi.

Biz zullisonayn adiblar bo'lgan Mavlono Lutfiy, hazrat Alisher Navoiy, Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur, Nodirabegim, Boborahim Mashrab, Jahon otin Uvaysiydek fozil va fozilalar avlodimiz. Bizning tomirlarimizda buyuk allomalar qoni oqmoqda. Ularning ma'naviy merosini davom ettirish barobarida ommalashib borayotgan xorijiy tilni o'rganishga ham, o'rgatishga ham e'tibor berishimiz lozim.

Shuni alohida qayd etish lozimki, har qanday xorijiy tilni mukammal egallash o'z tilini chuqur anglashdan boshlanadi. Chunki ona tilini yo'qotgan xalq o'zligini, milliy ruhini yo'qotadi. Davlatimiz rahbari Sh.M.Mirziyoyev ona tilimizga: **"O'zbek tili xalqimiz uchun milliy o'zligimiz va mustaqil davlatchilik timsoli, bebaho ma'naviy boylik, buyuk qadriyatdi"**, deya juda yuksak baho bergan edi.

Bu yerga yig'ilgan barcha olimlarimizni, muxtasar qilib aytganda til fidoyilarini bugungi anjuman bilan ISFT jamoasi nomidan qutlaymiz va yana bir bor institutimizga xush kelibsiz, deymiz.

"Tillarni o'qitishda zamonaviy yondashuvlar" mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyamizni ochiq deb e'lon qilaman.

I. TIL NAZARIYASI VA AMALIYOTI SHU'BASI

YANGI LUG'ATLAR – O'ZBEK LUG'ATSHUNOSLIGI TARAQQIYOTINING KO'ZGUSI

Durdona XUDAYBERGANOVA,
O'zbek tili, adabiyoti va folklori instituti
bo'lim mudiri, filologiya fanlari doktori, professor

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются новые толковые словари узбекского языка, принципы их составления и роль словарей в развитии узбекского языкознания.

Ключевые слова: узбекская лексикография, толковый словарь, словарь синонимов, отраслевой словарь, синоним, синонимический ряд, лингвистический термин.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2020-yil 20-oktyabrdagi "Mamlakatimizda o'zbek tilini yanada rivojlantirish va til siyosatini takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi PF-6084-sonli Farmonida "...o'zbek tilining lug'at boyligini oshiruvchi lingvistik, sohaviy-terminologik, izohli lug'atlar yaratish" [1] ga doir begilab berilgan vazifalar hamda mazkur farmon asosida qabul qilingan "2020-2030- yillarda o'zbek tilini rivojlantirish va til siyosatini takomillashtirish konsepsiyasini 2020-2022-yillarda amalga oshirish dasturi" [2] o'zbek lug'atshunosligida bir qator jiddiy lug'atlarning yaratilishida muhim rol o'ynadi. Ta'kidlash joizki, O'zR FA O'zbek tili, adabiyoti va folklori instituti olimlari mazkur farmonda belgilangan lug'atlarni tayyorlashda juda katta hissa qo'shdilar.

Mazkur farmon asosida tayyorlangan lug'atlardan biri O'zR FA O'zbek tili, adabiyoti va folklori instituti olimlari tomonidan yaratilgan olti jildli "O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati" [3] hisoblanadi. Bu lug'at uning lotin yozuviga asoslangan o'zbek alifbosida tayyorlangan dastlabki nashri hisoblanadi. Lug'atda hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tilida keng qo'llanayotgan 80 mingdan ortiq so'z va turg'un so'z birikmalarining lug'aviy ma'nolari izohlangan. Ushbu lug'aviy birliklar fan, texnika, san'at va madaniyat sohalarida qo'llanuvchi terminlarni, o'zbek xalq shevalariga doir so'zlarni, ayrim tarixiy va eskirgan atamalarni o'z ichiga oladi. Lug'at annotatsiyasida qayd qilinganidek, u "o'zbek tilshunosligi va turkiyshunoslik bo'yicha mutaxassislar, tarjimonlar, ommaviy axborot vositalari xodimlari, oliy ta'lim muassasalarining o'qituvchilari va talabalari, shuningdek, keng o'quvchilar ommasi uchun mo'ljallangan" [3; 4].

Mazkur lug'at 2020-yilda "O'zbekiston" nashriyoti davlat unitar korxonasida chop qilingan izohli lug'atning to'ldirilgan va qayta ishlangan nashri hisoblanadi. Lug'atning mazkur yangi nashri 3000 dan ziyod yangi lug'aviy birlik bilan to'ldirilgan bo'lib, ular o'zbek xalq shevalari, xalq so'zlashuv tilidan hamda boshqa davlatlar bilan o'zaro iqtisodiy, siyosiy, madaniy aloqalar natijasida o'zbek tiliga xorijiy tillardan kirib kelgan so'zlardan iborat. Shuningdek, lug'at juda ko'p illyustrativ misollar bilan ham boyitildi, so'zlar ma'nosining izohlari takomillashtirildi. Ushbu lug'atda keyingi davr o'zbek tili lug'aviy tarkibida sodir bo'lgan ma'noviy o'zgarishlar ko'rsatib berildi.

Olti jildidan iborat "O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati" avval nashr etilgan ikki jildli izohli lug'at materiallaridan tanqidiy foydalangan holda, o'zbek va jahon lug'atchiligining yangi, ijobiy yutuqlarini, O'zbekiston mustaqilligi yillarida hayotimizda ro'y bergan tub o'zgarishlar va shu munosabat bilan o'zbek tili lug'at tarkibida paydo bo'lgan yangidan yangi so'z va terminlarni e'tiborga olib yaratilgan lug'atdir.

Olti jildli "O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati" o'zbek tilini yanada rivojlantirish uchun, o'zbek tili va o'zbek tilshunosligining nafaqat respublikamizdagi, balki xorijdagi, butun dunyodagi nufuzi, obro'-e'tiborini oshirish uchun xizmat qiladi.

Yuqorida qayd qilingan farmon asosida institut olimlari ikki jilddan iborat "O'zbek tili sinonimlarining katta izohli lug'ati" ni ham yaratdilar [3]. Ma'lumki, "O'zbek tili sinonimlarining izohli lug'ati" birinchi marta 1974-yilda akademik Azim Hojiyev tomonidan yaratilgan. Ushbu lug'atning so'zlik hajmi nisbatan kam qamrovli bo'lib, "O'zbek tili sinonimlarining katta izohli lug'ati"ni yaratish o'zbek tilshunosligi oldida turgan muhim vazifalardan biri edi. 2022-yilda nashr qilingan "O'zbek tili sinonimlarining katta izohli lug'ati"da birinchi marta ona tilimizdagi so'zlarning ma'noviy nozikliklarini ko'rsatuvchi sinonim so'zlar to'laqonli tarzda leksikografik yondashuvda tadqiq qilindi. Lug'at hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tilida mavjud bo'lgan sinonimik qatorlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Ta'kidlash joizki, lug'at tuzuvchilari jiddiy izlanishlar olib borib, unga o'zbek xalq shevalari, tarixiy qatlamga oid sinonim so'zlarni ham kiritdilar. Lug'atda sinonimik qatordagi so'zlarning o'zaro ma'noviy munosabatlari, bu ma'noviy farqlanishlarni yuzaga keltiruvchi jihatlar, sinonimlarning funksional uslublarga munosabati yoritilgan, sinonimik qatorlardan o'rin olgan so'zlarning ma'no nozikliklarini hamda tilda qo'llanishini dalillovchi illyustrativ misollar keltirilgan. Lug'atdan o'zbek tilshunosligi va turkiyshunoslik bo'yicha tadqiqot olib borayotgan mutaxassislar, oliy ta'lim muassasalarining o'qituvchilari va talabalari, tarjimonlar, ijodkorlar, umuman, o'zbek tilining o'ziga xos jihatlariga qiziquvchi shaxslar foydalanishlari mumkin.

2023-yilda ushbu lug'at ixchamlashtirilgan va umumta'lim maktablari o'quvchilari hamda akademik litseylar talabalariga moslashtirilgan holda "O'zbek tili sinonimlarning izohli lug'ati" nomi ostida nashr qilindi [4]. O'quvchilarning o'z ona tili boyligini o'zlashtirishlarida, shuningdek, "Ma'nodosh so'zlar" mavzusini o'rganishlarida ushbu lug'atning ahamiyati juda katta.

O'ZR FA O'zbek tili, adabiyoti va folklori instituti olimlari yuqorida qayd qilingan farmonda belgilangan lug'atlardan tashqari yana bir qancha lug'atlarni ham tuzib o'quvchilar hukmiga havola etdilar. Shunday lug'atlardan biri shu yilning boshida nashr qilingan "Zamonaviy tilshunoslik terminlarining izohli lug'ati" hisoblanadi [5].

O'zbek tilshunosligida shakllangan va shakllanib borayotgan yangi sohalar, yangi yo'nalishlar natijasida ushbu fan terminologiyasidan o'rin olgan yangi terminlarning leksikografik talqini va tadqiqini amalga oshirish bugungi kunning dolzarb vazifalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Hozirgi vaqtda ilmiy tadqiqot olib borayotgan filolog mutaxassislarda tilshunosligimizda yangi paydo bo'lgan terminlarning izohli lug'atiga katta ehtiyoj bor. Bunday lug'at oliy o'quv yurtlari talabalari va magistrilariga ham zarur bo'lmoqda. Qator oliy o'quv yurtlarida zamonaviy tilshunoslik yo'nalishlari bilan bog'liq fanlar, maxsus kurslarni o'qitish yo'lga qo'yilgan. Ushbu lug'at ana shu zarurat natijasida shakllantirilgan bo'lib, unda zamonaviy tilshunoslikka doir pragmalogiyistik, sotsiolingvistika, kognitiv tilshunoslik, lingvomadaniyatshunoslik, assotsiativ tilshunoslik, psixolingvistika, matn tilshunosligi, diskursshunoslik, medialingvistika sohalarining asosiy terminlari izohlangan. Lug'atni yaratishda taniqli o'zbek tilshunoslarining asarlaridan, xorijiy ilmiy adabiyotlar, turli lingvistik terminlarning izohli lug'atlaridagi ma'lumotlardan foydalanildi. Shuningdek, o'zbek tilshunosligida 20-asrning so'nggi choragi hamda XXI asrning dastlabi o'n yilliklarida yaratilgan tadqiqotlarga murojaat qilindi. Lug'atda zamonaviy izohli lug'atlardagi usullar qo'llangan. Ko'plab terminlarning leksikografik talqini ilk marta amalga oshirilayotganini nazarda tutgan holda ayrim terminlarga doir lug'at maqolalariga mutaxassislarning bu boradagi muhim qarashlari qo'shimcha ma'lumot sifatida kiritildi. Ayrim munozarali terminlarning izohiga aniqlik kiritish, xorijdan to'g'ridan to'g'ri qabul qilingan yangi olinma terminlarning o'zbekcha muqobillarini yaratish, dublet terminlarning asosiy variantlari tanlab olish, terminlarni tartibga solish ishlariga alohida e'tibor qaratildi. Lug'at so'ngida foydalanuvchilarga qulaylik yaratish maqsadida kognitiv tilshunoslik, pragmalogiyistik, lingvomadaniyatshunoslik, sotsiolingvistika, assotsiativ tilshunoslik, medialingvistika, matnshunoslik, metaforashunoslik kabi lingvistik sohalar va yo'nalishlarning guruhlashtirilgan tarzda ko'rsatkichi ilova qilindi. Lug'at zamonaviy tilshunoslik masalalari doirasida izlanish olib borayotgan filolog mutaxassislar, tadqiqotchilar, doktorant va magistrantlarga mo'ljallangan.

Bu kabi lug'atlarning ko'psonli adadda nashr qilinishida O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasi huzuridagi O'zbek tilini rivojlantirish jamg'armasining moddiy jihatdan qo'llab-quvvatlashi katta rol o'ynadi. Yuqoridagi lug'atlarning barchasi mana shu jamg'armaning mablag'lari hisobidan nashr etilgan.

Xulosa tarzida aytish mumkinki, keyingi yillarda nashr qilingan qator lug'atlar o'zbek lug'atshunosligining yanada taraqqiy etganligini ko'rsatadi. Bu lug'atlar, shubhasiz, o'zbek xalqining intellektual darajasini ko'tarishga, dunyoqarashini boyitishga, o'zbek tilining dunyodagi eng boy tillardan biri ekanligini ko'rsatishga xizmat qiladi.

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ERKALASHNI IFODA ETUVCHI LEKSIK BIRLIKLAR ETIMOLOGIYASI

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Аннотация. Целью данной статьи является изучение на примере английского и узбекского языков этимологии языковых единиц, выражающих ласку. В данную статью включены результаты исследований происхождения ласкательных слов и выражений в английском и узбекском языках, а также их заимствованные эквиваленты.

Ключевые слова: ласкание, английский и узбекский языки, этимология, анализ словарей, ласкательное значение.

Ma'lumki, tillarning ichki rivojlanishi ichki va tashqi qonuniyatlarga bo'ysunadi, ya'ni o'zaro hamkorlik jarayonida tillar taraqqiyoti ichki qonunlar ta'sirida emas, balki tashqi ta'sirga ko'proq bog'liq bo'ladi. Mamlakatlararo aloqalarning rivojlanishi mazkur mamlakatlarda yashovchi xalq va elat madaniyatining bir-biriga yaqinlashuviga shart-sharoitlar yaratib beradi. Tillar ham bir-biriga ta'sir ko'rsatib boyib boradi; bunday hamkorlik tillarning ichki rivojlanishiga ham sabab bo'ladi [2; 157].

F. De Sossyur tashqi va ichki lingvistikani qarama-qarshi qo'yadi. Uning fikricha, tashqi va ichki tilshunoslikda til xalq tarixi, geografik joylashishi bilan bog'lab tekshirilishi lozim [5; 90-91].

Har bir til leksikasining ma'lum foizi boshqa tillardan o'zlashgan bo'ladi. Uning ayrimlari o'zining ajnabiy bo'yog'ini yo'qotib, xuddi o'zinikidek tuyuladi, ayrimlari esa fonetik, grammatik yoki semantik o'ziga xosligi-yu, g'ayritabiyligi bilan yot so'zligicha qoladi [1; 117].

Ingliz tilida zamon taqozosi bilan ispan, italyan, fransuz, ivrit va rus tillaridan o'zlashtirilgan suffikslar ishtirokidagi so'zlar ko'pchilikni tashkil qiladi. Masalan, ispan tilidan -o suffiksi (kidd-o, buddy-o, daddy-o, boy-o,) so'zlarga qo'shilib ifoda etiladi [4; 85-87].

Tadqiqotimiz natijalaridan qiyoslanayotgan tillarga aynan chetdan o'zlashtirilgan so'zlar ham erkalash ma'nosini ifoda etuvchi so'zlarga o'z ta'sirini ko'rsatganligi aniqlandi. Masalan, Webster lug'atining ma'lumot berishicha [197], ingliz tiliga fransuz tilidan minion (suyukli), beau (go'zalim), belle (go'zalim), ispan tilidan caballerro (kavaler), italyan tilidan nymph (qizgina), courtesan (asira), cicibeo (sevgilim), charlatan (shayton), Inamorato (sevgilim), Inamorata (sevgilim), arab tilidan esa peri (parivash), sheik (sulton) kabi erkalash ma'nosini ifoda etuvchi leksik birliklar kirib kelgan. Fikrimizni misollar bilan to'ldiramiz:

Kiss me, kiss me my sweet Inamorata

You are a symphony a very beautiful sonata my Inamorata [11].

O'zbek tilining izohli lug'atidan olingan ma'lumotga ko'ra, mazkur tilga fors-tojik tilidan gulandom, gulbadan, devona, dilbar, jigar, jonivor, nigor, mahliqo, pariroy va shu kabi boshqa so'zlar, arab tilidan mahbuba, mahbub, ofatijon, farishta, xumor, javhar, muhabbat, jinni, ma'shuqam, habib kabi so'zlar o'zlashgan. To'plangan misollar rus tilidagi -ishka, -chik, -ka erkalash affiksleri o'zbek tilida ot so'z turkumiga qo'shilib, nutqda erkalashni ifodalashini ko'rsatdi (Asalishka, asalchik, asalka, Xayrishka, Boburchik, ponchik, Nargizka va b.). E. Qilichev bu borada shunday deydi: "O'zbek tilida, ayniqsa, yoshlar nutqida ba'zan erkalashning ruscha shakllari uchraydi: Nazarchik (Nazar), Lolyachka (Lola), Adik (Adiba) kabi. Ayrim ruscha shakllar erkalash shakllari bilan sinonim tarzda ham ishlatilmoqda:

Dedilar bir yig'inda, kerakmas hech xon demoq,

Xayrixonning o'rniga Xayrichkasi yaxshiroq" [8; 21].

R.R. Xadyatullaevning ta'kidlashicha, -jon suffiksi ba'zida ruscha atoqli ismlariga qo'shilib keladi (Sashajon, Ivanjon kabi) [6; 75].

O'zbek tilida juda asalsan degan fikr ba'zi hollarda rus tilidagi вообщем so'zining o'zbekcha talaffuz etilishi orqali, ya'ni vabshe asalsan kabi ko'rinishda ham so'zlashuv nutqida uchrashi kuzatildi.

Demak, ingliz tiliga ispan, italyan, fransuz, arab tillari EFSMni shakllanishida o'z ta'sirini ko'rsatgan bo'lsa, o'zbek tilida esa arab, fors-tojik, rus tillaridan mazkur mavzuga tegishli so'zlar o'zlashganligini kuzatish mumkin.

Erkalash ma'nosini ifoda etuvchi leksik birliklarning etimologik chegaraga doir tahlili jarayonida mazkur maydon doirasidagi leksik birliklarning tarixiylik jihatlari ham o'rganib chiqildi. Ma'lumki, tarixan so'zlar yangi va eskirgan bo'lishi mumkin. Erkalashning eskirgan so'zlar guruhiga kiruvchi qismi tadqiq etilayotgan tillarning har ikkida ham uchradi. Masalan, ingliz tilidagi Webster izohli lug'ati [7; 21-975] erkalashni ifoda etuvchi pumpkin, sweeting, leman, mistress, moppet, brave, chit kabi so'zlarni eskirgan, arxaiik so'zlar qatoriga kiritadi. Oxford Thesaurus lug'atidagi ma'lumotlarga ko'ra esa [10; 605], swain, concubine, doxy, leman, courtesan, cicibeo kabi so'zlar ham nutq faoliyatidagi eskirgan so'zlar hisoblanadi. So'rovnomalar natijasiga ko'ra, bo, boyfriend, fiance, chum, chap, wench kabi erkalash ma'nosini ifoda etuvchi leksik birliklar nutq faoliyatidan chetlashib borayotganligi aniqlandi.

O'zbek tilining izohli lug'atida asira, begoyim, begim, boyvuchcha, bibish, buzrukvor, volida, qoqindiq kabi erkalash ma'nosini ifoda etuvchi leksik birliklarning lug'aviy izohida nutq faoliyatida eskirganligini ko'rsatuvchi pometalar mavjud. Malika, malak, xonzoda kabi so'zlar tarixda aslida podshohlar oilasiga mansub shaxslarga qarata aytilgan bo'lsa-da, hozirgi kunda o'zbek tilining adabiy va so'zlashuv tilida suyish va erkalash ma'nolarida sevikli yorlarga nisbatan ifoda etib kelinadi. Masalan:

Sen ko'kdagi malagim, men yerda yupun, xorman,

Sevarmi deb so'radim, yoqqan har zarra qordan [3; 104].

Xon Odilbikani yupantirmoqqa boshladi:

– Parizodam, malikam, qo'ying, eshinni o'zim o'ldiraman... [7; 314]

O'zbek tilida bu kabi erkalash ma'nosini ifoda etuvchi leksik birliklar insonlar tabaqasiga qaratib ifoda etiladi deyish noto'g'ri, albatta. Ular tilda asl ma'nosida ifoda etilmasdan, balki erkalash, hurmat ma'nolarini ko'chim orqali ifodalaydi. Qolaversa, o'zbek tilining izohli lug'atida o'g'il bolalarga qulun so'zi erkalash ma'nosini ifodalashi haqida ma'lumot berilsa-da, hozirgi kunda bu so'z nutqda qo'llanilmaydi.

R.R. Xadyatullaevning fikricha, -choq, -chuq, -chiq, -chak erkalash-kichraytirish suffiksleri hozirgi o'zbek tilida sub'ektiv bahoni ifoda etishi sezilmay qolmoqda [6; 72].

Lekin, bizning fikrimizcha, mazkur suffikslar qoʻshilgan qoʻzichoq, toychoq, kelinchak, yupanchiq kabi soʻzlar hali ham oʻzbek tilida erkalash va kichraytirish maʼnolarini ifoda etadi.

Erkalashning sotsiolingvistik xususiyatlari borasida olib borilgan tahlillarga koʻra, ingliz va oʻzbek tillarida erkalash maʼnosini ifoda etuvchi soʻzlar, soʻz birikmalari va frazeologik birliklar umumxalq va kichik guruhlar tomonidan ifoda etilishi aniqlandi. Qon-qarindoshlik doirasida, doʻstona, yaqin munosabatlarda, sevishganlar nutqida, shevada, adabiy va soʻzlashuv tillari normalarida hamda yosh jihatdan erkalashning ifoda etilishi bir-biriga qardosh boʻlmagan tillarda misollar orqali izohlandi. Etimologik chegaralanishga koʻra, erkalash chet tillardan oʻzlashgan leksik birliklar va suffikslar orqali ifodalanishi bilan xarakterlanadi. Tarixiylik jihatlariga koʻra, mazkur soʻzlarning baʼzi qismi vaqt oʻtishi bilan nutq faoliyatidan chetlashib boradi. Erkalash yoʻnaltirilgan obyektga koʻra esa hayvonot dunyosi, oʻsimliklar olami, osmon jismlari, vaqtni anglatuvchi otlar, jonsiz predmetlar, tabiat hodisalariga nisbatan ifoda etilishi aniqlandi. Ingliz va oʻzbek xalqlari ijtimoiy hayot tarzida roʻy beradigan hodisalar erkalash maʼnosini ifoda etuvchi leksik birliklarning shakllanishiga oʻz taʼsirini koʻrsatadi. Mazkur tillarda erkalash insonni oʻrab turgan tabiatning barcha vakillariga nisbatan ifoda etilishi aniqlandi. Ingliz tilida erkalash maʼnosini ifodalashda, asosan, soʻzlar oldiga sweet soʻzini hamda soʻzlarga -ie, -y kabi suffikslar qoʻshib ifodalansa, oʻzbek tilida erkalashning ifoda etilishi ingliz tilidan farqli oʻlaroq, juda keng grammatik, suffiksial qamrovni oʻz ichiga oladi.

Xalqning tarixi va ijtimoiy hayot faoliyati erkalash maʼnosini ifoda etuvchi leksik birliklarning shakllanishida hamda nutqda qoʻllanilishida oʻz aksini topadi. Bu esa til birliklari va ularning maʼnolariga kognitiv lingvistika nuqtai nazaridan qarashning naqadar ahamiyatli ekanligini bildiradi.

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ONA TILI – MILLATNING RUHI

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Аннотация. В данной статье приведены размышления автора о национальном языке, культурно значимых единицах языка – пословиц, фразеологизмов, афоризмов, преобразованиях и изменениях в лексике современного узбекского языка; даны рекомендации лингвиста о языковом воспитании в семье.

Ключевые слова: национальный язык, пословица, фразеологизм, заимствование, неологизм, языковое воспитание, языковая культура.

Bu ko'hna dunyoda millat deb atalmish birlik borki, uning ong-u shuuri dunyoni, undagi necha ming, balki undan-da ortiq sir-u sinoat, tilsim-u tilsimotlarni til orqali idrok etadi, xalq tarixining olis o'tmishida qolib ketgan qadriyatlarni sohibiga ham shu til yetkazadi. O'zbek tilining mo'tabar manbalari bo'lgan "Bitiktosh"lar, "Devonu lug'otit turk", "Qutadg'u bilig", "Devoni hikmat"dek asarlar ham ona tilining buyuk xizmati tufayli xalqimiz tafakkurini boyitib kelmoqda. Tilning, shu jumladan, ona tilining favqulodda qudrati "Yuksak ma'naviyat – yengilmas kuch" asarida shunday ifodalanadi: "O'zlikni anglash, milliy ong va tafakkurning ifodasi, avlodlar o'rtasidagi ruhiy-ma'naviy bog'liqlik til orqali namoyon bo'ladi. Jamiki ezgu fazilatlar inson qalbiga, avvalo, ona allasi, ona tilining betakror jozibasi bilan singadi. Ona tili – bu millatning ruhidir" [1; 83].

Tabiiyki, bu bebaho meros shu xalq bilan birga yashab, birga taraqqiy etadi. Ana shu rivojlanish jarayonida ba'zi milliy an'analar unutilishi, esdan chiqishi mumkin. Ba'zilar esa, aksincha, yana-da rivojlanish, yangirish, ta'bir joiz bo'lsa, zamonaviylik kasb etishi – bor gap. Albatta, ayni ikki evrilishning birinchisi – u yoki bu milliy an'ananing yo'qlikka yuz tutishi xalq ma'naviy dunyosiining kemtik bo'lib qolishiga, benihoya betakror milliy o'zi xoslikning zaiflashuviga olib keladi. Milliy urf-odat va an'analarning saqlanishi, rivojlanishi esa xalq ma'naviyatining yuksalishiga, dunyo ayvonida barqaror turmog'iga, millat "menligining" ramzi sifatida yashashiga zamin hozirlaydi. Ona tili ana shunday qadriyatlarning oliy shaklidir, desak mubolag'a bo'lmaydi. Zotan, ona tili unda so'zlovchi kishilarning o'zini, o'zligini namoyon etadi. Bugun mustaqil davlatimiz va davlatchiligimiz sharofati bilan ona tilimiz bo'lgan o'zbek tilining huquqiy maqomi tiklandi, qonuniy muxofazasi ta'minlandi. Butun umrini tilning olis tarixini o'rganishga bag'ishlagan zahmatkash tilshunos Ergash Umarovning aytishicha, Sibir o'lkasida yashovchi turkiy xalqlar, xususan, yoqut, tuva, xakas tillari tamoman yo'qolib yoki unutilish ketish arafasida turibdi, chunki unda so'zlovchi kishilarning soni borgan sari kamayib bormoqda, globallashuv deya ta'riflanayotgan davrning buhronlarida qolib ketmoqda. Yaratganga shukrlar bo'lsinki, o'zbek tilining millionlar bilan o'lchanadigan sohibi – so'zlovchisi bor.

Milliy ma'naviyatimizning tiniq tajassumi, ayniqsa, ajdodlardan avlodlarga o'tib kelayotgan, o'zga tillardan aynan ifodasini topib bo'lmaydigan maqol va matallar, hikmatli so'z-u ibora atalmish qayroqi so'zlarda betakror injaliklar bilan ifodalanadi. Masalan, "Toza ko'zaning suvi toza", "Ahmoqning aqli to'pig'ida", "Beli og'rimaganning non yeyishini ko'r", "O'n qatim o'yla, bir qatim so'yla", "O'ylab gapirsang ham o'ylab gapir", "Dono bilan nodon bir buloqdan suv ichmas" kabi maqollar; "Alifni kaltak deydi", "Igna tashlasang, yerga tushmaydi", "Attorning qutisida ham yo'q gaplar" singari matallar; "boshi ko'kka yetmoq", "ko'zi to'rt bo'lmoq", "o'pkasini cho'pga ilgan", "bir yoqadan bosh chiqarmoq", "ko'nglida kiri yo'q", "og'ziga qatiq ivitmoq" tarzidagi qayroqi iboralar, "Vatan – onaning ko'ksidan boshlanadi", "Vatan yuki zalvarli bo'lsa ham maloli yo'q", "Ilm kelinchakka o'xshaydi, u hikmat va pinhoniyligni yoqtiradi", "Adabiyot yashasa, millat yashar" kabi hikmatlarda o'zbekona ruh, tajribaning tarang mantigi barq urib turadi. Ular namoyon etadigan ma'nomazmunni o'zbek turmush tarzidan ayro holda tasavvur qilib ham, tushuntirib ham bo'lmaydi.

Bugun O'zbekiston dunyoning barcha mamlakatlari bilan ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, madaniy-ma'naviy sohalarda teng huquqli munosabat o'rnatib kelmoqda. Shu bois bir qator davlatlarning universitet-u ilmiy markazlarida

o'zbek tilini o'rganuvchilar soni oshib, o'zbek tilini ilmiy o'rganishga bag'ishlangan tadqiqotchilar safi kengaymoqda. Masalan, AQSh, Germaniya, Xitoy, Janubiy Koreya davlatlarining oliy o'quv yurtlarida o'zbek tilini ilmiy-amaliy jihatdan o'rganayotgan, o'rgatayotganlarning soni salmoqli. Ayni paytda yurtimizda ham xorijiy xalqlar madaniyatini rivojlantirish, boyitish maqsadida tashkil etilgan milliy-madaniy markazlarning faoliyat yuritishi uchun keng imkoniyatlar yaratib berilgan. Buning yaqqol namunasi sifatida yangidan qad rostlagan O'zbekiston Milliy kutubxonasi negizida tashkil etilgan "Koreya oynasi" nomli koreys tili o'rgatish markazini ko'rsatish mumkin.

Xalqaro hamkorlik va fan-texnika taraqqiyotining tabiiy mahsuli sifatida o'zbek tilining lug'at tarkibi ham yangi-yangi tushunchalarning ifodasi bo'lgan o'zlashma so'zlar bilan boyimoqda. Turmushning turli sohalariga oid bu so'zlarni o'zlashtirishda me'yor asosiy mezon bo'lib turibdi. Ayniqsa, axborot texnologiyalari sohasiga juda ko'plab yangi tushuncha va so'zlar kirib keldiki, bu shu sohaning rivoji, jamiyatning tabiiy ehtiyoji, talabi, taqozosi bilan bog'liq. Masalan, internet, sayt, veb sayt, fleshka, brauzer, provayder, gigabayt, megabayt kabi lisoniy birliklar tildan muqim o'rin egalladi, o'zbek xalqining konseptual manzarasida bu so'zlar ifodalaydigan tushunchalar muqimlashdi.

Internet jurnalistikasining asta-sekin shakllanib borishi bilan bevosita ayni soha so'zlari ham tilimizga kirib kelmoqda. Masalan, ingliz tilidan aynan o'zlashgan blog ("egasi tomonidan matnli, tasvirli yoki multimediali axborot bilan muntazam to'ldirib boriladigan veb sahifa [2; 507-508]"; "onlayn-kundalik" – O'zining shaxsiy veb sayti va blogiga ega bo'lishni istagan yosh jurnalistlar uchun zarur tavsiyalar berildi. (Turkiston, 2015, 20 iyun), blogger ("ijtimoiy-siyosiy, iqtisodiy va boshqa tUSDagi axborotni ommaviy muhokama uchun Internet tarmog'idagi veb sahifasiga joylashtiruvchi jismoniy shaxs; blog muallifi, blog yurituvchi shaxs [2; 508]" – Mamlakatimizda ijtimoiy mas'uliyatli bloggerlarni rag'batlantirishga katta e'tibor berib kelinmoqda. (Turkiston, 2015, 17 iyun), blogpost (odamlarning o'qishi uchun mo'ljallab muayyan shaxs blogida e'lon qilingan xabar, maqola va boshqa yozma asar [3]" – Uni [Nosirni] finalga olib chiqqan "Immunitet" nomli blogpostini islom niqobi ostida faoliyat olib borayotgan turli diniy oqimlar ning kirdikorlarini ochishga qaratilgan. (Turkiston, 2015, 17 iyun) kabilar shular jumlasidandir.

Ona tilimizning ichki imkoniyatlariga tayanib, yangi so'zlar yaratish va so'z yoki ibora ma'no qamrovining yangi ma'nolar bilan boyishi ham tilning tabiiy ehtiyojidir. O'zbek tili lug'at tarkibi ana shunday so'zlar hisobiga rivojlanib borayotgani hech kimga sir emas. Ommaviy axborot vositalari ko'p va xo'p qo'llanayotgan modernizatsiyalamoq, globallashtirish, integratsiyalashmoq, legallashtirish, liberallashtirish, kreditlash yoki aviabozor, aviakorxonalar, aviata'shuv, aviaxodim, aviaqatnov; mediata'lim, mediamahsulot, mediamarkaz, mediamadaniyat, mediasavodxonlik kabi so'zlar o'zbek tilining ichki imkoniyati asosida hosil qilingan.

O'zbek tili leksikasi alohida so'zlardan tashqari bir qator birikma nomlar bilan ham kengayib bormoqda. Masalan, vakolatli davlat organlari, o'zini o'zi boshqarish organlari, xususiy tadbirkorlik subyekti, kichik biznes vakillari, ishbilarmon doiralari kabilar o'zbek tilining ifoda imkoniyatlari kengayib borayotganligini ko'rsatadi.

Til mohiyati e'tibori bilan insonga naf keltirishga xizmat qiladi. O'z navbatida, har kishi ona tili sofligi uchun baholi qudrat harakat qilmog'i kerak. Basharti shunday qilmaganda ham, ismi qo'yilgan, ilk bor alla eshitgan tiliga hurmat-u ehtiromini saqlashi, eng kamida, milliy tilining zarariga ishlaydigan harakatlardan tiyilishi lozim. Ammo, taassuf-la aytish mumkinki, ba'zi zamondoshlarimizning ona tiliga bo'lgan bepisand munosabatini ko'rib, yoqangni ushlaysan. Ularning qorishiq tilda muloqot qilayotganidan yoqa ushlaysan, ko'ngildan "bular o'zbekmi?" degan o'y o'tadi. Baraka topgur, agar xorijiy tilni biladigan bo'lsang, marhamat, joyini topib, faqat o'sha tilda gapir. Hech kimning e'tirozi yo'q. Uddasidan chiqmasang, tilingga bepisand bo'lma.

Albatta, bu kabi holatlarni bartaraf etish bir kishining ishi emas. Avvalo, oilada tilga munosabatni to'g'ri yo'lga qo'yib olish kerak. Ota-onaning o'zi farzandiga to'g'ri til tarbiyasi borasida namuna ko'rsatishi zarur. Ta'lim-tarbiya muassasalarida o'qituvchi va murabbiylar ona tiliga bo'lgan munosabat borasida ibrat bo'lmog'i lozim. Xullas, oila, maktab va mahalla hamkorligidagi ishlarning bir qismi sifatida yosh avlodni o'zbekona so'zlashga o'rgatish maqsad qilingan bo'lishi lozim.

Bugun televidenie yoki radioda davlat tilining obro'sini ko'tarish borasida gap ketganda, aksar hollarda ko'cha-ko'ydagi yozuvlarning ajnabiy tilda ekanligi, yoshlarning ona tiliga bepisandligi, fikrini davlat tilida erkin, lo'nda ifoda eta olmayotganligidan yozg'iriladi. Bu – bor gap, ammo meni og'rintiradigan tomoni ularning davlat tilidek katta tushunchani faqat shu holatida tasavvur qilayotganlari, tushunayotganlaridir.

Menimcha, muammoni bu tarzda ko'rsatish, ta'rifini keltirib sanayverish, muammoning sababiga ta'sir etishni chetga surib qo'yib, aybdorni topishdek muddao bilan maydonga chiqaverish bilan ish bitmaydi. Mabodo shunday bo'lganida, bugun bizda davlat tilining nufuzi, amaliyotga joriy etilishi borasida birorta muammo bo'lmas edi.

Muammoning sabablari sifatida quyidagilarni ko'rsatib o'tish mumkin:

Birinchidan: o'zga tilni afzal ko'rayotgan, o'zbekcha gapira olmayotgan fuqarolarimizda ma'naviy o'lchov kichik. Ma'naviy o'lchovning kichikligi shundaki, ular chet tilida so'zlashni madaniyatlilik deb biladilar. Biz yurtdoshlarimiz, millatdoshlarimizning shuuriga tortilgan "parda"larni (buning sabablari ko'p, albatta) sirib tashlashdan ishni boshlashimiz, madaniyatlilik, ma'naviyatlilik aslida kishining ona tiliga hurmati bilan belgilanishini, davlat tiliga bepisandlik hamma zamonda, hamma joyda madaniyatsizlik, ma'naviyatsizlik sanalishini tushuntirishimiz, bunday o'g'itni bolalikdayoq bolalar qulog'iga quyishimiz kerak.

Ikkinchidan: oilada til tarbiyasining noto'g'ri yo'lga qo'yilganligi, lisoniy muhitning o'zbekcha emasligidir. "Qush inida ko'rganini qiladi" deyilgani bejiz emas, ota-ona tutumining g'arbchaligi, ota-ona nutqining quramaligi yoki muomalada yot tilni afzal ko'rayotganligi farzandni ham shunday tutumda yashashga, shunday lahjada chuldirashga o'rgatmoqda. Bunday muhitda o'sayotgan bola olamni o'ta milliy andazada emas, o'ta g'arbcha yoki qurama lisonda anglashga odatlanmoqda. Agar ota-ona farzandiga milliy tutum, milliy til namunasini ko'rsata bilsa, bolada milliy tutum, milliy til layoqati birkir shakllanadi. Ajdodlarimiz xo'bbilib aytgan: Qush inida ko'rganini qiladi.

Uchinchidan: uzoq yillar davomida davlat tilida ish yuritishni barcha uchun birdek zaruratga aylantira olmadik. Davlat tili talablarini bir chekkaga surib qo'ysak ham, davlat tilida yozmasak, gapirmasak ham, mushugimizni birov pisht demadi. Aksincha, ayrim korxon va tashkilotlarda ishlash, ishga kirishda davlat tilini puxta bilganlik uchun emas, chet tillardan birini (u rus tilimi, ingliz tilimi, baribir) egallaganlik uchun e'tibor berildi, bu alohida iste'dod sifatida tushunildi.

Davlat tilini bilishni, davlat tilida ish yuritishni zaruratga aylantirish kerak deyishimizning eng sodda tavsifi shuki, agar siz davlat tilida ish yuritmasangiz, yozmasangiz, gapirmasangiz bo'lmaydi, qo'polroq qilib aytganda, ishingiz bitmaydi. Zarurat ehtiyojni keltirib chiqaradi. Bu davlat tilini amaliy hayotimizning eng zaruriy vositasiga aylantiradi-qo'yadi. Dunyoning qaysi davlatiga bormang, yashamang, avvalo, o'sha davlatning tilini o'rganmasangiz kuningiz o'tmaydi. Amerika yoki Xitoy qo'ya turing, qardosh Turkiyada ham kamida turk tilida gapirishni o'rganib olgachgina, ishingiz yurishadi. Hayotiy vaziyat, tabiiy muhit sizni turkcha gapirishga majbur qiladi. Chunki, kerak ekan, bolalar yapon, xitoy tillarini o'rganib, unda biyron gapirmoqdalar. Kerak ekan, bugun "bani o'zbek" ingliz tilini o'rganib, okeanortida tirikchilik qilib yuribdi.

Ushbu uzun qissadan hissa shuki, davlat tili – O'zbekiston otlig' davlatning tili. U qonun bilan himoyalangan. Bu tilning qonuniy talablariga barcha birdek rioya etishi shart, chunki bu tilga bepisandlik, aslida, davlatga bepisandlikdir. Demak, yoshu qarining shuuriga ona tilining muqaddasligi, juda zarur milliylik ekanligini singdira olsak, o'quvchilarda til ta'limi orqali o'zbekona lutf malakasini shakllantira bilsak, jamiyat hayotining turli jabhalarida faqat va faqat davlat tilida ish yuritish kerakligini tushunsak, tushuntirsak, davlat tili millatidan qat'i nazar barchani O'zbekiston xalqi sifatida birlashtirishini anglab olsak bo'ldi, marra bizniki.

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INTERNET OAVDA MEDIKONTENT TILI VA USLUBINING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI

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Аннотация. В данной статье анализируются мнения различных ученых относительно медиаконтента интернет-СМИ и его структурных элементов. Раскрыта важность 360-градусных, цифровых и VR-технологий, дающих эффект виртуальной реальности. Вопрос языка и стиля медиаконтента основан на научно-теоретической точке зрения.

Ключевые слова: интернет-медиа, медиаконтент, язык, стиль, виртуальная реальность, цифровые и VR-технологии, платформа, формат, мультимедиа.

Mediakontent allaqachon rasmi matn degan qarashdan ancha yiroqlashdi. Raqamlashuv va mediakonvergentsiya jarayonlari internet OAV mediakontentini yangicha rakursda taqdim eta boshladi. Natijada global tarmoq foydalanuvchilari yangi tendentsiyalar, innovatsiyalar va, ayniqsa sun'iy intellekt imkoniyatlarini qamrab olgan materiallarni qabul qilmoqda. Foto birlashtirilgan oddiy matn o'rnini endilikda virtual reallik effektini beruvchi 360 darajali, raqamli va VR-texnologiyalar egallamoqda. Fikrimizning amaliy tasdig'i sifatida Rossiyaning "Jurnalist" jurnali "Ta'lim" bo'limi muharriri K.Nigmatullinaning fikrlarini keltirish maqsadga muvofiq: "Media va kommunikasiya sohasi mutaxassisi yozma va nutqiy savodxonlikning an'anaviy ko'nikmalaridan tashqari, media va kommunikasiyalar qanday tashkil etilganligini va kelajakda ular bilan nima bo'lishi mumkinligini tushuniradi. Biz media va raqamli savodxonlikni bilamiz, ba'zi mutaxassislar ma'lumotlar infratuzilmasi, sun'iy intellekt, va, aniqrog'i, ma'lumotlar uzatishning yangi standartlari (hozirda 5G deyiladi) mavjudligini e'tirof etadilar [4].

Russia Beyond bosh muharriri V.Pulya ham 5G tarmoqlari media bozorga qanday ta'sir qilishi haqida fikr bildiradi. Uning aytishicha, 5G – mobil aloqaning beshinchi avlodi. Ushbu mobil standart reklama beruvchilar uchun yangi tarkib, o'quvchilar uchun yangi mediakontent va jurnalistlar uchun yangi vositalarni taqdim etadi. Shuningdek, muallif kontentda quyidagi o'zgarishlarni sanab o'tadi:

– (4k, 8k) formatli yuqori tezlikda striming xizmatlari (katta hajmli videolar) yanada ko'payadi. Kontentni o'sha zahoti yuklab olish imkoniyatlari kengayadi;

– odamlar yanada ko'proq foydalanuvchi tomonidan yaratilgan kontentni suratga olib, uni bir zumda tarmoqqa yuklash imkonini beradi. Jonli efirlar ancha sifatli bo'lganligi bois, ularni ko'rish ehtiyoj ortadi. Hatto 360 darajada aylantirilishi mumkin bo'lgan jonli ko'rsatuvlar ko'payadi;

– ikki qurilma o'rtasida ma'lumot almashishda kechikish deyarli yo'qoladi. Yana bir muhim yangilik past unumli qurilmalardan samarali o'yinlarni o'ynash uchun striming xizmatlarini rivojlantirishga turtki beradi;

– 5G virtual va kengaytirilgan voqelikning striming taraqqiyotiga sabab bo'ladi. Ushbu "og'ir" kontent odatda qurilmaga uzoq yuklab olish orqali tarqatiladi. Aynan 5G esa kontentni har qanday qurilmaga uzatish orqali, texnologiyalarni yanada ommalashuvini ta'minlaydi;

– Mediadagi raqobat distribusiyasi tomonga o'tadi. 5G operatorlari kontent ta'minotchilariga o'z shartlarini etish imkoniyati vujudga keladi. Kabel tarmoqlari va 5G operatorlari o'rtasida konvergent jarayonlar kuzatiladi. Natijada Amazon, Apple, Google kabi texnologik gigantlar ushbu poygada ishtirok etadilar [6].

Biz ham yuqoridagi olimlar bildirgan fikr-mulohazalarga qo'shilib, hozirgi mediakonvergentsiya sharoitida internet OAVning mediakontent tili va uslubi konvergent jarayonlarning integratsiyasi bilan bevosita rivojlanayotganligini kuzatdik. Shu bilan birga, nashriyotlar hozirgi axboriy raqobat va tezkor axborotga egalik qilish sharoitida auditoriya talabini qondirish uchun tezkorlik, interfaollik hamda axborot manbalarining ishonchiligi kabi tamoyillaridan unumli foydalanmoqdalar. Bu esa, yuzer talab qiluvchi axborotning yangi formatlariga boy bo'lgan mediakontentni shakllantirishga zamin yaratadi.

An'anaviy nashriyotlar o'z mediakontentini taqdim etishda yangi media platformalar (radiodan internetgacha, uyali telefon, planshet va ma'lumot ekranlari)dan foydalanishni boshlagan bir paytda jurnalist faoliyatining tabiati o'zgardi. U yanada mobil va ochiq bo'ldi. Jurnalistlar ovoz yozish uskunalari va uydagi

video kameralardan qanday foydalanishni bilsalar ham, ularni xech qachon o'zlarining ishlab chiqarish vositasi deb bilishmagan. Biroq, bugungi kunda ushbu formatlar, ayniqsa, video vositasi ustunlik qilib, tobora ko'proq pullik reklamalarni jalb qilmoqda [2; 30]. Ya'ni ushbu kontekstdagi konvergensiya bir marotabalik ma'lumot va xabarlarini yaratish va ularni turli platformalarda ko'paytirish tamoyiliga asoslangan jarayon sifatida taqdim etiladi. Endilikda ular umumiy axborot mahsulotlarini yaratish jarayonida ishtirok etuvchi transmedia mahsulotlarini yozish, o'zaro axborot almashish, e'lonlar, OAV materiallariga havolalarni taqdim etish tamoyiliga asoslanadi [3; 124].

Internet makonida materiallarni taqdim etish shakllari nafaqat virtual muhitning xususiyatlari, balki o'quvchining xatti-harakati bilan ham belgilanadi. An'anaviy matbuot iste'molchilaridan farqli o'laroq, veb-sahifalarga tashrif buyuruvchilar matn bilan tez tanishishni afzal ko'radilar va alohida qiziqish uyg'otadigan materiallar to'g'risidagi juda ko'p ma'lumotlar to'plami orasidan "tortib olish" tamoyiliga amal qiladilar. Bu haqiqat D.Morks va Ya.Nilson tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqotlar bilan tasdiqlangan. Test ishtirokchilarining 79% har qanday yangi veb-sahifani skanerlaydi va faqat 16% an'anaviy tarzda – so'zma-soz' o'qiydi [1; 99], deb qayd etganlar.

Veb-saytlar va ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda joylashtirish uchun mo'ljallangan mediakontent tez ko'rishga moslashtirilgan bo'lishi va vizual nuqtai nazardan juda jozibadorligi bilan ajralib turishi kerak. Veb-muhitda nashr etilgan mediakontent internet OAVning multimediyaviy imkoniyatlari bo'lgan multimediyaviylik, interfaollik va gipermatnlilikning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini namoyon qilishi kerak. Bundan tashqari, veb-saytlar va ijtimoiy tarmoqlar uchun ma'lumotlarni tayyorlashda matn, fotosuratlar, illyustratsiyalar, audio va video materiallar o'quvchilarning talablarini qondirishi, qiziqish uyg'otishi uchun vizual nuqtai nazardan to'g'ri ishlab chiqilgan ma'lum bir veb-muhitning xususiyatlarini hisobga olish lozim [5; 96-102].

Haqiqatan ham, internet OAVning multimediyaviy imkoniyatlari tarmoq foylanuvchilariga yana ham faol bo'lishlari uchun bir qator yangi qulayliklarni vujudga keltirdi. Bugun, hatto, internet jurnalisti bo'lmagan har qanday kishi tayyor namunalar asosida bir soat ichida veb-sayt yoki bloglarni tashkil etish, yuritish va do'stlashish imkoniyatiga ega. Veb-saytlardagi foto, audio va video materiallarni yuklash, slayd-shou yaratish, katta hamjdagi materiallarni arxivlash, jurnalistika yangi janrlari storitelling va longridlarning ommalashuvi onlayn jurnalistikaning o'ziga xos jihatlarni aks ettiruvchi vositalar sifatida xizmat qilmoqda.

Media-kontentning quyidagi xususiyatlariga alohida e'tibor qaratish lozim:

- Matn ixcham va mazmunli bo'lgan holda axborot mazmuni bilan ajralib turadi. Internet nashr uchun material moslashtirganda, bosma nashrdagi materialga nisbatan matn hajmini 50%ga kamaytirish kerak. Shuning uchun ba'zi ekspertlar onlayn nashrlar uchun matn yozish uslubini qisqartirilgan deb tavsiflaydilar.

- Etkazilgan mazmunning ma'nosini osonroq idrok etish uchun sintaktik tuzilmalarni soddalashtirish.

- "Teskari piramida"ning kompozitsion tamoyilidan foydalanish.

- Ma'lumot beruvchi sarlavha va lid. Bosma nashrda, veb-saytda va ijtimoiy tarmoqdagi postda bir xil maqola har bir axborot uzatish kanalining xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda turli xil sarlavhalarga ega bo'lishi kerak.

- Axborotni tizimlashtirish va diqqatni jam qilish.

- Ma'lumotni tezroq va osonroq qabul qilish uchun raqamlangan va markirovka qilingan ro'yxatlar ko'rinishidagi kichik sarlavhalar va ro'yxatlar qo'llaniladi. Bitta paragraf bitta to'liq fikrni o'z ichiga oladi.

- Giperhavalalardan faol va keng foydalanish.

- Heshteglardan foydalanish (inglizcha: hashtag - hash – "qafas" belgisi + teg - belgi). Ular xabarlarini umumiy hodisalar tasmasiga moslashtiradi va ularni kontekstga joylashtiradi.

Foydalanish maqsadiga ko'ra heshteglarning asosiy xususiyatlari:

- nashrning asosiy g'oyasini shakllantirish uchun kalit so'zlar yoki iboralardan foydalanish;

- axborotni tezkor tematik qidiruvni amalga oshirish;

- mavzu bo'yicha o'quvchini qiziqtiradigan guruh tarkibi.

- Tasviriy materialdan foydalanish.

- Rasmga matnni joylashtirish.

- Matnni video va audio materiallar bilan to'ldirish [5;99-100].

Xulosa tariqasida quyidagilarni qayd etish maqsadga muvofiq:

1. Bosma nashrlarga qaraganda internet OAVda mediakontent tili va uslubi o'ziga xos xususiyatlarga ega. Internet resurslar bilan boyitilgan internet OAVning multimedia platformasi ixchamlik va vizualizatsiya

texnologiyalaridan foydalanishga asoslangan axborotni taqdim etishning yangi, noan'anaviy, ijodiy usullarini talab qilmoqda;

2. Taqdim etilgan xususiyatlarga muvofiq, konvergent jarayonlar oqimida yangi internet media konsepsiyasi shakllantirildi. Natijada internet OAVda mediakontent o'zgartirish, uning tashqi dizaynini tashkil etish, kommunikatsiyani mustahkamlash, yangi platforma va formatlar orqali mediakontent tili va uslubini tayyorlash, qayta ishlash, saqlash va internet auditoriyaga yetkazish eng dolzarb vazifalardan biriga aylandi.

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O'QISH VA O'RGANISHDAGI MUAMMOLARNI BARTARAF ETISHDA PSIXOLINGVISTIKANING O'RNI: DISLEKSIYA

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Annotatsiya. *Psixolingvistika – bu tilni qayta ishlash usullari, ya'ni odamlar tilni qanday tushunishlari, ishlab chiqarishlari, egallashlari yoki yo'qotishlarini o'rganish bilan shug'ullanadigan tilshunoslik va psixologiyaning kesishgan qismidir. Shuningdek, psixolingvistika tilshunoslikning fonologiya, morfologiya, sintaktika, semantika kabi barcha bo'limlari tadqiqida, o'qish va yozishni o'rganishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bundan tashqari bu fan ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash jarayonida aralashadigan kognitiv jarayonlarni ham qamrab oladi. Quyida psixolingvistikaning ba'zi jihatlariga to'xtalib o'tildi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *psixolingvistika, yozma va og'zaki nutq, ta'lim, o'rganish*

Til odamlarning his-tuyg'ulari, fikr va g'oyalari kabilarni ifodalash imkonini beradi, ular o'rtasidagi aloqani ta'minlovchi asosiy vosita rolini o'ynaydi. Ba'zan o'zaro til orqali munosabatlar buzilishi, fikrni ifodalashda muvaffaqiyatsizlikka uchrash, muloqotda kognitiv va hissiy muammolarning paydo bo'lishi kuzatiladi. Mana shu kesimda Psixolingvistika yoki Til psixologiyasi fani vujudga kelgan deb hisoblanadi. Ma'lumki, psixologiya – bu psixik jarayonlarni o'rganadigan fan. Bu so'z yunoncha: psixo – ruh yoki aqliy faoliyat va -logiya – o'rganish, ta'limot ma'nosini beruvchi qismlardan hosil bo'lgan. Tilshunoslik, ya'ni lingvistika esa lotincha lingua – “til”, -ista – “band bo'lish, mashg'ulot” va -ico “nima bilandir bog'liqlik” kabi so'z va qo'shimchalardan hosil bo'lgan va bu fan tilga tegishli barcha qadimgi va zamonaviy qonun-qoidalarni qamrab oladi. Yuqoridagi ikki – psixologiya va lingvistika fanlaridan psixolingvistika yo'nalishi shakllandi. Bu termin dastlab 1946-yilda amerikalik psixolog N.Pronko tomonidan fanga kiritilgan deb hisoblanadi, u XX asrning 50-yillaridan boshlab dunyo ilm-faniga keng yoyila boshlandi. O'zbek tilidagi tadqiqotlarda psixolingvistika va til psixologiyasi kabi terminlarda atalib kelinmoqda [11, 8].

Til psixologiyasidan fikrlash, yozish, tinglash, vizual tushunish va ogʻzaki ifoda kabi til koʻnikmalarini tahlil qilishda foydalaniladi. Yozma nutq til oʻrganishning muhim vositalaridan biri boʻlib, u orqali odamlarda aqliy va kognitiv jarayonlar rivojlanadi. Ogʻzaki nutq, oʻz navbatida, xabarlarini cheksiz tarzda uzatish imkonini beradi. Umuman olganda, nutq xoh ogʻzaki yoki xoh yozma shaklda boʻlsin, u odamlarga deduktiv, tanqidiy va ijodiy fikrlashga erishishda ulkan imkoniyatlar taqdim etadi. Umuman, psixologiya inson tafakkuri, his-tuygʻu va xatti-harakatlarini oʻrganishga bagʻishlangan boʻlsa, tilshunoslik esa tilning qanday namoyon boʻlishini oʻrganadi. Ikkala nazariya va yondashuvlar qoʻshilgan oʻrinda yangi tadqiqotlar rivojlanadi, inson haqidagi, uning til bilish, soʻzlash qobiliyatlari kengroq mushohada etiladi.

G.Nasirovaning fikricha, til nutqiy faoliyatda yuzaga chiqqani tufayli tilshunoslikda ham, psixologiya fanida ham tekshirish obyekti hisoblanadi. Shunga asosan, bu ikki fanning sintezi sifatida, kesishgan nuqtada psixolingvistika (lingvopsixologiya) yoʻnalishi yuzaga keldi. U ichki nutqni tekshirish jarayoni, nutqni qabul etish, tilni egallash kabi masalalarni oʻrganadi [7].

Psixolingvistikaning maqsad va qoʻllanilishiga quyidagilar hisobga olinadi:

Uning asosiy maqsadi inson tilni yaratish va ishlatishi paytida sodir boʻladigan nevrologik kabi psixologik jarayonlarni anglash va tushuntirishdir, bunda quyidagi jihatlar ajralib turadi:

1. Inson miyasi ogʻzaki yoki yozma ravishda qabul qilingan xabarlarini qanday tushunishini bilib olish, idrok eshitishning vizual turida ongda kechadigan hissiyotlar bilan qanday farqlari bor va ular qanday paydo boʻladi, degan savollarga javob berish.

2. Soʻzlar ketma-ketligi qanday ishlab chiqarilishi va tartiblanishini bilish.

3. Insonning gapirish va tushunish qobiliyatini taʼminlaydigan tuzilmalar va jarayonlarni tahlil qilish.

4. Til malakalarining funksional tashkil etilishini belgilash.

5. Tilning yoshga doir rivojlanib borishini oʻrganish va hk.

Til oʻrganishda eng avvalo, oila muhim rol oʻynaydi. Aynan oila yadrosida inson bolalik davridan boshlab uni rivojlantirish, oʻzini ifoda etish va u orqali atrof-muhit bilan muloqot qilishni oʻrganadi. Bizningcha, oilada buni ragʻbatlantiradigan eng kuchli omillardan biri bu, oilaning fikr va gʻoyalarni bir-birlari bilan oʻzaro ishonchda toʻsqinlik va xavfsiz ifoda eta bilishlaridir.

Amerikalik olimlar P.Seymur va S.MakGregor tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan psixolingvistik model (1984) bugungi kunda oʻqish va imloni rivojlantirishni oʻrganishdagi eng toʻliq modellardan biri deb tan olingan. Bu model til oʻrganishda psixolingvistik aralashuvning turli funksiyalarini tahlil qiladi va toʻrtta asosiy prosessorning harakatini oʻz ichiga oladi: grafik, fonologik, semantik va orfografik.

Oʻqishni yozish jarayonini tahlil qilishning ushbu modelidan turli mexanizmlar yoki prosessorlardagi mavjud kamchiliklarni aniqlash mumkin, ular asosida disleksiyaning har xil turlari – morfemik, vizual-analitik va fonologik farqlanadi. Disleksiya oʻzi nima? Disleksiya (qadimgi yunonchadan $\delta\upsilon\lambda\epsilon\xi\alpha$ – nutq buzilishi), bu umumiy oʻrganish qobiliyatini saqlab qolgan holda, aynan oʻqish va yozish koʻnikmalarini egallash qobiliyatining buzilishi, demakdir.

Tarixiy jihatdan, aksariyat Yevropa mamlakatlarida "disleksiya" tushunchasi yozma nutq bilan bogʻliq barcha muammolarni oʻz ichiga oladi:

a) oʻqish mahoratini oʻzlashtirish bilan bogʻliq muammolar;

b) yozish mahoratini oʻzlashtirish bilan bogʻliq muammolar;

c) savodxonlik muammolari;

d) arifmetikani oʻzlashtirish bilan bogʻliq muammolar;

e) harakatlar va ularning ketma-ketligining buzilishi bilan bogʻliq muammolar;

f) diqqatni jamlash bilan bogʻliq muammolari [2].

Har xil disleksiya turlarini aniqlash bir qator aniq baholash vazifalari asosida oʻrganilgan identifikatsiya mezonlariga muvofiq belgilanadi. Disleksiya, shubhasiz, taʼlim oluvchining u yoki bu perdmelni oʻrganishdagi muammolarini tahlil qilishda eng koʻp qiziqish va shu bilan birga, eng koʻp qarama-qarshi fikrlarni keltirib chiqaruvchi hamda yozma tilni oʻrganishdagi buzilishlarni keltirib chiqaradigan qiyinchiliklardan iborat. Oʻqituvchilar disleksiyada talabalarning oʻqishni kam yoki umuman oʻzlashtirmasliklari uchun tinchlantiruvchi tushuntirishni topdilar, bu oʻzlarini har qanday masʼuliyat yoki texnik-pedagogik harakatlardan ozod qildi. Koʻp yillar davomida disleksiya tilchi olimlarda katta qiziqish uygʻotganligi bois, bu terminning koʻp va xilma-xil taʼriflari paydo boʻldi. Ushbu qiyinchilikni oʻrganishni birinchi boʻlib qayd etgan olimlardan biri B.Halgren disleksiyani quyidagi mezonlarga asoslanib tavsiflagan [5]:

1. Yozishni o'rganishdagi qiyinchilik.
2. O'qish va yozishda o'rtadan past muvaffaqiyatga erishish.
3. O'qish va yozish ko'rsatkichlari hamda maktabdagi boshqa fanlar o'rtasidagi nomuvofiqlik yoki nomutanosiblik.
4. O'qish va yozishdagi muvaffaqiyat bilan umumiy intellekt o'rtasidagi nomuvofiqlik.

Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, B.Halgren mezonlariga mos keladigan boshqa ko'plab ta'riflar ham mavjud, disleksiya sindromini tushuntirish va unga aralashish uchun bir yoki boshqa omillarga ta'sir qilishda psixolingvistika ajralib turadi, bu rivojlanish disleksiyasi asosan psixolingvistik jarayonlardagi yetuklik yoki kamolotdan ortda qolish bilan bog'liqligini ta'kidlaydi. Psixolingvistik nuqtai nazar axborotni qayta ishlashning kognitiv nazariyasining yondashuvlaridan kelib chiqadi, ya'ni, psixolingvistik nuqtai nazardan, disleksiyaning bir nechta turlari, aniqrog'i, sintaktik, semantik va fonologik ishlov berishning psixolingvistik qobiliyatlari bilan bog'liq buzilishlarga asoslangan bo'lib, ular sezgi qobiliyatidan ko'ra ko'proq kognitiv xususiyatga ega.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, biz savodxonlikning psixolingvistik tahlili asosida quyidagi qayta tarbiyaviy ta'sir etishlarni ko'rsatishimiz mumkin:

a) Psixolingvistik nuqtai nazardan yondashish o'qish va yozishni o'zlashtirishda fonologik, semantik va morfologik ishlov berishning turli funksiyalaridan foydalanish zaruratini yuzaga keltiradi, shu bois, disleksiyaning o'rganishda faqat an'anaviy ravishda ko'proq e'tibor berilgan psixomotor yoki perseptiv omillarga e'tibor qaratmasdan, balki fonologik, semantik va morfologik ishlov berishning turli funksiyalarini birga olib borish juda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

b) Psixolingvistik nuqtai nazar bir qator vazifalarni (semantik, vizual ishlash, ovoz chiqarish va boshqalar) osonlashtiradi, bu bizga sub'ektning kamchiliklari qaysi kompetensiyalarda yotganini va ular qanday turdagi disleksiyaning namoyon etishini yorqinroq aniqlash imkonini beradi.

c) Fonologik disleksiyaning tiklash uchun fonetik o'qish usullaridan foydalanish qulay va maqsadga muvofiqdir.

Qanday bo'lmasin, disleksiyaning qayta tarbiyalashda psixolingvistik nuqtai nazardan yondashish, mavzularda psixolingvistik ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish, assotsiativ faoliyat olib borish, imlo va boshqalarni hisobga olish kabilar o'quvchilarning o'qish va o'qitishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Tadqiqot natijalari tilni o'rganishda disleksiyaning yengib keyingi bosqichlarga o'tish imkonini tushuntiradi, ularni psixolingvistika va unga moslab sotsiolingvistika nuqtai nazaridan tadqiq qilishda nazariy asos vazifasini o'taydi, shuningdek, til tizimi, yozma va og'zaki nutqni mukammal egallashning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini aniqlashga xizmat qiladi.

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BOLALAR UCHUN IBORALAR RASMLI IZOHLI LUG'ATINING MILLIY XUSUSIYATLARI

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Аннотация. В данной статье обоснована актуальность составления узбекского фразеологического словаря для детей в картинках, перечислены основные принципы составления такого словаря с упором на национальные ценности.

Ключевые слова: учебный словарь, словарь в картинках, фразеологический словарь, словарная статья, иллюстративный пример, национальные ценности.

Rasmlı kitoblar bu – bolalar adabiyotining alohida mustaqil bir janri [1]. Bolaligimizda kitob-rasmlarni yaxlit qabul qilamiz, tinglah va ko'rish tuyg'ulari omuxta bo'lib, so'zlar ohangini tasvirlar bilan, mustaqil o'qishni boshlaganimizda esa, kitob muqovasi bilan uyg'unlashtiramiz [2]. Demak, bolalar tarbiyasi, ularda mutolaa madaniyatini shakllantirishda rasmlı kitoblar nihoyatda muhim o'rin egallaydi.

Rasmlı kitoblar konsepsiyasi ta'lim jarayoni uchun nihoyatda dolzarbdır. Zero, qabul qilinayotgan muhim ma'lumot rasm bilan uyg'unlashtirilsa, uning o'zlashtirilish darajasi va xotirada saqlanish darajasi ortadi. Shuning uchun til ta'limi samaradorligini oshirishda rasmlı kitoblar fenomenini rivojlantirish kerak. Shu maqsadda Innovatsion rivojlanish agentligi moliyalashtirgan loyiha asosida "Bolalar uchun iboralarning rasmlı izohli lug'ati" yaratilmoqda.

Aytish joizki, so'nggi paytlarda o'zbek tili ta'limi samaradorligini oshirish maqsadida bir qancha o'quv lug'atlari yaratilgan. Hatto o'quv lug'atlari taraqqiyoti, o'zbek tilidagi mavjud o'quv lug'atlar tahliliga bag'ishlangan, maxsus dissertatsiya himoya qilingan [4]. Mengliyev B. va boshqalar muallifligida kichikroq "O'zbek tilining iboralari o'quv lug'ati" [5] ham chop etilgan. Ammo o'zbek tilining rasmlı iboralar lug'ati hali yaratilgan emas. Vaholanki, rus va ingliz tilshunosligi, xususan, leksikografik amaliyotida bu keng tarqalgan bo'lib, nutq o'stirishda muhim vositalardan biri bo'lib xizmat qilmoqda. Masalan, rus tilida quyidagi rasmlı iboralar lug'ati mashhur: T.B. Розе "Большой фразеологический словарь для детей" (2010), Н.В. Баско "Фразеологический словарь. Почему мы так говорим" (2011), С. Волков "Детский фразеологический словарь в картинках" (2012), Е.В. Грабчикова "Фразеологизмы в картинках" (2018). Ingliz idiomalari jamlangan quyidagi lug'atlar nashr etilgan: Kövecses Zoltán "A Picture Dictionary of English Idioms" (1998), А.С. Бикеева "50 English Idioms in Pictures" (2017) va b.

O'zbek tilshunosligida yuqorida tilga olingan iboralarning o'quv lug'atidan avval iboralar jamlangan "O'zbek tilining izohli frazeologik lug'ati" chop etilgan. Sh. Rahmatullayev muallifligida 1978-yilda nashr etilgan mazkur lug'at lingvistik lug'at bo'lib, unda o'zbek tilidagi iboralar izohi, ularning variantlari, antonim va sinonimlari keltirilgan [6]. Mazkur lug'at 2022-yilda to'ldirilgan holda lotin yozuvida chop etildi [8]. Iboralar xalqning milliy-madaniy qarashlari, urf-odatları, an'analari bilan bog'liqligi haqida ko'p aytilgan. Teliya iboralar milli-madaniy dunyoqarsh etalonlari, stereotiplari vazifasini bajarib, ulardagi ramziylikni ko'rsatib, madaniy kodlarning lisoniy tashuvchisi ekanligini e'tirof etadi [3; 250]. Iboralar o'zida madaniyat

belgilarini mujassam etgan eng muhim lisoniy birliklardir. Aynan iboralarda xalqning milliy qadriyatlarini va madaniy stereotiplari tajassum topadi, aynan iboralarda xalqning o'tmish manzaralari gavdalanadi. Masalan, "yaqin do'st" ma'nosidagi to'n kiyishgan iborasi xalqimizning o'tmishda do'st tutinshning muhim komponentlaridan biri – kiyim almashish odatini aks ettiradi: Qo'lyi kassir uning to'n kiyishgan oshnasi. Buning ustiga Toshqul uylanayotganda Qo'lyi kuyovboshlatar bo'lgandi. (Muhammad Ochil. Tovuq sho'rva). Ma'lumki, bunday odat hindularda ham mavjud; bu odat Mayn Ridning mashhur "Boshsiz chvandoz" asarida ham bayon qilingan, asar qahramoni Morris Djerald Genri bilan do'st tutinib, biri ikkinchisiga plash, ikkinchisi esa serape beradi (hindular ustki kiyimi). "O'qimagan" ma'nosidagi "alifni kaltak demoq" yoki "indamadi" ma'nosidagi "lom-mim demadi" iboralari esa tarix taqozosi bilan o'zbek xalqi bevosita daxldor bo'lgan islom madaniyati bilan bog'liq. Oxiri o'ylanmay yoki chala-chulpa qilingan ishga nisbatan "dumi xurjunda" iborasini ishlatamiz. Iboraning kelib chiqishi o'zbek xalq ijodi an'analari, ya'ni Afandi haqidagi latifa bilan bog'liq. Afandi eshagini sotish uchun bozorga olib ketayotgan ekan, yo'lda botqoqdan o'tayotib, dumi loy bo'libdi. Loy dum xaridorga xunuk ko'rinmasligi uchun dumini kesib xurjuniga solib qo'yibdi. Bozorda bir xaridor: – Xo'p yaxshi eshak ekan-u, dumi yo'q ekan-da, – desa, Afandi unga: – Yoqqan bo'lsa savdosini qilaver, dumi xurjunda, – deb javob qaytargan ekan.

Iboralar madaniyat haqidagi bilimlarning to'g'ri shakllanishida juda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Shu nuqtayi nazardan bolalar uchun rasmi iboralarning lug'atini tuzish bugungi leksikografiya oldida turgan muhim vazifalardan biri deb hisoblaymiz. Zero bunda axborot qabul qilishdagi muhim xotira turi – ko'rish xotirasi faollashadi. Ko'rish qobiliyati muayyan tasvir va obrazlarni saqlash va xotirada jonlantirish bilan bog'liq. Materialni eslab qolish va uni qo'llash ko'p jihatdan aynan ko'rish qobiliyatiga asoslanadi. Inson tasavvur qila oladigan narsasini osonroq eslab qoladi. Ko'rish xotirasi nutqiy faoliyat orqali yanada mustahkamlanadi. Bunda albatta assotsiatsiyaning roli katta. Masalan, "anqoning urug'i" iborasiga chizilgan rasm bolaning xotirasida shu rasmga berilgan matnli axborot yoki audioizoh assotsiatsiyasini uyg'otadi va bola shu tariqa iboraning ma'nosini eslab qoladi.

Lug'at uchun o'zbek madaniyati va o'zbek turmush tarzini yorqin ifodalaydigan va o'zbeklar nutqida faol qo'llanadigan iboralarni saralab olish lozim. Masalan, o'zbeklar nutqida ko'p qo'llanadigan "qovun tushirmoq", "tarvuzi qo'ltig'idan tushdi" o'zbek xalqining xo'jalik yuritish usuli bilan bog'liq (o'zbeklar qadimdan tarvuz, qovun, handalak kabi poliz ekinlarini ekishadi), "otdan tushsa ham egardan tushmaydi", "oyog'i uzangida", "uloqni olib ketmoq" kabi iboralar o'zbeklarning ot boqish odati va chavandozligi bilan bog'liq, "to'nini teskari kiyimoq", "gappa to'n kiygizmoq", "do'ppisi yarimta", "kavushini to'g'rilab qo'ymoq" iboralari o'zbek milliy kiyimlari bilan bog'liq bo'lib, milliy realiyalar hisoblanadi.

Lug'at uchun ishlanayotgan rasmlarda o'zbeklarning etnik, madaniy va antropometrik xususiyatlarini e'tiborga olish lozim. Ya'ni, rasmdagi obrazlar o'zbek millatiga xos odamni aks ettirishi kerak. Yevropa millatiga xos sariq sochli, ko'k ko'zli insonlarni tasvirlash yoki amerikaliklarga xos kovboy shlyapasidagi odamlar tasvirini keltirish o'rinli emas. Masalan, ro'mol taqqan o'zbek ayoli, do'ppili yoki sallali kishilarni tasvirlash maqsadga muvofiq.

Iboralarga rasm chizish ko'jihatdan rassomning mahorati, tasavvur olami kengligi va topqirligiga bog'liq. Bitta ibora turli xalqlarda bo'lishi mumkin, ammo har bir rassom o'z tasavvuri, milliy qarashlaridan kelib chiqib, har xil rasm yaratishi mumkin. Masalan, rus tilida "делать из мухи слона" iborasi, o'zbek tilida esa "pashshadan fil yasamoq" iborasi mavjud. Quyidagi ularga chizilgan rasmlarni keltiramiz.

Iboralarning ma'nosini bolalarga tushunarli tilda, ularning yosh xususiyatlarini hisobga olib izohlash kerak. Bunday lug'atlarda frazeologik lug'atlarda keltiriladigan lingvistik ma'lumotlarni, masalan, iboralarning antonim va sinonimlarini keltirish o'rinli emas, deb o'ylaymiz. Zero bu o'quv materialini murakkablashtirib, bolaning ibora ma'nosini tushunishiga va uni o'zlashtirishiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin.

Lug'at izohida imkon qadar iboraning shakllanish tarixini bayon etish maqsadga muvofiq. Bunda iboralarning ma'nosi yanada oydinlashib, uni eslab qolish uchun bolada assotsiatsiyalar yanada ko'payadi, uni eslab qolish osonlashadi. Masalan, "Daqyonusdan qolgan" (eski, qadimiy, yaroqsiz) iborasi izohida ibora talqini va illyustrativ misol hamda tasvirdan tashqari ushbu iboraning shakllanishiga asos bo'lgan Diokletian haqidagi rivoyatni ham keltirib o'tish kerak. Bunda albatta, iboralar bo'yicha qilingan tadqiqotlar asqotadi. Masalan, "og'iz juftlamoq" iborasi shakllanishi haqida ma'lumot keltirishda T.Tog'ayevning izlanishlaridan foydalanish mumkin: "Bu ibora aslida "og'iz jo'blamoq" bo'lgan. Birinchi o'zbek romani – "O'tkan kunlar"da Abdulla Qodiriy buni shu shaklda to'g'ri qo'llagan: – Man, – dedi Otabek va o'zining mantiqsiz javobidan o'ngg'aysizlanib, tuzik javob berishka og'zini jo'blag'an ham edi, chiqg'uchi – siz kimsiz? – degan savol bilan uni to'xtatib qoldi. "Jo'blamoq" fe'lining yasalishiga asos bo'lgan jo'b so'zining ma'nosini bilib olishimizga to'g'ri keladi. Umuman, bu turkiycha-o'zbekcha so'z mumtoz adabiyotimizda, xalq og'zaki ijodi tilida qo'llanib kelgan. Xususan, jo'b so'zi Navoiy hazratlari tomonidan asarlarida birmuncha faol qo'llangan. Bu so'z "teng, mos, bop, munosib" kabi ma'nolarga ega ekanligi qayd etilgan [7; 142].

Iboralarni "O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati" yoki Sh.Rahmatullayevning yuqorida tilga olingan frazeologik lug'atlaridan olish shart emas. Masalan, hozirda publitsistik matnlarda yoki og'zaki nutqda omadi keldi ma'nosidagi "ketmoni uchdi" iborasi faol bo'lib, u frazeologik lug'atlarda qayd etilmagan. Uning faol qo'llanishi va madaniy foni boyligini e'tiborga olib, uni lug'atga kiritish mumkin. Ushbu iboraning kelib chiqishi o'zbek kinematografiyasi yutuqlaridan bo'lmish "Abdullajon" filmi bilan bog'liq. Kinodagi o'zga sayyoralik bola

Abdullajon tufayli qishloqdagi barcha ketmonlar uchish xususiyatiga ega bo'ladi, aholi bozorga, ishga, mehmonga ketmonda boradi. Shu tariqa, ketmoni uchmoq "ishi yurishmoq", "omadi chopmoq" ma'nosida ishlatiladigan bo'lgan.

O'ylaymizki, yuqorida keltirilgan fikrlar "Bolalar uchun iboralarning rasmi lug'ati"ning milliylik xususiyatlarini ta'minlashga xizmat qiladi. Quyida esa, ushbu lug'atga kiritilgan "po'stagini qoqmoq" iborasi izohi va rasmi bilan tanishtiramiz:

PO'STAGINI QOQMOQ

Ayovsiz tanqid qilmoq, ta'zirini bermoq.

Po'stak – o'siq junli oshlangan teridan tayyorlangan to'shak. Ko'pincha ostonaga tashlanganligi uchun uni tez-tez qoqib turish kerak bo'lgan. Po'stak qoqish va tanqid qilish o'rtasidagi ayovsizlik iboraning shakllanishiga asos bo'lgan.

Haqiqatan kalamush ekan u. Bugun po'stagini qoqib, ishdan olishdi. Hamma yoqni kemirib tashlagan ekan... (Ilhom Zoyir, "O'g'irlangan" pul mojarosi). – Rahmat sizga, - bosh qimirlatib qo'ydi Alamazon. – Bir tanqidchi uniyam boplab po'stagini qoqdi. Juda nomdor, unvondor tanqidchi. (A.Obidjon, Akang qarag'ay Gulmat).

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SIFAT TURKUMIGA OID DIALEKTAL SO‘ZLARNING ADABIY TILNI BOYITISH IMKONIYATLARI

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Аннотация. Целью данной статьи является оценка лингвистической значимости прилагательных, активно используемых в узбекских говорах и разговорной речи. В исследовании проанализированы лексические пробелы, выявленные в процессе сравнения лексики узбекского литературного языка и народных говоров. Констатируется необходимость восполнения лексических пробелов, исходя из внутренних возможностей узбекского языка для сохранения чистоты языка и обеспечения его развития.

Ключевые слова: лексическое развитие языка, лексический пробел, диалектизм, прилагательные, разговорные слова, насыщение лексики.

Tilda har bir tushuncha o‘z nomiga ega bo‘lishi lozim. So‘zni ko‘chma ma’noda qo‘llayverish albatta ko‘p ma’nolilikni keltirib chiqaradi. Ko‘pma’nolilik esa ba’zi leksik birliklarning turlicha talqin etilishiga sabab bo‘ladi. Ba’zi olimlar haqli ta’kidlaganidek, "...ko‘p ma’nolilik yolg‘on tushunchadir; qayerda ikkita ma’no bor, o‘sha yerda ikkita so‘z bor" [1; 39]. Bitta so‘zni bir necha tushunchani ifodalashga "majburlash" to‘g‘ri emas.

So‘zlashuv nutqida faol qo‘llaniladigan so‘zlar orasida sifat turkumiga oid, xususan, insonga xos xususiyatlarni ifodalovchi so‘zlar ham salmoqli ulushga ega. Zero, inson suhbat jarayonida, asosan, o‘zganing ishlarini, yurish-turishini, xulq-atvorini, kechmishini tahlil qilishga, baholashga e’tibor qaratadi.

Shaxs xususiyatini ifodalashda turli lisoniy vositalardan foydalanish mumkin, biroq ular ichida eng ko‘p tarqalgani leksik birliklar orqali ifodalashdir [2; 751]. Shaxsga xos xususiyatni ifodalovchi aksar leksemalarda leksik ma’nodan tashqari muayyan salbiy yoki ijobiy munosabatni ifodalovchi qo‘shimcha ma’no ottenkalari ham qorishiq namoyon bo‘ladi, bu jihatlar mazkur LSGdagi leksemalarning uslubiy bo‘yoqdorligi va modal ma’nolarining qavariq namoyon bo‘lishiga zamin hozirlaydi.

F.Musayevaning ta’kidlashicha, "sheva vakillari voqelikning salbiy jihatlariga ko‘proq diqqat qilib, aynan ularni nomlashga e’tibor qaratishadi" [10; 48]. Kishiga o‘zganing muayyan xususiyati yoqmas ekan, buni nutqda ifodalashda favqulodda bo‘yoqdor so‘zlarni tanlash va ishlatishga intilish ham mazkur tipli so‘zlarning qo‘shimcha sub’ektiv ma’no olishini taqozo etadi. Ana shu omil sabab shaxsga xos xususiyatlarni ifodalovchi so‘zlar qatorida salbiy munosabat ifodalangan so‘zlarning miqdori ijobiy bo‘yoqqa ega bo‘lgan so‘zlardan ancha ko‘p ekanligini qayd etish joiz. Adabiy til va shevalar leksikasini taqqoslashda ham mazkur qonuniyatning amal qilishi kuzatildi.

Quyida adabiy til leksikasi uchun bo‘shliq bo‘lgan ayrim shu tipdagi so‘zlarni tavsiflashga harakat qilamiz.

Manman, takabbur tushunchalariga o‘xshash xususiyatlar shevalarda jiddiy farqlanadi. Adabiy tilda bu farqlanishlar so‘z birikmalari orqali ifodalansa-da, xalq shevalarida ularni ifodalovchi so‘zlar allaqachon barqarorlashib ulgurgan bo‘ladi [5; 95]. Bu orqali kerakli tushunchalar nomlanishidan tashqari nutqiy energiya iqtisod qilinadi hamda nutqning ta’sirchanligi ham oshiriladi. Xususan, "faqat o‘zini haq deb biladigan" ma’nosiga ega гансър [4; 88] so‘zi ham muayyan nutqdagi tejamkorlikni, ta’sirchanlikni ta’minlash ehtiyojidan shakllangan.

Shevalarda qo‘llaniluvchi эшқын "o‘zini boshqalardan ustun qo‘yuvchi" [15; 76], ҳәкәри "o‘zini baland tutuvchi" [4; 87], чувәчәқ "nimjon, ammo o‘zini kuchli hisoblovchi" [13; 378] гүбүрдәк "o‘ziga bino qo‘yib gapiruvchi" [9; 24] kabi so‘zlar ham u yoki bu darajadagi manmanlikka o‘xshash xususiyatlarni nomlash ehtiyojidan shakllangan. Bu kabi so‘zlarning manman leksemasidan farqlanishi ularning muayyan lisoniy ehtiyoj natijasida til leksikasiga qabul qilinishiga xizmat qiladi.

Qorako‘l tumanidagi qarluq lahjasiga oid shevalarda "o‘z so‘zini o‘tkazishga urinuvchi" ma’nosida пешгър [3; 78] so‘zi qo‘llanadi. O‘zbek adabiy tilida mazkur tushunchani ifodalovchi so‘z mavjud emas. Demak, uni to‘ldirishda peshgir so‘zidan foydalanish mumkin. Asli fors-tojik tilidagi birliklardan yasalgan bu so‘z tez tushunishli hisoblanadi. Binobarin, aksar qarluq shevalarida pesh so‘zi "ilg‘or, o‘ktam" ma’nolarida qo‘llanilishi ham peshgir so‘zining tez tushunilishini ta’minlashga xizmat qiladi.

Toshhovuz viloyatidagi o'zbek shevalarida вэрқы so'zi "og'zida gap turmaydigan (sirni saqlay olmaydigan)" ma'nosida qo'llanadi [9; 21]. Mazkur so'z ham adabiy tildagi muayyan leksik bo'shliqning to'ldirilishida katta ahamiyatga ega. Nutqda qo'llanadigan og'zi bo'sh, sir saqlay olmaydigan kabi birliklar o'rnida mazkur so'zning qo'llanilishi lisoniy tejamkorlikka ham xizmat qiladi. Shu bois mazkur so'zni ham adabiy lashtirish lozim.

Хъръш [4; 86] so'zi, asosan, bolalarga nisbatan qo'llaniladi. Mazkur so'z "janjallashib, tortishish uchun bahona izlovchi" ma'nosiga ega. Bu so'z "tekkanga tegib, tegmaganga tosh otuvchi" iborasiga yaqin. Biroq unda "bezorilik" semasi nisbatan sustroq namoyon bo'ladi. Bu jihatlar mazkur farqli tushunchalarni alohida nomlashga xizmat qiluvchi xirish so'zining adabiy lashtirishini taqozo qiladi.

Бэбэр so'zi Vodil shevasida "tez gapiruvchi" ma'nosiga ega. Bu so'z, asosan, qisqa vaqtda ko'p so'zni aytish jihatidan xarakterli bo'lib, gapdon, so'zamol kabi so'zlardan farqlanadi. Mazkur tushuncha Qozog'istondagi o'zbek shevalarida бэдык [15; 83] tarzida nomlangan. Bizningcha, bidiq shakli ushbu tushunchani nomlashda imtiyozliroq. Zero, uni eshitish orqali bidirlamoq, bidir-bidir kabi so'zlar eslanadi va shu orqali "tez gapiruvchi" ma'nosi osonroq anglanadi.

Janubiy Qozog'istondagi o'zbek shevalarida, shuningdek, ayrim qipchoq shevalarida "erkak kishini xushlovchi, yaxshi ko'ruvchi ayol" ma'nosi эрсэк [15, 91] so'zi orqali ifodalanadi. Bu so'z qadimgi turkiy tilda ham shu ma'noda qo'llanilgan. Bu esa mazkur so'zning adabiy til lug'atlarida qayd etilishiga imtiyoz beradi.

Qipchoq shevalarida qo'llaniluvchi кэйпэнг [13; 361] so'zi "o'ylamay so'zlaydigan" ma'nosida qo'llanadi. Har bir gapni o'ylab gapirish qanchalik muhim ekanligi barchaga ma'lum. O'ylamay gapirish so'zlovchining obro'sizlanishi, nutqining samarasiz yakunlanishiga ham sabab bo'ladi. Mazkur xususiyatlarni alohida nomlash so'z birikmasi orqali ifodalanayotgan tegishli tushunchaning leksemalashishini ta'minlaydi.

Xulosa qilish mumkinki, sifat turkumiga oid so'zlar ko'pgina nutqiy vaziyatlarda faol qo'llaniladi. Bunday so'zlarni topish va sinchiklab o'rganish, ulardan til leksikasidagi bo'shliqlarni to'ldirishda maqsadli foydalanish til rivoji uchun juda muhim. Ayniqsa, yuqoridagi kabi lisoniy va ijtimoiy ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan so'zlarning adabiy tilda faollashuvi va me'yorlashuvi tilning boyishiga, shuning barobarida, adabiy tilning ifoda imkoniyatlari kengayishiga xizmat qiladi.

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JADID SHE'RIYATI TILIDAGI LUG'AVIY BIRLIKLARNING SHAKL VA MA'NO MUNOSABATLARIGA KO'RA TASNIFI

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Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются лексические единицы в языке современной поэзии с точки зрения соотношения формы и значения. В частности, отдельно с точки зрения лексических единиц языка анализировалась поэзия современного просветителя Чолпона.

Ключевые слова: джадид, просвещение, поэзия, творчество, язык, единство, эпоха, мыслитель, родина, единство, смысл, труд, сема, лексема, внимание.

XIX asr oxiri XX asr boshlaridagi notinch va tahlikali zamonda yashab, ijod etgan jadid mutafakkirlarining she'riyatida muhabbat, vatan, ozodlik – umuman olganda, ijtimoiy hayotdagi barcha-barcha mavzular tarannum etilgan. Jadidlar o'z hayotini qaynoq ijodiy va ijtimoiy faoliyatga bag'ishladi. Bundan tashqari jadid namoyandalari o'z ijodiy faoliyati davrida adabiy til muammolariga alohida e'tibor qaratdilar. Ana shunday jadid ma'rifatparvarlaridan biri Cho'lpon she'riyatining tili o'zining ma'no nozikligi va har bir so'zning o'z o'rnida qo'llanganligi bilan boshqa ijodkorlar she'riyatidan alohida ajralib turadi. Xalqning rivojini taraqqiy etishini til bilan bog'lagan. Cho'lpon til masalasiga alohida e'tibor va diqqat bilan qaradi. Ayni paytda shu diqqat – e'tibori isbotini uning she'riyati tilida kuzatish mumkin.

Cho'lpon she'riyati tilidagi lug'aviy birliklarning shakl va ma'no munosabatlari tahlilida uning she'riyatidagi har bir lug'aviy birlikning ma'no qirrasini ochish mumkin. So'zning leksik-semantik xususiyatlari uning leksik, grammatik va semantik jihatlarini o'zida mujassamlashtiradi. Chunki so'zlar tilning lug'at tarkibini shundagina tashkil etmay, umuman, tilning sistema va strukturasidagi barcha bog'lanishlarni taqozo etadi.

Ko'pincha so'zning ma'nosi haqida gapirganda uning predmet va tushuncha bilan aloqasi va tilda qanday ifodalanishi ko'zda tutiladi [1; 95].

Leksik ma'no ideal hodisa deb talqin qilinadi. Hozirgi tilshunoslikda bu ideal hodisani moddiylashtirish yo'llari topilmoqda. Shunday yo'llardan biri leksik ma'nosi semantik qismlarga parchalab o'rganish bo'lib, qismlar tahlil (semik tahlil) usuli deb yuritiladi. Shu usul bilan farqlanadigan hodisa sema deyiladi.

Semik tahlil usulidan dastlab leksik birliklarni turlicha semantik guruhlar (tematik, leksik-semantik guruhlar)ga birlashtirishda foydalanildi [2; 66].

Tilshunoslik nuqtayi nazaridan so'z aytilish va ma'noning birligidan iborat. Biroq so'zning predmet va tushunchalar bilan bog'lanishi hisobga olinsa, u borliqdagi biror narsaning odam ongidagi in'ikosi bo'lib, bu in'ikos tafakkur yordamida amalga oshiriladi. Shu sababli so'z biror tushuncha, predmat, hodisa yoki belgini ifodalay oladi. Ayrim olingan so'zga tegishli bo'lib, boshqa so'zlardan farqlay oluvchi ma'no shu so'zning leksik ma'nosi birinchi navbatda o'sha so'z o'zagining ma'nosi bilan bog'liq bo'ladi va har qanday affiks qo'shilganda ham saqlanib qoladi.

Tilning mazmun rejasida so'zning asosiy ma'nosi semema termini bilan ataladi. Ifoda rejasida esa leksema deb yuritiladi. Tilning ifoda va mazmun rejaları bir-biri bilan uzviy bog'liq holatda qaraladi [2; 98].

Yuqoridagi nuqtayi nazardan kelib chiqqan holda Cho'lpon she'riyati tilidagi ayrim lug'aviy birlikning shakliy va ma'noviy munosabatlari tahlilga oilindi. So'zning ko'p ma'noli bo'lish xususiyati polisemiya deyiladi. Til birliklari bir yoki birdan ortiq ma'noni anglatadi. Bir ma'noni anglatish hodisasi monosemiya, bunday xususiyatli til birligi monosemantik birlik deyiladi, (yunoncha monos – "bir", sema, semion – "belgi", semantikos – "bildiruvchi") [3; 23].

Yuqoridagi fikrlarning butunlay aksi hisoblanmish polisemiya hodisasi (polis – "ko'p") til birliklarini alohida diqqat bilan o'rganishni talab qiladi. So'zlarning ko'p ma'noliligi hodisasini monografik tadqiq etgan tilshunos M.Mirtojiyev quyidagilarni yozadi: "Ma'lumki, tilda polisemantik so'zlar vujudga kelish imkoniyatlarining ko'p bo'lishi va tilda polisemiyaning nihoyatda taraqqiy etganligi fikr ayirboshlash uchun hech mahal qiyinchilik tug'dirmaydi. Uning taraqqiyoti obyektiv mavjudotni o'zaro bog'liq holda anglash, ularni qiyosiy o'rganish,

taraqqiyotlarning tilda aks etib turishi kabilar natijasi bo'ladi. Ya'ni polisemiya sivilizatsiya belgisidir. Qaysi xalqda fan, texnika, madaniyat, san'at taraqqiy etgan bo'lsa, o'sha xalq obyektiv borliqning o'zaro aloqasini shuncha ko'proq ko'radi, ularni bir-biriga ko'proq qiyos etadi va ular tilda ko'proq aksini topadi".

Olim ayni paytda yana quyidagilarni ta'kidlaydi: "Biz ya'ni o'zbek tilini ham semantik salmog'i og'ir tillardan biri sifatida qayd etmoqchimiz. Bunda o'zbek tiliga oid lug'atlarni varaqlash va boshqa lug'atlarga solishtirish sabab bo'ladi. Bundan tashqari o'zbek badiiy adabiyotida so'z o'yini, askiya va tuyuq kabi janrlarning boshqa til badiiydagi nisbatan keng ekani ham mazkur fikrimizni tasdiqlaydi" [4; 136].

Ko'rinadiki, ko'pma'nolilik har qanday tildagi mutlaqo qonuniy hodisa bo'lib, uning mavjudligini nutqning ifoda imkoniyatlarini kengaytirishga ko'maklashadi. Matnga konteksga ko'ra ko'p ma'noli so'z muayyan bir nutqda o'zining aniq bir ma'nosi bilan reallashadi, ya'ni uning ko'p ma'noliligi fikrning yanglish anglanishiga olib kelmaydi. Aksincha, ayniqsa, badiiy nutqda ko'p ma'nolilik o'ziga xos ifodalilik vositasi sifatida xizmat qilishi mumkin.

Jamiyat rivojlanishining qizg'in pallasiga kirgani sari tilda o'ziga xos taraqqiyot yuz berishi mumkin. Nutqda yangi so'zlar qatlami (neologizmlar) paydo bo'lib, ular xalqchillashadi. Xalq ruhiyatini o'zida tobora kengroq aks ettiradi. Jumladan, Cho'lpon she'riyatini olib tahlil qiladigan bo'lsak, unda polisemantik so'zlarning ko'p miqdorda qo'llanilishini kuzatish mumkin.

O'zbek tilining lug'at boyligida birgina ma'no ifodalovchi so'zlar ko'p ma'noli so'zlarga nisbatan kamroq, ya'ni tilimizdagi so'zlarning aksariyati ko'p ma'noli so'zlardir. Bu esa polisemiya hodisalarning eng ko'lamli ekanligidan dalolat beradi. Masalan, yer, ko'z, yuz, bet, nur, oyoq, bosh kabilar polisemantik so'zlardir. Polisemantik so'zning asosiy xususiyati shuki, so'zning ma'no tolalari bir bosh ma'no (markaz)ga birlashib turadi va albatta, bir turkum doirasida bo'ladi [5; 41].

Cho'lpon she'riyatida ko'p ma'noli lug'aviy birliklardan unumli foydalangan. Uning yaqqol isbotini quyidagi misralarda kuzatish mumkin:

Sharqning qaysi burchagiga qarasang
Yo'qlik, o'lim, zulm, qarg'ish ko'rarding
"Tomug'" degan so'zni bilmak istasang
Sharqni boshdan – oyoqqacha yurarding.
Bir zamonlar yer yuzinga o'z boshli,
Ulug', shonli, madaniyat tug'dirg'on
U go'zal Sharq shirin tuproq so'ng zamon
Bo'ldi chetlar panjasida ko'z yoshli... [6;13]

Yuqoridagi satrlarda "(boshdan-oyoq" va "yuz" so'zlari ko'p ma'noli so'zlardir. Ular quyidagi ma'nolarni ifodalaydi:

1. Boshdan to oyoqqacha.
 2. Boshidan to oxirigacha; tugal, tamom.
- "Yuz" polisemantik leksemasi ham bir qancha semalarga ega.
- I. 1. Odam boshining old tomoni, chehra, aft, bet.
 2. Inson betining u yoki bu tomoni, yonoq.
 3. Biror narsaning ustki tomoni, yuzasi; sath, sirt.
 4. Ayrim narsalarning u yoki bu tomoni, tarafi, qirg'og'i.
 5. Obro', e'tibor; yuz-xotir.
 6. Kesish yoki chopish asboblarining tig'i.
 7. Tekislik yoki sirtning chiziqlar bilan o'ralgan qismi, sath.
 - II. 1. 100 raqami va shu raqam bilan ifodalangan son, miqdor.
 2. So'zlashuv tilida ko'p, ko'p marta [7; 332, 465].

Polisemantik leksema bo'lgan "yuz" leksemasi mumtoz adabiyot lug'atidan quyidagi ma'nolarni bera oluvchi so'z sifatida o'rin olgan:

1. Chora, iloj, tadbir.
2. O'zbek urug'laridan birining nomi.
3. Chehra, bet, aft.
4. Bahodir, pahlavon.
5. Sanoq son [8; 182].

Bu kabi ko'p ma'noli so'zlarni nafaqat Cho'lpon she'riyatida, umuman, ko'plab jadid namoyandalarining she'riyatida kuzatish mumkin. Bu ijodkorlarning nechog'li serqirra, qalami o'tkir, tafakkuri keng, ijod yo'li ravon ijodkorlardan ekanligidan dalolat beradi. Ularning o'zbek tili va ravnaqi uchun qo'shgan hissasi she'riyati orqali o'z aksini ko'rsatib turibdi.

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TILSHUNOSLIKNING YANGI YO'NALISHI: MOZIY VA BUGUN

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Аннотация. Актуальность представленной в статье проблемы заключается в том, что в ней рассматривается новая область языкознания – нейролингвистика, её специфические аспекты, история становления и современные процессы развития.

Ключевые слова и фразы: нейролингвистика, нейрохирургия, анатомия головного мозга, эпилепсия, речевые нарушения, эмпирический метод, левое и правое полушария.

Neurologist T.V.Chernigovskayaning ta'kidlashicha, til va tafakkurga doir qarashlar Sharq va Yevropa faylasuflari izlanishlarida qadimdan o'z ifodasini topib kelgan. Miloddan avvalgi II ming yillikning o'rtalarida yashagan Edwin Smith miya jarohatlanishiga oid 26 holatni qayd etib, u tomonidan tavsiya etilgan terapiya Misr shifokorining miya anatomiyasi va funksiyalarini yaxshi bilishini namoyon etadi. Taxminan yarim asr o'tgach, Yerning boshqa qismida, Janubiy Amerikada, maxsus jarrohlik (trepanatsiya) izlari mavjud bo'lgan ko'p sonli bosh suyaklari kuzatiladi. Qizig'i, bunday turdagi neyroxirurgiya operatsiyalari deyarli odatiy sanalib, bronza va vulqon shishasidan yasalgan asboblardan bajarilgan va hatto bosh og'rig'i, epilepsiya, boshqa asab va ruhiy kasalliklarni davolashda qo'llanilgan [3; 40].

Demak, neurologiya sohasi asab tizimining faoliyati, tuzilishi va vazifalarini o'rganuvchi nevrologiya hamda til haqida ma'lumot beruvchi lingvistika fanlarining o'zaro uyg'unligidan hosil bo'lar ekan, ilmiy manbalarga tayanib aytish mumkinki, eramizdan avvalgi 3500-yillardayoq tilning miyada joylashganligi haqidagi ilk qarashlar mavjud bo'lgan [2; 566]. Ularda ta'kidlanishicha, bosh suyagining muayyan qismidagi jarohat tananing boshqa a'zolariga ham ziyon yetkazishi mumkin. Shu sababdan o'sha davr olimlari inson a'zolari va ularning faoliyati miyaning turli maydonlariga bog'liq, deb hisoblaganlar. Ayniqsa, Gippokrat, Gerofil, Platon, Demokrit, Aristotel, Galen kabi zabardast faylasuf olimlarning xulosalari asosida o'sha qadimgi davrlardan inson tanasining har bir a'zosi faoliyati miya bilan aloqador ekanligi ta'kidlangan. 1770-yilga kelib, logann Gesner tomonidan yozilgan "Til amneziasini" nomli monografiyada nutq buzilishlariga yangicha qarash yuzaga kela boshladi. Shu bilan birga, bu davrga kelib, miyaning turli nuqtalarida, ayniqsa, miya po'stlog'ida bajariladigan mavjud yuqori darajadagi vazifalar haqida bahs-munozaralar paydo bo'la

boshladi. XIX asr davomida nutqiy buzilishlar doirasidagi bilimlar kengayib, bu haqdagi ma'lumotlarga o'sha davrdayoq tamal toshi qo'yilgan edi.

Olim Frans Iosif Gall birinchilardan bo'lib, aqliy qobiliyat aynan bosh miya po'stlog'ida ekanligini hamda miyadagi kulrang modda faol to'qimalar (nervlar), oq modda esa biriktiruvchi to'qima ekanligini isbotladi. Tadqiqotning empirik usuli yordamida olim miyaning turli funksiyalarini bosh miyaning muayyan po'stlog'i hududlari bilan bog'laydi. Masalan, u nutq artikulyatsiyasi va so'zni xotirada saqlab qolish o'zni peshona bo'lagining ikki sohasida ekanligini aniqladi. Gall g'oyalarini uning shogirdi Jan-Batist Bull davom ettirib, peshona bo'lagi sohalaridagi turli jarohatlarning nutqiy buzilishlar bilan bog'liq bo'lgan hamda boshqa bo'lak sohalaridagi jarohatlarning bunday buzilishlar bilan bog'liq bo'lmagan holatlarini aniqlaydi.

1861-yilga kelib, fransuz olimi Pol Broka bir bemorni kuzatishi orqali ikkita farazni ilgari suradi: birinchidan, insonning ruhiy holatlari bilan bog'liq faoliyati miya yadrosi orqali amalga oshadi. Ikkinchidan, nutqiy buzilish bosh miyaning chap yarimsharidagi jarohat asosida yuzaga keladi.

Nevrolog Karl Vernike esa Broka tadqiqotlarini, ayniqsa, insonning ruhiy holatlari miya yadrosi orqali amalga oshishiga oid qarashlarini qo'llab-quvvatlab, nutqni tushunish muammolari bilan bog'liq hamda bugungi kunda Vernike sohasi deya mashhur sanalgan bosh miyaning yangi sathini ixtiro qiladi. Olim insult bilan kasallangan bemor ustida izlanish olib boradi. Bemor gapirar, eshitar, ammo og'zaki va yozma nutqni qiyinchilik bilan tushunardi. Uning vafotidan keyin Vernike bemorning chap yarim sharlari yon va o'rta sohalaridagi jarohatlanganini aniqlaydi. Va olim eshitish sohalariga yaqin sanalgan aynan shu maydonlar nutqni tushunish jarayonlarida ishtirok etishi bo'yicha xulosalarini keltiradi. Keyinchalik Vernike bosh miyada nutq bilan bog'liq aniq ikki maydon mavjudligini asoslaydi. Bular bugungi kunda nutqni qabul qilishga javob beruvchi Vernike sathi hamda nutqni ifodalashga xizmat qiluvchi Broka sathi sanaladi.

Nemis olimi Lyudvig Lixtshteyn Vernikening qarashlarini to'ldirib, "hukm markazi" sanalgan uchinchi maydonga asos soldi. Olim so'z miya tomonidan qabul qilinganidan so'ng aynan hukm markaziga ma'no ifodalashi uchun yo'naltirilishini ta'kidlaydi. Neyrolingvistika taraqqiyotining keyingi bosqichi bevosita L.R.Luriya va uning izdosh-shogirdlari faoliyati bilan bog'liq bo'lib, ular tomonidan nazariy qarashlar asosida nutqiy buzilishlarni tizimli tahlil qilish joriy etildi [1; 666].

XX asr o'rtalaridan boshlab neyrolingvistika doirasida L.Vigotskiy, A.Luriya, R.Yakobsonlar tomonidan aniq ilmiy-amaliy kuzatuvlarga asoslangan qarashlar ilgari surila boshlandi. Ayniqsa, neyrolingvistikaga oid qonun-qoidalarning amaliy jihatdan o'rganilishi esa N.Xomskiy maktabining paydo bo'lishi bilan yanada rivoj topdi. Xususan, hozirgi kunga qadar alohida e'tirof etiladigan E.Linnebergning quyidagi xulosalarini ta'kidlash lozim:

– til tug'ma xususiyatlari, har bir turning o'ziga xos jihatlari va biologik tabiati (miya funksiyalari) bilan belgilanadi;

- inson tilining ayrim xususiyatlari universaldir (barcha tillar uchun yagona asos mavjud);
- ontologik rivojlanish o'smirlik davriga qadar jismoniy yetilish orqali sodir bo'ladi.

Shu o'rinda Boduen de Kurtenening neyrolingvistika bo'yicha bildirgan quyidagi fikrlarini ham keltirishni joiz deb bildik: "...aslida havoda suzuvchi tillar emas, balki lisoniy tafakkurga ega insonlar mavjud" [4].

I.M.Sechenov, L.V.Shcherbalar ham bevosita Boduen de Kurtene maktabining zabardast izdoshlari sifatida neyrolingvistikaga oid muhim qarashlarini qoldirganlar. Neyrolingvistikaning psixologiyaga oid manbalari L.S.Vigotskiy tadqiqotlarida o'z aksini topgan.

Neyrolingvistikaning bugungi kundagi taraqqiyotida T.V.Axutina boshqarayotgan Rossiya neyrolingvistikasi asoschisi A.R.Luriyaning Moskva neyrolingvistlar maktabi hamda T.V.Chernigovskaya boshchiligidagi Balonov–Deglinning Peterburg maktabi alohida e'tirof etiladi [5].

Ta'kidlash lozimki, neyrolingvistika sohasidagi tadqiqotlar lingvistik ma'lumotlar miyaning qaysi qismida qayta ishlanishi, vaqt o'tishi bilan bu jarayon qanday o'zgarishi, til o'rganish va o'zlashtirishda til qismlari qanday munosabatda bo'lishi kabi masalalar ustida olib boriladi.

Davr o'tishi bilan texnika-texnologiyada erishilayotgan yutuqlar natijasida mutaxassislar nutq jarayoni mobaynida inson miyasi qay tarzda faoliyat ko'rsatishini o'rgana oladilar. Bugungi kunda til bilan aloqador ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash jarayoni ancha murakkab mexanizmni talab qilishi va bir qancha miya sohalarining birgalikdagi faoliyati bilan bog'liq ekanligi aniqlangan.

Til qanday tug'iladi, rivojlanadi, boshqariladi, umuman, insonning nutqiy qobiliyati, jummalarni tuzish, qolaversa, xorijiy tillarni o'rganish jarayonida miyaning ishlash mexanizmi qay tarzda boshqariladi – bularning barchasi bugungi neyrolingvistikaning asosiy tadqiq manbayi bo'lib qolmoqda.

Garchi dunyo ilmi miqyosida neyrolingvistika ham qadimiy, ham navqiron soha hisoblansa-da, o'zbek tilshunosligida bu borada keng fundamental miqyosda tadqiqotlar amalga oshirilmagan.

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ПСЕВДОНИМЫ КАК ОБЪЕКТ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ АНТРОПОНИМИКИ

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Аннотация. *Ushbu maqolada insonning lingvistik ongi, milliy-madaniy qadriyatlarini va dunyoqarashini aks ettiruvchi etnolingvistik birliklar – taxalluslar ko'rib chiqilgan va tahlil qilingan. Taxalluslarning qarindoshlikni anglatuvchi tushunchalardan shakllanishi, genetik rivojlanishi, shaxsiy idrok, fikrlash va ijtimoiy-siyosiy, iqtisodiy omillar ta'siri ostida paydo bo'lishi bilan farq qilishi ko'rsatilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *onomastika, antroponim, semantika, tushuncha, kognitiv belgilar, apellyativ, metaforizasiya.*

Псевдонимы по отношению к деятельности владельца делятся на три категории: литературные, сценические и политические псевдонимы.

В узбекском языке литературных псевдонимов больше, чем сценических.

В конце XVIII – начале XIX вв. в узбекской литературе появляются авторы, недовольные своим бедственным положением, которые выступают под вымышленными псевдонимами, например, Гулхани, Машраб, Махмур, Нишоти.

Есть много причин для принятия псевдонима – чтобы скрыть от цензоров свою мысль, автор политической фельетонно-критической статьи выбирает псевдоним.

Рассматривая образование русских и узбекских псевдонимов, можно выявить отношения между личными именами и псевдонимами.

В образовании некоторых псевдонимов мы эту связь видим, а в некоторых – нет, поэтому, как предлагает В.И. Супрун, внутреннюю ядерно-периферийную структуру можно разделить на два вида [5; 76]:

- 1) псевдонимы, связанные с настоящим именем автора: Салтыков-Щедрин, Алсу (Алсу Сафина), Анна Ахматова (Анна Горенко); Хакима (Хакима Абдурахим қизи), Анбар отин (Анбар Фармонкул қизи);
- 2) псевдонимы, не связанные с настоящим именем автора: Акунин Борис (Григорий Чхартишвили), Андрей Белый (Борис Бугаев); Увайсий (Жаҳон отин Сиддиқбобо қизи), Мутриба

(Саломат Парда қизи).

В узбекских псевдонимах XX в. наблюдается в основном усечение в фамилиях суффикса -ов (Гафур Гулям – Гафур Гуломов, Асқад Мухтор – Асқад Мухторов), а узбекские псевдонимы XV и XIX вв. в основном

не связаны с настоящим именем поэта (Хироми, Бобур, Фуркат).

В русских псевдонимах отдалённость от своего настоящего имени наблюдается с конца XIX – начала XX вв., например, Иегудаил Хламида, Максим Горький, Усталая, Тэффи, Артём Весёлый и т. д. Только после 40-х появляется связь псевдонима с настоящим именем, например, Вениамин Каверин – Вениамин Зильбер, Борис Полевой – Борис Кампов и т. д.

Рассмотрим узбекские псевдонимы XV в. Алишер Навои в своей тазкира прокомментировал тахаллусы некоторых писателей.

Муфлиси – узбекский поэт, живший в XV в., псевдоним поэта намекает на социальный статус автора [1; 34] (с араб. «муфлис» означает «обанкротившийся»); Мавлоно Кавкаби: «Он молодой астролог и он выбирает подходящее прозвище для своей науки» (МН, 86); Саккокий: тот, кто был мастером ножей, занимался изготовлением ножей, «саккок» в значении нож (Навоий. Наводир ушшабоб. 1959, 588); Райхони: «Райхони использовал тахаллус... из-за его отношения к роду деятельности ему дали прозвище Джамий. Он из царевичей и его псевдоним свидетельствует о том же» (МН, 76); Зулолий: «Не путайте свой разум, поэзия Зулолий чиста и ясна, он от того и получил тахаллус Зулолий (МН, 76); Амири – Мирзаолим Мушриф был во дворце хана канцелярским служащим, от того имеет псевдоним «мушриф» [7; 331]; Малик: «Он считал себя из поколения Малик-Равзанов, оттого его псевдоним Малик» (МН, 78); Бу-Али: «Он ходит как сумасшедший, если бы он не был сумасшедшим, у него не было бы псевдонима Бу-Али» (МН, 83), т. е. он не должен равнять себя с Абу Али ибн Сино [2; 64]; Жалол Таиб Шерози: «Несмотря на то, что занимался врачеванием, написал дастан «Гул и Навруз», который стал популярным среди молодежи» [4; 124]; Отои: «Отец Отои Исмаил был сыном Иброхима младшего брата Ахмада Яссави. Значит, Отои был потомком известных шейхов-отцов. По этой причине его псевдоним стал Отои, а не Атои от слова ота-отец» [3; 5] и др.

Кажется, что поэты выбирали тахаллусы по разным мотивам, например, в таких псевдонимах, как Шавки, Вафои, Якини, Мир Ишки, выражены надежды и мечты писателя. Учёные называют этот тип псевдонимов, полученными «для собственного духовного удовольствия» [6; 33].

Отсюда становится ясно, что в узбекских псевдонимах XV в. нет связи с именем и фамилией. Такое явление продолжается до начала XX в. Начиная с середины XX в. появляется связь псевдонимов с именем или фамилией, только под сатирическими произведениями ставят сезонные псевдонимы, не связанные с именем и фамилией, а имеющими большую связь с содержанием сатирического рассказа (Жулкунбой, Бойкуш, Думбулбой, Думбул жияни – А. Кодир, 1894–1938).

Псевдоним имеет некоторые уникальные особенности:

1. Один автор подписывается более чем одним псевдонимом. Таких можно назвать поэтами или политическими деятелями с множеством псевдонимов. Например, Алишер Навои рассказывает о 4-х псевдонимах Мавлоно Яхья Сайбака (XVI в.): «Сначала пользовался псевдонимом Туффони, потом Фаттохи, но Хумори и Асрори – тоже его псевдонимы» (МН, 17) [2; 74]. У узбекской поэтессы Мохларойим (1792–1842) было три псевдонима: Комила, Нодира, Макнуна [7; 220].

Писатель Абдулла Каххор (1907–1968) публикует в газетах и журналах стихи и статьи под псевдонимами Ниш, Норин Шилпик, Мавлоно Куфур, Гулёр, Эркабой, Элбой, Ялангоёк; Абдулла Кадыри публикуется под несколькими псевдонимами: Шоши, Алимов, Жулкунбой, Бойкуш, Думбулбой, Думбул жияни, Думбулдевова, Думбулугли, Калвак Махсумнинг жияни, жиян Совринбой, Овсар, Жиртаки, Шигой, Йуловчи; Шарафиддин Шамсиев имел более 27 псевдонимов: Шукрия, Доий, Шарафзода, Хуршид, Али Тошканди, Шукри, Тошканди, Шамсиддин Шароф, Шамсиддин Тошкандий, Дилхаста, Факир, Тожали, Ужар, Индамас, Инжик, Шукри, Шароф, Чаёнбай, Шохиди, Алин Шоши, Алон Шукри, Шоши, Элибой, Жаркинбой, Жиян [10; 218-220].

Такое множество псевдонимов было характерно только для писателей-сатириков и политиков, например, у А.П. Чехова (1860–1904) насчитываем более сорока псевдонимов:

только буквы: А.П., А-н Ч-те, Ан. Че-в, А. Ч, А. Че, Ан. Ч., Ан, Ч-е, Ч. Б. С., Ч. без С., С. Б. Ч., ...въ, Ц, Z;

выдуманные фамилии: Антоша Чехонте, Ч. Хонте, А. Чехонте, Г. Балдастов, Макар Балдастов, Шиллер Шекспирович Гёте, Василий Спиридонов, Сволачёв, М. Ковров, Дон Антонио Чехонте, полковник Кочкарев, Пурселепетанов, Акакий Тарантулов, Н. Захарьева, Смирнова, Кисляев, Шампанский;

словосочетания: *Вспыльчивый человек, Брат моего брата, Врач без пациентов, Человек без селезёнки, Юный старец, Прозаический поэт;*

предмет: *Гайка № 6, Гайка № 9;*

название птиц: *Грач, Архип Индейкин, Индейкин, Петухов;*

ироничные слова: *Дяденька, Антош, Зевуля, Проптер, Лаэрт, Рувер, Рувер и Ревур, Улисс, Некто, Известный, Анче;*

растение: *Крапива.*

Параллельно в эти же годы в Азербайджане в юмористических журналах печатают свои сатирические статьи, фельетоны, рассказы такие писатели, как Джалил Мамедкулузаде (1866–1932), Омар Фаик Нейманзаде (1872–1937). Рассмотрим некоторые псевдонимы азербайджанского писателя сатирика Омар Фаик Нейманзаде, у которого насчитываем более 20 псевдонимов: Бир Эронли (один Иранец), Умид (мечта), Ола Қарға (сорока), Лаглаги, Дардли (грустный), Бозор жужаси (базарный цыплёнок), Визвиза (жужание), Дали (чокнутый), Хейрани (удивлённый), Аччик суз (горькое слово), Мулла Кулу, Ийна (игла), Мумин (верующий) и т. д. У Джалила Мамедкулузаде было тоже много псевдонимов, но в основном он подписывался под псевдонимом Мулла Насреддин, а также выпускал сатирический журнал под названием «Мулла Насреддин». Он тоже, как и Чехов, был мастером коротких рассказов – фельетонов [11].

Таблица 1

Число сезонных псевдонимов принятых русскими писателями*

№	Ф.И.О. русских и узбекских писателей	Число псевдонимов
1.	А.П. Чехов	Более 40
2.	Иехил-Лейб Арьевич Файнзильберг	10
3.	М.Горький	11
4.	Кир Булычёв	11

Число сезонных псевдонимов принятых узбекскими писателями*

№	Ф.И.О. русских и узбекских писателей	Число псевдонимов
1.	А.П. Чехов	Более 40
2.	Иехил-Лейб Арьевич Файнзильберг	10
3.	М.Горький	11
4.	Кир Булычёв	11

* Составлено автором диссертации.

Хотелось бы отметить и то, что у некоторых псевдонимов наблюдается несколько значений, например, у основы псевдонима Садриддина Айни айн 48 значений.

Не отставали от сатириков и политики, которые прибегали к разным маневрам. Из-за пристального внимания общества политик были вынуждены скрывать своё имя. Особенно это наблюдается перед революциями, с ростом народного недовольства над властью имущих. Например, в России Зиновьев, Григорий Евсеевич – Овсей-Герш Аронович Радомысльский; Каменев, Лев Борисович – Лев Борйсович Рóзенфельд; Камо – Симóн Аршáкович Тер-Петросян; Кйров – Сергёй Мирóнович Кóстриков; Молотов – Вячеслав Михайлович Скрябин; Троцкий Лев Давидович (Перó, Антид Ото, Л. Седóв) – Лейба Давидович Бронштéйн и др.

В Узбекистане Махмуд Максудович Ходиев – поэт, писатель, журналист, общественный деятель, главный редактор общественно-политических изданий «Фергана» и «Еленге». Он являлся

секретарём Антирелигиозной комиссии и Комиссии по борьбе за раскрепощение женщин (Худжум), выступал под псевдонимом Бату[9,]; Косим Солихов (1902–1938), узбекский журналист, драматург и критик, джадид – Зиё Саид; Абдулла Бадриев (1893 –1936) – Абдулла Бадрий; Ашурали Зохиоров (1885–1937), известный просветитель, джадид – Ашурали Зохирий; Отажон Хошимов (1905–1938), литературный критик – Хошим Отажон; Шокир Сулаймонов (1900–1942) – Шокир Сулаймон.

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TABIAT UNSURLARINI ATOVCHI NOMLARNING LINGVOMADANIY XUSUSIYATI

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассмотрены лингвокультурные особенности единиц, называющих природные элементы, которые являются составной частью устойчивых единиц узбекского языка.

Ключевые слова: лингвокультурология, устойчивая единица, лингвокультурный код, культурная информация, лингвокультурные характеристики, национально-культурное единство.

Xalqlarning bir-birini o'zaro tushunishi uchun lingvistik tadqiqotlar zarurati, milliy madaniyatlar muloqoti allaqachon umume'tirof etilgan haqiqatdir. Boisi, u yoki bu til o'z egasi tafakkuri, dunyoqarashi, turmush tarzi, qadriyatlar, fe'l-atvori, e'tiqod va an'analari o'zida yorqin ifodalaydi. Aniqki, "Xalq madaniyati til orqali verballashadi, aynan til madaniyatining tayanch, asosiy tushunchalarini harakatga keltiradi va ularni belgilar ko'inishida, ya'ni so'zlar vositasida ifoda etadi [5; 15]". Bugungi davrda muayyan til lisoniy birliklarini o'zi mansub millat madaniyati bilan aloqadorlikda o'rganuvchi lingvomadaniyatshunoslik jahon tilshunosligidagi yetakchi hamda istiqbolli yo'nalishlardan biriga aylandi, tilshunoslikning mustaqil yo'nalishi sifatida tan olindi. Mazkur sohaning obyekti, tilshunos olim Durdona Xudoyberganova ta'kidlaganidek, "Lisoniy belgining ma'nosi va madaniy birikuvidan tarkib topuvchi, semantikasida madaniy axborot yaqqol namoyon bo'luvchi til birliklari, ya'ni frazeologizmlar, etalonlar, ramzlar, metaforalar, turg'un o'xshatishlar, nutqiy etiketkalar, urf-odat va marosimga doir so'zlar, topishmoqlar, milliy realiyalar, arxetiplar, mifologemalar, lakunalar, pretsedent birliklar va b." [6; 41]. O'zida o'zi tegishli millatning yuksak ma'naviyati, milliy tafakkuri, ruhiyatining o'ziga

xosligini yaqqol aks ettiruvchi lingvomadaniy birliklar (lingvokulturemalar) sanaluvchi "...barqaror birliklarda asrlar davomida shakllangan, asoslangan, umummilliy xarakterdagi madaniy kod – obrazlar saqlanadi" [4; 21]. O'zbek xalqi barqaror birliklarida o'zbek millati milliy mentalitetining rang-barang qirralari, milliy qiyofasi o'z aksini topadi. O'zbek xalqi adabiy merosida milliy o'zlikni namoyon qiluvchi barqaror birliklar bisyor. Ularning lingvomadaniy mohiyatini ochib berish uchun teran va asosli tadqiqotlarni yaratishimiz lozim.

O'zbek tili barqaror birliklarida tayanch qism bo'lgan tabiat unsurlarini nomlovchi birliklar: olov, tuproq, havo, suv so'zlari o'zida madaniy axborot tashiydi. Quyida berilayotgan tahlil buning isbotidir.

Ibtidoiy davrlarda kishilar dastlab olovdan qo'rqishgan, keyinchalik undan o'zlarini himoya qilish uchun vositasi sifatida foydalanishgan. Zardushtiylik dinidan ham ayonki, ba'zi insonlar olovga sig'inishgan, uni ulug'lab, muqaddas hisoblashgan. Bugungi kunda ham ayrim hududlarda o'lik chiqqan uyda uch kungacha olov yoqilmasligi, yangi kelin-kuyovlarning olov atrofida aylanishlari va shu kabi odatlar buning isbotidir.

Ko'zidan o't chaqnamoq, oyog'idan o't chaqnamoq, yuragiga o't solmoq, tovonidan (tuyog'idan) o't chaqnamoq iboralarida o't (olov) so'zi milliy-madaniy ma'noga ega. Ko'zlaridan o't chaqnamoq iborasi "g'azablanmoq, jahl qilmoq" ma'nolarida qo'llaniladi. "Sevinmoq, xursand bo'lmoq" ma'nolarini ifodalovchi ko'zlari chaqnamoq iborasi tarkibiga qo'shilgan o't (olov) so'zi undagi ijobiy buyoqdorlikni yo'qotib, uning salbiy ma'noda ifodalanishiga sabab bo'lgan. Serjahl va g'azab otiga mingan kishi ko'zlarining me'yordan katta ochilishi olovning shiddat bilan yonish holatiga o'xshatilgan. O't (olov) leksemasining milliy-madaniy xususiyati so'zlashuv nutqida faol qo'llanuvchi yuragiga o't solmoq, yuragiga o't bermoq iboralarida yanada yaqqol namoyon bo'ladi. Yigit-qizlar o'rtasida faol qo'llanuvchi yuragiga o't solmoq iborasida o't lingvomadaniy kodi sevgi uchquni, kurashga shaylangan polvonlarga nisbatan qo'llanuvchi yuragiga o't bermoq iborasida esa madad, mador, kuch-quvvat ma'nolarini anglatadi. Go'ng tepada o't yonar (Bo'ri) topishmog'ida esa o't lingvomadaniy kodi yirtqich bo'ri ramzi sifatida keltirilgan.

Quruqning o'tiga ho'l kuyar, Quruq shoxning oloviga ho'l shox ham yonar maqollari To'qayga o't ketsa, ho'l-u quruq baravar yonadi maqolining variantlaridir. Bilamizki, agar biror yerni olov olsa, u yerdagi va uning yaqin atrofidagi barcha narsa yonib kulga aylanadi. Ushbu maqollarda o't-olov lingvomadaniy kodi urush, ofat-falokat ma'nolarini aks ettirib, bu vositasida biror-bir falokat yuz bersa, hamma baravar aziyat chekishi tasvirlangan.

Topishmoqlarda quyosh olov lingvomadaniy kodi orqali yorqin tasvirlangani kuzatildi. Quyidagi topishmoqlar fikrimiz dalilidir: Hu uzoqda Olatov, Olatovda bir olov, Tunda unga tegmasdan Ko'tarar ko'kka birov (Quyosh); Ko'kka chiqib olov-shar, Bizga ziyo ulashar (Quyosh). Tunda yonar sonsiz cho'g', Kunduz izlasang ham yo'q (Yulduz); Tunda ko'rib, cho'g' deysiz, Tongda ko'rib yo'q deysiz (Yulduz) topishmoqlarida yulduz qip-qizarib, yarqirab turadigan cho'g'ga taqqoslangan. Mazkur topishmoqlarda yulduz cho'g' lingvomadaniy kodi zamirida yashiringan.

El yuragi pok bo'lsa, Yov yuragi xok bo'lar maqolidagi xok lingvomadaniy kodi vositasida agar el, inson yuragi pok bo'lsa, dushman, raqib tarafning yer bilan yakson bo'lishi aytilgan. Bu maqol orqali odamlar sofdillikka, birlikka chaqirilgan. Er bo'l, er bo'lmasang, qaro yer bo'l maqolidagi qaro yer lingvomadaniy kodi El yuragi pok bo'lsa, Yov yuragi xok bo'lar maqolidagi xok lingvomadaniy kodi bildirayotgan ma'no-mazmunga teng.

Kuchingni yelga berma, yerga ber. Bunda yel kodi "behuda, bekor, foydasiz" ma'nolarini anglatadi. Mazkur maqol orqali kishilarga kuchingni yel, ya'ni shamolga berma, yerga ber: gul ek, daraxt ek, yerni bog'-u bo'stonga aylantir deb nasihat qilinmoqda. Kuchingni yelga berma, yerga ber maqolining birinchi gapidan anglashiladigan mazmun yelga uchmoq, yelga uchirmoq (yoki sovrumoq) iboralarida ham ifodalanadi. Yelga uchmoq iborasi havoga ketmoq iborasi bilan, yelga uchirmoq (yoki sovrumoq) iborasi havoga sovrumoq (yoki sovrilmoq) iborasi bilan ma'nodosh bo'lib, bir xil ma'noni ifodalayapti. Ushbu iboralarda yel so'zi bilan havo so'zi o'zaro ma'nodosh hisoblanadi.

Suv – dunyoni tashkil etuvchi to'rtta ramziy asosiy elementlardan biri, birlamchi materiyaning ramzi. Qadimgi mif, rivoyat va hikoyalarda daryolar xudolar sifatida tasvirlangan (Misrda Nil, Hindistonda Gang daryosi va boshqalar muqaddas hisoblangan, ular xudolar sifatida tasvirlangan). Turli millat xalq og'zaki ijodiga xos bo'lgan barqaror birikmalar kuzatilganda, suvning hayot manbayi sifatida qadrlanishi ayon bo'ldi. Jumladan, "Rus folklorida biz daryo nomini uchratamiz: Volga – ona, uning o'z irodasi va xarakteri bor, u hukmdor va qo'riqchi.

Xristian adabiyotida suv, daryo, ko'l hayot va xristian ta'limotining ramzi hisoblanadi. Suv va suv manbalari onaning ramzi bo'lib, tug'ilish, ayollik tamoyili, hayot manbayi bilan bog'liq" [1; 79]. Dono xalqimiz ham bir

turkum maqollarida suvni obi-hayot deb e'zozlaydi, uning qadriga yetish, tejab-tergash, ifloslantirmay, toza va pokiza saqlash lozimligi yuzasidan nasihat qiladi. Bu hol ular yaratgan bir necha maqollarda, jumladan, Suv oltindan aziz; Suv – zar, Suvchi zargar; Suv keldi, nur keldi; El hayoti yer bilan, yer hayoti suv bilan kabi maqollarida yorqin namoyon bo'lgan.

Islom dinining muqaddas kitobi "Qur'oni karim"ning "Baqara" surasida "U sizlar uchun Yerni "poyandoz", osmonni "bino" qilib qo'ydi va osmondan suv tushirib, u sababli sizlarga rizq sifatida mevalar (mevali daraxtlar) ni undirdi" [3; 4] degan oyat bor. Bundan ma'lumki, butun borliqning boshlang'ich asosi, ibtidosi to'rt unsur (suv, havo, tuproq, olov)ning biri suvdur. Obi hayot ta'rifini olgan ne'matni atovchi suv so'zi barqaror birikmalarda keng qo'llaniladi. Bu suvning hayot manbai ekanligidan, unga insonning ehtiyoji benihoya ko'p bo'lganligidan hamdir. Mazkur fikrimiz suv bilan havoday (nihoyatda, juda-juda) iborasidayoq o'z isbotini topadi.

O'zbek xalqi barqaror birliklarida suvga inson, rizq-nasiba, yorug'lik, poklik; ofat-falokat ramzi sifatida qaraladi. Jumladan, Qulunli biyadan quduq suvi ortmas maqolida quduq suvi rizq-nasiba – oziq-ovqat, noz-ne'mat, yashash uchun keraklik yegulik ma'nosini bildiradi.

Ariq qazimasang, otizga suv chiqmas maqoli Mehnatsiz rohat yo'q; Mehnat qilmay rohat ko'rmas, Urug' sepmay ekin o'rmas; Yer qazimasang, oltin chiqmas, Qarmoq solmasang – baliq maqollarini yodga soladi. Sababi, mazkur maqollarning barchasida Ariq qazimasang, otizga suv chiqmas maqolidan anglashiladigan ma'no – har qanday rohat ortida mashaqqatli mehnat borligi uqtirilgan. Ariq qazimasang, otizga suv chiqmas maqolidagi suv lingvomadaniy kodi "yorug'lik", rohat-farog'atda yashash ramzi bo'lib kelgan. Suv lingvomadaniy kodi vositasida har bir mehnat qilgan kishining "otizi", ya'ni dasturxonni noz-ne'matlarga to'la bo'lishiga ishora qilingan.

O't bilan suv – tilsiz yov; Suvning ishi o'pirmoq, O'tning ishi kuydirmoq; Suvning ko'rinishi muloyim, Bag'ri – tosh maqollarida "Suv garchi sekin, muloyim, beozor oqqani bilan, suzishni bilmagan yo ehtiyot bo'lmagan kishini g'arq qiladi" deyilgan hamda suvning, o'tning ana shunday xavfliligini ta'kidlab, undan saqlanish choralarini ko'rish zarurligi uqtirilgan [2; 345]. Shu boisdan ham "O't balosidan, suv balosidan o'zing saqla" degan ezga niyat qilinib, buning har bir duoda aytilishi odat bo'lib qolgan.

Dunyoni suv bossa, to'pig'igacha chiqmaslik iborasi o'taketgan beg'am, haddan tashqari beparvo odamga nisbatan qo'llaniladi. Bunda suv lingvomadaniy kodi ofat, falokat ma'nosini ifodalaydi. Suvga tushsa cho'kmaslik, suv kelsa – simirmoq, tosh kelsa – kemirmoq iboralarda yoki dunyoni suv olsa, o'rdakka ne g'am maqolidagi suv lingvomadaniy kodi dunyoni suv bossa, to'pig'igacha chiqmaslik iborasidagi suv lingvomadaniy kodi anglatgan ma'noga yaqin. Boisi, bu iboralarda ham suv lingvomadaniy kodi og'ir sinov, qiyinchilik ma'nosini o'zida saqlagan. Sirtiga suv tegizmaslik iborasida suv lingvomadaniy kodi dog' (kishining o'z sha'niga dog' tushiradigan xatti-harakat qilmaslik) ma'nosida kelgan. Siqib suvini chiqarmoq iborasida suv lingvomadaniy kodi oxirgi madori, yakuniy kuchi degan ma'noga ishora qiladi. Ushbu ibora biror kishini u yoki bu muammo, masala bilan bog'liq bo'lgan voqealarda tergashga, unga zulm o'tkazib madori qolguncha qiynashga nisbatan aytiladi. Bir odam ariq qaziydi, ming odam suv ichadi; Bir tomchi suv chumoliga daryo ko'rinadi; Yer – xazina, suv – gavhar maqollarida suv lingvomadaniy kodi ijobiy buyoqqa ega bo'lib, rizq-nasiba ma'nosini ifodalaydi.

Tagiga suv quymoq iborasi amalidan, obro'e'tiboridan mahrum qilmoq ma'nosiga teng. Bunda suv lingvomadaniy kodi suv so'zining oquvchi, oqib ketuvchi ma'nolarini o'zida saqlab, mansab, amaldan ayrilishni bildiradi.

Suvga suyanma, yovga sig'inma maqolining Suvga suyanma, folga ishonma ko'rinishi ham bor. Suvga suyanma, yovga sig'inma maqolida suv lingvomadaniy kodi vositasida suvning oqishiga ishora qilinib, o'zganing fikri, o'zganing aqli insonning o'ziga o'zining fikridek foyda keltirmasligi nazarda tutilgan. Suv bunda puch narsa, beburd kimsa ramzini ifodalagan. Ma'lumki, bu barqaror birikma birovning aqliga suyanib ish qiluvchilarga, birovning fikri bilan yuradigan mustaqil bo'lmagan kishilarga qarata aytiladi.

Suv lingvomadaniy kodi ba'zi maqollarda fe'l-atvori, yurish-turishi, qilish-qilmishi, gap-so'zi odamiylikdan uzoq bo'lgan shaxslarni bildirib kelgan. Ya'ni "suyuq" kishilar suvga tashbeh qilinib,uyuq odam deyilgan, hozirda ham hayotga yengil-yelpi qaraydigan odamlarga qarata shunday deyiladi. Ushbu ma'no-mazmun Suvni ming qaynatsang ham quyulmas maqolidagi suv lingvomadaniy kodi vositasida yanada aniq ifodalangan. O'zbek tili barqaror birliklarining bir nechtasida suv so'zi madaniy ma'nolariga ega bo'lib o'zi ishtirokida shakllangan barqaror birliklardagi milliy-madaniy bo'yoqni ta'minlagan.

O'zbek tili barqaror birliklarida tayanch qism bo'lgan lingvomadaniy kodlarning mohiyatini ochib berish, bu borada teran va asosli tadqiqotlarni yaratishimiz lozim. Chunki u yoki bu madaniyat o'zi mansub tildagi lingvomadaniy kodlarda o'z ifodasini topadi. Lingvomadaniy kodlar to'liq idrok etilmasa, u qatnashgan matn yoki birikmaning mazmun-mohiyati butunicha anglashilmaydi. Har qanday millatning lingvomadaniyatini to'liq idrok etish uchun uning madaniyat kodlarining ham ahamiyati katta.

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O'ZBEK TILSHUNOSLIGI VA TURKOLOGIYADA BARQAROR BIRLIKLAR TASNIFI

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Аннотация. В данной статье освещена проблема классификации устойчивых (паремиологических) единиц в узбекском и тюркском языкознании, указаны их лингвостилистические особенности, приведены статистические данные их распространения. Также предложены рекомендации по расширению сферы использования паремиологических единиц.

Ключевые слова: устойчивые сочетания, диалектная парема, лингвостатистика, классификация, загадки и поговорки, тюркские устойчивые единицы.

O'zbek tilshunosligida barqaror, turg'un birikmalar doirasida asosan ibora va tasviriy ifoda vositalariga nisbatan munosabat bildirish mavjud bo'lib, bu holat maktab darsliklarida ham uzoq yillar shu an'anaviy qarash ko'p yillar mavjud edi. Hozirgi zamonaviy tilshunoslik esa yangicha va kengroq yondashuvni talab etmoqda. Yer sharida mavjud har bir millat, xalq ona tilining milliy koloriti undagi madaniy xoslangan lingvistik birliklarda aks etadi. Mazkur unsurlar orasida fanda paremiologik birliklar deya nom olgan barqaror qurilmalar ham borki, ular millat olam manzarasini ifodalash bilan birga milliy lisoniy ongning uzviy, ajralmas, hayot tajribalari mahsuli hisoblanadi.

O'TILda paremiologik (yunoncha paroimiya – masal, ramzli hikoya) birliklar turg'un ibora, maqol, matal sifatida izohlangan [16; 650]. "O'zbek tilining paremiologik lug'ati"da paremiologiya hikmat+fan tarzida talqin etilib, "maqol, matal, aforizmlar singari hikmatli iboralar butunligini o'rganuvchi fan" deya izohlanadi, o'zga lug'atlarda esa lotincha parema – "barqaror", logos – "ta'limot" ma'nolarini anglatishi aytilgan [9; 5].

O'zbek tilshunosligida paremiologik birliklarning til va nutq hodisasi sifatidagi ahamiyatini yoritishga doir bir qator ishlar amalga oshirilgan. Jumladan, maqollarning sintaktik jihatlarini X.Abdurahmonov, maqol va matallar leksikasi, ularning dialektal xususiyatlari M.Sadriddinova tomonidan o'rganilgan.

Maqol, matal atama (maqol va matal)larini izohlash va ularning farqlarini ajratib tasniflashda S.Ro'zimboyev va H.Ro'zmetovlar oltita e'tiborli jihatni ko'zda tutgan [12; 27]. Ularning fikricha, maqol va

matallar grammatik asoslar miqdoriga ko'ra teng bo'lishi mumkin, lekin matallar asosida tugal bo'lmagan ifodaning yotishi, maqollar singari qofiyaga, ohangdoshlikka ega emasligi ular orasidagi differensial belgilarni yuzaga chiqaradi. Matallarda fikr (xuddi maqollar singari) obrazli, ko'chma ma'noda qo'llanilishi mumkin, lekin ularda fikr va muhokamaning tugal natijasini ko'rmaymiz [19; 18].

O'zbek tilshunosligida maqollar, matallar, hikmatli so'zlar kabi barqaror birikmalarni ularning lingvistik xususiyatiga ko'ra tasnif qilish masalasiga XX asr ikkinchi yarmidan boshlab e'tibor qaratildi. 1984-yilda nashr etilgan "O'zbek tilining paremiologik lug'ati"da 8449 ta birlik jamlangan bo'lib (1-jadval), ular orasida N.Ostroumov to'plamidan keltirilgan 575 ta parema mavjud. Shuningdek, lug'atdan 289 ta tarixiy paremalar, M.Koshg'ariyning "Devonu lug'otit turk" asaridan 197 ta, Muhammad Sharif Gulhaniyning "Zarbulmasal"idan 119 ta hamda 2 ta individual-muallif (H.Olimjon – Baliq suvsiz, shoir xalqsiz yashay olmaydi; M.Shayxzoda – Basharning ozodligi – dunyoning obodligi singari) parema(aforizm)lari joy olgan. 8449-1182=7267 ta paremiologik birlik esa o'zbek xalq maqollari, matallaridan, turli xil ilmiy manbalardan jamlangan. Biroq lug'atda PBlar alohida ajratib berilmagan.

1-jadval

№	Manbalar	Miqdori	Jami
1.	N.Ostroumov to'plamida ifodalangan paremalar	575 ta	8449 ta
2.	Tarixiy paremalar	289 ta	
3.	"Devonu lug'otit turk" asaridan	197 ta	
4.	"Zarbulmasal" asaridan	119 ta	
5.	Individual-muallif aforizmlari	2 ta	
6.	O'zbek tilidagi turli manbalardan	7267 ta	

1-jadval. "O'zbek tilining paremiologik lug'ati"da jamlangan birliklar tasnifi

PL (paremiologik lug'at) tarkibidan o'sha davr manzarasini akslantiruvchi, hukmron mafkura manfaatlarini ifoda etuvchi: Sotsialistik zamon – mehnatkash omon; Bog'li kolxoz – yog'li kolxoz; Kolxoz – baraka daryosi; Kolxoz – ishlaganga tishlatadi; Kolxoz – kengchilik, mo'lchilik; Paxta – kolxoz ro'zg'orining fili; Paxtazor – mardlar maydoni kabi paremalar ham o'rin olganki, ular til va madaniyatning zamon va makon kesimidagi mutanosibligi, xalq qaysi davrda, qanday jamiyat g'oyasi bilan yashayotganiga ishora beruvchi o'ziga xos "aniqlagichlardir".

Sh.Shomaqsudov va Sh.Shorahmedovlarning hammualliflikdagi "Nega shunday deymiz?" nomli to'plamida 942 ta maqollar turli xil variantlari bilan izohlangan [14; 352]. Maqollarning leksik-semantik xususiyatlarini izohlashda rivoyatlar, afsonalar, hikoyalar va daliliy manbalar asos qilib olingan. Biroq bundagi barqaror birliklar morfologik, grammatik tomondan yoritilmagan. Variantlari va mazmundoshlari aralash holda berilgan, ba'zi maqollarda ular mutanosib kelmagan. Shunga qaramay, manbada maqollar etimologiyasiga murojaat, maqollarning aniq va to'g'ri variantda ifodalanishi, eng muhimi, to'plamning "O'zbek tili paremiologik izohli lug'ati"ning debochasi ekanligi o'ta ahamiyatlidir.

Ushbu mualliflar tomonidan 1990-yilda "Hikmatnoma" nomi ostida o'zbek xalq maqollarining izohli lug'ati, undan keyin 2032 ta maqollarning (variantlari bilan 20 mingdan ortiq) "Ma'nolar mahzani" nomli izohli to'plami yaratildi. Ushbu lug'at va to'plamda ham maqollarning lingvistik jihatlari tavsiflanmaydi. Biroq mazkur lug'at keyingi istiqbolli ishlar uchun muhim manba vazifasini bajarishi bilan e'tiborlidir.

Ma'lumki, paremiologik birliklar sirasiga maqollar, matallar va hikmatli so'zlar (aforizmlar) qamrab olinadi. H.Berdiyev va R.Rasulovlar muallifligidagi "O'zbek tili paremiologik lug'ati"da hikmatli so'zlar PBlarning uchinchi turi sifatida keltiriladi. Garchi muallif va xalq hikmatli so'zlari didaktik maqsadda adabiy-badiiy jihatdan to'plab o'rganilgan, tavsif etilgan, maqollarning esa adabiyotshunoslik, folklorshunoslik va birmuncha lingvistik tomonlari o'rganilgan bo'lsa ham, o'zbek tilshunosligida matallar va hikmatli so'zlarning tavsifiga alohida ahamiyat berilmagan. Shu jihatdan olib qaraganda paremiologik birliklarni tasniflash zarurati yuzaga keladi va biz ularni quyidagicha tasniflashni maqsadga muvofiq deb bildik (2-jadval):

Tashqi tasnif (maqol, matal, hikmatli soʻzlar)												
BARQAROR BIRIKMALAR	Maqollar											
	Ichki tasnif	Alifbo tartibida	Tematik tasnif	Leksik tasnif	Morfologik tasnif	Sintaktik tasnif	Grammatik tasnif	Dialektal tasnif	Koʻchma maʼnosiga koʻra tasnif	Leksikografiik tasnif	Lingvostatik tasnif	Areal tasnif
	Matallar											
	Ichki tasnif	Alifbo tartibida	Tematik tasnif	Leksik tasnif	Morfologik tasnif	Sintaktik tasnif	Grammatik tasnif	Dialektal tasnif	Bir va koʻp maʼnoliligiga koʻra tasnif	Leksikografik tasnif	Lingvostatistik tasnif	Areal tasnif
	Iboralar											
	Ichki tasnif	Alifbo tartibida	Dialektal tasnif	Mavzusiga koʻra tasnif	Tarkibiga koʻra tasnif	Tuzilishiga koʻra tasnif	Lingvodidaktik tasnif	Leksikografik tasnif	Areologik tasnif	Etnik guruhga xoslanganlik	Lingvostatistik tasnif	Leksik tasnif

2-jadval. Oʻzbek tilida paremiologik birliklarning tasnifiy jihatlari

Paremiologik birliklarning tashqi tasnifiga "topishmoq"lar ham mansubdir [8; 374]. Shu kabi, sintaktik qurilmaning barqarorlik tabiatidan kelib chiqib, xalq jonli nutqidagi "tez aytishlar"ni ham paremiologik birlikka kiritishimiz mumkin. Bunga sabab bu birliklarga yaqinlasha tilshunosligimizda tadqiq obyekti sifatida qaralmagan, faqat adabiyotshunoslik, aniqrogʻi folklorshunoslik doirasidagina oʻrganilgan. Gʻani gʻildirakni gʻizillatib, gʻildiratdi, qishda qatiq qotib qoldi, oq choynakka koʻk qopqoq, koʻk choynakka oq qopqoq, qishda kishmish pishmashmish, pishsa kishmish qishmashmish kabi tez aytishlar azaldan hech bir oʻzgarishsiz hatto transformatsiyaga uchramagan holatda bugungacha til xazinasida oʻz oʻrnini yoʻqotmasdan kelmoqda. Yer tagida oltin qoziq, u hammaga boʻlar oziq (sabzi), kichkina dekchi, ichi toʻla mixcha (anor), oʻzi bitta koʻzi mingta (elak), qat-qat qatlama, aqling boʻlsa tashlama (kitob) singari topishmoqlar ham nutqiy xususiyatlarini saqlagan holatda barqarorlik qoidasini buzgani yoʻq.

Topishmoqlar va tez aytishlar yaratilishiga koʻra tashqi jihatdan hikmatli soʻzlarga oʻxshaydi. Yaʼni ular ham "muallif ijodi" va "xalq ogʻzaki ijodiga mansublik" singari ikki xil belgini ifoda etadi. Ikkinchi toifadagi belgida umummilliy til va uning dialektlariga xos lisoniy tabiat boʻy koʻrsatadi. Shu tufayli PBlarni dialektal jihatdan oʻrganish ham muhim ahamiyatga egadir. Ayniqsa, hududiy jihatdan yigʻilgan paremiologik birliklar milliy tilimiz ravnaqi uchun amaliy ahamiyatga ega.

Janubiy Surxondaryo oʻzbek shevalarida mavjud paremiologik birliklar oʻziga xos jihatlari bilan ajralib turadi. Masalan, i:tti:ng laħādi:ni qī:di:rib (ilojsiz narsani qidirib, imkoni boʻlmagan ishni bajarishga urinish (Jar.)), bilāk ki:mnikī, ki:ji:z ošānīki (Ang.) – kigiz tayyorlash juda murakkab jarayon boʻlib, unda bilak kuchidan unumli foydalaniladi. Kigizning sifatli va chiroyli chiqishida bilakdagi kuch muhimligi nazarda tutilgan. mi:s kasā mi:stār kasā, mi:s keli:n misopir keli:n (maqolning birinchi qismidagi "mistar" soʻzi chizgʻich maʼnosida boʻlib, bu soʻz A.Navoiyning "Hayrat ul-abror" asarida ham uchraydi. Ikkinchi jumlada musofir leksemasining semantik maydonida ifoda topgan kelin semasida bir vaqtning oʻzida baho semasi va ijtimoiy komponentning faollashuvini kuzatishimiz mumkin. Yaʼni uzoqdan, begona joydan kelgan kelin oltin, kumush kabi qimmatbaho metalga emas, balki misga qiyos etilgan. Mazkur maqolning "Yaxshi qiz mahalladan chiqmaydi" maqoliga zid qoʻyilishini inobatga olsak, oʻzbek lingvomadaniyatida qarindosh boʻlmagan va ustiga-ustak, musofir kelinga oʻgay koʻz bilan qaralgani maʼlum boʻladi.

A.Omonturdiyev va B.Rahmonovlarning "Surxondaryo dialektal-etnografik maqollarining izohli lug'ati"da vohadagi sheva maqollari hududiy (tumanlarning ayrim mahallalari) jihatdan ajratilib, ko'chimi, umumxalq va dialektal varianti tasniflangan. Bu ish o'zbek shevalari barqaror birikmalarining mukammal izohli lug'atini tuzishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

T.Mirzayev, A.Musoqulov, B.Sarimsoqovlar tomonidan tuzilgan "O'zbek xalq maqollari" [10; 496] to'plamida 70 ta turli xil mavzuga bo'lingan maqollar tarkibida uchragan ayrim sheva va eskirgan so'zlarning kichik izohli lug'ati berilgan bo'lib, ushbu to'plam ham dialektal maqollar tadqiqi uchun amalga oshiriladigan ishlar uchun zarurdir.

Turkiy tillarning barchasida (dunyo tillarida bo'lganidek) paremiologik birliklar mavjuddir. Ularni tasniflash, tadqiq etish borasida tilshunoslarning qarashlari qaysidir tomondan bir-biridan farq qilsa ham ularni bog'lab turuvchi o'xshash unsurlar juda ko'p. Bu ularning tarixiy ildizi bir ekanligidan dalolatdir. Buni Mahmud Koshg'ariy XI asrda "Devonu lug'otit turk" asari orqali turkiy xalqlarning turli sohalar, xususan, paremiologik birliklar masalasida ham mushtarakligini asoslab berdi. Jumladan, muallif 300 ga yaqin maqol (asarda "saw" atamasi bilan keladi)lar orqali umumturkiy xalqlarning madaniyati, kundalik hayoti, turmush tarzi, ma'naviyati bir ekanligini namoyon etadi

[6; 168-169]. Buni o'zbeklarning "maqol", "otalar so'zi"; turklarning "atasozu"; ozarbayjonlarning "atalar sozu"; turkmanlarning "naqyl ve atalar sozi"; qozoqlarning "babalar sozi", "maqal-matel"; qirg'izlarning "naqal-lakaplar"; qoraqalpoqlarning "naqyl-maqal", "mysal sez", "nəsiyat sez"; tatarlarning "mokal" deb atashida ham kuzatamiz. Bu turkiy tillar barqaror birikmalari semantik strukturasiyning bir-biriga muvofiq kelishini hech bir lug'atsiz anglash mumkinligini ifodalaydi. Qiyoslang, qq./: Juoiryanlar emes, buyiryan aldi – o'zb. Yugurgannikimas buyurganniki; Ne ekser, soni orasan – Nima eksang, shuni o'rasan; qijmildayan qir asar – Qimirlagan qir oshar; Bir kojlek burin tozdiryan – Bir ko'ylak ko'p (oldin;ortiq) yirtmoq; Kiymeser de tonij bolsin – Berarga noning bo'lmasa ham, shirin so'zing bo'lsin; Yer basina kun tuosa, yetigi menen suov kesher – Suv kelsa simirib, tosh kelsa kemirib kabi (ayrim fonetik jihatlarini mustasno qilgan holda) ikki tildagi bir xil paremalar bu turkiy xalqlarning har tomonlama uyg'unligini asoslaydi.

Qirg'iz va o'zbek xalq maqollarida ham bu xil holat uchraydi. B.Kerimjanova [4; 188], S.Musayev [5; 188] ishlarida maqol va matallarning farqli va o'xshash jihatlarini izohlangan. Vaqting ketdi – naqding ketdi – Ubakittan utturganiy – iriskidan kuru kalganiy; O'zni kovlasang o'char, qoshningni kovlasang ko'char – O'ttu ko'lo'son ochot, qonshunu ko'lo'son ko'chot" (var. diss. ketti kovlasang...chiqadi) kabi muqobillik matallarda uchramaydi.

M.Temirova o'zbek va qirg'iz xalq maqollarining tadqiqida ekvivalentlikni to'rt guruhga bo'lib tasniflaydi: fonetik, leksik, morfologik va sintaktik. Shuningdek, funksional jihatlarini yetti guruhga ajratib tahlil qiladi. Turkiy xalqlarga xos bo'lgan merganlik, ovchilikka aloqador: Ovchi qancha ov hiylalarini bilsa, ayiq ham shuncha qochish yo'llarini biladi – mergen tileyt kiyikti, kiyik tileyt biyikti", ot haqidagi Yolg'iz otning changi chiqmas, changi chiqsa ham dong'i chiqmas –x al'yiz attin çarji çikpajt, çarji çiksada danği çikpajt maqollari leksik-semantik va sintaktik qurilishi jihatidan bir-biriga mos kelishi yuqoridagi fikrlarimizni tasdiqlaydi.

Bu holat muomala odobi haqidagi o'zbek-qozoq maqollarida ham uchraydi: zaman qapi:b ajtadi, yaqsi: tavi:p ajtadi [17; 217-324]; ajti:lgan soz, ati:lgan oq. Shuni alohida ta'kidlash lozimki, P.Bakirovning rus, o'zbek, qozoq tili materiallari asosida nominasentrik maqollarining semantik va struktur xususiyatlariga bag'ishlangan tadqiqot ishi [1; 286] ham har jihatdan nafaqat turkiy xalqlar, shu bilan birga g'arb va sharq paremiologiyasini o'rganishda ahamiyatlidir.

Matal termini ko'p turkiy tillarda uchramaydi. Qozoq tilida esa "pogovorka"ning ekvivalentini bildiradi. Qozoq maqol va matallarini diniy jihatdan o'rgangan B.Mansurov qozoq tili paremalarini Payg'ambarimiz (s.a.v.) hadislari bilan qiyoslab, maqol va matallarda insonning ezgu fazilatlarini ulug'lovchi, undagi illatlarni qoralovchi ma'nolarni hadislar orqali tushuntirib bergan. Tadqiqotda turkiy xalqlarning maqol va matallari negizida, tadrijiy takomilida hadislarning o'рни va ahamiyatini leksik-grammatik, lingvokonseptual, lingvosemiotik tomondan tadqiq qilingan. Olim "maqol" so'zi arabcha "qavlun"dan olingani, bu esa PBlar uchun hadislar muhim manba bo'la olishini ko'rsatadi [7; 24]. Xuddi shuningdek, hadislarning turk xalq maqollariga ta'sirini Selman Basharan ham atroflicha tadqiq etgan [2; 191]. U turk xalq maqolarini hadislar bilan taqqoslagan va ishonch, ilm, ibodat, shifo, axloq (yaxshi va yomon odatlar) va umumiy mavzularga ajratgan.

Xulosa sifatida ta'kidlash lozimki, o'zbek tilshunosligida va turkologiyada barqaror birikmalar tasnifi, ularning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari boshqa birliklar bilan aloqasi, o'xshash va farqli tomonlari atroflicha tadqiqlanishi zarur. Shundagina barqaror birikmalarining, ayniqsa, maqol va matal kabi birikmalarining

alohidalik sifatлари ochiq lanadi va qat'iy to'xtamga kelishga asos bo'ladi. Adabiyotshunoslik, folklorshunoslik tarkibidagi vositalarning lingvistik, lingvopoetik xususiyatlari singari dolzarb masalalar tahlili uchun metodologik yo'l yaratiladi.

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REKLAMA MATNLARINING SOTSIOLINGVISTIK TADQIQI

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Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются социальные характеристики рекламных текстов, социолингвистические аспекты, специфика использования языковых единиц при выражении гендерных различий, возрастные различия в рекламных текстах, анализ рекламных текстов, предназначенных для детей.

Ключевые слова: реклама, социолингвистика, психолингвистика, медиасимволика, медиатекст.

So'nggi yillarda ommaviy axborot vositalari tilini tahlil qilish, mediamatnlarning har bir turiga bag'ishlangan tadqiqotlarning ko'payishi uning o'rganish obyekti kengayganini ko'rsatmoqda. Bugungi zamonaviy jamiyatda iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy omillar rivojiga xizmat qiluvchi reklamanning jamiyatdagi o'rnini ham ortgani bois uning tadqiqi dolzarblik kasb etmoqda. Reklama – jamiyatdagi ma'lum mafkuraviy yukni tashir ekan, mahsulot iste'molida jamiyat turmush tarzi talablaridan kelib chiqqan holda o'z xizmatini taklif etadi.

Ommaviy axborot vositalari, ayniqsa reklama matnlari tadqiqi rus va xorij tilshunosligida izchil tadqiq qilingan. Jumladan, Teun Van Deyk, Martin Montgomeri, Alan Bell, Norman Feyerklafl, Robert Fauler ingliz

tilidagi reklama matnlarini sosiolingvistik, mediastilistik, lingvokognitiv, pragmalingvistik aspektlarda tadqiq etishdi [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. Bu ishlarda reklama matnlarining tuzilishi, qo'llanish doirasi, uslubiy xususiyatlari, kishilarga ta'sir ko'rsatish kuchi kabi masalalar tahlil qilingan.

Rus tilshunosligida A.P.Repyevning "Reklama tili" [6], S.N.Berdishevning "Reklama matni" [7; 182], N.A.Savinaning "Социолингвистические характеристики рекламного текста" [8; 44-54], S.A.Korochkovaning "Социолингвистическая характеристика рекламных текстов в гендерном аспекте" [9] tadqiqotlarida reklama matnlarining o'rganilishi, janr xususiyatlari, lingvostilistik ahamiyati, ijtimoiy-madaniy xususiyatlari, gender farqlanishi kabi masalalar tahlilga tortilgan.

O'zbek tilshunosligida reklama matnlarining imperativlik, undash, da'vat qilish, ishontirish ma'nosining o'zbek tilida ifodalanish usullari, mexanizmlari va qonuniyatlari K.Yusupova tomonidan ilmiy ochib berilgan. [10; 58] Ammo uning sotsiolingvistik jihatlari, reklamaning ijtimoiylik belgisini ifodalovchi yoshi, jinsi, mavqeyi, kasb-kori kabi ijtimoiy omillari farqlangan tadqiqotlar mavjud emasligi uning ijtimoiy til xususiyatlarini ham o'rganish kerakligini ko'rsatdi.

Ma'lumki, "Sotsiolingvistika insonlar mazkur lisoniy belgilarni ularning yoshi, jinsi, ijtimoiy holati, bilimi va madaniyatlilik darajasiga ko'ra qanday qo'llashlarini, ya'ni ijtimoiy muhitning ularning nutqiy muomalasiga qanday ta'sir qilishini o'rganadi" [11; 3]. Reklama matnlari tadqiqida ham ijtimoiy omillar ta'sirida yuzaga kelgan matnlarni kuzatish mumkin. Masalan, adresant o'z mahsulotini reklama qilayotganda albatta adresatning ijtimoiy belgilarini, yoshini, ayollar yoki erkaklar uchun mo'ljallanganligini inobatga olgan holda o'z mahsulotini taklif etadi. Rus tilshunosligida reklamaning gender farqlanishi bilan bog'liq bir qator tadqiqotlar yaratilgan. Ularda auditoriyaning jins jihatidan farqlangan tadqiqotlar tahlilida ayollar uchun mo'ljallangan reklama matnlarida ekspressiv-emotsional til birliklaridan foydalangani, erkaklar uchun mo'ljallangan reklama matnlarida esa psixologik ta'sir ustuvorlik qilgani ko'rinadi.

Reklama matnining mavzusi (reklamada qanday mahsulot muhokama qilinmoqda) ba'zi hollarda qabul qiluvchining jinsini aniq ko'rsatadi. Erkaklar va ayollar mahsulotlarining mavjudligi, ularning qiziqishlari o'rtasidagi tafovut erkaklar va ayollar reklama mavzularini farqlashda namoyon bo'ladi. Masalan, dekorativ kosmetika reklamasi ayollar uchun mo'ljallangan aniq reklama turi sifatida qabul qilinadi. Biroq, bir qator mahsulotlar erkaklarga ham, ayollarga ham murojaat qilishi mumkin. Bunday hollarda adresatni aniqlashda uning lingvistik xususiyatlari, ekstralingvistik va albatta, vizual omillar ham yordam beradi.

Tilning ifodali vositalari reklama qilinyotgan mahsulotning muhim qirralarini ochishda zaruriy vosita hisoblanadi. Masalan, vizual(ko'ruv) reklama matnlarida lingvistik vosita sifatida asosan yuqori emotsional-ekspressivlikka ega bo'lgan sifat turkumiga oid so'zlar qo'llaniladi. Chunki reklama qilinyotgan xizmatlar, tovarlarning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, afzalliklarini alohida ta'kidlab, bo'rttirib ko'rsatish, asosan, sifat so'z turkumi orqaligina amalga oshiriladi. Masalan, xushbo'y, nozik, shaffof, sof, asl, toza, haqiqiy, tabiiy, chin, arzon, ommabop, hammabop, yoqimli, ko'rkam, yorqin, porloq, xushbichim, orasta, zebo kabi. Shuningdek, reklama matnlarida buyruq tarzidagi da'vat fe'llari ham ko'p qo'llanilishi ma'lum. Masalan, his eting, tashrif buyuring, marhamat qiling, tanishib chiqing, tanlang, kuting, ishtirok eting, ega bo'ling, shoshiling, lazzatlaning, quvoning va hokazo: Sog'liqni o'yla – Nestle Sutini tanla! Mutlaqo sof va tabiiy! Mahsulot sertifikatlangan (Nestle suti reklamasi).

Reklama ma'lum bir jamiyat ta'sirida shakllangan va uning o'ziga xos madaniy va milliy xususiyatlarini aks ettiruvchi, shuningdek, dunyoning milliy o'ziga xos manzarasini aks ettiruvchi ma'lum bir lisoniy va madaniy hodisa hisoblanadi. Reklama maxsus lingvistik va madaniy hodisa sifatida lingvomental stereotiplarga amal qiladi, ular asosida u yoki bu reklama matni yaratiladi. Reklama asosida muayyan jamiyatning xususiyatlari, madaniy qadriyatlari, etnik xususiyatlari haqida ma'lum xulosalar chiqarish mumkin. Bir tomondan, reklama matnlari, boshqa matnlar singari, dunyoning mavjud manzarasini aks ettirsa, ikkinchi tomondan, ular uni shakllantiradi, yangi tasvirlar va haqiqatlarni yaratadi, ularsiz zamonaviy jamiyatni tasavvur qilib bo'lmaydi [12].

O'zbek tilida ayollar uchun mo'ljallangan reklamalarda ekspressiv-emotsional til birliklari, baho munosabatini ifodalovchi leksik birliklar keng qo'llanadi. Masalan, Kukmara idishlari – ayollar orzusi! Kukmara idishlari Rossiyada ishlab chiqarilgan; Yaxshi uy bekalari "Gloss" ni yaxshi ko'radilar (kir yuvish kukuni "Gloss"); Bolajonim haqiqiy tadqiqotchi. O'zi uchun yangi hidlarni kashf etadi, lekin ularni uzoq vaqtga saqlab qolish oson emas. Yangi Vernel bilan o'zingizni 100 kungacha intensiv hushbo'y hid bilan qurshab oling. Vernel oshiq qildiruvchi hid. ("Vernel" kir yuvish vositasi reklamasi). Misollardan ko'rinadiki, ayollar uchun mo'ljallangan reklama matnlarida nutqiy ta'sir vositalaridan, ijobiy baho anglatuvchi til birliklaridan keng foydalaniladi.

Reklamalarning berilishida yosh bilan bog'lik jihatlar ham farq qilinishini ko'rish mumkin. Masalan, bolalar uchun mo'ljallangan reklamalarda ularga xos dunyoqarash, fikrlashga e'tibor qaratiladi va tabiiyki, shunga mos til birliklaridan foydalaniladi. Masalan, Assalomu alaykum aziz opalar! Man hozir sizlarga haqiqiy chocolate qilishni ko'rsataman. Buning uchun bizga kerak Oyim, non va chocotella. Nonni olamiz, chocotellani surtamiz. Diqqat bilan tinglang! Mana qarshingizda tayyor chocotella. Reklama matnini kichik yoshdagi bola o'qigan va bu bolalarga xos kayfiyat berishiga xizmat qilgan. Matnda bola tilining adabiy tildan chekingani, ya'ni Men olmoshi o'rnida Man deb qo'llagani va so'zlashuv uslubiga oid matni ham bolalarga xos reklama matnlarining o'ziga xos xususiyati hisoblanadi. Chunki bolalar adabiy til me'yorlariga amal qilmasligi va uslublararo farqni bilmasligi ma'lum.

Reklama yaratuvchisining adresatning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini inobatga olishi reklamanning muvaffaqiyati uchun ham muhim hisoblanadi. Masalan, Zizi reklamasini olaylik. Unda bolalarning o'yinga tushgan holda, qo'shiq qilib kuylangan reklama matni auditoriyani, ayniqsa, bolalarni bir zumda jalb qilishi shubhasiz. Misolga e'tibor qaratsak: Zizi o'ynab chaynagin, do'stlarni ham chorlagin! Kayfiyatni chog'lagin! Zizi bilan quvnagin! Zizi manda bor-ku, mevalarga boy-ku! Ey, senda-chi Zizi bormi?! Reklamada bolalar va multiqahramonning birga o'ynagan holda Zizi saqichini reklama qilishi bolalar auditoriyasini o'ziga jalb qiladi. Reklama uchun tanlangan matnda esa da'vat fe'llarini qo'llash orqali reklama samaradorligini oshirishga erishiladi.

Yana bir misolga e'tibor qaratsak: Yoqtirmaysanmi bizni, xohlamaysanmi bizni! Quvnoq ta'm – sladokda mujassam! Reklama samaradorligiga xizmat qiluvchi omillardan biri – mediaviy vositalar uyg'unligi hisoblanadi. Yuqoridagi reklamada ham mediaviy belgilar – matn va unga hamohang tayyorlangan ohang, bola nutqining berilishi reklamanning nutqiy ta'sirini oshirgan.

Bolalar uchun mo'ljallangan reklamalarda tibbiy reklamalarning ham alohida o'rni bor. Jumladan, Bobotik, Anaferon, Lineks, Pikovit, Bepanten, Supradin Kids kabi reklamalar faqat bolalarga mo'ljallanganligi bilan ajralib turadi. Tabiiyki, reklama matnida ham "bolalar uchun", "bolalarga mo'ljallangan" kabi til birliklaridan keng foydalaniladi: O'rvi va grippni davolashda, profilaktika qilishda; farzandingiz immunitetini mustahkamlashda va bir oylikdan oshgan bolalar uchun mo'ljallangan (Anaferon dori vositasi reklamasidan)

Ko'rinadiki, reklama matnini o'rganish nafaqat uning sotsiolingvistik, balki lingvokulturologik, pragmalingvistik, psixolingvistik jihatlarini ham tadqiq etish zaruratini ko'rsatadi. Chunki ommaviy axborot vositalari orqali uzluksiz beriladigan reklama katta auditoriyani qamrab olgani sabab, uning til bilan bog'liq jihatlarini tartibga solish, adabiy til qonuniyatlariga amal qilingan samarali reklama matnlarini tavsiya qilish dolzarb ahamiyat kasb etadi.

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O'ZBEKONA NUTQIY STRATEGIYA VA NUTQIY TAKTIKA HAQIDA

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Аннотация: В статье автор рассуждает об управлении узбекского коммуникативного процесса, а также речевой стратегии и тактике.

Ключевые слова: прагмалингвистика, коммуникативная сел, диалог, иллюкутивная сила, речевая стратегия.

Sistem-struktur tilshunoslikning Praga lingvistik to'garagida ma'ruzalar o'qigan venger tilshunosi F.Kifer pragmatika sohasining pressupozitsiya masalasi bilan shug'ullangan. Uning pressupozitsiyaga bag'ishlangan ishida kontekstual erkin va kontekstual tobe ma'no haqida fikr yuritiladi va ularning quyidagicha farqi keltiriladi: sintaktik shakl va leksik birliklar orqali anglashiladigan ma'no kontekstual erkin ma'no, kontekst bilan shartlangan ma'no esa kontekstual tobe (bog'liq) ma'nodir [6; 333]. Pragmatikaning nutqiy muloqot mavzusiga bag'ishlangan ishlaridagi nutqiy vaziyat, kontekstga doir qarashlar Kifer nazariyalari ta'sirida ham rivojlangan deyishimiz mumkin.

Dialogik tadqiqotlar nutqiy vaziyat va konteks tahlilisiz hech qachon to'la va mukammal bo'lolmaydi. Shuningdek, muloqot ilmida yana "kommunikativ maqsad" tushunchasi ham ko'p qo'llaniladi. Kommunikativ maqsad "...so'zlovchining kommunikativ niyatini, ya'ni shu gapdan ifodalangan obyektiv mazmun elementlarining ahamiyatlilik darajasini belgilashni (aktual bo'laklarga ajratish) hamda darak, so'roq, buyruq ifodalashni, ikkinchidan, pressupozitsiya axborotini o'z ichiga oladi. Shunday qilib, til birligi sifatida gap semantikasiga faqat nominativ plan – propozitsiya plani oiddir. Kommunikativ plan esa jumla semantikasining, demak, nutq semantikasining predmetidir". [8; 94].

So'nggi yillarda nutqiy muloqotning o'rganilishida kommunikativ maqsad tushunchasidan tashqari "kommunikativ strategiya", "kommunikativ taktika", "kommunikativ sabotaj" kabi terminlarning qo'llanilishini uchratamiz. Mazkur terminlar dialogik muhit uchun juda qulay bo'lib, unda suhbatdoshlar o'z nutqiy muloqoti orqali kerakli maqsadni amalga oshirishda foydalanadilar. Ma'lumki, strategiya va taktika atamaları dastlab harbiy sohada qo'llanuvchi tushunchaga nisbatan ishlatilgan. Mazkur atamaning falsafiy talqini ham bunga guvohlik beradi. V.Alimasovning "Strategema – fikrlash va eyngish ilmi" nomli maqolasida strategemalarning quvlik, hiyla, nayrang, aldash, chalg'itish deb tushunilishi qayd etiladi. Muallif yozadi: "Ammo ushbu ilk etimologik ma'no (lashkar, qo'shin; ergashtiraman, boshqaraman ma'nolari ko'zda tutilmoqda) hozir transformatsiyaga uchragan, ya'ni strategemaga inson aql-u idroki, faoliyati bilan bog'liq barcha sohalarga taalluqli voqelik sifatida qaralmoqda". [1; 55]. Shuning uchun ham til ilmiga oid tadqiqotlarda ham mazkur atamalarga tez-tez murojaat qilinayotganini kuzatamiz.

Har bir tilning vazifasi jamiyat va undagi insonlarning ma'naviy ehtiyojlari bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'ladi. Muloqot ishtirokchilarining o'z fikrini tinglovchiga yetkazishda, unga ta'sir etishda, o'z mental aktini sodir etishda bir necha usul va yo'llarni qidirishi tabiiy jarayondir. Nutqiy akt mavzusi bilan shug'ullanib kelayotgan olim M.Hakimov "kommunikativ taktika – so'zlovchining fikr ifodalash usuli" deya ta'rif beradi [4; 155]. Rus olimasi T.M.Nikolayeva fikricha esa, "kommunikativ sabotaj" va "lingvistik demagogiya" tushunchalari bir-biriga yaqin [7; 154-165]. Olimaning tadqiqotida "kommunikativ sabotaj" ommaviy tarzdagi ongni boshqarish usuli sifatida qo'llaniladi. O.S.Issers talqiniga ko'ra esa: "Nutqiy strategiya – bu kommunikativ maqsadga erishishga yo'naltirilgan harakatlar majmuidir" [5; 54]. "Nutqiy taktika" termini ostida esa bir necha usullar jamlamasidagi ma'lum tarkib, ya'ni nutqiy strategiyaning bir qismi tushuniladi. Ta'kidlash lozimki, mazkur terminlar ostida o'rganilayotgan hodisalarda so'zlovchining kommunikativ maqsadini ro'yobga chiqarish usul va vositalarigina emas, balki o'ziga xos suhbatdoshning raqib nutqiy va mental bosimidan himoyalash usuli sifatidagi qarashlarga ham duch kelamiz [9]. Bunday qarashlar o'z

asosiga egaligi bilan nutqiy muloqot jarayonida tadqiqotchilarni mazkur hodisalarni o'rganishga undaydi, degan fikrdamiz. "Mental akt yoki mental holat so'zlovchi nazarda tutgan illokutiv akt ma'nosi tinglovchi tasavvuri bilan o'zaro muvofiq kelishidir" [3; 130].

O'zbek tilidagi dialoglarda nutqiy strategiyalarning milliy ruhdagi o'zbekona ko'rinishi tariqasida quyidagi dialogni keltirish o'rinlidir.

– Fuzuliy yaxshi kitob, – dedi Kumush, – men ham yolg'iz qolgan kezlarimda bu kitobdan boshimni ololmas edim, sizammi?

– Otabek garansib qolg'an, o'zini ovutmoqchi bo'lg'an bu oliyjanob go'zalga nima deyishni bilmas, qayerdan so'z boshlashqa hayron edi:

– Kim yig'latdi sizni?

– Yig'labmanmi?

– Ko'zingiz, kibrakingiz...

– O'zi shunaqa...

– Yig'latgan men emasmi?

– Kitobni nega yopdingiz? Ochib o'qung, men eshitay.

– Ota-ona rizolig'ini bir tomchi ko'z yoshingizga arzitdimmi?

– Men rozi, men ko'ndim, – dedi da'atan Kumush, bu so'zni nimadandir qo'rqqandek shoshib aytdi. (A.Qodiriy. O'tkan kunlar).

Mazkur dialogda Kumushning Otabekning uylanishiga o'z roziligini ehtiyotkorlik bilan ifodalash usulidan ma'lumki, Otabek kutgan noqulay nutqiy muloqot yuzaga kelmadi, aksincha, tinch holatdagi rozilik mazmunining yashirin tasdiq ishorasi (Fuzuliy yaxshi kitob... Kitobni nega yopdingiz? Ochib o'qung, men eshitay) o'ziga xos nutqiy taktika bilan bayon etildi. Ushbu dialogda qo'llanilgan mohirona nutqiy harakat – taktika dialogning boshlanishidagi nizoli holatdan so'zlovchini ham, tinglovchini ham qutqarib qolgan. Shunga ko'ra mazkur qo'llangan usulni himoyalash usuli sifatidagi taktika deb baholash maqsadga muvofiqdir.

Pragmalingvist olim M.Hakimov o'z qarashlarida illokutiv kuch haqidagi fikrlarini bayon etar ekan, mazkur tushunchani "ifoda imkoniyati" tarzida berishni ma'qul ko'radi va shunday yozadi: "Ifoda imkoniyati (illokutiv kuch) ko'rinishlaridan biri bu fikr ifodalash uslubi yoki taktikasi hisoblanadi. So'zlovchi o'z niyatini amalga oshirish uchun nutqiy ta'sir etish usuli yoki taktikasi vositasi bilan tinglovchining ichki ruhiyati yoki ichki pozitsiyasini aniqlab oladi... Bunga ko'ra so'zlovchi kommunikativ niyatini, maqsadlarini bayon qilish uchun qulay bo'lgan ma'lum nutqiy vaziyat yuzaga kelishini kutadi, shu ma'noda illokutiv akti vaziyat etilishi bilan propozitsional mazmunning ostiga yashiradi va ifoda etadi" [2; 141]. Olim keltirilgan mulohazalar orqali nutqiy taktikani illokutiv kuch bilan bog'liqligini asoslab bergan. Aslida illokutiv maqsad, illokutiv kuch, intensiya, tagma'no, tagbilim kabi tushunchalar nutqiy taktika yoki nutqiy strategiyani amalga oshirishda bir maydon ichida birlashuvchi asosiy qurol tushunchalar vazifasini o'taydi.

Olim qo'llagan "individual strategiya" tushunchasi ham diqqatga sazovor bo'lib, mazkur tushuncha tilshunosligimizda nisbatan yangi tushuncha hisoblanadi. Uningcha, "so'zlash va fikrlashni to'g'ri ifodalash uchun individual strategiya mahoratiga ham ega bo'lish lozim" [2; 26]. Bu o'rinda gap yana aylanib kelib, so'z ustasi va "suhbat guli"ga aylana olgan zakiy va oqil suhbatdoshning mahoratiga taqaladi. Darhaqiqat, muloqotda maqsadga yetish omili so'z orqali ekan, undan qay tarzda foydalanish ham shaxsiy, ham lisoniy, ham aqliy, ham ijtimoiy bilim va tajribalarga asoslanadi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, pragmalingvistik tadqiqotlar ko'lamini nihoyasiz bo'lib, u hayot bilan, insonlarning xohish-irodasi, maqsad va intilishlari bilan chambarchas bog'langan. Mazkur holatlarni lisoniy tafakkur va lisoniy qobiliyat orqali amalga oshirishni yoritish esa tilshunoslar oldiga qiziqarli sayohatga o'tlanishdek qizg'in va jo'shqin hayrat hissini berishi shubhasizdir. Bunday maroqli sayohatdan bosh tortish aslo mumkin emasdek, nazarimizda.

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ПРИЧИНЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ИНТЕРНАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЛЕКСИКИ

Шахло УРИНОВА,
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Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada rus tilining internatsional leksikasi ko'rib chiqilgan, internatsional leksika shakllanishning ekstralingvistik va intralingvistik omillari tahlil qilinadi va bunday o'zlashmalardan namunalalar keltirilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *internatsioanal leksika, ichki omil, tashqi omil, o'zlashma so'z, neologism, donor til, qabul qiluvchi til.*

Интернациональная лексика является наиболее общим пластом лексики большинства языков мира. В словарях и лингвистических энциклопедиях приведены различные толкования термина «интернациональная лексика». Вот как характеризует её Т.Жеребило: «Совокупность интернационализмов, используемых в различных языках в пределах того или иного культурно-языкового ареала, для каждого из которых характерна собственная интернациональная лексика: 1) интернациональная лексика европейского ареала включает языковой материал из латинского, древнегреческого, западноевропейских языков; 2) интернациональная лексика восточного ареала включает слова, взятые из персидского, арабского языков. Удельный вес интернациональной лексики в современных языках достаточно велик (примерно 10 %). Интернациональная лексика распространена в терминологии точных наук, в общественно-политической терминологии [1; 123].

Причины формирования интернациональной лексики можно разделить на экстралингвистические (внешние) и интралингвистические (внутриязыковые).

Экстралингвистические факторы образования интернациональной лексики заключаются в следующем:

1. Заимствование слов вместе с заимствованием вещи или понятия. В этом случае заимствуется и новое понятие, и его вербальное обозначение. Например, появление в нашей жизни новых понятий и новых реалий, таких как, например электробус, электрокар, принтер, сканер, лазер, компьютер, чип, тостер, чоппер, новых профессий: менеджер, маркетолог, мерчандайзер, супервайзер, риэлтор, визажист, имиджмейкер, футуролог, блогер, вайнер и многих других обусловили появление в языке и их наименований. Расширение интернациональной лексики напрямую связано с развитием науки, технологий, экономики, культуры, искусства, производственных отношений, глобализацией во всех отраслях жизни. Многие из этих слов в начале имеют статус неологизма, затем прочно входят в повседневную жизнь и утрачивают свою новизну, переходя в активный лексикон носителей языка. Например, изрядное количество терминов, связанных с развитием космонавтики (космонавт,

спутник, космодром, луноход, марсоход), находящихся в 50-70-е гг. XX века в статусе неологизмов появилось и др. Сегодня все эти слова стали общеупотребительными.

2. Обозначение с помощью заимствованного слова специального понятия, существующего в языке, но немного отличающегося от него. Это и ведёт к заимствованию интернационального термина. «Потребность в специализации предметов и понятий ведет к заимствованию научных и технических терминов, многие из которых имеют русские соответствия: лат. трансформатор – рус. преобразователь; лат. компрессия – рус. сжатие; франц. пилотировать – рус. Управлять, англ. модератор – рус. ведущий и т.п. [2; 137]. Также можно привести следующие примеры: рекорд (англ. record); ректор (лат. rektor); ремонт (франц. remonte) (compression – англ); пилот (франц. pilote), ренессанс (франц. renaissance).

3. Глобализация, способствующая расширению международных связей, которая и приводит к пополнению интернационального пласта лексики в языках мира.

Таким образом, экстралингвистические факторы, не связанные с внутренним развитием языка, оказывают значительное влияние на процесс заимствования интернациональной лексики. Экстралингвистическая реальность во многом обуславливает развитие языковых связей, интенсивность языкового контакта и характер его функционирования. В современных условиях глобализации, усиливающей взаимозависимость и взаимообусловленность национальных государств и регионов, интенсификацию языковых контактов, возрастает потребность в выявлении внешних факторов образования иностранных слов в национальных языках мира.

Интралингвистические факторы формирования интернациональной лексики можно обозначить следующим образом:

1. Тенденция к замене описательного наименования однословной единицей. Это свойственно большинству языков, в том числе, русскому и узбекскому). Например: снайпер – вместо меткий стрелок, мотель – вместо гостиница для автотуристов, спринт – вместо бег на короткие дистанции, вебинар – вместо дистанционный семинар, электробус – вместо электрический автобус и т.п.

2. Укрепление в языке заимствованных слов с определенной морфологической структурой. В таких случаях заимствование нового иноязычного слова значительно облегчается. Например, слова, имеющие значение лица и общий элемент -мен. В настоящее время подобные слова составляют довольно значительную группу персоналий: бизнесмен, конгрессмен, кроссмен, спортсмен, бармен и др. В последнее время участились случаи заимствования персоналий с англоязычным элементом -ер: копирайтер, промоутер, трейдер, маклер, брокер.

К внутри лингвистическим причинам появления заимствований в языке Л.П. Крысин относит следующие:

1. Устранение полисемии исконного слова и упрощение его смысловой структуры.

2. Потребность уточнить, детализировать соответствующее понятие, разграничить некоторые смысловые оттенки, прикрепив их к разным словам.

3. Наличие в заимствующем языке тенденции к образованию структурно аналогичных слов или наличие класса слов, структурно однотипных с воспринимаемой лексической единицей.

4. Наличие в языке-приемнике определенного лексического ряда заимствований с общим значением и повторяемостью какого-либо одного структурного элемента (можно добавить, что это способствует более легкой адаптации заимствования, однотипного со словами уже существующего лексического ряда).

5. Тенденция к соответствию нерасчлененности обозначаемого понятия с нерасчлененностью обозначающего, т.е. язык стремится назвать обозначаемое (если оно представляет собой единое целое) отдельным словом, а не группой слов или словосочетанием [3].

Анализ функционирования иноязычной лексики показывает, что иноязычные термины, заменившие исконные словосочетания, не всегда приспособляются и укореняются в лексической системе принимающего языка, в котором уже сложились определенные микросистемы с общими структурными признаками.

Также стоит отметить, что вышперечисленные внутриязыковые причины не существуют отдельно, они взаимосвязаны между собой. Например, явление языковой экономии может быть обусловлено тенденцией к экспрессивности или немотивированного языкового знака.

V zaklyucheni mojno skazat', cho intralingvistikheskie faktory, svyazannye s vnutrennimi tendentsiyami razvitiya yazyka, sposobstvuyut formirovaniyu zaимствованной leksiki v yazyke. Proniknoveniе иностранных слов и их адаптация в языке-реципиенте очень часто обусловлено необходимостью обозначения, номинации новых реалий и предметов, а также потребностью уточнения соответствующего существующего понятия. Совокупность внутриязыковых причин формирования иноязычной лексики может отличаться от набора таковых факторов в других языках, ибо каждый конкретный язык уникален по-своему.

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ODDIY FOLKLORIZM – IBORALARNING LINGVOPOETIK TAHLILI

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Аннотация. *Статья посвящена анализу разновидности обычных фольклоризмов – фразеологизмов. Раскрываются отличительные особенности пословиц и фразеологизмов, приводится лингвопоэтический анализ фразем в произведениях Чулпана.*

Ключевые слова: *фольклоризм, обычный фольклоризм, сложный фольклоризм, фразеологизм, пословица.*

"Hech shubhasizki, til o'ziga muhtasham mazmun va muntazam mohiyat ato etadigan barcha katta-kichik birliklarning teran va tarang tashakkuli, tanosibi, ayni paytda tinimsiz takomili tufayli betimsol sinoatli tilsim o'laroq asrlar osha tirikdir. Shu narsa ham ochiq haqiqatki, bu tilsim silsilasida lug'aviy birliklar favqulodda ayricha o'ringa sohibdir... Tilning chinakam sehr-u joduli lug'aviy birliklari olamida yana bir mutlaqo uzviy qatlam mavjudki, uni mutaxassislar "iboralar" yoki "frazеologizmlar" // "frazеologik birliklar" termini bilan ataydilar" [1; 3].

"O'zbek tilida xalqning o'ziga xos tafakkur tarzini, badiiy tasavvurini, qudratini ko'rsatuvchi iboralar mavjud. Iboralar, umuman olganda, hayotdagi voqea-hodisalarni kuzatish, jamiyatdagi maqbul va nomaqbul harakat-holatlarni baholash, turmush tajribalarini umumlashtirish asosida xalq chiqargan xulosalarning o'ziga xos obrazli ifodalaridir" [2; 75]. Frazеologizmlar fikrni aniq va qisqa ifodalashga xizmat qiladi.

Avvalgi tadqiqotlarda aytganimizdek, iboralar ham oddiy folklorizm hisoblanadi. Ammo folklorshunos olim L.Sharipova o'z tadqiqotida iboralarni janr xususiyatiga ega emasligi uchun oddiy folklorizm bo'lolmasligini, B.Sarimsoqov fikrlariga qarshiligini aytadi: "Og'zaki nutqqa xos ifoda hamda oborotlar oddiy folklorizmlar bo'lolmaydi. Chunki ular nutqqa xos hodisa bo'lib, maqol, matal kabi tilda hamisha tayyor holda uchrasa ham badiiy ijod mahsuli sifatida janriy belgilarga ega emas. Shu ma'noda folklor janri bo'lgan maqol va matal o'zlashuviga alohida e'tibor berish lozim" [3; 34], deb ta'kidlaydi. Tilshunos olim Sh.Maxmaraimova to'g'ri ta'kidlaganidek: "Frazеologizmlar millatning o'zigagina xos bo'lgan munosabat bildirish, baholash shakli bo'lib, bunda millatning ma'naviy-qadriyatini manzarasiga tegishli belgilar frazeologik ma'noni tarkib toptiruvchi asosiy sabablardan hisoblanadi" [4; 271]. Shuningdek, biz ham B.Sarimsoqov fikriga qo'shilamiz. Chunki iboralar xalq og'zaki nutqida tayyor holda imkoniyat sifatida mavjud bo'lib, har safar yangitdan

yaratilmaydi, balki tayyor holda nutqqa olib kirilaveradi. Shu ma'noda, turg'un ibora va muayyan qolipga ega oborotlarni ham oddiy folklorizmlar sifatida qabul qilish mumkin, degan fikrdamiz.

Xalq maqollarini o'zbek tilshunosligida o'rgangan B.Jo'rayeva "Maqollarning lisoniy mavqei va ma'noviy uslubiy qo'llanilishi" mavzucidagi tadqiqot ishida maqollarni ibora bilan umumiy hamda farqli jihatlarini etimologik, ma'noviy va sintaktik jihatdan farqlagan va quyidagicha fikr bildirgan: "Frazeologiya doirasini tor ma'noda tushunish o'rinni bo'lib, maqol bilan ibora faqat bir nuqtada umumiylikka ega. Ya'ni maqol ham, ibora ham idioma sanaladi. Ammo bu o'xshashlik ulardagi boshqa farqli jihatlarini inkor etmaydi, chunki, maqol o'tkir kuzatuvchanlik asosida vujudga kelgan fikrlarning xulosasi hisoblanadi, frazeologizm esa tayyor so'z tizimlarining ko'chma ma'no ifodalash va shu holatda turg'un so'z bog'lanmasiga aylanishidir. Maqollar kamida bitta gapga teng kelib, hukm ifodalaydi; ibora esa gapda atamalik xususiyatiga ega bo'lib, leksik tushuncha anglatadi" [5; 45].

Atoqli tilshunos olim A.Hojiyevning "Frazeologizmlar so'zlar kabi yaxlit bir ma'no (belgi, harakat kabilarni) ifodalasa-da, lekin frazeologik ma'no ko'p jihatdan leksik ma'nodan farq qiladi. Shu sababli frazeologizmlar so'zlarga sinonim bo'lgan hollarda ham frazeologik ma'no bilan leksik ma'no bir-biriga teng bo'lmaydi... Juda ko'p frazeologizmlar bildiradigan ma'nolarni bir so'z bilan ifodalab bo'lmaydi", deb ta'kidlaydi. Buyuk tilshunos olimi N.Mahmudov A.Hojiyevning fikrlariga qo'shilgan holda, quyidagilarni aytib o'tadi: "so'z shaklan ixcham, ibora esa tarkibli (kamida ikki so'zdan iborat), ya'ni hajman katta, agar har ikki birlik ham ayni bir ma'no ifodasi uchun xizmat qiladigan bo'lsa, til vositalarini tejash tamoyiliga muvofiq til egasi ixcham birlikni tanlamog'i joiz, ammo tilda ixcham emas, balki "qo'pol" birlik – ibora ham yashayaptimi, demak, bu til taraqqiyotidagi yana bir tamoyil – til vositalaridagi ortiqchalik tamoyili harakatining natijasidir. ...Aytish mumkinki, so'z va iborani bir-biriga tamoman teng, mutlaq ekvivalent hodisalar sifatida baholash maqsadga muvofiq emas, bunga, ayniqsa, frazeologik ma'noning o'ziga xosligi, ko'lamdorligi, hajman boyligi, emotsional-ekspressiv zanginligi, umuman, frazeologik semantikaning murakkabligi yo'l qo'ymaydi" [1; 7].

O'zbek tilshunosligida iboralarni o'rganish o'tgan asrning 50-yillaridan boshlangan. Bu borada mashhur tilshunos Sh.Rahmatullayev xizmatlari beqiyosdir. O'zbek tilshunosligida frazeologiya sohasining shakllanishi va rivojlanishida olimning "O'zbek frazeologiyasining ba'zi masalalari" nomli monografiyasi va "O'zbek tilining izohli frazeologik lug'ati"ning ahamiyati katta bo'lgan [6, 7]. Shuningdek, tilshunos olimi Sh.Toshxo'jayeva ta'kidlaganidek: "mashhur tilshunoslar Sh.Rahmatullayev, B.Yo'ldoshev, A.Mamatov, A.Rafiyev, Sh.Almamatova va boshqalarning xizmatlari alohida e'tirof etish lozim. Sh.Rahmatullayev o'z tadqiqotlarida frazeologizmlarning ma'no xususiyatlari, shakl va ma'no munosabatlari borasida maxsus monografik ishlar olib borish bilan birga, o'zbek tilidagi frazeologik birliklarning izohli lug'atini yaratdi va bu bilan amaliy tilshunoslik sohasiga katta hissa qo'shdi. B.Yo'ldoshev frazeologizmlarning uslubiy xususiyatlari, A.Mamatov ularning shakllanishi, Sh.Ganiyeva esa frazeologizmlarning ma'no tuzilishi, ularni shakliy va mazmuniy modellashtirish muammolari xususidagi ilmiy tadqiqot ishlari bilan o'zbek frazeologizmini ilmiy jihatdan o'rganilishiga va bu sohaning alohida fan sifatida shakllanishiga hissa qo'shmoqdalar [8; 90].

Tilshunos olim N.Mahmudov iboralar va ularning lug'aviy tavsifi muammolari tahliliga bag'ishlangan maqolasida korparativ iboralar to'g'risida so'z yuritadi va ular hozirgi kunga qadar yetarli darajada e'tibor berilmaganligini ta'kidlaydi. "Tilda idiomalarga yaqin turadigan yoki frazeologizm maqomida bo'lgan turg'un o'xshatishlar asosidagi birliklar mavjud bo'lib, ularni komparativ frazeologizmlar sifatida qarash mumkin, ular ko'p asrlar mobaynida kishilar nutqida qo'llanish natijasi sifatida turg'unlashib, so'zlovchilar ongida muayyan modellar shaklida mustahkamlanib qolgan, o'xshatish etalonining, ya'ni o'xshatish asosidagi obrazning muayyan belgi-predmet bilan muntazam va qat'iy aloqasi yuzaga kelgan. Ular til sistemasidagi frazeologik iboralarning alohida, o'ziga xos bir guruhini tashkil etadi va tayyor holda nutqqa olib kiriladi [1; 11]

Yosh tilshunos olim G'.Ismoilov o'zbek, qozoq va qoraqalpoq tillarida misolida frazeologik birliklarni lingvomadaniy va lingvokognitiv jihatdan tadqiq qilmoqda va ushbu mavzuda bir qator tadqiqotlarini e'lon qilib bormoqda. Olim "Frazeologik birliklarda sonlarning ifodalanishi" nomli maqolasida iboralarda sonlarning ifodalanishi va ular asosida shakllangan iboralarning diniy-mifologik kognitiv strukturasi ochib bergan. Uning fikricha: "Frazemalarning ko'pchiligi inson hayotiy faoliyati, ma'naviy va jismoniy holati bilan

bog'liq hodisalar asosida shakllangan bo'lib, ular tarkibidagi zoologizm, somatizm, mifologik hodisalar, ranglar va son kabilar frazemalarning semantik tayanch komponenti vazifasini o'taydi. Turkiy tillarda ham son komponentli frazemalar ma'lum miqdorda faol ishlatiladi. Sonlar har qanday madaniyat tarkibiga singib borada hamda undagi axborotni mazmuniy guruhlariga uyushtiradi. Bu holat ushbu madaniyatda yozma yoki og'zaki ijod an'anasi mavjud yoki mavjud emasligidan qat'iy nazar, bilimlarning avloddan avlodga o'tishini ta'minlaydi. Turkiy tillarda sonlar mantiqiy asos sifatida frazeologizmlarni shakllantirgan hamda bu sonlar diniy-mifologik va madaniy-etnik xususiyatlarni o'zida mujassam etgan holda shu til vakillarining milliy va madaniyati, urf-odati va an'analariga muvofiqdir" [9; 4].

Tilshunos olim Sh.Maxmaraimova frazeologizmlarni tadqiq qilar ekan, idiomatik frazeologiya (idiomatika) to'g'risida so'z yuritadi. Bilamizki, idiomalar ko'chma ma'noda keladi. Olima idiomalarni badiiy adabiyotda obrazlilikni tashkil etuvchi asosiy til vositalaridan biri ekanligini, badiiy asar tarjimasida bunday iboralarning tarjima qilinyotgan tildagi ekvivalenti yozilishini aytadi: "idiomalar badiiy adabiyotda obrazlilikni tashkil etuvchi asosiy til vositalaridan bo'lib, ular asarda kesatiq, qochiriq ma'nolarini ifodalaydilar. Badiiy asar tarjimasida bunday iboralar o'rniga tarjima qilinyotgan tildagi ekvivalentlarni topib qo'yiladi. Boshqa tilda idiomaning mazmunini anglatuvchi ibora topilmasa, o'sha ibora aynan berilib, sahifa ostida uning ma'nosi tushuntiriladi yoki mazmun tarjima qilinadi" [4; 286].

Har qanday mahoratli yozuvchi o'z asarlarini xalq iboralari, matallari, maqollar bilan to'yintiradi. Ba'zan muallif nutqi orqali, ba'zan asar qahramonlari nutqida qo'llangan iboralar asarning badiiy quvvatini oshirishga va ta'sir kuchini ta'minlashga xizmat qiladi. Cho'lpon ham o'z asarlarining ta'sirchanligini ta'minlash maqsadida iboralardan ustalik bilan foydalanadi.

Yozuvchi o'z asarlarida iboralardan voqelikni tasvirlashda, uni kitobxon ko'z o'ngida aniq gavalantirishda foydalanadi. Tabiiyki, yozuvchi bunda to'g'ri kelgan, har qanday iboralarni o'z asariga olib kirmaydi, balki asar tilining emotsional-ekspressivligini oshiradigan, badiiy-estetik niyatiga xizmat qiladigan, asar qahramonining xatti-harakati va ruhiyatini ochib beradigan chinakam xalq iboralaridan saralab tanlab oladi.

Cho'lpon "Kecha va kunduz" romanida qahramonning ruhiy holatini tasvirlashda bir nechta iboralarni ketma-ketlikda qo'llaydi. Miryoqub, bir joyda bir nafas o'tirolmaydigan narsa, olti-yetti kundan beri mingboshining yonidan jilmaydi. Jahli chiqib to'nini teskari kiymoqchi bo'lgan mingboshini gap bilan sovutadi va yo'lga soladi. (misolni qolgan qismini ham olish kerak. holat yaxshi ochilmagan) Ushbu matnda "to'nini teskari kiymoq", "gap bilan sovutmoq", "yo'lga solmoq" iboralari mavjud. O'zbek tili frazeologik lug'atida "to'nini teskari kiymoq" va "yo'lga solmoq" iboralari berilgan va quyidagicha izohlangan: "To'nini teskari kiymoq kim? [o'zining] o'chakishgan holda qaysarlik qilmoq. Yo'lga solmoq kim? 1 kimni? yoki nimani? ketish tomoniga to'g'rilab jo'natmoq, yurg'izmoq. 2 kimni? to'g'ri yo'lga qaytarmoq. 3 kimni? manfaatdor bo'lgani holda biror ishga rag'batlantirmoq. 4 nimani? faoliyatini yaxshilamoq" [10; 517, 587]. Ammo "gap bilan sovutmoq" iborasi lug'atda berilmagan. Ushbu ibora yozuvchining ijod mahsuli bo'lib "tinchlantirmoq" ma'nosini beradi. Ushbu iboralarning ketma-ket kelishi, matnning uslubiy bo'yoqdorligini oshirgan va lingvopoetik yuk olgan. Mingboshining jahli juda ham qattiq chiqqanligini, buning oqibatida birovga, hatto o'ziga ham biror zarar yetkazishi matndan anglashiladi.

Cho'lpon mos iboralarni tanlabgina qolmay, balki ularni asar qahramonining ruhiy holatiga moslab o'zgartiradi. Xalq iboralarning tuzilishini va mazmunini o'zgartiradi, ularga yangicha ma'no beradi. Bunday iboralar asarda go'zal tasvir yaratadi, asarning ta'sirchanligini oshiradi.

Frazeologik birliklarning funksional-uslubiy xususiyatlarini tadqiq qilgan tilshunos B.Yo'ldoshev tomonidan badiiy asarlarda iboralarni o'zgartirgan shaklda ko'rsatib bergan. Cho'lpon xalq iboralarni quyidagi usullarda o'zgartirgan shaklda qo'llagan:

1. Ibora tarkibidagi ayrim so'zlarni almashtirish. "Frazema gap tarkibida boshqa so'zlar bilan munosabatga kirishar ekan, ba'zan aniqlik kiritishni, konkret shart-sharoitga moslashishni talab qiladi. Ana shunday hollarda ibora komponentlaridan biri boshqa so'z bilan almashtiriladi" [11; 130]. Bu usulda ibora tarkibidagi so'z boshqasi bilan almashtirilganda, uning ma'nosi yana kuchayishiga xizmat qiladi. Bunday iboralar lingvopoetik ma'no kasb etadi. Masalan: – Qo'y endi, kechquruning maslahatini qilaylik. Bugun kechqurun kuyovni bir ish qilib suyganiga qovushtirmaslik bo'lmaydi. Juda alangasi osmonga chiqib ketdi! O'zi ham xunuk ish bo'ldi. ("Kecha va Kunduz"). Alangasi osmonga chiqib ketdi iborasi fig'oni falakka chiqdi iborasining o'zgartirgan varianti hisoblanadi. "O'zbek tilining frazeologik lug'ati"da fig'oni

falakka chiqdi iborasiga quyidagicha ta'rif berilgan: "Ruhan ortiq darajada bo'g'ilib, shovqin qilmoq" [10; 166]. Ushbu matnda fig'on so'zi alanga so'zi bilan, falak so'zi esa osmon so'zi bilan almashtirilgan. O'zbek tilining izohli lug'atida alanga so'zi quyidagicha izohlangan: "ALANGA 1 Yonib turgan o'tdan, olovdan ko'tarilayotgan yolqin" [12; 83]. Yozuvchining so'zlarni almashtirish orqali "kuyov"ning "jahli alangga bo'lib, butun bir osmonni tutib ketganligini", me'yordan ortiq darajada bo'rttirib ko'rsatishga xizmat qilganligini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Bu bilan iboraning ma'nosi yanada kuchayishiga, tasvirlanayotgan holatni bo'rttirib ko'rsatishga erishilgan.

2. Iboralar tarkibini kengaytirish. "Bunday holatda iboraning an'anaviy strukturasi kengayadi, iboraning o'zida esa semantik siljish yuz beradi, uning ekspressiv bo'yoqdorligi ortadi" [11; 133]. Iboraning leksik tarkibiga yangi so'z yoki so'z birikmasi kiritiladi. Xalqda yerga kirib ketmoq, yer yorilmadi-yu, yerga kirib ketmaslik iboralari keng qo'llaniladi. "O'zbek tilining frazeologik lug'ati"da yerga kirib ketmoq iborasi qo'yidagicha izohlangan: "Qattiq izza bo'lmoq, o'sal bo'lmoq"[10; 550]. Cho'lpon iboraga yangi so'z, ya'ni, yer so'zi oldidan yetti qat sifatlovchisini qo'shib iborani kengaytiradi va ketmoq fe'lining o'rnida uning inkor shakli – ketmaydi fe'lini qo'llaydi. Bu bilan ibora qo'shimcha konnotativ ma'no kasb etadi, ya'ni "izza bo'lish", "uyalish" ma'nosi o'rniga "bezbetlik", "sur" ma'nolari anglashiladi. Masalan: Uyalmaydi Miryoqub, xijolatidan yetti qat yer ostiga kirib ketmaydi... uni yer ham o'zining mahram qo'yniga olishdan tortinadi, chekinadi! ("Kecha va Kunduz").

3. Iboralar tarkibini qisqartirish. "Iboralar qisqaruvi dastlab nutq jarayonida boshlanadi va asta-sekinlik bilan tilda iboralarning to'la (yoyiq) va qisqargan variantlari paydo bo'la boshlaydi" [11; 142]. O'zbek tilida shovqini olamni buzadi, ovozi olamni buzadi iboralari xalqimiz tomonidan ko'p qo'llaniladi. Cho'lpon ushbu iborani qisqartirgan holda qo'llaydi: Biror choynak ortib qolsa, sovutib qo'yarmiz. Akam ba'zi vaqtda yaxna choy deb nax olamni buzub yuboradi. ("Nonushta"). Misoldan ko'rinib turibdiki, iboraning tarkibi qisqarishiga qaramasdan uning ma'nosiga putur yetmagan, o'z ma'nosini saqlab qolgan.

Xullas, Cho'lpon xalq og'zaki ijodi namunalarining katta bilimdoni sifatida iboralardan mohirlik bilan foydalangan. Bu bilan asarlarining badiiyligi, estetik ta'sirchanligi oshishiga erishgan.

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JURNALIST VA BLOGERLAR NUTQI ETIKASI

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Аннотация. В данной статье освещается культура и экспрессивные особенности речи журналистов и блогеров. Автор перечисляет негативные факторы, влияющие на эффективность речи и приводит рекомендации по совершенствованию речи.

Ключевые слова: речевая этика, культура речи, журналист, блогер, коммуникация, экспрессивность.

Ommaviy axborot vositalarining bugungi globallashuv jarayonida tutgan orni juda muhimdir. Xususan, televideniye, radio va internet tarmoqlaridan kuniga minglab axborot ma'lumotlar uzatiladi. Teleradiokanallarida va internet tarmoqlarida faoliyat olib borayotgan diktora yoki boshlovchi jurnalistlarning nutqlari ravon, talaffuzlari aniq bo'lishi kerak. Jurnalistning nutq madaniyati, ovozi yangilikning qimmatini oshirishga xizmat qiladi. Ovozning ta'sirchan kuchi va uning inson ruhiyatiga ta'sir etish imkoniyatlarini rad etib bo'lmaydi. Ovozning noto'g'ri qo'yilishi, tovushning past-balandligi axborotni yetkazishda to'sqinlik qilishi mumkin. Shuningdek, suxandonning adabiy til me'yorlariga amal qilgan holda ko'rsatuv olib borishi, davlat tilining boy imkoniyatlaridan mohirona foydalanish orqali ta'sirchanlikka erishishi, boshlovchi matn yozayotganda professional metodlarni qo'llashi kabi omillar jurnalist muvaffaqiyatini belgilab berishiga asoslangan.

M.Jumayev, D.Rahmonov [1], K.Adashboyeva [2] kabi tadqiqotchilarning maqolalarida teleboshlovchilarning nutq madaniyati, reportyor sifatida ishlash va axborot teleko'rsatuvining olib boruvchisi maqomiga erishish tadriji, telejurnalistning ijodkorligi, mavzu va uslub tanlashdagi mahorati, ko'rsatuvlarni tayyorlashdagi ishtiroki haqida bir qancha fikrlarni keltirib o'tishgan. Rus olimlaridan E.P.Proxorov jurnalistlar kasbiy etikasiga quyidagicha ta'rif beradi:

"Jurnalist kasbiy etikasi – bu kasbiy ijodiy tashkilotlarning yuridik jihatdan mustahkamlanmagan, lekin jurnalistik muhitda qabul qilingan va jamoatchilik fikri kuchini qo'llab-quvvatlovchi axloqiy yozma buyruqlar – prinsiplar, me'yorlar va jurnalistning axloqiy fe'l-atvor qoidalari" [3; 302]. Shu o'rinda, har qanday jurnalist yoki bloger (OAV)ning asosiy faoliyati jamiyat vakillari bilan muloqot qilishdan iborat. Bizga ma'lumki, bu soha vakillari og'zaki yoki yozma nutqqa murojaat qilishadi.

H.Saidov teleradio yangiliklarining o'ziga xosligi va tildan foydalanish masalalari, A.Pardayev, F.Ro'ziyev, X.Mahamadaliyevlar [4; 24] esa teleradiokanallarida adabiy til me'yorlariga rioya etish, teleboshlovchilar nutqi kabi muammolarni ilmiy-nazariy jihatdan tadqiq qilishgan.

Yurtimizda ommaviy axborot vositalarini "to'rtinchi hokimiyat" deb bilamiz. Jamiyatda bo'layotgan har bir o'zgarishlarni bilishimizda uning tutgan o'rnini katta. Bu soha nafaqat mafkura yaratadigan, uni shakallantiradigan manzil, qurol sifatida, balki turli ijtimoiy-siyosiy qarashlarni jamiyatga tezkor va aniq yetkazadigan vosita sifatida qaraymiz. So'nggi yillarda jurnalistik va bloger nutqining individual xususiyatlarini o'rganish hamda tadqiq qilishga alohida e'tibor berilmoqda.

Jamiyatda har kim o'z fikrini bemalol bildirishi, murojaat va e'tirozlari, taklif hamda shikoyatlarini erkin ifoda etisha olyapti. Bu borada jurnalist, blogerlarga katta imkoniyatlar berildi. Bular internet, undagi ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, portallar, gazeta-jurnallar, tv va radio, xullas, axborot yetkazishning barcha vositasini, onlayn va oflayn, an'anaviy va noan'anaviy instrumentlarni qamrab oldi. Shunga yarasha insonning so'z va axborot olish erkinligi, jurnalistik faoliyat erkinligi kafolatlari tubdan mustahkamlandi, bunday huquqlarga daxl yoki qarshilik qilganlarga nisbatan tegishli javobgarlik choralari kuchaytirildi. Yurtimizda shaffof va tezkor axborot maydoni vujudga keldi. Turli axborot saytlari rivojlana boshladi, blogerlik harakati keng quloch yozdi. Bugun har kim va har bir tashkilot, xoh u matbuot sohasi bo'lsin, xoh boshqa soha o'z sayti, "Telegram"

kanali, "Facebook", "Youtube", "Instagram" kabi ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda o'z sahifalarini yuritishi oddiy holga aylandi. Tabiiyki, bunday holatda axborot olish va yetkazish jabhasida ham raqobat keskin kuchayib ketdi.

Bugungi kunda jamiyatda auditoriya qamrovi bo'yicha, umuman, kontent reytinglarida nodavlat ommaviy axborot vositalari, xususan, internet saytlari, shuningdek, blogerlar yuritayotgan onlayn kanallar yetakchi o'rinlarda turadi [6]. Biz ularning bu yutuqlaridan faqat xursand bo'lamiz. Shu o'rinda davlat va nodavlat ommaviy axborot vositalari o'rtasida sog'lom raqobat paydo bo'ldi.

Har qanday yo'nalishda faoliyat olib borayotgan jurnalist yoki bloger – so'z tanlashdagi va qo'llashdagi mahoratining tadqiq etilishi tilshunosligimiz rivojida o'ziga xos ahamiyatga ega. Hozirgi kunda ommaviy axborot vositalari vakillariga jurnalistlar qatoriga blogerlar ham kiritilmoqda. Jurnalistning individual mahorati hamda nutqi aynan shu jihat orqali yaqqol ko'rinadi. Keyingi vaqtlarda shu soha vakillariga imkon qadar qo'shilayotgan blogerlardan ham jurnalistga xos bo'lgan me'yorlarga amal qilishni davr taqozo etmoqda. Tilshunosligimizda jurnalist nutqining o'ziga xosligi, jumladan, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar orqali faoliyat olib borayotgan blogerlar nutqi ham adabiy til me'yorlariga amal qilinishi kabi jihatlar bosh mavzu sifatida ko'tarilmoqda. Telejurnalist nutqini uslubiy jihatdan tahlil qilish, jurnalist va bloger tilning badiiy tasvir vositalaridan, shuningdek, umuman tildan foydalanishdagi mahoratini va bu orqali uning o'zbek tili rivojidagi o'rnini belgilashdan iboratdir. Ular nutqining uslubiyatini o'rganish quyidagi vazifalarni bajarishni taqozo etadi:

- Jurnalistikaning o'zbek tilshunosligida o'rganilish holatini ilmiy-tanqidiy baholash;
- Jurnalist va blogerlar nutqining fonetik xususiyatlarini tahlil etish;
- Jurnalist va blogerlar nutqining lingvistik tamoyillarini o'rganish;
- Jurnalist va bloger nutqining morfemik xususiyatlarini tahlil qilish;
- Jurnalist va blogerlar nutqi grammatik-stilistik jihatdan tahlil qilish. Bundan tashqari sohada faoliyat olib borayotgan jurnalist va blogerlar gender tengligi ham muhimdir.

Bugungi tilimizdagi eng noxush qusurlardan biri – so'z va iboralarni soxta liboslarga burkab, chirmab, go'yoki shu tilda chiroyli so'zlash uchun so'zlarning mazmuni va mohiyatiga yetmasdan talqin qilish holatlari ko'p uchramoqda. Teleradiokanallarda, ayniqsa, xususiy televideniye hamda radiokanallarda duch kelgan matnni alohida umumxalq tiliga xos bo'lgan so'zlar orqali jonli efir paytida foydalanish odat tusiga aylandi. Jumladan, "Qadringiz va qaddingiz doimo baland bo'lsin" degan oddiy va hamma uchun tushunarli jumalarni yosh boshlovchilar har kungi ko'rsatuv yoki eshittirishlarda foydalanib kelmoqda. Aslida ommaviy axborot vositalari vakillari efir paytida, albatta, adabiy til qonuniyatlaridan kelib chiqqan holda til me'yorlariga amal qilishi lozim.

Imlo va talaffuzlarda ham juda jiddiy muammolar yuzaga keladi. "U" tovushi bilan "o" tovushini, bo'g'iz "h" tovushi va chuqur til orqa t "x" ovushini farqlolmaydiganlar "hayot" so'zini "xayot" so'zi deya bemalol aytishmoqda. Ba'zi jurnalistlarning ochiqdan-ochiq beboshligi, savodining g'orligi buning ustiga tinglovchi bilan chaq-chaqlashishi efir mas'uliyatini his etmasligiga toqat qilib bo'lmaydi. Ayniqsa, nodavlat teleradiokanallardagi ko'ngilochar ko'rsatuvlar, "shou" dasturlarda sheva va lahjaga xos bo'lgan so'zlardan foydalanishmoqda. Aslida, "Jurnalist" – o'z nutqi, tashqi ko'rinishi hamda dunyoqarashi bilan qolgan soha vakillaridan ajralib turishi lozim. Jumladan, hozirgi kunda faoliyat olib borayotgan jurnalist: teleboshlovchi, suhandon yoki sport sharhlovchilariga – "O'zbekiston" telekanali "Assalom O'zbekiston" ko'rsatuvchi suxandoni Rustamova Dildora, "Sevimli" telekanali "Yangi zamon" dasturi muxbiri Olimov Jahongir, "Zo'r tv" telekanali "Bu kun" informatsion tahliliy dasturi muxbiri Nosirova Iroda hamda "Sport" telekanali futbol sharlovchilari Hamidov Xayrulla va Fayziyev Davronlarni namuna qilib ko'rsata olamiz.

Blogerlardan huquqiy maslahat va jamoatchilik uchun qonunlarimizda bo'layotgan muhim yangiliklarni yoritib boruvchi "Xushnubek.uz" telegram kanali blogeri Xudoyberdiyev Xushnubek, tilshunos va jurnalist "Asanov formati" telegram kanali blogeri Asanov Eldar, sport sharhlovchisi, "Kun.uz" sayti muxbiri hamda bloger Akmalov Boburlarni yuqorida nomi keltirilib o'tilganlar ro'yxatiga qo'shishimiz mumkin.

Aksincha, ba'zi jurnalist va blogerlarning xato va kamchiliklarini umumlashtirgan holda quyidagi fikrga kelimiz. Muloqot paytida e'tibor qaratilishi lozim bo'lgan xotolar:

1. Teletomoshabinlarning talab-istaklarini e'tiborga olish zarur, avvalambor, odamlar uchun kerakli bo'lgan voqea-hodisalarga qiziqish bildirish kerak. Shuning uchun har qanday axborotni uzatishda yoki fikrni bildirishda auditoriyaning manfaatlaridan kelib chiqish zarur.

2. Auditoriyani bilmaslik axborot uzatishida yoki fikr bildirishda konkret auditoriyaning xususiyatlari talab-ehhtiyojlari manfaatlariga tayanish lozim;

3. Muloqot ikki yoqlama jarayon ekanligini hisobga olmaslik bu axborotni uzatish jarayonining o'zi - hali muloqot o'rnatiladi degani emas, auditoriya ham munosabat bildira boshlagandagina muloqot o'rnatiladi va samara beradi.

Jurnalist va blogerlar nutqining muhim fazilatlaridan biri – ifodalilik, ta'sirchanlikdir. Ifodali, ta'sirchan nutq tinglovchida qiziqish uyg'otadi, uning ongiga tez yetib boradi, uning e'tibori va qiziqishini qozonadi. Nutqning aloqaviy sifatlari-aniqligi, to'g'riligi, mantiqiyliqi, sofligi (tozaligi) – nutqning ta'sirchanligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi [7; 84].

Jurnalist va bloger nutqi samarador bo'lishi uchun quyidagi talablarga javob berishi kerak:

1. Nutq auditoriyaga mos bo'lishi kerak;
2. Nutq aniq bo'lishi kerak;
3. Nutq ta'sirchan bo'lishi munosabat uygotishi lozim;
4. Nutq aniq maqsadga yo'naltirilishi kerak;

5. Nutq o'qilmaydi balki tinglanadi. Shu bois sof muloqot bilan bog'liq talablar vujudga keladiki, ularni hisobga olish zarur. Bizningcha, bugungi kun jurnalistlari hamda blogerlari o'zlari ustiida ko'proq ishlashlari, o'zlariga yanada talabchan bo'lishlari kerakligini taqozo etadi. Bloger auditoriya talab etadigan yangiliklarning, turi va mazmunini his qilishi kerak, aks holda u an'anaviy jurnalistika vakillari va boshqa blogerlar bilan raqobatga bardosh berolmaydi. Blogerlarga qo'yiladigan yana bir talab – turli rahbarlar va politexnologlarning bevosita yoki bilvosita buyurtmalarini bajarishdan bosh tortishdir. Blogerlik faoliyatini olib boradigan muallif nafaqat savodli, shu bilan birga u ham tashqi, ham ichki erkinlikka ega bo'lishi zarur. Blogerlarning bir qismi odatda muntazam yozadigan doimiy mualliflar bo'lmaydilar.

Bizning fikrimizcha, jurnalist va blogerlar vakillarining milliy madaniy leksikondan foydalanishiga turli xil auditoriyani hisobga olgan holda ehtiyotkorlik bilan yondashish kerak. Madaniy haqiqiylik va inklyuzivlik o'rtasida muvozanatni saqlash juda muhimdir. Ommaviy axborot vositalari faoliyatining tashkilotchilari, ya'ni jurnalist va blogerlar o'z faoliyatining ijtimoiy va ijodiy erkinligi uchun tinimsiz kurash olib boradilar. Har bir jurnalist hamda bloger o'z faoliyatining ijtimoiy va ijodiy muammolarini hal etishi eng yuqori erkinlikdir. Shunday qilib, jurnalist va blogerlar har bir tayyorlagan material, ma'lumotni o'z auditoriyasiga yetkazib berishda nutq madaniyatiga e'tibor qaratishi lozim deb hisoblaymiz. Hozirgi kunda davlat va nodavlat teleradiokanallarida hamda ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda faoliyat olib borayotgan muxbir, suxandon, teleboshlovchi, sharhlovchi hamda blogerlar adabiy til qonun-qoidalariga to'liq amal qilishi shart ekanligini ta'kidlab o'tmoqchimiz.

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RAMZ VA PRETSEDENT NOM MUNOSABATI

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Аннотация. *Одной из проблем лингвокультурологии является вопрос о соотношении символов с прецедентными именами. В данной статье символ описывается как лингвокультурный концепт, также обсуждается его связь с эталоном. Также автор рассматривает вопрос о роли имён в системе символов.*

Ключевые слова: лингвокультурология, символ, миф, образ, эталон, прецедентное имя.

Insoniyat tarixiy taraqqiyoti davomida, ibtidoiy dunyoqarash shakllangan zamonlardayoq moddiy borliqdan tashqari ramzlar olamida ham yashagan. Shu jihatdan ramzlar inson tasavvuri va tafakkurining eng dastlabki hosilalaridan deyish xato bo'lmaydi. Sh.Turdimov ramz sifatida kelayotgan, anglanayotgan narsaning (u nima bo'lmasin) o'zida bir qancha tushunchalarni jamlab, turg'un assotsiatsiya (imuquq) uyg'otishini ramzning asosiy xossasi deb aytadi [5; 5]. Olimga ko'ra, turmush, fan, adabiyot va san'atdagi ramzlar vazifasiga ko'ra farqlanib, bir sohada ramzlar tizimi ikkinchi sohada bu xil vazifani bajarmasligi mumkin. Turmushdagi ramzlar tizimi kommunikativ vazifa bajarishga, fandagi ramzlar tushunchalarni bildirishga, san'at va adabiyotdagi ramzlar tizimi esa kechinma, voqelik va holatni badiiy-estetik anglatishga xizmat qiladi [5; 5]. Rus tilshunosi V.Maslova ramzlarning quyidagi xususiyatlarini ajratadi: obrazlilik, motivlashganlik, mazmun kompleksligi, ko'p ma'nolilik, ramz mazmun chegarasi yoyilib ketishi (noaniqlik), simbolning arxetipligi, alohida olingan madaniyatda ramzning universalligi, ularning boshqa madaniyatlardagi ramzlar bilan kesishuvi, ramzlar tizimining milliy-madaniy o'ziga xosligi, mif va arxetipda o'rnashganlik [7; 76].

Ramz tadqiqi miflardan boshlanadi deyilsa, mubolag'a bo'lmaydi. Miflar etnos dunyoqarashi va e'tiqodining qadimiy shakli bo'lish bilan bir qatorda majoziylik asosida millat madaniyatining boshlang'ich nuqtasi sifatida ham namoyon bo'ladi. Y.Stepanov ramzlar ilmiy emas, balki poetikaga daxldor tushuncha deb hisoblaydi. Olimga ko'ra, ramzlar faqatgina ma'lum poetik tizimlar doirasida qimmatli va ayni vaqtda faqat shu shu doiradagina haqiqiydir [9]. Turli xalqlarning madaniyat tizimida muhrlangan ramzlar o'zaro farqli tushunchalarni, dunyoqarashni, qadriyat va an'analar tizimini ifodalashi mumkin. Y.Lotman aytganidek, madaniyat, bir tarafdin, meros qoldirilgan matnlar bo'lsa, boshqa tarafdin, meros ramzlar tizimidir [9].

Ramzlar asosida obraz yotadi. Ramzlar obraz asosida yuzaga keladi, ya'ni har qanday ramz – obraz, biroq obrazni ramz sifatida qabul qilish uchun ma'lum cheklov va mezonlar mavjud. N.Fray sh'riyatdagi obrazlarning "ramziyligi"ga quyidagi alomatlarni keltiradi: 1) kontekstda abstrakt ramziy ma'no anglashiladi; 2) obrazni to'g'ridan to'g'ri tavsiflash imkonsiz yoki yetarlicha emas; 3) obrazda mif, afsona, folklor bilan assotsiatsiya yashiringan bo'ladi [4; 76].

Tilshunos Sh.Usmanovaga ko'ra, "ramz – tashqi dunyoning turli madaniyat vakillari ichki dunyosi, ongi, tafakkuri va ruhidagi aksi. Ramz belgi bo'lib, uning dastlabki ma'nosidan boshqa ma'no uchun shakl sifatida foydalaniladi" [1; 160]. Shuningdek, olima ijtimoiy muloqot tizimida muayyan obyektlar, masalan, predmet, harakat, hodisa, matn, tasvir, hayvon, o'simlik, rang, raqam va hokazolar ramz bo'lib kelishi; ramzlar moddiy, tushunchaviy, so'zli, tasviriy va ovozli bo'lishi mumkinligini alohida ta'kidlaydi. Aslida ramz va etalonni bir hodisa sifatida qarash ko'p kuzatiladi. Lekin, bizningcha, bu ikki hodisaning umumiy nuqtalari bo'lgani holda, ayrim farqli jihatlari ham mavjud. Masalan, bo'ri totemi ramz sifatida turkiy xalqlarda jasurlik, bo'sunmaslik ramzi sifatida kelsa, o'z navbatida bizning lingvojamiyatimiz uchun ochlik etaloni hamdir – bo'ridek och komparativ iborasi fikrimizni dalillaydi. Bir obyektga nisbatan turli madaniyatlarda turlicha ramzlar tizimi shakllanishi ijtimoiy, maishiy, diniy, tabiiy omillar asosida shakllanganligini kuzatish mumkin. Masalan, aksar xalqlarda it kulti vafodorlik, do'stlik ramzi sanalsa-da (it so'zi haqoratni ham ifodalaydi, lekin ramz sifatida bizning madaniyatimizda vafodorlik ramzi sifatida qo'llanadi), beloruslarda

it kultiga salbiy munosabat kuchliroq ekanligi anglashiladi. Bu holat belorus frazeologik birliklar tizimida it bilan bog'liq birliklarning tahlilida yanada oydinlashadi. Beloruslar yomon odam yoki dangasa, landovur ma'nolarini ifodlashda it komponentli iboralarga murojaat qilishi ma'lum bo'ladi [8]. Tabiat hodisalariga munosabat ham aynan shunday: arab xalqlarida, ayniqsa, issiq iqlimli mamlakat xalqlari uchun yomg'ir baraka ramzi sanalsa, doimiy namlikda bo'lgan Yevropa xalqlarida yomg'ir tushkunlik, depressiv kayfiyat, yomon hodisalarning ramzi o'laroq namoyon bo'ladi.

Pretsedent nomlardagi ramziylik funksiyasiga Y.Karaulov tomonidan pretsedent matn muammosi tadqiq obyektiga aylanganda etibor qaratilgan. Olim qayd etishicha, "pretsedent matn ramzining lisoniy ifoda etish usuli boshqa qatlamga oid stereotiplarining ifoda etish usuli bilan muvofiq keladi: masalan, qanotli jumalarga aylangan sitata yoki faqat badiiy obrazni ifodalashgagina emas, balki adresatda tanlangan pretsedent matn bilan bog'liq boshqa turli konnotatsiyalarni faollashtiruvchi atoqli ot" [3; 102]. Onomastik birliklar voqelikdagi aloqa vositasi bo'lib xizmat qiladilar, shu sababli ham atoqli otlar tilning eng qadimiy birliklaridan sanalib, ularga xos bo'lgan mifologik tabiat ramzlar tizimi bilan bevosita aloqador ekanligidan dalolat beradi. Badiiy onimlar tadqiqi bilan shug'ullangan Y.F.Kosichenko badiiy matndagi onimlarni tasnif qilgan ekan, semiotik tahlilga ko'ra ularni indeksal, ikonik va simvolik turlarga ajratadi va simvolik (ramziy) onimlar pretsedent nomning aynan o'zi ekanligini qayd etadi. Badiiy matndagi onimlarning simvolik tipi yuqori informativlikka ega ekanligi, shuningdek, dunyoviy va madaniy qadriyatlar bilimiga yo'l ochadi, deb yozadi olim.

O'zbek tilshunosligida atoqli otlar, xususan, pretsedent nomlarning ramz sifatida kelishi bilan bog'liq ilmiy qarashlar D.Xudoyberganova va D.Andaniyazovalarning ishlarida kuzatiladi [6; 133]. D.Xudoyberganova ramziylik atoqli otning pretsedentlik xususiyatini yuzaga chiqaruvchi asosiy jihat ekanligini e'tirof etadi. D.Andaniyazova dissertatsiyasida Ka'ba, Makkatillo toponim va oykodomonimlari muqaddaslik ramzi, Toj mahal sevgi ramzi, Sahroyi Kabir toponimi "muayyan sharoitning yo'qligi", "taraqqiyotdan mahrumlik, hayotdan, rivojlanishdan orqada qolib ketganlik" holatining, shuningdek, Elsinor, Ichon qal'a, Dishon qal'a, To'polondaryo singari qator poetonimlarning ramziylik kasb etganini badiiy matndagi misollar orqali dalillaydi [2; 123-136].

Pretsedent nomning ramz sifatida kelishining yaqqol namunalaridan yana biri Amerika Qo'shma Shtatlarining ramzi sifatida ozg'indan kelgan Sem amaki (inglizchada "Uncle Sam" abbreviaturaga aylantirilganda "Un[itred]" "S[tates]" of "Am[erica]" – Qo'shma Shtatlar bilan mutanosib keladi) tasviri ko'z oldimizda gavdalanadi [7]. Odatda, Sem amaki tasviri qirrador yuz tuzilishiga ega, cho'qqisoqol, Amerika bayrog'i elementlari mavjud bo'lgan silindr va ko'k frak kiygan oq tanli, ozg'in keksa yoshli kishi qiyofasida gavdalanir. Bu obrazning ommalashishi 1812-yilda Britaniya-Amerika urushi bilan bog'lanadi. O'sha davrlarda Nyu-York harbiy bazasiga Sem Uilson ismli qassob front uchun bochkalarda g'osht topshirib boradi. Sem doim bochkalar ustiga "U.S" ishorasini yozib qo'ygan, harbiylar esa buni Sem amakidan deb hazil tariqasida gapirib yurganlar. Keyinchalik Nyu-York gazetalar vatanparvarlik ramzi sifatida Sem amakining suratini chop etadi va shu voqeadan so'ng Sem amaki Amerika timsoli sifatida keng ommalashadi. Yoki yana bir universal nom e'tiqodi boshqa bo'lgan g'arb xalqlari vakillarining dunyoqarashi, e'tiqodi va qadriyatlari asosida ommalashgan Santa Klaus diniy Rojdestvo bayrami va keyinchalik uning ta'sir ko'lamini va ichimlik markasining keng targ'iboti natijasida Yangi yil ramziga aylanishini ham keltirishimiz mumkin.

Atoqli otning stereotip, etalon va ramzlar tizimidan joy egallashi aynan shu nomning pretsedentga aylanganini ko'rsatadi. Pretsedentlik lingvomadaniy jamiyat vakillari lisoniy xotirasidan mustahkam o'rin egallaganlik va diskursda qayta-qayta jonlanish xususiyati bilan ham namoyon bo'ladi. Biroq pretsedent nomning etalonga aylanishi yoki ramz sifatida namoyon bo'lishini aynan bir narsa deb bo'lmaydi. Aslida har ikki holatni chalkashtirish ko'p uchraydi. Ramzda majoziylik kuchli bo'lishi, uning sifat yoki xususiyat bilan bevosita aloqasi bo'lmasligi mumkin. Biroq etalon tanlangan xususiyatning markazida turuvchi unsur sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Masalan, Humo qushining tinchlik yoki davlat, hokimiyat ramzi ekanligida reallikdan uzoqlik kuzatilib, majoziylik unsuri yetakchilik qiladi, biroq Hotamtoyning saxiylik etaloni bo'lib belgilanishi shu nom (obraz) atrofida asosiy va eng yetakchi jihat – saxiylik shu personajga xos ekanligini ko'rish mumkin. Anglashiladiki, etalonda reallikka yaqinlik, xususiyatning sohibi ekanlik jihati yetakchilik qilsa, ramzlarda badiiy tasavvur va obrazlilik ustuvorligi kuzatiladi. Nomning mashhurligi u bilan bog'liq stereotip qarashlarni shakllantiradi va bu nom atrofida o'ziga xos stereotipik bilimlar tizimi yuzaga

kelishiga olib keladi. Bir pretsedent nomga nisbatan turli lingvomadaniy jamiyatlarda turlicha stereotiplar shakllanganligini ko'rish mumkin.

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SHAVKAT RAHMON SHE'RLARIDA ALLITERATSIYANING IFODALANISHI

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Аннотация. В данной статье на основе лингвопоэтических анализов рассмотрено явление аллитерации в поэзии Шавката Рахмона, демонстрирующая богатые лингвистические возможности узбекского языка.

Ключевые слова: аллитерация, гласные звуки, художественный текст, поэтическая реализация, лингвопоэтика, художественный замысел.

Fonetik sath nutq tovushlarini o'rganadi, tildagi so'zlar, iboralar, gaplar nutq tovushlari vositasida shakllanadi va yuzaga chiqadi. Badiiy adabiyotda ko'proq lirik asarlarda tovushlar, urg'u va ohang hissiy ta'sirchanlikni oshirishda muhim poetik vositadir. She'riy matnda fonetik birliklarning aktualashuvi turli holatlarda voqeyalanadi. Ijodkor o'zi yaratayotgan asarga o'quvchi diqqatini tortish, uni hayajonga solish yoxud hissiy ta'sir qilish uchun tafakkurida paydo bo'lgan g'oyalar, tasavvurlarni nutqiy jarayonda rang-barang, jilolangan, she'riy intonatsiya, ritmlarni o'zining strukturasi qamrab olgan, talaffuzi va aytilishida ohangdoshlik, qofiyadoshlik kabi hodisalarni singdirgan tovush va tovushlar birikmasi orqali ham ifodalaydi. Natijada badiiy matnda ayrim tovushlar qavatlanadi, tushib qoladi yoki ketma-ket takrorlanib ohangdoshlik hosil qiladi, shunday usullar bilan fonetik ekspressivlik ta'minlanadi.

Fonetik ekspressivlik tovushlar takroridan hosil bo'lgan ohanglarda yaqqol ko'rinadi. Tovushlar takroridan yaralgan badiiy ohanglar xalq qo'shiqlari, masallari, tez aytishlari va mumtoz adabiyotimiz namunalari orqali bizga ma'lum. Ularda takrorlar asosiy tasviriy vosita bo'lib kelgan. "Takrorlar she'riyatning ohangdoshlik va xushohanglik xususiyatlarini kuchaytirish orqali musiqiylikni maksimal darajada ta'minlaydi. Shu bilan birga ular fikr va ma'noning turli qirra darajalarini anglatadi" [1; 386]. S.Karimovning "Badiiy uslub va tilning ifoda tasvir vositalari" kitobida takrorning o'ttizga yaqin, masalan, alliteratsiya, anafora kabi turlarining mavjudligi" [2; 44] haqida ma'lumot berilgan.

Alliteratsiya badiiy matnda tovushlarning poetik aktuallashuvida muhim vosita hisoblanadi. Alliteratsiya fonopoetik vosita sifatida she'riy matn intonatsion butunligi shakllanashida faol ishtirok etadi va ohangdorlikni kuchaytiradi. Tilshunos olim M.Yo'ldoshev alliteratsiya haqidagi "... badiiy tafakkur ifodasi, bu ifodaning ta'sir quvvatini kuchaytirishda undoshlar asosida yuzaga keladigan alliteratsiyaning favqulodda o'rne juda qadim zamonlardayoq anglab yetilganini ham alohida qayd etish lozim" ekanligini ta'kidlaydi [5; 165]. Alliteratsiyaning she'riyatdagi o'rne o'zbek tilshunosligida bir necha tadqiqot ishlarida o'rganilgan. Jumladan, A.Shofqorovning "Mirtemir she'riyatida takrorning ma'noviy-uslubiy xususiyatlari" mavzusidagi nomzodlik dissertatsiyasining "Mirtemir she'riyatida fonetik takrorlar" nomli I bobida hamda S.Umirovning "O'zbek she'riyatida lingvistik vositalar va poetik individuallik" mavzusidagi filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) dissertatsiyasining "Poetik matnda takror usulini qo'llashning prosodik va kompozitsion tamoyillari" nomli II bobida fikr bildirilgan. Shuningdek, J.Yuldashevning "Usmon Nosir lingvopoetikasi" mavzusidagi filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) tadqiqotining III bobi, birinchi faslida alliteratsiya Usmon Nosir she'rlari misolida chuqur o'rganilgan.

Cho'ng shoir Shavkat Rahmon ijodida ham alliteratsiya matn mazmuniga mos shakily turli poetik ma'no aks ettirgan go'zal namunalarni kuzatamiz.

*Tog' xo'rsinib yubordi og'ir –
vodiylarga yugurdi shamol,
yuzlarini yashirdi hilol.
Tog' xo'rsinib yubordi og'ir,
Teran xobdan uyg'ondi yurak,
tog'lar kabi xo'rsinmoq kerak. ("Tog' xo'rsinib yubordi og'ir")*

Vertikal alliteratsiyaning ajoyib namunasi bo'lgan ushbu parchada shoir o'quvchining nafaqat e'tiborini jalb qilishni, balki asar mazmunini tovushlar uyg'unligi orqali ham ifodalamoqchi bo'lganini ko'ramiz. Ya'ni Shavkat Rahmonning ushbu she'ri Vatanimiz hali mustaqillikka erishmagan paytda yozilgan bo'lib, unda xalq yuragida yillar davomida yetilib kelayotgan erk sog'inchini yanada yorqinroq, kuchliroq aks ettirish, kurashish payti kelganligi haqida yashirin da'vati aks etgan. Shoir ijodida uning badiiy niyatini to'liq gavdalandiruvchi bir necha poetik obrazlar bor. Ulardan biri "tog'" obrazidir. Bu haqda adabiyotshunos olim R.Mullaxo'jayeva "She'rda tog' obrazi sabr-toqatni kuch-qudratga aylantirgan bardoshning poetik ifodasi", deya ta'riflaydi [3; 117]. She'rda tog' ho'rsinishi – bardoshning sinishiga mengzanadi. Shuning uchun ham shoir "tog'lar kabi ho'rsinmoq kerak" kerakligini ta'kidlaydi. "T" undoshi hosil bo'lish o'rne va usuliga ko'ra til oldi, portlovchi undosh. "She'rda shoir badiiy niyatini "t" tovushining takrori orqali beradi hamda o'quvchida kuchli emotsionallikni qo'zg'atadi

Nutqning fonetik "qiyofasi"ni yaratishda alliteratsiya muhim vositalaridan biri sanaladi. Masalan.

*Kelar qora rido kiygan tun,
sukunatning qushlarin suyar,
suronlardan horgan shaharni
silab-siypab uxlatib qo'yar. ("Safsarlashar oqshomgi osmon")*

Alliteratsiya asosida aloqalanib poetik yuk olgan ushbu parchadagi sukunatning, suyar, suronlardan, silab-siypab leksemalari tarkibidagi "s" tovushi tunning tasviriy ifodasi sokinlikni ifodalab, muhim poetik vazifa bajargan. Shoirning mahorati tunning mohiyatini tovushlar zamiriga joylay olganida va matnning mazmun va shakl uyg'unligiga erisha olganida yaqqol seziladi, go'yoki ss jim tun deya otganday o'quvchi ongida tasavvur uyg'otadi.

Ijodkor voqea-hodisalarning nazarda tutilgan muhim tomoniga o'quvchi diqqatini tortish, uni bo'rttirib tasvirlash niyatida ham she'riy asarlarda ayrim tovushlarni takrorlaydi. Masalan, quyidagi she'rda erksiz xalq ruhiyati lirik qahramon ruhiyati misolida aks ettirilgan.

*Asov ko'ngil ...
ergashar andom,
qadim yo'ldan qayga yetaklar.
Qorong'ilik quyular qandoq,
qandoq titrar edi chechaklar.
O'sib borar qop - qora besha,*

sovib borar yo'llar tuprog'i.
Ko'ngil tashna
Qondiray desam,
qaynab turar g'amlar bulog'i. ("Qumaru")

Lirik qahramonning o'zlikni anglashga bo'lgan harakatsizlikka qarshi ruhiy isyoni tasviri ifodalanishida "q" undoshi kuchli poetk aktuallashgan, gorizantal va vertikal alliteratsiyadan foydalanilgan.

Umuman, Shavkat Rahmon o'z she'rlarida nafaqat matn mazmuniga, balki uning shakily va tovush qobig'iga ham e'tiborli bo'lib mos tovushlarni badiiy maqsad ifodasi uchun saralay bilgan, mazmun va shakl uyg'unligiga erishgan. Bu favqulodda holat bo'lib, she'rning o'ziga ohangini hosil qilgan. Shuningdek alliteratsiyadan unumli foydalanib, turli shakllarni yuzaga keltirgan va ularning har biriga poetik vazifa yuklay olgan.

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ИННОВАЦИОННЫЙ ПОДХОД В ОБУЧЕНИИ ЛЕКСИЧЕСКИХ ТЕМ ДЛЯ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ГРУПП ВЫСШИХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЙ

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada rus tilini chet tili sifatida o'qitishning an'anaviy va innovatsion usullari taqqoslash orqali ko'rib chiqilgan, shuningdek, rus tili darslarida lug'atni o'rgatishning kognitiv modelini yaratish imkoniyatlari tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: integrativ yondashuv, usul, rus tilini o'qitishning an'anaviy va innovatsion yondashuvlari, lug'at o'qitishning kognitiv modeli.

Разработка лексических знаний и навыков, пронизывающих все уровни языковой системы, считается ключевым фактором успешного освоения иностранного языка. Словарный запас, в своей иерархической структуре, формирует цельное представление о мире, отражая взаимосвязь между человеком, культурой и обществом в рамках национальной специфики как части общемировой системы ценностей.

Мы предлагаем новый методический подход к решению указанной проблемы, который заключается в разработке комплексной инновационной модели обучения лексике на занятиях по русскому языку как иностранному в традиционных университетах по гуманитарным специальностям. Наша цель, озвученная в научном исследовании на тему "Улучшение системы и инновационные подходы к преподаванию лексики при обучении русскому языку как иностранному", успешно достигается. Этот проект был реализован в рамках научного направления, связанного с лингвокультурологическим описанием различных уровней языковых единиц и методологическими принципами преподавания языков, под руководством доктора филологических наук, профессора

Р.К. Боженковой. Это исследование можно связать с другими работами, выполненными в рамках этого научного направления, такими как "Понимание текста как лингвокультурологическая категория" Р.К. Боженковой (2020), "Логико-синтаксические механизмы кодирования возможных культурных смыслов в тексте" Н.А. Боженковой (2015), "Формирование личности в процессе обучения русскому языку: теория и опыт практической работы" Н.П. Шульгиной (2017), "Понимание текста в контексте лингвокультурологии" Р.К. Боженковой (2015) и другими.

В то же время, в условиях глобальной трансформации системы высшего образования происходит изменение содержания и структуры общепризнанной методологии преподавания русского языка как иностранного и его составляющих. Происходят потяжкие изменения в структуре и содержании концепции «язык - культура - личность», а также появляются новые методы обучения русскому языку и его носителям. В данном случае речь идет о том, чтобы использовать уже накопленный педагогический опыт для комплексного усвоения студентами иностранного языка в тесной взаимосвязи с их интеллектуальным становлением и потребностями.

Этим требованиям в современной методике преподавания РКИ всецело отвечают личностно, коммуникативно и профессионально ориентированный подходы.

Возникновение коммуникативно-ориентированного (коммуникативного) подхода было ознаменовано стремлением методистов представить язык именно как средство общения. В этом подходе реализуются важнейшие требования к современному учебному процессу: коммуникативное поведение преподавателя и иностранного студента на занятии, а также использование заданий, моделирующих реальные ситуации общения [3; 192].

Главным критерием отбора лексического материала в рамках рассматриваемого подхода служит принцип функциональности, предполагающий организацию лексики по определенной тематике на основе частотности употребления слов для данной ситуации общения, а также выбор основных сфер коммуникации и постановка проблем для коллективного обсуждения [4].

В центре личностно-ориентированного подхода находится личность иностранного студента, и главной целью обучения языку становится его всестороннее воспитание и комплексное и непрерывное образование. Преподавание РКИ в рамках данного подхода включает в себя не только овладение разными видами речевой деятельности, но и овладение знаниями, которые обеспечивают более высокое качество коммуникации [5].

Вместе с тем профессиональную компетенцию иностранных студентов определяет, с одной стороны, объем специально-научных знаний, а с другой - уровень владения иностранным языком [2]. Именно поэтому целью профессионально ориентированного подхода к обучению РКИ является развитие способности решать в процессе общения средствами изучаемого языка (в том числе и лексическими) не только общекультурные, но и профессиональные задачи, связанные с формированием таких знаний и навыков, которые помогут будущим специалистам адаптироваться к новым условиям, преодолеть коммуникативный барьер в рамках профессионально-делового общения, а также повысят их конкурентоспособность на рынке труда [2].

Поставив целью работы обоснование выбора и разработки инновационных подходов к преподаванию лексики русского языка, мы считаем, что в полной мере можем опираться на описанные выше современные подходы, предположив, что важным и плодотворным для реализации целей нашего исследования будет создание когнитивной модели обучения лексике в курсе РКИ, на развитие у иностранных студентов способности осуществлять все виды речевой деятельности (говорение, письмо, аудирование и чтение) на основе сформированных лексических навыков, а также знакомить их со стратегиями речепонимания и речевоспроизводства. Кроме того, результаты проведенного анализа психолого-педагогической и методической литературы позволили в качестве основополагающих считать следующие составляющие:

- 1) коммуникативная направленность процесса обучения;
- 2) взаимосвязанное обучение всем видам речевой деятельности (говорение, чтение, аудирование, письмо);
- 3) учет профессиональных интересов иностранных студентов;
- 4) усвоение лексики, отражающей национально-культурные особенности страны изучаемого языка;

5) активизация когнитивной деятельности иностранных студентов и учет их интеллектуально-познавательных способностей.

В систему лексических знаний и навыков мы включаем следующие компоненты: понимание семантики лексических единиц и правильный выбор значения многозначного слова в определенном контексте или ситуации общения, комбинирование единиц между собой на основе правил лексической и грамматической сочетаемости и распознавание в речи границ каждого отдельно взятого слова, а также использование знакомых лексем в процессе осуществления разных видов речевой деятельности.

Структура занятий:

Компонент структуры занятия	Характеристика компонента
1. Введение в языковую среду	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Формулировка темы и основной цели занятия. • Подготовка иностранных студентов к активной учебно-познавательной деятельности
2. Актуализация известной лексики	Выполнение заданий, направленных на реализацию лексики, изученной на предыдущих занятиях, в речи
Компонент структуры занятия	Характеристика компонента
3. Предъявление новой лексики	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Работа со словарем, включающая в себя основную (тематическую) и вспомогательную (учебную) лексику. • Семантизация лексем. • Чтение и запись новых слов
4. Тренировка введенной лексики	Тренировка новой лексики путем выполнения языковых упражнений
5. Закрепление лексики на основе учебных текстов	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Анализ функционирования лексических единиц в их естественном окружении; • Обобщение и систематизация лексического материала, развитие речевых умений на основе текстовых упражнений
6. Активизация новой лексики в речи	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Выполнение творческих заданий коммуникативного характера на продуцирование нового текста с введенной лексикой
7. Подведение итогов занятия	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Концентрация внимания иностранных студентов на материале, изученном на занятии. • Ориентация на задачи следующего урока

Результатом создания когнитивной модели обучения лексике русского языка стало схематичное представление структуры урока с описанием его основных компонентов, представляющих собой последовательно сменяющиеся стадии изучения новых слов. Следующим этапом должна стать работа, связанная с определением особенностей организации занятий и их непосредственной разработкой в рамках представленной модели обучения лексике.

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SOTSIOLEKT VA JARGON

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Аннотация. В статье приведены сведения о социолекте и разновидности социолекта – жаргоне, являющимися объектами изучения социолингвистики, рассмотрены профессионализмы, функции и значение социолектов.

Ключевые слова: социолингвистика, социолект, региональный диалект, жаргон, общий жаргон, военный жаргон, профессионализм.

Har bir tilning adabiy tilga mansub bo'lmagan, biroq xalqning katta qismi uchun asosiy muloqot vositasi hisoblangan so'zlari mavjud. Bu so'zlar kundalik hayotda ko'p ishlatilgani bois tilshunoslikda ulardan voz kechib bo'lmaydi. Muloqot uchun qulay hisoblangan bu birliklar tilshunoslikda sotsiolekt deb yuritiladi. "Sotsiolekt" atamasi tilshunoslikda nisbatan yaqinda – XX asrning ikkinchi yarmida paydo bo'lgan. U ikki qismdan: jamiyatga munosabatni ko'rsatadigan ijtimoiy qismdan va "dialekt" so'zining ikkinchi tarkibiy qismidan hosil bo'lgan; bu mohiyatan "ijtimoiy dialekt" iborasining bir so'zli birikmasidir.

V.M.Jirmunskiy jamiyatdagi mavjud tilning hududiy dialektlarga bo'linishidan tashqari, o'z navbatida, sotsial dialektlarga bo'linishini ta'kidlab shunday yozadi: "Har qanday tilda hududiy dialektologiya mavjud ekan, unda sotsial dialektologiya ham bo'lishi kerak" [4; 61].

Sotsiolekt – muayyan jamiyatda ijtimoiy kelib chiqishi, kasbiy mansubligi, qiziqishlari umumiy, yosh jihatidan yaqin bo'lgan kishilar yoki shunday sotsial belgilariga ko'ra birlashgan guruhlar qo'llaydigan tilning yashash shakllaridan biri. Sotsiolektlar adabiy tildan asosan leksik, qisman grammatik jihatdan farqlanadi. Masalan, shifokor nutqi bilan harbiyning nutqi leksikasi va ifoda tarziga ko'ra farq qiladi. Shifokor nutqida og'ir-vazminlik, harbiy nutqida tezlik, keskinlik ustuvor bo'ladi [2; 77].

Chex tilshunoslari tomonidan sotsiolektlar yuzasidan tadqiqotlar olib borilgan va ular quyidagicha tasniflangan:

1. Tilshunos Y. Filipes sotsiolektlarni uch guruhga ajratgan: a) professionalizm; b) sleng; c) jargon;

2. J. Xloupek nazariyasiga ko'ra: a) professional nutq; b) sleng; c) argo;

3. L. Klimeshning qarashlariga ko'ra ijtimoiy nutq birinchi navbatda a) jargon

b) jinoyatchilarning argosiga bo'linadi [5; 14]. Tilshunos Y.Filipes tomonidan keltirilgan tasnif zamonaviy tilshunoslikdagi sotsiolektlar tasnifi bilan deyarli o'xshashdir. Lekin Filipes tadqiqoti davomida argoni sotsiolektning alohida turi sifatida tasniflamagan, u argoni jargonning bir turi sifatida keltirib o'tgan. Klimeshning qarashlari esa zamonaviy tilshunoslikdagi sotsiolektlar tasnifiga mos emas.

Angliya-Amerika tilshunosligida ham, rus tilshunosligida ham sotsiolektlarni ifodalash uchun odatda uchta termin ishlatiladi. Bular: argo, jargon, sleng. Biz sotsiolektlar yuzasidan o'tkazgan tadqiqotimiz natijasida esa sotsiolektlarni 4 ta turga: jargon, argo, sleng va professionalizmlarga ajratdik.

Jargon [fr. jargon – safsata] – kasb-kor asosida birlashgan ijtimoiy va professional guruhlariga xos, faqat a'zolari tushunadigan va adabiy tildan biroz farq qiluvchi til; bu guruhlar ishlatadigan so'zlar ma'nosi ko'p ham yashirin emas, oddiy nutqdan to'liq ajralmagandir [3; 426].

O'zbek tilining izohli lug'atida jargon quyidagicha izohlanadi: "Jargon [fr. argone – ma'lum bir guruhga oid so'z] biron ijtimoiy yoki professional guruhga xos, faqatgina ularning o'zlari tushunadigan va adabiy tildan farq qiladigan so'z va iboralar jargonlardir" [8; 423]. Jargonlarning yaratilish yo'llari ham ko'pincha tilning so'z yasash sistemasiga to'g'ri kelmaydi. Ular o'ziga xos sun'iy, shartli so'zlardir.

Uslubiyatga oid manbada jargon quyidagicha ta'riflangan: "yuqori tabaqa" kishilari nutqiga xos bo'lib, tor doirada qo'llanadigan "sinfy dialektlar", ular ommaga tushinarsiz va umumxalq tiliga yotdir" [1; 69]. Shuningdek, o'quv adabiyotlardan birida uning shunday ta'rifi keltiriladi: biron-bir ijtimoiy guruh vakillarining boshqalar nutqidan ajralib turish maqsadida qo'llaydigan, o'zicha mazmun berib ishlatadigan so'z va iboralari. Masalan oq (aroq), qizil (vino) – ichuvchilar nutqiga xos; strelka (uchrashuv) yoshlarning nutqida; ko'k, ko'kat (ADSh dollari), dodasi (biror narsaning zo'ri) – ko'proq bozorчилarning nutqida qo'llaniladi [6; 22].

Jargon tushunchasining yuqorida keltirilgan ta'riflaridan eng so'nggisi, nazarimizda, jargon termini uchun eng maqbul izoh. Sababi hozirgi kunda turli ijtimoiy guruhlar qo'llayotgan jargonlar, asosan, nutqqa ekspressiv bo'yoq, zamonaviylik tusini berish, so'zga o'zgacha ma'no yuklash, boshqalardan ajralib turish kabilar uchun xizmat qilmoqda.

Jargonlar kasbiy nuqtayi nazardan ham guruhlanishi mumkin. Kasbiy jargonlarning professional so'zlardan farqli jihati – ular faqatgina shu soha vakillarigagina tushunarli bo'ladi. Professional terminlar barcha uchun tushunarli, lug'atlardan o'rin egallaganligi bilan jargondan farq qiladi. Jargonlar o'zbek tilidagi lug'atlarga deyarli kiritilmagan. Ular asosan jonli nutqda "yashaydi".

A.Spirs o'z tadqiqotlarida jargonning barcha xususiyatlarini keltirib o'tadi:

1. Adabiy tilda nomi bo'lgan narsa va hodisalarning boshqacha, juda tor guruhdagi atamasidir.
2. Ekspressiv-uslubiy bo'yoqqa ega.
3. Aksariyat jargonlar muvaqqat bo'lib, vaqt o'tishi bilan unutiladi yoki adabiy tilga o'zlashadi.

Zamonaviy tilshunoslikda jargonning bir nechta turi mavjud bo'lib, ular:

Akademik jargon – ma'lum bir soha yoki kasb-kor egalari tomonidan qo'llanadigan va yuqori darajada ixtisoslashgan terminlar. Bu turga mansub so'zlar odatda nomutaxassis kishilarga tushinarsiz bo'ladi, sohaviy tushunchalarni aniq yetkazish uchun ishlatiladi. Shu ma'noda korporativ jargonlardan farqlanadi.

Biznes jargoni ishbilarmon va biznes vakillari nutqida adabiy tildagidan farqli ma'nolarda qo'llanadigan til birliklari bo'lib, so'z, ibora yoki qisqartma shaklida mavjud bo'ladi.

Harbiy jargon harbiy xizmatchilar nutqiga xos, shu soha vakillari faoliyatida amal qiladigan harbiylashgan tushunchalarni anglatadigan so'z va iboralar. Harbiy jargonlarda qisqartmalar ko'p uchraydi.

Huquqiy jargon huquqni muhofaza qilish, jamoat xavfsizligini saqlash, sud-tergov faoliyati kabi sohalarga oid tushunchalarning adabiy tildagidan farqli nomlaridan iborat. Masalan, ichki ishlar organlari xodimlari nutqida operatsiya so'zi "kimnidir jinoyat ustida ushlab, jinoyatchilikning oldini olish maqsadida uyushtirilgan maxsus tadbir"ni bildiradi.

Professional jargon kasbi yoki faoliyatiga ko'ra muayyan guruhga uyushgan kishilar nutqida maxsuslashgan ma'noda qo'llanadigan so'z va iboralar. Professional jargonlar umumadabiy sinonimlardan hissiy to'yinganligi, usluban keskinligi bilan ajralib turadi. Masalan, kompyuter ustalari nutqida mashina jargoni kompyuter so'zi o'rnida ishlatiladi. Professional jargonlar ilmiy-texnik tushunchalarni ifodalamasligi bilan fan terminlaridan farqlanadi.

Sanoat jargoni qo'llanish doirasi va ma'no jihatidan texnik terminologiyaga yaqin turadigan, ammo sanoat ishlab chiqarishining maxsus sohasi nutqini xarakterlovchi so'z hamda iboralar.

Talabalar jargoni talabalar nutqida alohida ma'no yuki bilan qo'llanadigan so'z va iboralar. Masalan, dum so'zi talabalar nutqida "baho olinmagan fan"ni ifodalaydigan jargon so'zidir.

Tibbiy jargon sog'liqni saqlash sohasi mutaxassislari tomonidan o'zaro muloqotda keng ishlatiladigan, asosan, aloqani qisqartirish va yengillashtirish uchun ishlatiladigan maxsus so'z va iboralar. Bunday so'z va iboralar bemorlarga tushunarli bo'lmaydi.

Ters jargon muayyan so'zdagi bo'g'inlarning o'rnini almashtirish yoki so'zga qo'shimcha bo'g'in qo'shish yoxud unilarni ikkilantirish bilan hosil qilingan yoshlarga xos so'z va iboralar. Ters jargonlar muayyan

axborotni maxfiylashtirish yoki soʻz oʻyini qilish maqsadida yasaladi. Masalan, ingliz tilida cafe soʻzidan hosil qilingan feqa, metro soʻzidan yasalgan trome ters jargon hisoblanadi [2; 24].

Jargon muayyan ijtimoiy muhitda yuzaga keladi va shu ijtimoiy muhit doirasidagi shaxslarning manfaati uchun xizmat qiladi. Jargonlarni kuchli rivojlangan va aniq terminlarga ega biror kasb tili bilan aralashtirmaslik maqsadga muvofiqdir. Q. Rasulov oʻzining "Sotsiolekt va nutq" nomli maqolasida jargon sotsiumning oʻz nutqi bilan boshqalardan ajralib turish maqsadida oʻzicha mazmun berib ishlatadigan soʻz va iboralari sanalib, professionalizmlarni ham oʻzida mujassamlashtirishini aytib oʻtgan edi. Chunki, professionalizm biror kasb-hunar egalari nutqiga xos soʻz yoki ibora sifatida, sotsiolekt tarkibida bevosita jargon yoki, aksincha, jargon professionalizm boʻlib kelishi mumkin: avtomobillarga texnik xizmat koʻrsatuvchi usta nutqida kaltak yegan – urilgan (avtomashina), motor pishgan – yaroqsiz (avtomashina dvigatelining taʼmirga muhtojligi) xodovoy ketgan (harakatlantiruvchi qismlari yaroqsiz holga kelgan); sotuvchilar nutqida bozor oʻldi, bozor kasod (savdo boʻlmadi), tushib berish (narxni pasaytirish); oʻqituvchilar nutqida doskaga chiq(ing) (doska oldiga kelish), qoʻl koʻtarib gapir(ing) (ruxsat berilgach gapirish) kabi [4; 64]. Biz tadqiqotimiz davomida professionalizmlarning shu jihatiga eʼtibor berib, uni sotsiolektlar tarkibiga kiritdik.

Jargonizmlar adabiy tilda ishlatilmaydi. Ulardan jonli soʻzlashuv nutqida yoki badiiy asar tilida uslubiy maqsadlaridagina foydalanish mumkin.

*Xohi pivo, xohi vino, xohi konyak, xohi oq,
Noʻsh etib, uyga kelurman, yerda turmaydur oyoq. (Habibiy)*

*Bir maktabda gap mish-mish,
Turgʻunning dumi bormish.
Xoʻsh, bu ajab, qanday dum?
Hech kimda yoʻq-ku bu dum!
Bilsam, voqea oʻzga,
Ilinmas qoʻlga, koʻzga!
"Ikki" degan oti bor,
Na oʻzi, na zoti bor... (Q.Muhammadiy)*

Ushbu keltirilgan misollarning dastlabkisida "oq" soʻzi ichuvchilar tilida qoʻllanadigan soʻz boʻlib, spirtli ichimlikning bir turi sifatida qoʻllangan. Ikkinchi misolimizda esa talabalar nutqida qoʻllanuvchi "dum" soʻzi "topshirilmagan imtihon" yoki "qarz" maʼnolarini ifodalashga xizmat qilgan.

Jargon tadqiqi boʻyicha fikrimiz soʻngida jargonning foydali va salbiy oqibatlarini haqida fikr bildirmoqchimiz. Bizningcha, koʻp hollarda jargon tili mutaxassislar uchun oʻz sohaslarida samarali muloqot qilish uchun muhim vosita boʻlishi mumkin. Bu ularga murakkab va tushunchalarni ixchamroq yetkazish va asosiy tushunchalarni tushuntirishga vaqt sarflamasdan bir-birlarini tez anglash imkonini beradi. Bu holat, ayniqsa, tibbiyot sohasida ijobiy hisoblanadi. Salbiy jihati esa, har doim tilning adabiy normalariga putur yetkazuvchi, adabiy tilning qadr-qimmatini kamsituvchi hodisa ekanligidir.

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XALQARO HUQUQIY TERMINLARNING O'ZBEK YURIDIK TILIGA O'ZLASHISH USULLARI

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Аннотация. В статье рассмотрены международные юридические термины, являющиеся частью юридической терминологической системы, проанализированы факторы их заимствования в национальный язык.

Ключевые слова: юридический термин, международное право, терминология, заимствование, калька, семантическая калька, фразеологическая калька.

XXI asr davlatlarning siyosiy va huquqiy tizimi insoniyat boy tajribasining barcha ijobiy tomonlarini sintezi bilan xarakterlanadi. Ushbu tajribalar barqaror rivojlanishi va ijtimoiy taraqqiyot uchun eng maqbul shart-sharoitlarning demokratik davlat va fuqarolik jamiyati vujudga keltirishini tasdiqlaydi. Har qanday davlatning milliy huquqiy tizimi boshqa milliy huquqiy tizimlar va xalqaro huquq bilan bog'lamasdan o'rganib bo'lmaydi. Bunday huquqiy "uchburchak" umumiy huquqiy hudud sifatida xizmat qiladi. Unda turli normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar o'zaro ta'sirda bo'ladi, to'qnashadi va birgalikda faoliyat ko'rsatadi. A.M.Vasilev to'g'ri ta'kidlaganidek, "Huquq nazariyasi kategoriyalari va ularning tizimli rivojlanishi bilan bir qatorda dialektik va amaliy huquqiy mantiq darajasida faoliyat yurita olish ko'p jihatdan huquqiy bilimlarning amaliy ta'siriga bog'liq" [1; 13]. Yildan yilga bu hamkorlik yanada yaqqol ko'zga tashlanadi va amaliy ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Davlatlar o'rtasida bunday aloqalarning kengayib borishi bilan tillararo so'z o'zlashtirish jarayoni ham kuchayadi Yuqorida ta'kidlaganimizdek tilning leksik tarkibi sof leksik qatlam va boshqa tillardan o'zlashgan qatlam asosida shakllanadi. Dunyo tillari orasida birorta ham til yo'qki, unda ozmi ko'pmi o'zlashgan so'z uchramasin yoki "ma'lum darajada aralashgan bo'lmasin" [2; 37.] Uzoq o'tmishga nazar tashlansa, chet so'zlar o'zga tillarga asosan og'zaki muomala yo'li bilan (chunki yozuv hali yuzaga kelmagan) o'tganligini ko'ramiz. Og'zaki muomala esa yaqin qo'shnichilik natijasida xalqlarning bir hududdan boshqa bir hududga ko'chishi qolaversa, savdo-sotiq ishlarida muloqotga kirishish jarayonida yuz bergan. Bu so'z o'zlashuv sabablarini bir tomondan xarakterlasa, ikkinchi tomoni esa xalqlar ruhiyati bilan bog'liqdir. Hozirgi kunda esa O'zbek tili huquq sohasida o'zlashgan qatlam alohida o'rin egallaydi. Boshqa tillardan so'z o'zlashtirish xalqalar o'rtasida kechadigan siyosiy, iqtisodiy va madaniy aloqalarning tabiiy natijasi sifatida o'zini namoyon qiladi.

So'z o'zlashishining asosiy manbai sifatida kishilar o'rtasidagi og'zaki aloqalar va rasmiy hujjat yozishmalarining standartlar asosida shakllantirishga bo'lgan ehtiyoj natijasi sifatida ko'rsatish mumkin. Huquqiy sohada yangi tushunchalarning qo'llanilishi esa xalqaro munosabatlarda diplomatik xizmatchilar o'rtasida og'zaki suhbatlar, turli davlatlarga va tashkilotlar o'rtasidagi rasmiy va norasmiy bitimlar asosida yuzaga keladi. O'zbek tili lug'ati tarkibining boyishi va takomillashuvida tashqi manba muhim rol o'ynaydi. Shuningdek, har bir soha terminologiyasida bo'lgani singari yuridik terminologiyaning salmoqli qismi ham chetdan so'z o'zlashish ta'sirida to'lib boradi va mukammalashadi. O'zbek tiliga boshqa tillar ta'siri ikki muhim hodisada ko'zga tashlanadi.

- 1) o'zbek tiliga chet tilidan kirgan so'zlarni qabul qilishda;
- 2) chet tiliga oid so'zlarni o'zbek tiliga moslashtirishda.

So'zlarning bir tildan ikkinchi bir tilga o'tishi va o'zlashishi nisbatan murakkab jarayon hisoblanib, ijtimoiy –tarixiy va murakkab lingvistik sharoit bilan bog'liq hodisadir. Tildan tilga so'z o'zlashishi uchun avvalo real sharoit bo'lishi lozim. O'zbek tili o'tmishda bir qator qardosh bo'lmagan boshqa sistemadagi tillar bilan ham aloqada bo'lgan. Shuningdek, o'zbek tili o'z rivojining milliy til va ijtimoiy millat tili davriga kelib rus tili bilan aloqa va hamkorlikka kirishdi. Bu jarayon esa o'z navbatida yuqorida aytib o'tilgan til leksikasining ona tilimizga kirib kelishi va millatning so'zlashuv nutqiga singib borishiga sabab bo'ldi.

Xalqaro va milliy huquqiy tizimlarning o'zaro ta'siri muammosini o'rganishning predmet bazasini va tegishli konseptual apparati aniq belgilanmasdan amalga oshirib bo'lmaydi. Biroq, yuridik adabiyotlarda "huquqiy tizim" toifasining mazmuni tadqiqotchilar tomonidan turlicha ta'riflangan bo'lib, bu nafaqat alohida olimlarning ushbu muammoga individual yondashuvi bilan izohlash mumkin. O'tgan asrning ikkinchi yarmidan 80-yillarning oxirigacha bo'lgan ilmiy ishlarda xalqaro va milliy huquq doirasini ajratish borasida aniq chiziq tortildi deyish mumkin. Bundan tashqari xalqaro huquqshunoslarning ishlarida qoida tariqasida xalqaro huquq tizimi va ichki huquq o'rtasida hech qanday chiziq farqlar yaqqol berilmagan, faqatgina ekvivalent sifatida tegishli tushunchalar ko'rsatib o'tilgan. Shunga qaramay o'sha davrda ham universal davrning asosiy parametrlarini, shu jumladan nafaqat xalqaro huquqni, balki uning subyektlarini, ular o'rtasida yuzaga keladigan huquqiy munosabatlarni, xalqaro huquqni amalga oshirish shakllari va usullarini aniqlashga e'tibor qaratilgan ilmiy izlanishlar olib borildi. Jumladan D.I.Feldmen xalqaro huquqiy tartibga solishning universal konsepsiyasi, I.I.Lukashuk davlatlararo xalqaro tizim nazariyasi kabi masalalarni tadqiq qilgan. Hozirgi vaqtda xalqaro tashkilotlar normativ manbalarni model qonunlarni kiritish orqali kengaytirishning zaruriyati sezilarli darajada o'sdi. Bularning barchasi zamonaviy dunyoda xalqaro va milliy huquqning o'рни va ahamiyati haqida umumiy fikrga kelish, ularning o'zaro bog'liqligi va istiqbolining asosiy parametrlarini aniqlash maqsadida xalqaro huquqshunoslarning va huquq fanlari vakillari o'rtasidagi o'zaro hamkorlikni faollashtirish zarurligini oldindan belgilab beradi. O'zbek qonunchiligini takomillashtirish bo'yicha faol ish olib borilayotgan hozirgi davrda davlatning ichki va xalqaro huquqiy tartiboti metodlarini qo'llash talab qilinadi. Bugungi kunda qonunchilikning har qanday bo'limi xalqaro shartnomalar bilan aloqadorlikka ega. O'zbekiston Respublikasi jahon hamjamiyatiga faol kirib bormoqda, xorijiy mamalakatlar bilan xalqaro aloqalarni mustahkamlab shartnomaviy va diplomatik aloqalarni kengaytirmoqda. Bu jarayon esa o'z navbatida normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar tuzishda ma'lum bir standartlarga amal qilish zaruratini yuzaga keltiradi. Mazkur muammolarni bartaraf etishda normativ huquqiy hujjatlarning asosiy bo'g'ini bo'lgan atamalardan to'g'ri foydalana bilish muhim o'rin tutadi. Shu ma'noda G.G'ulomova milliy qonunchiligimizning nufuzi va qadr-qimmatini oshirish, o'zbek xalqining huquqiy madaniyatini yanada shakllantirish uchun ma'lum bir maqsadga qaratilgan tadbirlarni belgilab olish kerakligini ta'kidlaydi. Bunday vazifalarning eng asosiylari sifatida quyidagilarni keltirib o'tadi.

- o'zbek yuridik terminologiyasining yagona standartlarini yaratish;
- xalqaro siyosiy-huquqiy terminlarni yaratishda milliy xususiyatlarni hisobga olish;
- jahon andozalariga muvofiq, xalqaro yuridik terminlarni qanday bo'lsa shundayligicha qabul qilish;
- qonun loyihalarini ishlab chiquvchi ishchi guruhlar tarkibiga huquqshunoslarning bilan bir qatorda, filologlarni ham albatta jalb qilish [3; 25].

Yuridik terminlar standartlari qonunni to'g'ri tushunish, uni amalga to'g'ri tadbir qilish uchun zarur bo'lsa terminlar bo'yicha yo'riqnomalar esa terminlar birligining bo'lishini ta'minlaydi. Xalqaro huquqiy terminlardan foydalanishda milliy til xususiyatlari va qonunchilik talablarining o'ziga xos jihatlari ham hisobga olish zarur. Xalqaro yuridik terminlarni dunyo xalqlari qanday ishlatayotgan bo'lsa biz ham shunday ishlatishimiz lozim. Huquq sohasiga boshqa tillardan terminlar kirib kelishi yoki ichki imkoniyatlar asosida yangi huquqiy terminlarning yasalishi natijasida ham o'zbek tili leksik qatlami boyib bormoqda, shuningdek yangi huquqiy tushunchalar yuzaga kelmoqda. Jumladan, huquqiy sohada keyingi paytda milliy-huquqiy tizim, lingvistik ekspertiza, filologik ekspertiza, qonun ustunligi kabi yuridik terminlar til tizimiga kirib keldi. Bundan tashqari xorijiy so'zlarni o'zgartirishsiz aslida qabul qilinish holati ham nisbatan ommalashgan. Shuni alohida qayd etish kerakki, yuridik sohaga mansub leksik qatlam ham til leksikasi umumiy qonuniyatlari asosida rivojlanib boradi. O'zbek yuridik tilida qo'llaniladigan so'zlar ham milliy tilning sof terminlari va boshqa tillardan o'zlashtirilgan terminlardan tashkil topadi. Xalqaro yuridik tilda qo'llanilayotgan ko'pgina so'z va terminlar milliy yuridik tilga kirib boradi va aksincha milliy yuridik tildagi ayrim so'z va terminlar xalqaro huquqqa o'tadi. Professor Sh.Ko'chimovning ta'kidlashicha hozirgi zamon xalqaro huquqining asosiy yuridik terminlarini quyidagi tillarga oid so'zlar tashkil qiladi [5; 120]. Masalan:

- Lotin tilidan o'zlashgan xalqaro yuridik terminlar: konstitutsiya, integratsiya, diktatura, kodeks, manifest;
- Fransuz tilidan o'zlashgan xalqaro yuridik terminlar: suverenitet, diplomatiya parlament, order, dekret, attashe, ministr;

Nemis tilidan o'zlashgan xalqaro yuridik terminlar: adyutant, veksell, abonent;

Ingliz tilidan o'zlashgan xalqaro yuridik terminlar: monopoliya, monarxiya, gegemon, demokratiya;

Yunon tilidan o'zlashgan xalqaro yuridik terminlar: amnistiya, anarxiya, protocol, apartid;

Arab tilidan o'zlashgan xalqaro yuridik terminlar: alkogolizm, adat, algorifm.

Xalqaro huquq sohasiga oid so'z o'zlashtirish bir necha usul bilan amalga oshadi. Ulardan quyidagilarni tahlil qilamiz.

1. So'zni o'zgarishsiz qabul qilish. Bunday usulda so'z o'zlashtirganda qabul qilinayotgan leksik birlik na fonetik, na grammatik o'zgarishga uchraydi.

2. Kalkalash yo'li bilan so'z o'zlashtirish

a) Semantik kalkalash yo'li bilan so'z o'zlashtirish

b) Frazelogik kalkalash yo'li bilan so'z o'zlashtirish devalyatsiya (qog'oz pullarni bekor qilish)

Bulardan birinchisi milliy yuridik tilimizda eng mahsuldor usul hisoblanib, soha lterminologiyasining asosiy qismini tashkil qiladi. Misol tariqasida "Yuridik terminlarning ruscha-o'zbekcha lug'ati" [4] ni tahlilga tortilganida lug'atga kiritilgan asosiy terminlarning o'zbek tilidagi muqobili berilgan: avans (bo'nak), agent(vakil), avtor(muallif), arenda(ijra) va boshqalar. Lekin ayrim terminlar hech qanday o'zgarishsiz qabul qilingan va aslida kiritilgan. Misol tariqasida: attashe, balans, banditizm, bankrot, birja, deputat, diktatura, demokratiya, parlament va boshqalar. Ikkinchi usul kalkalash yo'li bilan so'z o'zlashtirish Boshqa til materialidan qismma-qism nusxa olish bilan yasalgan so'zga kalka deyiladi. Kalkalashda so'z o'zlashtiruvchi so'zning ma'nosi va morfemik tuzilishi saqlanadi, ammo bu morfemik tuzilish o'zlashtirilayotgan tilning materiali bilan to'ldiriladi. Semantik kalkada nusxa olish prinsipi saqlanadi. Bir tildagi so'zga uning boshqa tildagi ekvivalenti qidirib topiladi va shu o'zlashtirilayotgan leksik ma'no yuklanadi. X.Dadaboyev semantik kalkalash usuli haqida o'z qarashlarini bayon qilib quyidagi fikrlarni aytib o'tadi. "Semantik kalka (metaforalashish)da kelib chiqishi jihatidan chet tiliga xos bo'lgan yangi ma'noni o'zbek tili lug'ati tarkibida ishlatib kelinayotgan so'z o'zlashtiradi" [6; 120]. Misollarga murojaat qilinganda yuqorida keltirilgan lug'atda bunday birliklar o'zbek tilidagi ma'noviy jihatdan yaqin bo'lgan birliklar bilan birga kalkalash usuli orqali o'zlashtirilganligi namoyon bo'ladi. Shunday so'zlar qatoriga appelyatsiya(norozilik arizasi), immigrant (muhojir), instansiya (bosqich), gomeseksualist (besoqolbozlik). Frazelogik kalka chet tilidagi birikmani qismlarga bo'lib, so'zma so'z tarjima qilishdir. Bu usulda termin o'zlashtirish huquqiy terminologiyada biroz boshqacha holatda ham uchraydi. Ya'ni o'zlashtirilayotgan birlik qismlarga ajratilgan holatda har biri alohida tarjima yoli bilan yoki tarkibidagi ma'lum so'zlar o'z holaticha o'zlashadi. Masalan алтернат(xalqaro shartnomaning matnini navbat bilan imzolash), вербальная нота (verbal nota), гаагский трибунал (gaga tribunali) вагнера закона (vagner qonuni), курьер дипломатический (diplomatik kuryer) va boshqalar.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, so'z o'zlashtirish huquqiy sohada ham faol qo'llaniladigan jarayon bo'lib, qonunchilik uslubida matnning aniq tushunilishini ta'minlaydi. Boshqa soha terminologiyasidan farqli ravishda yuridik terminlar tarkibida xalqaro terminelementlar mavjud leksemalar midqor jihatidan yuqoridir. Buning asosiy sababi, milliy yuridik tilda yaratilgan normativ qonun hujjatlarining jahon hamjamiyati standartlariga mos bo'lishidir.

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DIGLOSSIYA HODISASIGA SOTSIOLINGVISTIK QARASH

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Annotation. *The phenomenon of diglossia is considered a comprehensive concept in linguistics, reflecting the linguistic situation in the country. This article highlights the theories and views advanced on the emergence, development and social functions of the diglossia phenomenon.*

Key words: *diglossia, bilingualism, subcode, diaglossic regions, language preservation, social inequality.*

Ijtimoiy lingvistikada diglossiya deganda umumiy nutq jamoasi ichida tilning ikki ko'rinishi amal qiladigan holat tushuniladi. Diglossiya (diglōssia. yun. "di" – "ikki" va "gloss" – "til") yagona milliy til egasi bo'lmish jamoaning tilning turli subkodlarida gapira olishi, sharoit va muloqot doirasidan kelib chiqib, tilning bir subkodidan ikkinchi subkodiga o'ta olishi, bir til doirasida turli uslublardan foydalana olishi demakdir. "Diglossiya" termini nafaqat bir milliy tilning turli subkodlarida gapira olishni, balki turli tillarni bilish va ularni muloqot vaziyatiga ko'ra galma-gal qo'llay olishni ham anglatadi [1; 238].

Diglossiya hodisasi mahalliy va xorijiy tilshunoslarning ishlarida ko'p va xo'p o'rganilgan. Diglossiyaning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari J.Fishman tadqiqotlarida ko'rib chiqilgan, diglossiyaning rus adabiy tili tarixidagi maqomi esa A.V.Isachenko, B.A.Uspenskiy asarlarida ochib berilgan. 50-80-yillar tilshunosligida ushbu hodisani o'rganish muammolari yoritilgan. Emmanuel Rhoides 1885-yilda chop etilgan "Parerga" asarining muqaddimasida diglossiya "bir tilning ikki shakli" degan maxsus ma'noni anglatishini ta'kidlagan. Bu atama yunon tilshunosi Ioannis Psycharis tomonidan "diglossie" sifatida fransuz tiliga o'zlashtiriladi [2; 163]. Tilshunos diglossiyaning yunon adabiyotlarida zamonaviy yozma yunon tili ikki xil variantining yonma-yon yashash holati sifatida tasvirlagan.

Arab mamlakatlarida ham diglossiya termini mamlakatdagi lingvistik vaziyatni tasvirlash uchun qo'llangan. Bu hodisa haqida "Лингвистический энциклопедический словарь"da quyidagi fikrlar keltirilgan: "arab adabiy tili va arab shevalarining bir-biriga munosabati hamda ularning ijtimoiy nuqtayi nazardan funksional qo'llanishi diglossiyaga misol bo'la oladi" [3; 136]. Ijtimoiy lingvist Ch.A.Ferguson 1959-yilda diglossiya terminini ilk bor maqola sarlavhasida qo'llagan [4; 59]. Olim diglossiyaga quyidagicha ta'rif beradi: "jamiyatda bir vaqtning o'zida ukkita tilning yoki bir tilning turli funksional holatda qo'llanadigan ikkita shaklining amal qilishi" [5; 232].

Yuqorida keltirilgan fikrlardan kelib chiqib dunyo tilshunosligida diglossiya termini quyidagi ikkita hodisani ifodalash uchun xizmat qilishini ko'rishimiz mumkin:

1. Lisoniy jamoada bir tilning ikki shakli amal qilishi.
2. Lisoniy jamoada ikki yoki undan ortiq tilning amal qilishi.

Ammo biz ushbu terminni izohlashda yuqorida keltirilgan "diglossiya bu – bir tilning ikki shaklidir" degan fikrga tayanamiz. Chunki diglossiya ikkita til mavjud bo'lgan vaziyat, ammo bu tillar so'zlashuvchilar tomonidan bir til sifatida qabul qilinadi. Diglossiyada bir tilning ikki shakli o'rtasida ierarxik munosabat mavjud bo'ladi. Emmanuel Rhoides va Ioannis Psycharis tomonidan keltirilgan ta'riflarda diglossiya hodisasi aniq yoritilgan bo'lsa, Ch. Ferguson keltirgan ta'rifda diglossiya hodisasi bilingvizm kabi ta'riflangan. Bu hodisalarning farqini tilshunos quyidagicha ochib bergan: "agar bilingvizmda tillar funksional jihatdan teng bo'lsa, diglossiyada tillardan biri "yuqori" (H) til bo'lib, din, ta'lim, fan va boshqa aloqa sohalarida qo'llanadi, ammo kundalik muloqotda amal qilmaydi; ikkinchisi "quyi" (L) til hisoblanib, kundalik muloqotda va nutqning quyi funksional uslublarida qo'llanadi" [5; 234].

Tilshunoslikda diglossiya va ikki tillilik hodisalari bir-biriga yaqin tushunchalar hisoblanisa-da, ular o'rasida bir qancha farqlar mavjud. Diglossiyada tillarning qarindosh yoki noqarindosh ekanligi muhim emas va unda bir tilning ikki shevasi, adabiy til va sheva funksional jihatdan farqli qo'llanadi. Shuningdek, dunyo tilshunosligida muayyan lisoniy jamoada ikki yoki undan ortiq tilning qo'llanishi bilan bog'liq hodisa diglossiya sifatida talqin etilgan ishlar mavjud. Buni Ch.Ferguson alohida ta'kidlaydi va quyidagilarni diglossiya amal qiluvchi hududlar sifatida keltiradi:

№	Diglossik hududlar	Diglossik tillar
1	Gaiti	Gaiti kreoli (L – yuqori til), fransuz (H – quyi til)
2	Arab tilida so‘zlashuvchi mamlakatlar	Misir mahalliy dialekti (L – quyi til), standart arab (H – yuqori til)
3	Shveysariya	Shveysariya nemischasi (L – quyi til), standart nemis (H – yuqori til)
4	Yunoniston	Demotik yunon (L – quyi til), sof yunon (H – yuqori til)

Diglossik jamoalarda amal qiladigan dialektlar rasmiy va norasmiy jarayonlarda qo'llana olish xususiyatiga ko'ra ikki turga ajratiladi.

1. Yuqori til shakli hisoblanib, asosan, rasmiy doiralarda qo'llanadi. Unda adabiy til me'yorlariga qat'iy amal qilinadi. Masalan, o'zbek adabiy tili va uning shevalari. Adabiy til va shevalar qiyosiy tahlili ko'plab realiya va lakunalarni aniqlash imkonini beradi [6; 34].

2. Quyi til shakli hisoblanib, asosan, norasmiy doiralarda qo'llanadi. Ko'proq maishiy til sifatida qaralib, oila a'zolari va yaqin kishilar bilan muloqot jarayonida ishlatiladi. Masalan: Dehqonqu! Men ularni jigiti sanamayman, yo'q jigiti sanayman. Gapning o'roli keldi, aytayin... [7; 20]

Diglossiyaning yana bir turi mavjud bo'lib, u manbalarda standart diglossiya yoki ikki tilli diglossiya deb ham nomlanadi. Diglossiyaning bu turida bitta tilning turli shakllari faqat yozuv amaliyotida foydalanilsa, ikkinchi tilning turli shakllari muloqot jarayonidagina qo'llanadi.

Hozirgi kunda ba'zi mamlakatlarda diglossiya gender jihatdan ham farqlanmoqda. Masalan, Kanada "talaba pidgin" deb nomlangan dialektida odatda erkaklar o'rta maktabda so'zlashadi, ammo ijtimoiy o'zgarishlar tufayli bugungi kunda o'quvchi qizlar ham "talaba pidgin"dan foydalanishmoqda [8; 28].

Diglossiyaning jamiyatga ta'siri turlicha bo'lishi mumkin. Diglossiyaning o'ziga xos afzalliklari va kamchiliklari mavjud.

Diglossiyaning afzalliklari quyidagilardan iborat. Birinchidan, diglossiya jamiyatdagi turli til yoki uning shevalarini muhofaza qiladi va bu holat jamoalarga etnik o'ziga xoslik hamda tilni saqlash qolish imkoniyatini beradi. Ikkinchidan, ijtimoiy sharoitidan kelib chiqib, so'zlovchilar tildan erkin foydalanishlari mumkin. Masalan, yuqori til shaklidan fan, ta'lim, ommaviy axborot vositalarida, shuningdek, rasmiy muloqot jarayonlarida foydalanilsa, quyi til shakli kundalik muloqot va norasmiy vaziyatda qo'llanadi.

Diglossiya hodisasi yuqorida keltirilgan afzalliklar bilan birga quyidagi muammolarni ham keltirib chiqarishi mumkin. Avvalo, diglossiya jamiyat a'zolari o'rtasida ijtimoiy tengsizlikni yuzaga keltiradi. Yuqori til shaklida muloqot qiluvchilar quyi til shaklida so'zlashuvchilardan ko'proq imtiyozga ega bo'lishi, quyi til shaklidan foydalanuvchi lisoniy jamoani chetga surib qo'yishi mumkin. Bu holat ijtimoiy tabaqalanishga olib keladi. Ikkinchidan, ta'lim sohasida quyi til shaklida so'zlashuvchilar imkoniyatining cheklanganligidir. Ular sifatli ta'lim manbalaridan foydalanishda qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishadi. Bu ularning o'sib-rivojlanishiga ham o'z ta'sirini o'tkazmay qolmaydi. Uchinchidan, quyi til shaklida so'zlashuvchi jamoa yuqori til shaklida so'zlashuvchilarga tenglashishga harakat qilishi natijasida quyi til shaklida til eroziyasi xavfi yuzaga keladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, mohiyatan ikki tillilikni ifodalovchi diglossiya yakka shaxsga emas, muayyan lisoniy jamoaga qaratilganligi, madaniy meros bo'lmish tilni saqlab qolish xususiyatiga ega ekanligi bilan ahamiyatlidir.

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O'ZBEK TILI LEKSIKASI TARAQQIYOTIDA NEOLOGIZMLARNING O'RNI

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Аннотация. В данной статье приведены краткие размышления о лексическом пласте языка и роли неологизмов в его развитии. Также на основе примеров обоснована роль заимствованного пласта (арабских, персидско-таджикских, русских, английских) слов в узбекском языке, констатируется, что изменения, обновления, преобразования в обществе влияют на развитие лексического слоя языка.

Ключевые слова: лексический пласт, неологизм, новый пласт, заимствованный пласт, экстралингвистический фактор.

Tilning lug'at boyligi odamlar faoliyatining barcha sohalarida sodir bo'layotgan o'zgarishlarga tezda javob berishi kerak, shunda til o'zining asosiy funksiyalarini (fikrni shakllantirish va kommunikativ) bajarishi mumkin. Lug'atlarning vazifasi bu o'zgarishlarni qayd etish, hozirgi davrga xos bo'lgan jonli til hodisalarini (raqamli texnologiyalar, virtual muloqot, til me'yorlarini demokratlashtirish, shuningdek, "zamonaviy ona tilida so'zlashuvchilarning faol so'z yaratish", til o'yinlaridan boshlab, fikrni ifodalashning ifodali vositalarini izlash, ayniqsa, yoshlar va ijodiy kasblar vakillari orasida mashhur faoliyatga aylandi) [6; 37] aks ettirishdan iborat [7; 26].

Yuqorida aytilganidek, til qatlamlari orasida leksika har qanday jarayonga reaksiya beradigan qatlam hisoblanadi. Shu sababdan, doimiy o'rganilishni talab qiladi. Til leksik qatlamini davriy guruhlaydigan bo'lsak, eski qatlam so'zlari, zamonaviy qatlam so'zlari va yangi qatlam so'zlariga ajratamiz. Eski qatlam so'zlari (vaqtida faol bo'lgan tarixiy so'zlar va arxaizmlar) bugungi kunda umumtilda kam qo'llanadi. Zamonaviy qatlam so'zlari doimiy kommunikatsiya jarayonida faol bo'ladi. Shu qatlamga oid so'zlar o'zbek tili leksikasining asosini tashkil qiladi. Yangi qatlam so'zlari yoki neologizmlar hali tilda ommalashib ulgurmagan, tor doiralarda qo'llana boshlagan. Ammo bunday so'zlar til leksikasi taraqqiyotiga eng faol ta'sir o'tkazuvchi omildir. Til taraqqiyoti jamiyat taraqqiyoti bilan chambarchas bog'liq jarayondir. Jamiyatdagi o'zgarishlar, rivojlanishlar (ilm-fan, texnika, aloqalar), turli ijtimoiy tizimlar natijasida tilda yangi va eski so'zlar paydo bo'ladi. Jumladan, yaqin o'n yillikda ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning faol rivojlanishi ularning turlari va nomlaridan tashqari ular bilan bog'liq bir qator tushunchalarni paydo qildi. Davr talabi va til ehtiyoji sabab neologizmlar safi kengaydi.

Ma'lumki, milliy tilning, milliy adabiy tilning taraqqiyoti lisoniy va nolisoniy omillar ta'sirida yuz beradi. Globallashuv davrida tillarning shu jumladan, o'zbek tilining ham leksikografiyasi nolisoniy ya'ni, ijtimoiy tuzum shakllari, tarixiy jarayonlar, xalqalar va millatlar o'rtasidagi iqtisodiy, siyosiy, madaniy, ma'rifiy aloqalar, ilm-fan rivoji, ishlab chiqarish va texnika taraqqiyoti, shuningdek, tibbiyotdagi turli holatlar (ayniqsa, koronavirus pandemiyasi misolida yaqqol namoyon bo'ladi [9] kabi ekstralingvistik omillar ta'sirida yuzaga kelgan neologizmlar hisobiga boyidi. Masalan, Oksford lug'ati 2020-yil bahorida pandemiya bilan bog'liq bir qancha yangi so'zlarni qayd etdi: coronavirus (koronavirus), COVID-19 (yangi koronavirus keltirib chiqargan kasallik), lockdown (COVID-19 tarqalishining oldini olish uchun hukumat tomonidan kiritilgan majburiy karantin choralari), social distancing (ijtimoiy masofa), reopening (qayta ochilish). Adabiy tilning taraqqiyoti, avvalo, ichki omillarga tayanadi ammo misollarga, yuqorida va quyida keltirilgan ma'lumotlarga e'tibor qaratadigan bo'lsak, tildagi jarayonlarda ham intralingvistik ham ekstralingvistik omillar birga qatnashadi. Biri ikkinchisiga zamin yaratadi; til va jamiyat, til va ong, til va tafakkur jarayonlari shuni taqozo qiladi [2; 7].

Yuqorida ijtimoiy boshqaruv tizimlarini, davlat boshqaruv siyosatidagi o'zgarishlarni ham leksik qatlam bilan bog'ladik. XX asrga e'tibor qaratsak, bu davrda sovet hukmronligida o'ziga xos atamalar mavjud edi. Masalan, quloq, quloqlashtirish, sovet, pioner, kommunistik g'oya, kommunizm, qayta qurish, kolxoz, sovxoz, aksilingilobchi, leninchi. Bunday so'zlarni hozirda olimlar sovetizmlar atamasi bilan yuritmoqdalar. Sovetizmlarga sovet sotsialistik hukumati va ishchilar sinfi diktaturasi zamonasini ifodalaydigan birliklar, shuningdek, sotsialistik tizimning barcha sohalariga xos hodisalar nomlarini kiritish mumkin [8; 39].

Mustaqillikdan keyin bozor iqtisodiyotiga o'tish jarayonida ham bir qator so'z va iboralar ommalashdi. O'zbek modeli, milliy valyuta, kichik biznes, o'rta biznes, xususiy tadbirkorlik, qimmatli qog'ozlar bozori, tadbirkorlar palatasi, konsalting, injiniring, lizing firma, biznes-inkubator, biznes-reja, diller, makler, demping, davlat boji. Bular, o'z navbatida yangi izohli lug'atda ham o'z aksini topdi [4].

Yangi O'zbekistonni barpo qilish jarayonida ham yangi tushuncha va atamalar keng muamolaga kiritilmoqda. Yangi O'zbekiston, harakatlar strategiyasi, taraqqiyot strategiyasi, elektron hukumat, temir daftar, yoshlar daftari, ayollar daftari, hokim yordamchilari, ochiq budjet yoki tashabbusli budjet, yoshlar ittifoqi.

Til leksik qatlamidagi so'zlar, ma'lumki, o'z qatlam va o'alachgan qatlam so'zlaridan iborat. O'z qatlam so'zlari deya asl turkiycha so'zlarni nazarda tutamiz. O'zlashgan qatlam so'zlari esa tilimizga turli tillardan kirgan leksikalardir.

Ma'lumki, tilimizda asosiy o'zlashgan qatlam so'zlari arabcha va fors-tojikcha so'zlardir [5]. Bu so'zlarni biz qabul qilganmiz va nutqimizda hech qanday qiyinchiliklarsiz, muammolarsiz faol qo'llaymiz. Bugungi kunda bu til so'zlaridan yangi so'z yasashda foydalanmasakda, lug'atimizning asosiy qismini aynan shu til o'zlashmalari tashkil etadi: aloqa, asir, bahs, daftar, dars, dunyo(arabcha), bazm, bobo, bozor, darmon, darrov, dil (forscha) [1; 103].

XIX asrdan boshlab rus tilidan o'tgan so'zlar ommalasha boshladi. U so'zlar dastlab neologizmlar maqomida turgan bo'lsa, keyinchalik o'zlashma so'zlar sifatida lug'atlardan o'rin egalladi. Bugungi kunda rus tili va bu til orqali boshqa tillardan olingan so'zlar ham aksariyatni tashkil etadi. Asphalt (yunoncha), budilnik, budka, karavot, qulupnay, samavor (ruscha).

Yuqorida qayd etilgan o'zlashgan so'zlarning asosiy sababi hukmronlik siyosati bilan bog'liq bo'lsa, bugungi kunda tilimizda va nutqimizda paydo bo'layotgan neologizmlar va asta-sekin til leksikasining olinma so'zlar qatlamidan joy olayotgan so'zlarning asosiy qismi fan-texnika, internet taraqqiyoti natijasida ingliz tilidan kirib kelmoqda. Ya'ni ingliz tili yaqin yillarda dunyoning ko'plab tillari uchun donor tilga aylandi: blog, blogger, sayt, bot, chat, link, GIF, akkaunt, spam, admin, kuryer, broker, spiker, IT.

Demak, til leksik qatlami taraqqiyotiga asosiy ta'sir qiluvchi jarayon jamiyatdagi o'zgarishlar, yangilanishlar, rivojlanishlar bilan bog'liq ekan. Bu holatlar esa avvalo neologizmlarga murojaat qilishga sabab va omil bo'ladi. Tilshunos olim, professor Y. Odilov ta'kidlaganlaridek: "...Albatta, yangi so'zni olish bilan tilning so'z zaxirasi kengayadi, ammo xorijiy so'zlarning ko'payib ketishi yaxshi holat emas" [3]. Leksik boyligimizni chet emas o'z so'zimiz bilan boyitish har bir o'zbek til egasi oldiga mas'uliyat qo'yadi.

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WINDOWS OPERATSION TIZIMI TERMINOLOGIYASI HAQIDA UMUMIY TUSHUNCHALAR

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Аннотация. В данной статье представлен небольшой анализ перевода и лексикографической интерпретации узбекских терминов, используемых в операционной системе Windows. Кроме того, в данной статье отдельно изучается употребление и обоснованность адаптированных и переведенных терминов, встречающихся в операционной системе Windows.

Ключевые слова: windows, операционная система, операционная система Linux, CMD, MS-DOS.

Jahonda axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari yordamida windows operatsion tizimi dasturlari yaratilishi jadal sur'atlarda kechmoqda. Mazkur jarayon windows operatsion tizimi terminologiyasiga oid yangi tushunchalarning dunyo tillariga kirib kelishiga sabab bo'lmoqda. Bu holat, o'z navbatida, tizimda ishlatilgan o'zbek, ingliz tilidagi terminlarning lingvistik xususiyatlarini o'rganish, ya'ni, semantik va strukturaviy jihatdan tahlil qilish hamda leksikografik xususiyatlarini aniqlash, tarjima uslublarini takomillashtirish, uch tilli lug'atlarni yaratish kabi muhim topshiriqlarni kun tartibiga qo'yadi.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining tashabbusi bilan mustaqillikning dastlabki yillaridan boshlab ko'plab rivojlangan davlatlar bilan teng huquqli ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, madaniy-ma'rifiy aloqalar o'rnatildi. Bugungi kunda ushbu aloqalarning rivojlanishi davom etayotgani asnosida ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy sohalardagi hamkorlik natijasida jamiyat hayotiga Windows operatsion tizimida yaratilgan dasturlar keng moslashtirib borilmoqda va shuning barobarida ayni sohaga taalluqli ko'plab yangi tushuncha hamda terminlar kirib keldi. So'nggi yillarda bunday ilovalarning ko'payib ketayotgani natijasida mazkur sohaning zamonaviy leksikasini tadqiq qilish va terminologik apparatini tartibga solishga yo'naltirilgan muayyan ilmiy izlanishlar amalga oshirilishiga, ayni soha terminlari va tushunchalarining standartlari ishlab chiqilishiga, izohli lug'atlar yaratilishiga ulgurilmay qolmoqda.

Jahon tilshunosligida axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari terminlarini tartibga olish ishlari bir til terminlari doirasida ham, bir necha til terminlari doirasida ham amalga oshirilgan, shu bilan bir qatorda, ayni soha terminlari muayyan darajada tartibga solinib, ko'proq shu sohaga e'tibor qaratilgan bo'lsa-da, lekin mobil ilovalarning terminologiyasiga qiziqish bildirilmagan. Bunga esa ingliz leksik-semantikasida terminlarning faqatgina ma'nosi o'zgarishi orqali ilovalarda qo'llanilgani sabab bo'lgan.

Milliy tilshunoslikda ham windows operatsion tizimi terminlarining lingvistik xususiyatlari (leksikografik, semantik va tarjimaviy) haligacha aniqlanmagan va soha terminlarini tartibga solish mezonlari ishlab chiqilmagan. Shunga ko'ra, windows operatsion tizimi terminlarining mavzuviy guruhlarini aniqlash, leksik-semantik xususiyatlarini asoslash, terminlarning strukturaviy modellarini yoritish, o'zlashma va baynalminal terminlarning milliy tillarda barqarorlashuv jarayonlarini tadqiq qilish, tarjima qilish uslublarini takomillashtirish, terminlardagi sinonimik, antonimik va variantlilik holatlarini tartibga solish hamda maqbullarini qo'llash yuzasidan takliflar berish, leksikografik izohlarini ko'paytirish, tarjima lug'atlarini tuzish kabi masalalarning hal etilishi sifatli mobil ilovalar yaratilishi bilan birga, foydalanuvchilarga muayyan darajada yengillik yaratilishiga olib keladi.

Mazkur maqolada o'zbek tilshunos olimlari R.Sayfullayeva, B.Mengliyev, G.Boqiyeva, M.Qurbonova, Z.Yunusova, M.Abuzalova tomonidan yozilgan "Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili" o'quv qo'llanmasi, B.Mengliyev tomonidan yozilgan "Hozirgi o'zbek tili" darslik va til korpuslarini yaratish bo'yicha maqolalari, M.Umarxo'jayevning "Umumiy tilshunoslik" nomli o'quv qo'llanmalari va M.Umarxo'jayev tashabbusi bilan tashkil etilgan lug'atshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik markazi (ALTAIIM) jamoasi tomonidan maktab o'quvchilari uchun turli fanlardan yaratilgan ko'p tilli dasutr lug'atida foydalanilgan terminlar yordamida tahlil qilindi.

Xususan windows operatsion tizimida berilgan terminlar haqida to'xataladigan bo'lsak, "Google chrome" windows operatsion tizimi dasturidagi bir terminga e'tibor tortildi, "bukmarklar", ingliz tilida bu atama "bookmarks" tarzida, rus tilida esa "закладки" tarzida keltirilgan. Bundan ko'rinib turibdiki, rus tilida bu so'zning muqobili topilgan, lekin o'zbek tilida ushbu so'zning muqobili topilmaganligi sababli to'g'ridan to'g'ri "bukmarklar" atamasi qo'llanilgan. Imloda shu holatda yozilishi mumkin, lekin "bookmarks" ingliz tilidagi talaffuzi butunlay boshqacha holatda beriladi. Shu sababli ham ushbu atamaning bu tarzda berilishi bir qancha chalkashliklarga olib keladi, na talaffuz va na imlo qoidalariga bo'ysunadi. Xuddi terminlarning nomlariga o'xshab ushbu atamaning imlodagi yozilishi ingliz tilida qanday bo'lsa, o'zbek tilida ham shu tarzda qoldirilishi maqsadga muvofiq, faqatgina talaffuzda biroz farq qilishi lozim. Bundan tashqari ushbu atama bo'yicha qidiruv berilganda "Google translate" tizimida "bookmark" so'zining tarjimasini "xatcho'p" tarzida qo'llanilgan. Bu esa ushbu terminning muqobili mavjudligidan dalolatdir [1].

"Google chrome" windows operatsion tizimi dasturidagi to'g'ridan-to'g'ri o'zlashtirilgan atamalar ko'plab uchraydi. "Yangi inkognito varag'i" – uch komponentli birikmada etimologik jihatdan ikkita tildan kirib kelgan so'zlar mavjud, ulardan biri "inkognito" (ingliz tili) va "varaqa" (arab tilidan). Ko'rinib turganidek, "inkognito" atamasining ham xuddi "bookmarks" atamasiga o'xshab muqobili berilmagan, lekin ingliz-o'zbekcha lug'atlarda ushbu atamaning tarjimasini "yashirin", "boshqa nom bilan" tarzida berilgan [2]. Demak, o'z-o'zidan bu atama aynan o'zlashgan atamalar qatoridan chiqib ketadi. "Varaqa" xususida to'xtaladigan bo'lsak, "varag'i" – aslida "varaqa" ko'rinishida etimologik lug'atlarda beriladi, {i} egalik qo'shimchasi qo'shilishi natijasida {q} harfi {g} aylanadi hamda talaffuzda tovush o'zgarishi hodisasi ro'y beradi.

Keyingi termin haqida so'z borganda, "people nearby" – "yaqin-atrofdagi odamlar" atamasi so'zma-so'z tarjima qilingan bo'lib, "nearby" atamasi birikmali tarzda berilgan. Qo'llanilishi jihatdan yaqin-atrof birikmasi yasama so'zli juft so'z hisoblanib, "near-by" so'zining lug'atlardagi berilishi "yonma-yon" tarzida ham uchraydi[3]. Dasturdagi foydalanilish jarayonidan kelib chiqib ushbu atama so'zma-so'z tarjima qilingan. Bundan tashqari "atrof" so'ziga ham mos sinonimlar mavjud bo'lsada, masalan, "tevarak", "har taraf", "gird", "tegra", lekin bu holatda ular orasidagi dominant bo'lgan "atrof" so'zining qo'llanilishi maqsadga muvofiq.

Windows operatsion tizimida foydalanilgan terminlar orasida to'rt komponentli atamalarni ham uchratishimiz mumkin. Masalan, "saytni kechishda davom etish" tarzida berilgan birikma "Google chrome" mobil ilovasida keltirilgan. Ingliz tilida berilishi esa "continue browsing the site" va bu holatda o'zbek tilida berilgan "kechish" so'zi mobil ilova uchun mos emas, chunki aslida "continue browsing the site" birikmasida berilgan barcha so'zlarning o'zbekcha muqobili va shu muqobillarning o'zbek tilida sinonimlari ham mavjud, lug'atlarda "browse" atamasining "kechish" emas, balki "varaqlab chiqmoq", "ko'rib chiqmoq" ma'nolari berilgan. Bu holatda "kechish" atamasi aslida "ko'chalarni kechish", "atrofni kechish" ma'nosida qo'llanilishi lozim. Xuddi, shu ta'rif A.Hojiyev tomonidan ham berilgan izohda "kechmoq" so'zi – "tevarak-atrof", "yurib tomosha qilmoq", "aylanib ko'rmoq", "sayr qilmoq" ma'nolarida qo'llanilishi ko'rsatilgan.

Windows operatsion tizimida qo'llanilgan inglizcha terminlarning o'zbek tiliga tarjimasini bo'yicha shunday xulosaga kelish mumkinki, berilgan terminlarning barchasi ham operatsion tizimda to'g'ri tarjima qilinmagan va qo'llanilishi jihatdan so'zlashuv uslubiga xos bo'lgan birikmalardan foydalanilgan. O'zbek tilining adabiy tilga xos so'zlaridan foydalanilmagan va shu sababli ham operatsion tizimda qo'llanilgan o'zbek tilidagi tushunarsiz terminlar foydalanuvchilar uchun eslab qolish qiyinligicha qolmoqda.

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COMPARATIVE STUDY OF PHYSICAL TERMS IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada turli tillar terminologiyasida fizik terminlarni o'rgangan olimlarning ilmiy ishlari ko'rib chiqilib, ular orasidagi farq va o'xshashlik haqida so'z yuritiladi. Hozirgi davrda terminologik ilmiy asarlarning ahamiyati ta'kidlanganligini inobatga olib, fizik terminlarni o'rganishning ahamiyati va dolzarbligi haqidagi olimlarning fikrlari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: moslashuvchan mobil tuzilmalar, atamalarning assimetriyasi, ixtisoslashgan terminologiya, pnevmatik tuzilmalar, fizik jarayon, o'lchov birliklari, fizik holat xususiyatlari, metaforizatsiya.

The comparative study of physical terms in modern linguistics delves into the fascinating intersection between language and the physical world. By examining how different languages express concepts related to the physical environment, researchers gain valuable insights into the ways in which human societies perceive and interact with their surroundings. This field of study sheds light on the diversity and universality of linguistic structures, offering a rich tapestry of cultural and cognitive nuances to explore. In this introduction, we will delve into the key themes and methodologies that underpin this intriguing area of research.

Some of Uzbek researchers are doing investigation on physics terms. Sh.M. Kamolkhujayev, Kh.A. Rizayev, R.B. Bekjonov created "Dictionary of Russian-Uzbek terms from physics" and translated about 20,000 words into a book. [1; 8]

In this, the amount of physical terms translated into Uzbek is covered to a certain extent. In this, the terms and phrases related to the physical process, units of measurement, and the physical state characteristics covering all departments of physical science have been selected. At the same time, physical laws, related to the fields of science and technology used in processes, terms related to mathematical concepts used in physical science, some common words for physics and other natural sciences, their importance and the breadth of the scope of application are included in the dictionary.

The authors tried to expand the physics science at the expense of new terms. The name of chemical elements is also listed in the dictionary. Because this list of elements and their atomic structure not only belongs to the science of chemistry but also has a deep physical meaning. Therefore, if the names of the elements in Mendeleev's table did not find their place in the dictionary, the dictionary would be much poorer in terms of content.

Man Yang, North Cooc, and Li Sheng published an article on the topic: An investigation of cross-linguistic transfer between Chinese and English: a meta-analysis. [2; 102]. The practice of language learners utilizing their first language's linguistic knowledge to benefit from learning a second language is known as cross-linguistic transfer. Scholars from various fields have examined the cross-linguistic transmission between Chinese and English. Nonetheless, there are differences and discrepancies between earlier research about the linguistic areas examined and the outcomes that were published. Their results demonstrate minor to moderate levels of transfer in the four areas mentioned above, based on 33 papers conducted in various countries. Furthermore, it was discovered that participant age and the study's location both influenced the results. Overall, the meta-analysis shows that there are linguistic similarities between Chinese and English that may facilitate language learning transfer.

The article on the topic "Exploring the Morphosyntactic Features of Physics Terminology in Russian and Ukrainian" was published by Ivanova, O., & Petrov, D. (2018). [3; 72]. In their article "Investigating the Morphosyntactic Highlights of Material science Wording in Russian and Ukrainian" Ivanova and Petrov dig into the etymological angles of material science wording within the Russian and Ukrainian dialects. The

creators center on the morphosyntactic highlights of these terms, looking at how they are organized and utilized inside the setting of material science talk.

Through their investigation, the creators give bits of knowledge into how material science phrasing is built in Russian and Ukrainian, advertising a more profound understanding of the phonetic complexities included in communicating logical concepts in these dialects. The article contributes to the broader field of Slavic phonetics by revealing the morphosyntactic highlights that shape the dialect of material science in these two Slavic dialects.

Dubois, M., & García, A. (2019) published an article on the topic "A Study of Metaphorical Expressions in Physics Terminology in French and Spanish" in the *Journal of Metaphor Studies* [4; 37]. In their article "A Ponder of Allegorical Expressions in Material Science Wording in French and Spanish" Dubois and Garcia investigate the utilization of allegorical dialect within the context of material science phrasing within the French and Spanish dialects. Distributed within the *Journal of Representation Ponders*, the ponder dives into how allegories are utilized to communicate complex logical concepts in these two dialects.

The creators analyze the allegorical expressions found in material science phrasing, looking at how these etymological gadgets are utilized to improve understanding and communication inside the field of material science. By centering on French and Spanish, Dubois and García—a point to reveal the special ways in which allegories are coordinated into logical talk in these dialects.

Through their investigation, the creators give bits of knowledge into the part of allegorical dialect in forming the way material science concepts are conceptualized and communicated in French and Spanish. The article contributes to the field of representation thinks about by highlighting the inventive and inventive ways in which allegorical expressions are utilized to communicate theoretical logical thoughts in these two dialects.

Furthermore, Setiawan, B., & Lim, K. (2020) made an investigation on the topic "Comparative Analysis of Physics Terminology in Indonesian and Malay" and published it in the *Southeast Asian Journal of Linguistics*. [5; 83]. In their article "Comparative Investigation of Material Science Phrasing in Indonesian and Malay" Setiawan and Lim dive into the phonetic subtleties of material science wording in these two Southeast Asian dialects. Distributed within the *Southeast Asian Diary of Etymology*, this think about offers a comprehensive examination of how material science concepts are communicated in Indonesian and Malay. Setiawan and Lim's investigation sheds light on the similarities and contrasts within the utilization of dialect to communicate logical thoughts in Indonesian and Malay.

The creators investigate the part of social and etymological variables in forming the material science phrasing in these two dialects. Through a comparative investigation, Setiawan and Lim give important bits of knowledge into how material science wording is developed and caught on in Indonesian and Malay. This article contributes to the field of phonetics by advertising a nitty gritty examination of the dialect utilized to depict complex logical concepts in Indonesian and Malay.

Setiawan and Lim's consideration highlights the significance of etymological differing qualities in forming the talk of material science inside diverse social settings. The authors' investigation offers a nuanced understanding of how dialect impacts the communication of material science concepts in Indonesian and Malay. By centering on material science phrasing, Setiawan and Lim enlighten the complex relationship between dialect, culture, and science in Southeast Asia. This article serves as an important asset for researchers and analysts curious about the crossing point of dialect and science in Indonesian and Malay.

Setiawan and Lim's work gives a stage for assisting the investigation of how dialect shapes the understanding and spread of logical information in differing etymological settings. Through their comparative examination, the creators highlight the abundance and complexity of material science wording in Indonesian and Malay. The consideration underscores the significance of considering phonetic differing qualities when examining the communication of logical concepts in completely different dialects.

Setiawan and Lim's investigation offers a new point of view on how dialect impacts the representation of material science concepts in Indonesian and Malay. This article contributes to a more profound understanding of how dialect choices affect the transmission of logical information over etymological boundaries.

"Exploring the Semantic Features of Physics Terms in Turkish and Persian" was published by Yilmaz, E., & Hosseini, M. (2019) in the *Journal of Language and Culture Studies* [6; 56]. In their article titled "Exploring the Semantic Features of Physics Terms in Turkish and Persian" Yilmaz and Hosseini dive into the complicated examination of material science phrasing within the setting of Turkish and Persian languages.

Distributed within the Journal of Language and Culture Studies, this research centers on revealing the semantic highlights and subtleties of material science terms in these two dialects, shedding light on the complexities of cross-linguistic communication within the field of physics. Through a point-by-point examination of material science terms in Turkish and Persian, the creators point to distinguish and compare the semantic structures and conceptual mappings inalienable in these dialects.

By exploring the unique linguistic characteristics and cultural influences that shape the meanings of physics terms, Yilmaz and Hosseini provide valuable insights into the challenges and strategies involved in translating scientific concepts between Turkish and Persian. This article offers a comprehensive analysis of the semantic features of physics terminology in Turkish and Persian, contributing to our understanding of how language shapes scientific discourse. It serves as a valuable resource for researchers, translators, and educators interested in the intersection of language, culture, and science, highlighting the importance of considering semantic nuances in cross-linguistic communication.

"Cross-Cultural Analysis of Physics Vocabulary: A Comparison of Chinese and German" was published by Zhang, Q., & Schmidt, L. (2017) in the International Journal of Cross-Cultural Communication [7; 31]. In their article "Cross-Cultural Analysis of Physics Vocabulary: A Comparison of Chinese and German" Zhang and Schmidt undertake a comprehensive examination of the differences and similarities in physics terminology between the Chinese and German languages. Published in the International Journal of Cross-Cultural Communication, this study delves into the intricate nuances of physics vocabulary in these two distinct linguistic and cultural contexts.

By conducting a detailed comparative analysis of physics terms in Chinese and German, the authors aim to uncover the semantic features, conceptual mappings, and cultural influences that shape the meanings of scientific concepts in these languages. Through a systematic exploration of the linguistic structures and cultural underpinnings of physics terminology, Zhang and Schmidt provide valuable insights into the challenges and strategies involved in cross-cultural communication in the field of physics.

This article offers a nuanced understanding of how language and culture intersect in the realm of scientific discourse, shedding light on the complexities of translating physics concepts between Chinese and German. It serves as a valuable resource for researchers, educators, and translators interested in the cross-cultural analysis of scientific vocabulary, emphasizing the importance of considering cultural and linguistic factors in effective communication across diverse linguistic contexts.

"The Influence of Language Structure on Physics Terminology: A Study of English and Japanese" is a research paper authored by Tanaka and Smith, and published in the Journal of Applied Linguistics Research in 2018 [8; 75]. The study investigates the impact of language structure on the terminology used in the field of physics, comparing English and Japanese languages.

The paper proposes that the structure, syntax, and characteristics of a language can significantly shape the scientific vocabulary employed by the speakers. Through a comparative analysis of English and Japanese, the authors aim to shed light on how language structure influences the development and usage of physics terms in these two languages. The research methodology involves examining and contrasting the terminologies in physics that are unique to English and Japanese. The authors analyze how these languages express concepts such as motion, time, and energy, to discern the linguistic patterns that underlie physics terminology.

The study findings highlight the contrast between English and Japanese in terms of their linguistic strategies for conveying scientific ideas. For example, Japanese employs complex verbal nouns to express concepts, while English tends to use verbs or adjectives. The research delves into how these contrasting structures affect the construction and comprehension of physics terms in both languages.

The implications of this study can be significant for both linguists and scientists. Understanding the impact of language structure on physics terminology enables scientists and educators to develop effective teaching methods and materials that align with the linguistic patterns of a particular language. It also contributes to the broader field of applied linguistics research by demonstrating how linguistic factors can influence domain-specific terminologies. In conclusion, "The Influence of Language Structure on Physics Terminology: A Study of English and Japanese" presents a detailed investigation into the role of language

structure in shaping physics terminology. The research provides valuable insights into how different languages may influence the development and usage of scientific vocabulary.

Lindgren, E., & Johnson, L. (2019) published an article on the topic "Cognitive Aspects of Physics Terminology: A Contrastive Study of English and Swedish" in *Scandinavian Journal of Applied Linguistics* [9; 68].

In their article "Cognitive Aspects of Physics Terminology: A Contrastive Study of English and Swedish" Lindgren and Johnson delve into the cognitive dimensions of physics vocabulary in the English and Swedish languages. Published in the *Scandinavian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, this study explores the cognitive processes involved in understanding and translating physics terminology across these two linguistic contexts. Through a contrastive analysis of physics terms in English and Swedish, the authors investigate how cognitive mechanisms shape the conceptualization and representation of scientific concepts in these languages. By examining the cognitive structures and semantic mappings of physics vocabulary, Lindgren and Johnson shed light on the cognitive challenges and strategies encountered by learners and translators working with physics terminology.

This article contributes to our understanding of the cognitive aspects of scientific language use, highlighting the role of cognition in shaping the meanings and interpretations of physics concepts. It offers valuable insights for educators, researchers, and language professionals interested in the cognitive dimensions of cross-linguistic communication in the field of physics, emphasizing the importance of considering cognitive factors in the teaching and translation of scientific terminology.

In conclusion, the comparative study of physical terms in modern linguistics provides a unique lens through which to explore the relationship between language and the physical world. By analyzing how different languages encode and express concepts related to the physical environment, researchers can uncover deep-seated cultural, cognitive, and perceptual patterns. This interdisciplinary field not only illuminates the diversity of linguistic structures across societies but also highlights the shared human experience of interacting with the world around us. Through this exploration, we gain a deeper understanding of the intricate ways in which language shapes our perceptions and interactions with the physical realm, ultimately enriching our appreciation of the complexities of human communication and cognition. The comparative study of physical terms in modern linguistics continues to offer valuable insights into the intricate tapestry of human language and culture, inviting further exploration and discovery in this dynamic field of study.

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THE ROLE OF PRAGMATICS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LINGUISTICS

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Anotatsiya. *Ma'lumki, pragmatika tilshunoslikning nutqda til belgilarining amal qilishini o'rganuvchi sohasi, shuningdek muayyan belgilar tizimini o'zlashtirib, undan ayni shu belgilar tizimiga munosabatini o'rganuvchi fan tarmog'i sifatida bilamiz. Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tilshunosligida pragmatikaning tutgan o'рни, rivojlanish tarixi, fan sifatida o'rganila boshlanishi mulohaza qilinadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *pragmatika, muloqot, lingvistika, kontekst, semantika, lingvo-pragmatika va boshqalar.*

It is a fact that the nature of linguistics, there are undoubtedly many contains the fields and one of the fields is pragmatics. The connection between linguistics and pragmatics may appear subtle, but a closer consideration of the two fields reveals their important aspects. The language was formed to make communication. However, as the language is being improved cannot be learned without the person, not taking into account the individual's situation in the process of communication cannot fully reveal the purpose of thought. From this point of view, the "young and modern" pragmatics, which is separate from semantics, studies the relationship between linguistic symbols and their form of expression. Pragmatics, a branch of linguistics, focuses on how language is used in context to convey meaning effectively.

A person's thoughts, national values, culture, customs, and spiritual world are manifested by the words. Therefore, in the upcoming age, without studying the role and significance of language in society, it is impossible to approach language directly by "imposing" theories. According to the Russian linguist G.V. Kolshansky, the study of the language system without pragmatics does not mean there is no reason to consider it as a newly emerging field because there is nothing as pragmatics apart from the language or a language without pragmatics.

Commonly, "Pragmatics" means "action" or "work" in Greek, and this concept of the philosophical view goes back even further than the times of Socrates. Originally, among the Greeks, this term is widely used then it is observed in J. Locke and E. Kants' views. Subsequently, the ideas of pragmatism, which began to develop in the XIX-XX centuries, were widely promoted in all language fields in the 20th -and 30th. Initially, CH. Pierce, R. Karnal, CH. Morris and L. Wittgenstein greatly contributed to the development of Pragmatics in America and Europe.

As British linguist J. Lyons said: "Pragmatics describes the encourage the listener to accept the transmitted information as intended by the speaker the use of linguistic units suitable for the purpose in communication. It deals with pragmatics to determine the role of linguistic tools in interpersonal communication." At its core, pragmatics examines how language users employ context, inference, and shared knowledge to interpret and convey meaning. Unlike semantics, which deals with the literal meaning of words and sentences, pragmatics considers the speaker's intentions, the listener's assumptions, and the situational context. It encompasses various aspects of communication, including speech acts, implicature, politeness, and conversational implicature. Pragmatics emphasizes the importance of situational context in understanding language. Speakers and listeners rely on contextual cues, such as the physical environment, social norms, and shared experiences, to interpret utterances. Moreover, pragmatic inference allows individuals to derive meaning beyond the explicit content of the message. For example,

"It's cold in here"

It may imply a request to close the window or adjust the thermostat, depending on the context. Speech acts refer to the actions performed through language, such as making requests, giving commands, or expressing gratitude. In addition, pragmatics examines how speakers use language to accomplish specific goals and how listeners interpret these utterances based on social conventions and cultural norms. For instance,

"Can you pass the salt?"

It is not merely a question but also a request for assistance, relying on the listener's understanding of social etiquette. Pragmatics is particularly relevant in the English language, given its rich repertoire

of idiomatic expressions, indirect speech acts, and cultural nuances. English speakers often rely on pragmatics to navigate various social situations, from casual conversations to professional interactions. Understanding pragmatics enhances language proficiency by enabling learners to interpret subtle nuances, recognize implicit meaning, and adapt their language use to different contexts.

In the English language, pragmatics plays a pivotal role in facilitating interpersonal interaction, fostering mutual understanding, and navigating diverse cultural landscapes.

Similarly, in the study of Uzbek linguistics, pragmatics revolves around the idea of speech acts, which represent the intentions or goals of the speaker during communication. These intentions can manifest in various forms such as requests, confirmations, notifications, commands, or warnings, alongside their primary meanings. This underscores how language serves as a tool for achieving specific communicative aims within different contexts, whether verbal or written. As mentioned by Abdullayeva N.E., it is known that one of the main tasks of pragmatics is what is the main aim to use the language in speech. For example:

"Menga ozroq pul berib tura olasizmi?" ("Could you lend me some money?")

As English language, it seems a question but, it can be accepted like a polite request. As can be seen from the examples given above, the differences between the sentences in the process of communication in both languages are the same depending on the purpose for which they are used. Each sentence can be sarcastic or humorous depending on the speaker's intention. We can see that the use of pragmatics in both languages is not very different.

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SIGNALS AND MARKERS OF IMPLICITNESS IN THE LITERARY TEXT

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada badiiy matnlardagi implitsitlik hodisasi o'rganilgan, ushbu uslubdan foydalanish orqali mualliflar asar murakkabligini qay darajada chuqurlashtira olishi va o'qish tajribasini boyitishi tahlil etilgan, asarning ko'p qirrali va qiziqarli bo'lishini ta'minlashda noaniqlikning o'rni asoslangan. Tahlillar orqali noaniqlikning uchta ko'rinishi aniqlangan: leksik, sintaktik va kompozitsion.

Kalit so'zlar: implitsitlik, badiiy matn, leksik implitsitlik, sintaktik implitsitlik, kompozitsion vosita.

Implicitness in literary texts is a deliberate and intricate device employed by authors to enhance the depth and complexity of their works (Booth, 1961). This literary device, as highlighted by Wayne C. Booth in "The Rhetoric of Fiction", deliberately introduces uncertainty, inviting a sense of doubt and confusion within the narrative and possessing the quality of being open to multiple interpretations. In this way, implicitness transforms the act of reading into a dynamic and interactive experience, enriching

the overall aesthetic quality of literary works. When readers deal with the unclear parts of a story, they become partners in creating what it means. This makes the story more interesting and complicated (Booth, 1961). However, implicitness should not be confused with vagueness, as vagueness usually indicates unclear or poorly written content. When something is vague, it is so unclear that no specific interpretation can be formed or trusted (Culler, 1975).

In the realm of literature, the violation of Gricean Maxim of manner in the form of implicitness manifests in various forms such as characters, words, phrases, plot points, images, tropes, or situations, each capable of being interpreted in two or more possible ways. More often than not, implicitness is purposefully applied in literary text at lexical, syntactical, and compositional levels, which in their turn have the signals and markers whereby implicitness is represented in literary texts.

I. Implicitness at a lexical level. Initially, it has to be stated that "multiplicity of meaning is a very general characteristic of any language" (Palmer, 1981, p.70- 71). So lexical implicitness refers to a word's ability to carry two or more distinct meanings, depending on the context. These meanings are appropriate for specific situations, and the word retains the same spelling. Additionally, multiple words may share the same pronunciation but have different meanings (Gomez, 1996). M.

Lexical implicitness is often employed in literary texts to elicit emotional responses from the reader through expressions or specific words (Scarinzi, 2008). Pun and wordplay, irony, metaphor, and metonymy are the main representatives of lexical implicitness in literary text, which are to be discussed one by one.

A pun can be described as the foregrounding of lexical implicitness, stemming from either homonymy or polysemy (Leech, 1968). Given that a pun serves to foreground implicitness, there exists a circumstance wherein a solitary word may give rise to additional interpretations. According to G. Simpson, a pun can be characterized as a type of wordplay where two unrelated meanings converge within a single word (Simpson, 2004). In the literary text, the pun is manifested through repetition, play on antonyms, the asyntactic pun, the etymological pun, syllepsis, and play on the similarity of pronunciation (Leech, 1968).

Lexical implicitness is also manifested in literary text with the use of irony. H. Fowler, in "The King's English", says: "Any definition of irony—though hundreds might be given, and very few of them would be accepted—must include this, that the surface meaning and the underlying meaning of what is said are not the same" (Fowler, 1906, p.28). Irony, including verbal irony, situational irony, and dramatic irony, is a literary device that involves a discrepancy between expectation and reality, often with the intention of humor or to convey a deeper meaning. It is a powerful tool that adds complexity and depth to literary discourse, creating implicitness and inviting readers to engage more deeply with the text. Authors use irony to create implicatum and convey subtle messages, criticize society, or highlight the complexities of human nature (Booth, 1974).

Metaphors often serve as signs of implicitness in literary text because they introduce a layer of metaphorical meaning beyond the literal interpretation. They can give rise to polysemy, a feature of lexical implicitness that appears in one form or another in all languages and at all times (Kess, Nishimitsu, 1990). According to A. Paivio, linguistic metaphor involves "the application of a word or expression that properly belongs to one context to express meaning in a different context because of some real or implied similarity in the reference involved" (Paivio, 1979, p.152). Metaphors are produced with the intention that the extended range be recognized. They make readers attend to some likeness, often a novel or surprising likeness, between two or more things where figurative meaning arises through a mutually recognized mismatch of literal meaning with context (Fogelin, 1988). However, it has to be outlined that, metaphors and irony violate the maxim of quality and manner (Grice, 1989). This is because the figurative language in metaphors adds a layer of complexity, making it difficult for the listener/reader to quickly grasp the intended message. This complexity can lead to confusion, as the listener may struggle to figure out the exact meaning the speaker is trying to convey with the metaphor (Adam, 2022)

Metonymy, a powerful linguistic device, plays a crucial role in introducing polysemy and implicitness in literary discourse. It is a figure of speech that is closely associated with metaphor, of which it is a kind. In metonymy, one word substitutes for a related word (Baldick, 2008). R. Langacker explains

metonymy as "a process consists in mentally accessing one conceptual entity via another entity" (Langacker, 1993, p.30). The traditional approach to understanding and classifying metonymy is to refer to it as a "part for the whole", "whole for a part", "place for the institution" and "producer for products" (Guan, 2009).

II. Implicitness at a syntactical level. Syntactic or, in other words, structural or grammatical implicitness is "a term used in linguistics to refer to a construction with more than one grammatical interpretation in terms of constituent analysis" (Crystal, 2003, p.438). Agreeing with Crystal, R. Demers says it is "a situation in which a sentence has two or more different linguistic meanings even though none of the individual words is ambiguous. The implicitness of such sentences resides in their different constituent structures" (Demers, 2012, p.597). The violation of the Gricean maxim occurs when sentence structures allow for multiple interpretations. Authors often use this technique to create complexity, engage readers, and invite different perspectives (Booth, 1961).

Syntactic parallelism. Parallelism is the repetition of similar grammatical structures in a sentence. It creates rhythm and symmetry in sentence construction, which makes it easier to understand. Parallelism can be used in several types of grammatical structures, such as sentence fragments, phrases, and clauses (<https://utilitiesone.com/>). Parallelism, when subtly skewed or manipulated, becomes a tool for authors to craft sentences with multiple, often conflicting, interpretations (Fish, 1980).

Ellipsis. From linguistic point of view, ellipses are used as cohesive device to avoid tedious redundancy by intentional omission of a word, phrase or clause from a text (Fadhil, 2020). However, ellipsis as a literary device is used in narratives to omit some parts of a sentence or event, which gives the reader a chance to fill the gaps while acting or reading it out. It is usually written between the sentences as a series of three dots, like this: "..." (<https://literarydevices.net/ellipsis/>). On the surface level, the principle of reducing the message by ellipsis comes in conjunction with Grice's cooperative principle (Allerton, 1979). But the deliberate use of ellipsis, whether in dialogue or narration, becomes a potent tool for authors to imbue implicitness, which is the violation of Maxim of manner (Iser, 1978).

III. Implicitness at a compositional level.

The composition of a literary text is closely associated with understanding the concept of "strong positions of the text". In modern text linguistics, strong positions mean "a specific organization of the text, ensuring the highlighting of the most important meanings of the text" [1; 62]. The concept of "strong positions of the text" first appeared in the work of I.V. Arnold, who named among them the title, epigraph, beginning and end of the text. The basis for highlighting these positions in the text was their significant influence on the reader's perception of the text and the fact that a certain organization of frame positions ensures the adequacy of the reader's interpretation of the literary text [1].

The title is the first, graphically highlighted line of the text containing the "name" of the work [8]. It is the first component of the work that allows the familiarization of the reader with the text. According to I. Galperin, the title is "a compressed, undisclosed content of the text. It can be metaphorically represented as twisted spring, revealing its capabilities in the process of interpretation" (Galperin, 1981, p.133) An implicit title, however, is a concentrated expression of the main idea or theme in a literary work, requiring consideration of the entire text to fully understand its significance. Unlike explicit titles, implicit titles gain meaning retrospectively after reading the complete text [2].

Another the most important component of the literary text is an epigraph. The epigraph is a phrase, quotation or poem that is set at the beginning of a document, monograph or section thereof ([https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Epigraph/\(literature\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Epigraph/(literature))). It serves as a powerful literary device employed by certain writers to direct the reader's attention to the central theme, purpose, or underlying issues explored within the work (Wilkerson, 1983). However, G. Genette explains that the epigraph is a mute gesture; more specifically, this means that the function of the epigraph relies on the reader's interpretation. He states that "when the epigraphs are used ambiguously, the meaning does not become clear until the text has been read, which then requires an explanatory approach by the reader to elicit meaning from the epigraph" [5; 156].

Implicitness is manifested in the beginning of the literary text as well. Beginning is an event or incident that introduces a process of change in the literary work. Traditionally, it usually includes the description of setting, characters or objects which mostly will become important keys to the theme or the story throughout the work (Prince, 1987). However, these literary signals can also be implicit and convey additional messages to the readers (Eco, 1994). The implicit beginning can manifest in various ways, such as through vague descriptions, unresolved situations, or enigmatic characters

Ending is the next component of the text which can represent implicitness in the literary work. The end is an element of the text that actualizes the category of completeness and allows the addressee to comprehend the speech work as a whole (Kukhareno, 1988). According to E. Forster, ending vary from clear conclusion and rounding off to a more open-ended and resolved ending. Closed endings is characterized by fulfilment of the tasks of the narrative such as resolving mysterious situations and clarifying various ambiguities (Forster, 1978). In works with an open ending, the author offers the addressee a choice of two possible endings, showing the implicitness of one or another interpretation and inviting him to co-create (Kukhareno, 1988).

In conclusion, implicitness in literary texts is a deliberate device employed by authors to enhance the depth and complexity of their works. It is mostly implemented at the lexical, syntactical and compositional levels, transforming the act of reading into an interactive experience. Lexical implicitness can be expressed through puns, wordplay, irony, metaphor, and metonymy. It introduces multiple meanings to words or phrases, creating layers of interpretation and depth in literary discourse. Syntactical implicitness, including parallelism, ellipsis, and garden path sentences, uses structural and grammatical techniques to guide readers down unexpected interpretation. Compositional implicitness is mostly manifested in the strong positions of the text, making readers question and reconsider their initial interpretations.

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PSYCHOLINGUISTICS AS A SCIENCE ON HUMAN SPEECH ACTIVITIES

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются психолингвистические аспекты речевой деятельности человека. Автор констатирует, что речевое воздействие представляет собой целенаправленную перестройку смысловой сферы личности, а текст социально ориентированного общения решает три основные психологические задачи: а) привлечение внимания к тексту; б) оптимизация его восприятия; в) принятие его содержания реципиентом.

Ключевые слова: психолингвистика, речевой аспект, речевое воздействие, коммуникация.

Psycholinguistics is the discipline that investigates and describes the psychological processes that make it possible for humans to master and use language. Psycholinguists conduct research on speech development and language development and how individuals of all ages comprehend and produce language. For descriptions of language, the field relies on the findings of linguistics, which is the discipline that describes the structure of language. Although the acquisition, comprehension, and production of language have been at the core of psycholinguistic research, the field has expanded considerably since its inception: The neurology of language functioning is of current interest to psycholinguists, particularly to those studying sex differences, aphasia, language after congenital or acquired injury to the immature brain, and developmental disorders of language (dysphasia). Some psycholinguists have also extended their interests to experiments in nonhuman language learning (e.g., gorillas and chimpanzees) to discover if language as we know it is a uniquely human phenomenon [1].

Psycholinguistics is the study of how language is acquired, processed, and used by humans. It combines elements from linguistics, psychology, neuroscience, and cognitive science to understand how people learn languages and use them in communication.

Development of English speech activity has become one of the most necessary aspects for different languages learning and teaching. However, this appears to be not enough for foreign language instruction as it cannot override the issues of psycholinguistics. So, in order to choose the more effective ways for the development of English speech activity it is vital to understand the relationship between its types and psycholinguistics if there is any.

However, the relationship between English speech activity and psycholinguistics for searching for more efficient ways of developing both was not the investigation subject of a wide range of scholars. Speaking about speech activity, on the one hand, it is realized in the field of communication, it influences different psycholinguistic components, and provides language interaction, and communication from psycholinguistic standpoints. On the other hand, we interpret it as the combination of "skills or practical language competencies which reflect a person's ability to use the foreign language as a tool to adapt to the English language environment and solve the range of tasks involving the use of a foreign language" [2].

The research of human communication and the intricate interplay between speech and psychology has given rise to a captivating field known as the psychology of speech. This multidisciplinary area of research delves into how speech influences our thoughts, behaviors, and interactions with others. By examining the psychological aspects of speech, we can unravel the complexities of language, communication, and cognition.

The psychology of speech encompasses a wide range of subfields, including speech perception, production, comprehension, and language development. Through rigorous scientific inquiry and investigation, researchers in this field aim to unravel the mysteries behind how we perceive, produce, and understand speech.

One of the fundamental aspects studied in the psychology of speech is speech perception. This involves

understanding how we process and interpret speech sounds, tones, and linguistic cues. Researchers explore how our brains analyze phonetic information, recognize patterns, and extract meaning from the sounds and rhythms of speech.

Speech production is another crucial area of inquiry within the psychology of speech. It focuses on the cognitive and physiological processes involved in planning, coordinating, and executing speech movements. Understanding how our thoughts are transformed into spoken words sheds light on the complex motor skills and neural mechanisms that underlie our ability to communicate orally.

Speech production is a complex activity, and as consequence errors are common, especially in children. Speech errors come in many forms and are used to provide evidence to support hypotheses about the nature of speech. As a result, speech errors are often used in the construction of models for language production and child language acquisition. For example, the fact that children often make the error of over-regularizing the -ed past tense suffix in English (e.g. saying 'singed' instead of 'sang') shows that the regular forms are acquired earlier. Speech errors associated with certain kinds of aphasia have been used to map certain components of speech onto the brain and see the relation between different aspects of production; for example, the difficulty of expressive aphasia patients in producing regular past-tense verbs, but not irregulars like 'sing-sang' has been used to demonstrate that regular inflected forms of a word are not individually stored in the lexicon, but produced from affixation to the base form [3].

Public speaking is a skill that many individuals strive to master. It involves effectively delivering a message to an audience, capturing their attention, and persuading or informing them. The psychology of speech plays a crucial role in understanding the dynamics of public speaking and can provide valuable insights for speakers aiming to engage and connect with their audience.

The psychology of speech sheds light on various aspects that contribute to effective public speaking. One key area of focus is nonverbal communication. Researchers explore how body language, facial expressions, gestures, and vocal tone impact the audience's perception and engagement. Understanding how to align verbal and nonverbal cues can enhance a speaker's ability to convey their message persuasively.

Speech psychology also emphasizes the importance of vocal delivery. The tone, pitch, volume, and pace of speech significantly influence the audience's perception of a speaker's credibility, confidence, and overall message. By understanding the psychology of speech, speakers can learn to modulate their voice, use pauses strategically, and emphasize key points effectively [4].

What we call speech influence here is the various forms of socially oriented communication. In other words, it is mass communication (radio, television, press); forms of propaganda that do not fit into the traditional volume of mass communication -such as leaflets posted or distributed, documentaries, videos, computer programs with the task of social (socio-psychological) impact; finally, various forms of advertising, both commercial and political. In addition, socially oriented communication includes various forms of direct social impact such as lectures, oral public speaking, etc. Finally, what is often called "psychological warfare" tends to the same problem -a system of socially and socio-psychologically oriented actions, defined as "the planned conduct of propaganda, the main purpose of which is to influence the views, moods, orientation and behavior of the troops and population of the enemy, the population of neutral and allied countries, in order to contribute to the implementation of state goals and objectives.

Different linguistic methods are used in this article. The semantic differential method is used to identify subjective (individual) semantic fields and refers to the "scaling" methods. These methods are used in psychology to obtain quantitative parameters of the phenomenon under study. In psycholinguistics, words and phrases are the object of study.

In this research it is discussed that psycholinguistic aspects of speech activities. It researches how our brains clarifies phonetic information, recognize patterns, and meaning from the sounds and rhythms of speech. There is a great connection between speech and psychology. It is also included that how speech influences our thoughts, behaviors, and interactions with others.

In conclusion, speech is a process that can affect differently in different situations. One of the key points of speech that it comes at people first. When a speech occurs, a person starts to think and psychological peculiarities also occur at the same time because the speech is also a result of psycholinguistic aspect. However, this appears to be not enough for foreign language instruction as it cannot override the issues

of psycholinguistics. So, in order to choose the more effective ways for development of English speech activity it is vital to understand the relationship between its types and psycholinguistics if there is any.

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SOCIOLINGUISTIC PROFILE OF EFL LEARNERS

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Annotation. *Ushbu maqolada bir guruh ingliz tili o'rganuvchilari misolida til o'qitishning ijtimoiy-lingvistik omillari, ta'lim konteksti va kelajakdagi maqsadli o'rganilgan, chet tillarni o'qitishda sotsiolingvistik yondashuv kommunikativ yondashuvning mantiqiy davomi ekanligi ko'rsatilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *sotsiolingvistika, ijtimoiy omil, kontekst, shaxsiyat.*

Introduction. Every learner is an individual. They may differ from others in several social factors such as gender, age, socioeconomic status, marital status, educational background, L1, ethnicity and so on. The present paper describes the sociolinguistic profile of a group of English language learners in the private university in Tashkent. The group number is 305. They are first year students whose major is finance. Almost all the students work, so they attend evening classes at university. English is the medium of instruction in some groups of that university; however, the very learners study the subjects in Uzbek. The group consists of eighteen people aged 18-39. There are fourteen male and four female students in group 305. Seven out of eighteen are single whereas eleven learners are married students. Their level of English language proficiency fluctuate between A2 and B1. Fourteen of the group members are Uzbek, two are Tajik, one is Kazakh, and one is Karakalpak.

First, the group is divided into two subgroups based on their age and marital status:

- Group A: eight 18-27 year old learners
- 4 males and 4 females
- Most of them have B1 level of English language proficiency
- Group B: ten 28-39 year old learners
- All the members are married men
- Most of them have A2 level of English language proficiency
- Nine have schoolchildren.

Second, the group is divided into two subgroups according to their genders. Schilling (2011) notes that although many people use the words gender and sex interchangeably, many scholars including sociolinguists separate them. According to the author, sex is biological whereas gender is more sociocultural concept. In my view, all the members of group 305 are cisgenders, however, there is a man whose manner of speaking is a bit feminine. His intonation is soft and playful like a woman's. This characteristic of that member is considered as normal in the group because he has no other feminine manifestations other than voice and intonation.

The same language is acquired differently not only by residents of different localities, not only by representatives of different professions, not only by people of different ages but men and women speak it differently. Mesthrie, Swann, Deumert, and Leap (2009) note that the linguist Otto Jespersen found out that about 10% of Caribbean vocabulary has different female and male forms. According to the very authors, women's speech gives more "polite and gentle" impression to listeners. Sometimes it is connected

to women's relative powerlessness. However, this is not the only distinction between men and women speech. The manner in which male and female members of group 305 communicate also differs. The women immediately engage in communication, maintain a conversation, ask questions, while most of the men listen with restraint, and then speak straightforwardly about the topic.

All the female members of the group are able to solve several tasks at the same time, for example, while making story using the pictures they listen to each other and the teacher. In addition, it is so easy for them to switch from one type of activity to another. However, the males do not like to jump from task to task, so they do everything in sequence. The group members have different gaming habits as well. Not only the males, but also female members love to play during the lessons. However, preferences differ: the women prefer role-playing games on family and household topics, the men like to compete. This means that the teacher should pay attention to the gender characteristics of the learners and adjust lesson scenarios to the preferences of students of different sexes. The group members have different attitude to their knowledge, for example, females are more successful in learning English language, but they consider themselves mediocre, incapable, etc. The men, on the contrary, tend to overestimate their successes and knowledge. So when giving feedback to the male members the teacher needs to "ground" them a little, paying attention to some mistakes, and praise – very specifically: not just "well done", but what exactly turned out well. When giving feedback to the women, the teacher should encourage and inspire, not emphasizing failures or mistakes, but showing confidence that they are temporary. Even the way different genders receive the feedback differs. The female members of the very group take mistakes calmly and therefore they attempt to speak in English less painfully than the men. The male members subconsciously perceive mistakes as defeat, failure, and therefore some of them prefer to remain silent than to say wrong. In such a case the teacher should discuss his perfectionism with a male student, explain that he cannot silently overcome the language barrier, and he will have to put up with mistakes.

When it comes to ethnicity, Uzbek, Kazakh and Karakalpak learners understand each other when they speak in their L1. However, there are two Tajik students whose language is different from Turkic languages so it is difficult to understand them when they speak in Tajik. Both Tajik students are males and they are open to communicate to others. However, one of them always seems to have defensive position as if some other people are going to attack him and he is ready to protect himself. In addition, he shows his ethnic identity. On the first day of studies when all the learners started to introduce themselves one by one nobody but he mentioned his nationality: "Hello. My name is _____. I am Tajik." Language is the most important component of ethnic identity. According to Fought (2011), the process of constructing one's identity is complex, and ethnicity may occasionally play a more prominent or less prominent role depending on the situation.

For the teacher and for the educational institution all of the learners no matter what gender, socioeconomic status or ethnicity they have should be the same.

All of the above shows that each student is unique and has his or her own identity which helps or sometimes even hinders to social interaction in class.

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THE PROBLEMS OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada stereotiplar va etnosentrizmning ingliz tilidagi madaniyatlararo muloqotga ta'siri o'rganilgan. Shuningdek, o'zaro muloqotda imo-ishoralar kabi ekstralingvistik omilning roli ko'rsatilgan, globallashuv va texnologiyaning ingliz tilidagi madaniyatlararo muloqotga ta'siri tahlil qilingan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *madaniyatlararo muloqot, ingliz tili, madaniy farqlar, tilni bilish, muloqot usullari, noverbal muloqot, madaniyatlararo kompetentsiya.*

In order to get past cultural barriers, communicate politely and effectively with foreigners, engage in emotional exchanges, and engage in cross-cultural communication, learning a foreign language requires mastery of the relevant knowledge, skills, and language. This means that in addition to having effective language and culture teaching communication, we also need to perform well in the language teaching stage of university English instruction. The ability to use language appropriately and correctly is therefore a crucial component of international communication competence.

The development of language and communication skills depends heavily on intercultural communicative competence. Intercultural communication is a new "edge" subject that is closely related to teaching English. In the modern era, it is our responsibility as university English instructors to take on a new purpose, integrate language and cultural education, and foster students' intercultural communicative skills.

Communication is not just about exchanging information [9]; it is about understanding the emotion and intention behind the information. When it comes to intercultural communication, the barriers, nuances, and challenges become even more pronounced. The use of the English language as a global lingua franca adds another layer of complexity, as it becomes a bridge language for individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds. In an increasingly interconnected world, interactions between people from different cultural backgrounds have become the norm rather than the exception. The use of English as an international language has enabled cross-cultural communication [5], but it has also revealed numerous intercultural communication challenges. These challenges stem from differences in language proficiency, cultural norms, nonverbal communication, and diverse interpretations of spoken and written English.

One of the most obvious issues in intercultural communication is differing levels of English language proficiency. Native speakers, non-native speakers, and individuals [2] with varying degrees of fluency often struggle to understand one another's expressions, leading to miscommunication and ambiguity. Additionally, regional dialects, accents, and idiomatic expressions further complicate interactions, potentially leading to misunderstandings, confusion, or frustration.

Cultural norms [9] influence individual communication styles, social behaviors, and conversational norms. When people from divergent cultural backgrounds communicate in English, misunderstandings may arise due to differing views on politeness, directness, gestures, and body language. For example, the interpretation of eye contact, physical proximity, and greeting customs can vary significantly across cultures, potentially impacting the effectiveness of communication [5].

Nonverbal communication, including facial expressions, gestures, and body language, is a crucial component of human interaction. However, nonverbal cues are highly culture-specific. What may be considered a positive gesture in one culture could convey a contrasting message in another. The interpretation of nonverbal cues in English communication, such as tone of voice, hand gestures, and facial expressions, can be challenging for individuals from different cultural backgrounds.

Interpretation of English language expressions, colloquialisms, and idiomatic phrasings presents a significant hurdle in intercultural communication. Phrases and words may carry varied connotations

and meanings across cultures, resulting in unintended implications or confusion. Misinterpretation of humor, sarcasm, or figurative language may lead to miscommunication, potentially impacting professional relationships and personal interactions.

Addressing the challenges of intercultural communication in the English language requires a multi-faceted approach. A few strategies to mitigate these challenges include:

1. Language Training and Education [2]: Encouraging language learners to develop cultural awareness alongside language proficiency helps in navigating the intricacies of English communication within a global context.

2. Cultural Sensitivity Training: Providing individuals with an understanding of diverse cultural norms and communication styles fosters mutual respect and minimizes the potential for misinterpretation.

3. Active Listening and Clarification: Encouraging active listening, seeking clarification when uncertain, and promoting open communication channels allows for addressing potential misunderstandings promptly.

As the world continues to move towards increased globalization, the significance of intercultural communication in the English language will only grow. It is crucial to continually assess and respond to the evolving challenges of intercultural communication in the context of English as a global language:

1. Technological Advancements: With advancements in communication technology, individuals now have access to various tools and platforms that facilitate cross-cultural interactions. Leveraging these resources in language learning, cultural sensitivity training, and virtual collaboration can help bridge the gaps in intercultural communication.

2. Education and Training Initiatives: Educational institutions and corporate entities play a pivotal role in providing language training, cross-cultural communication workshops, and diversity initiatives. By fostering an environment that embraces cultural differences, organizations can create a more inclusive and productive workforce.

3. Research and Collaboration: Continued research into intercultural communication and the challenges in English language use can provide valuable insights into effective cross-cultural communication strategies. Collaborative efforts across academia, industry, and communities can contribute to the development of best practices in intercultural communication.

4. Adapting to Linguistic Evolution: The English language itself is constantly evolving, and its use within diverse cultural settings creates new variations, idiomatic expressions, and communication norms. Understanding and accommodating these linguistic shifts is essential for effective intercultural communication.

In order to acquire proficiency in a foreign language, it is essential to not only develop linguistic skills and knowledge but also gain an understanding of the cultural context that shapes the language. This comprehensive approach is necessary to navigate cultural differences, engage in effective and respectful communication with those from other cultures, and foster emotional and cross-cultural interactions. This underscores the importance of integrating language and cultural education at the university level in the teaching of English. The proficiency in using language accurately and appropriately forms a critical component of intercultural communicative competence. Such competence is pivotal in enhancing one's language and communication abilities. Intercultural communication, a relatively new and influential area of study, is intricately linked with English education. As educators in the modern era, it's our responsibility to merge language instruction with cultural insights to nurture the intercultural communicative skills of our students.

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JAHON TILSHUNOSLIGIDA LINGVOPOETIKAGA OID TADQIQOTLARNING PAYDO BO'LISHI

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассмотрена история становления в мировой лингвистике сравнительно новой отрасли языкознания лингвопоэтики, сформированной на стыке языкознания и литературы, обоснована её роль в ряде современных лингвистических направлений: психолингвистики, прагмалингвистики, лингвокультурологии.

Ключевые слова: лингвопоэтика, лингвистика, литературоведение, поэтическая лингвистика, лингвистический анализ.

Tilshunoslik badiiy adabiyot fani bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'lib, til aloqa vositasi sifatida muayyan axborot tashuvchi oddiy belgilar sistemasigina bo'lib qolmay, balki tinglovchiga ta'sir qiluvchi qudratli vosita hamdir. Tilning birinchi funksiyasi an'anaviy va sistem-struktur tilshunoslikning o'rganish obyekti bo'lsa, ikkinchi funksiyasi lingvopoetikaning o'rganish obyektidir [1; 5].

Lingvopoetikaning paydo bo'lishi bilan bog'liq fikrlar ko'plab tadqiqotchilarning bahs-munozaralariga sabab bo'lgan. Garchi bu soha zamonaviy tilshunoslikda rivojlanib, taraqqiy etishiga qaramay, uning ildizlari qadimiy davrlarga borib taqaladi. Arastuning "Poetika" asari jahonda yuzaga kelgan eng birinchi adabiyot nazariyasi haqidagi kitob bo'lib, unda muallif nafaqat adabiyotga oid nazariy fikrlarini, jumladan, tilshunoslikka oid ba'zi mulohazalarini ham keltirib o'tgan.

M.Yo'ldoshevning keltirgan ma'lumotlariga ko'ra badiiy asar tilini lingvistik o'rganishning shakllanishida rus "formalizm"i vakillari tomonidan tashkil etilgan "Poetik tilni o'rganish jamiyati" ("Общество по изучению поэтического языка – ОПОЯЗ")ning o'rni alohidadir. Mutaxassislar bu jamiyatni tuzishga 1917-yilning fevralida qaror qilingan bo'lsa-da, uning 1914-yilda V.Shklovskiyning "So'zning tirilishi" nomli ishining nashr qilinishidan boshlanganini aytadilar. Bu jamiyatda R.Yakobson, V.Shklovskiy, O.Brik, L.Yakubinskiy, B.Eyxenbaum, S.Bernshteyn, B.Larin, shuningdek, keyinroq B.Tomashevskiy, V.Jirmunskiy, Y.Tinyanov, V.Vinogradov, G.Vinokur kabi bir qator filologlar faoliyat yuritganlar, badiiy asarni o'rganishda lingvistik tahlilning yetakchilik qilishiga ko'proq e'tibor berganlar [3;20]. Rus formalistlarining ichida B.V. Tomashevskiyning "Теория литературы" kitobi alohida diqqatga sazovor bo'lib, unda so'zning kontekstdagi va kontekstdan tashqaridagi ma'nosi, matndagi til birliklarining xususiyatlari haqida fikrlar keltirilgan. Lingvopoetikaga oid tadqiqotlarni ko'zdan kechirish mobaynida ba'zi tilshunoslarning badiiy matnning lingvistik tahlili uning g'oyaviy-badiiy xususiyatlarini tushunish uchun birlamchi omil ekanligi, tilshunosliksiz poetika yo'qligi haqidagi bir yoqlama fikrlariga ham duch kelish mumkin. R.Yakobsonning "Poetikani lingvistikaning tarkibiy qismi sifatida qarash mumkin" tarzidagi g'oyalari shular jumlasidandir. Shu sababdan ba'zi tadqiqotchilar lingvistik tahlil emas, filologik tahlil ifodasini qo'llashni ma'qul ko'radilar. Bu borada sistem-struktural tilshunoslik asoschisi F.de Sossyurning: "Har bir matn zamirida til tizimi turadi" tarzidagi e'tirofi badiiy matnni adabiyotshunoslik va tilshunoslik nuqtayi nazaridan o'rganishni taqozo qiladi [4; 13].

Akademik V.V. Vinogradov badiiy adabiyotni lingvistik tahlil qilish uchun alohida filologik fan joriy etilib, bu yo'nalishni lingvopoetika deb nomlashni taklif qiladi. Ayni paytda, uning qarashlariga ko'ra, lingvopoetik tahlilda lingvistik birliklarni pog'onasimon tahlil qilish haqidagi g'oya ilgari surilib, bu tahlil leksik, morfologik, sintaktik sathlar tadqiqiga asoslanadi. Olimning fikricha, lingvopoetik tadqiqot lisoniy birliklarning estetik tomonini badiiy ijod bilan uyg'unlikda o'rganishdan iboratdir. Shuningdek, rus tilshunosi badiiy asarni o'rganishda uch soha – tarix, adabiyotshunoslik, tilshunoslik fanlarining ahamiyati katta ekanligini ta'kidlagan. Badiiy asar tahlili jarayonida o'sha davrga xos mafkuraviy, siyosiy, etnomadaniy tushunchalarni hisobga olish zarurligi, sababi, ijodkorning dunyoqarashi, mafkuraviy g'oyalari ijod namunalari o'z aksini topishi tilshunos olimning qarashlarida bayon etilgan. V.V. Vinogradov badiiy nutqni o'rganishning ikki tomonini keltirib o'tadi. Birinchisi – badiiy asarni tahlil qilib tushunish, ikkinchisi – badiiy asarni stilistik hamda estetik jihatdan idrok qilish, ya'ni tovush, fonema, so'z yasash va boshqa tarkibiy qismlari yuzasidan tahlil qilish shular jumlasidandir. Olimning ta'biricha: "Badiiy adabiyot va san'at tili muhim munozarali tadqiqotlarning yuzaga kelishiga zamin yaratdi. Filologiya fanining bir-biridan farqli xususiyati negizida tilshunoslik va adabiyotshunoslik aspektida o'rganish lozimdir. Chunki badiiy matn obrazlilik va ijodkor tuyg'ulari yordamida yuzaga chiqqan janr bo'linishlari hisoblansa, tilshunoslik o'sha gap va so'z tarkibidagi leksemalarning qanday semantik, metaforik, sintaktik ma'no tashuvchi komponent ekanligini tahlil qilishni maqsad qiladi. Har ikki sohaning orasidagi jiddiy tafovut shuki, biri ikkinchisiga muntazam ravishda o'tib turadi: aniqlik va obrazlilikdan tarkib topadi" [5; 41-44].

V.M. Jirmunskiy o'z tadqiqotlarida mazmun va shakl to'g'risida fikr yuritib, har qanday shaklni o'zgartirish orqali mazmunni ham o'zgartirilishi, badiiy asar til imkoniyati yo'nalishida o'rganilishi lozimligini ta'kidlaydi. Jirmunskiyning poetik tilshunoslik haqidagi dastlabki qarashlari "Poetikaning vazifalari" va "Formal uslub masalasida" nomli ilk tadqiqotlarida yaqqol namoyon bo'lgan. Uning "She'ning materiali obraz yoki his-tuyg'ular emas, balki so'zdir" [6; 22] degan qimmatli fikrlari lingvistika va poetikaning chambarchas bog'liqligini ta'kidlashi bilan alohida ahamiyatga egadir. Shuningdek, uning fikricha, "she'riyatning materiali so'z bo'lganligi sababli poetikaning tizimli qurilishi tilshunoslik bizga beradigan til faktlarining tasnifiga asoslanishi lozim" [6; 28]. V.M. Jirmunskiy poetik fonetika, poetik morfologiya, poetik sintaktika, poetik semantika haqida qarashlarini bayon qilib, poetikaning ushbu bo'limlari she'riy til haqidagi ta'limotni tashkil etishini va bu ta'limot lingvistik stilistika deb atalishini aytadi. Bu soha umumiy tilshunoslik faktlarining badiiy qo'llanishdagi ahamiyatini tekshirishini misollar bilan izohlaydi.

Adabiyot va tilshunoslik fanlarining bog'liqligi haqidagi fikrlar B.V. Tomashevskiyning asarlarida ham uchraydi. U adabiyot ijodkorning og'zaki yoki yozma lingvistik faoliyatining bir qismi ekanligi, shu jihatdan ham adabiyot tilshunoslik bilan chambarchas bog'liqligi haqidagi fikrlarni o'rtaga tashlaydi. Shuningdek, o'z asarida badiiy nutq va so'zlashish nutqining (asarida "amaliy nutq" termini ham ishlatilgan) farqli jihatlarini yoritib bergan: "Badiiy nutq biz so'zlashayotgan amaldagi nutqning badiiy qurilgan shaklidir. Tilshunoslik nutqning boshqa turlari singari badiiy nutqni ham o'rganadi" [7; 28]. Tilshunos olim lingvopoetikaning bo'limlari hisoblangan poetik sintaksis, poetik leksika, poetik evfoniya, poetik stilistika, poetik semantika muammolari yuzasidan o'z qarashlarini bayon etgan. She'r va nasrning ifoda usullari lingvistik jihatdan farqlanishi, she'ning ko'proq ritmikligi, she'riy tilning metrik tamoyillari xususida ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tgan [7; 113].

Shu jumladan, badiiy asar tilini o'rganishda lingvistik tahlilning yetakchilik qilishi yuzasidan olim G.O. Vinokurning fikrlari e'tiborga molikdir: "Badiiy tilning lingvistik funksiya bajarish jihatidan asosiy xususiyati shundan iboratki, tovushlar yordamida tushunilgan mazmun ayni mazmunni emas, balki shakl orqali ifodalangan ichki mazmunni yuzaga chiqarish uchun xizmat qiladi" [8; 28]. Tilshunos olim adabiy til va badiiy adabiyot tilini o'rganishga xizmat qiluvchi tushunchalar atrofida yuzaga kelgan chalkashliklarni bartaraf etishga urinib "Adabiyot tili va adabiy til" maqolasini yozdi. Badiiy asar tilidagi so'zlarga ikki xil munosabat mavjud bo'lib, ular: 1) termin sifatida; 2) obraz, timsol sifatidagi qarashlar ekanligini aytadi va bu masalani "She'riyat va fan" maqolasi orqali yoritishga harakat qiladi. Bu fan "poetik tilshunoslik" deb nomlanib, badiiy tilning umumiy filologik tabiatiga e'tibor bermay turib, uning hech bir tomonini ilmiy jihatdan o'rganib bo'lmasligini ta'kidlaydi.

Rus tilshunosligida R.A. Budagov turli yozuvchilarning tili va uslubi bo'yicha ko'plab tadqiqotlar amalga oshirgan. Olimning "Писатели о языке и язык писателей" kitobi jahonning bir nechta taniqli ijodkorlarining tili va uslubini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Xususan, Dante, Servantes, Pushkin, Gogol, Gorkiy kabi mumtoz

soʻz ustalarining tili va uslubi tahlil qilingan. R.A. Budagov "Turli yozma matnlarda tilning vazifasi ham shunga mos ravishda oʻzgaradi" [9; 233] singari fikrlari orqali badiiy adabiyot tilining vazifalari, boshqa til uslublaridan farqlarini ochib bergan.

Filologiya uchun muhim boʻlgan ushbu tadqiqotlarni amalga oshirish koʻplab zamonaviy olimlarning asarlarida, shu jumladan, O.S.Axmanova rahbarligida Moskva davlat universitetining filologiya fakulteti ingliz tilshunosligi kafedrasida jamoasining tadqiqotlarida davom etdi. XX asrning mashhur rus olimlari – O.S. Axmanova va uning shogirdlari V.Y. Zadornova, A.A. Lipgartlar oʻz asarlarida badiiy asarni lingvopoetik jihatdan tahlil qilishga eʼtibor qaratdilar. Ular uzoq vaqt olib borgan tadqiqotlar natijasida lingvopoetika sekin-asta rivojlana boshladi va tilshunoslik, adabiyotshunoslik fanlari asosidagi yangi soha lingvopoetika shakllandi. Tilshunoslikda lingvopoetikaning yangi alohida soha boʻlib shakllanishida yuqoridagi olimlarning xizmatlari beqiyosdir.

Lingvopoetik tahlil metodologiyasi va ogʻzaki badiiy ijod asarlarini lingvistik-stilistik tavsifda oʻrganishning ushbu turi oʻrtasidagi farq masalasi V.Y. Zadornovaning doktorlik dissertatsiyasining dastlabki ikki bobida koʻrib chiqiladi. V.Y. Zadornova lingvistik-stilistik tadqiqotlarning koʻplab yoʻnalishlarini koʻrib chiqadi, ular asosida lingvopoetik tahlilning asosiy tamoyillarini aniqlash mumkin boʻladi. Tilshunos olimaning taʼrifiga koʻra, "filologiyaning alohida boʻlimi sifatida lingvopoetikaning predmeti – bu badiiy asarda qoʻllaniladigan lingvistik vositalarning yigʻindisi boʻlib, ular yordamida yozuvchi oʻz gʻoyasini yuzaga chiqarish uchun zarur boʻlgan estetik taʼsirni taʼminlaydi" [11; 7]. Shuningdek, matnni lingvopoetik jihatdan oʻrganishda lingvistik hamda stilistik vositalarni shunchaki aniqlabgina qolmay, ular orqali yuzaga chiqqan badiiy asarning estetik taʼsirini tushunish zarur ekanligini keltirib oʻtadi. Ushbu soha yuzasidan bildirilgan V.V. Vinogradov, B.V. Tomashevskiy, L.V. Shcherba kabi olimlarning fikrlariga toʻxtalib, ushbu turdagi tahlil namunalari ularning asarlarida uchrashini aytadi. Shu bilan birga, V.Y. Zadornova "...badiiy asarlarning soni va xilma-xilligi shunchalik koʻpki, bu yerda umumlashma qilish nihoyatda qiyin. Masalan, Pushkin va Xlebnikov, Dikens va Joys uchun qandaydir yagona "lingvopoetik tahlil usuli" haqida gapirish mumkinmi? Mumkin emas" [12] degan fikri orqali har bir ijodkorning badiiy asari oʻziga xos poetik talqin talab qilishi haqidagi qimmatli fikrlarni bildiradi. Lingvopoetika sohasi yuzasidan muhim fikrlarni oʻrtaga tashlab, uning alohida filologik fan sifatida ildiz otishiga oʻzining koʻplab asarlari bilan hissa qoʻshgan V.Y. Zadornova lingvopoetika sohasining asosiy mohiyati, maqsadini aniq ifodalashga harakat qilgan.

Lingvopoetika masalalarini chuqur yoritib, tahlil qilish professor A.A. Lipgartning ishlari bilan bogʻliq. Uning fikricha, "Lingvopoetika filologiyaning bir boʻlimi boʻlib, unda badiiy matnda qoʻllanilgan, stilistik jihatdan belgilangan til birliklari, ularning vazifalari va gʻoyaviy-badiiy mazmunni yetkazish va estetik taʼsir hosil qilishdagi ahamiyati masalasi bilan bogʻliq holda tadqiq etiladi" [10; 35-37]. Lipgartning bu soha rivoji uchun hissa qoʻshgan yirik izlanishlaridan biri "Lingvopoetika asoslari" nomli kitobida oʻz aksini topgan. Asarda olim oʻzidan avvalgi tilshunos olimlarning lingvopoetika yuzasidan bildirgan fikrlari va amalga oshirgan tadqiqotlarini tahlil qilish bilan birga lingvistik poetika, lingvistik stilistika, adabiyotshunoslik fanlarining bogʻliqligi, oʻrganish davomida yuzaga keluvchi muammolar xususida ham fikrlarini bayon etgan. Shuningdek, Lipgart lingvopoetikaning adabiyotshunoslikning boʻlimlari hisoblangan adabiyot tarixi, adabiyot nazariyasi, adabiy tanqid bilan aloqadorlik tomonlarini yoritib berishga harakat qilgan. Uning fikricha, badiiy asarning adabiy tur jihatidan farqlanishi, qaysi davrda yuzaga kelganligi hamda qaysi yoʻnalishda yozilganligi uning lingvopoetik tahliliga ham taʼsir qiladi. Darhaqiqat, uning fikrlari isbotini lirik, epik, dramatik turlarda qoʻllangan lingvistik birliklarning farqlanishi jihatidan ham koʻrishimiz mumkin. A.A. Lipgartning lingvopoetik izlanishlar uchun usul va vositalarni yetarlicha yoritib berish xizmati orqali lingvopoetika sohasi keng ildiz yoya boshladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, badiiy adabiyot tilini oʻrganish, tahlil qilish koʻpdan buyon jahon tilshunoslar va adabiyotshunos olimlarini qiziqtirib kelmoqda. Chunki muayyan tilning rivojlanishi, taraqqiy etishida badiiy adabiyot tilining ahamiyati katta hisoblanadi. Ayni shu jihatdan lingvopoetika sohasining rivojlanishi tilshunos olimlar zimmasidagi ulkan vazifalardan biridir.

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ИСТОРИЯ ВОЗНИКНОВЕНИЯ ОПТАТИВНЫХ ПРЕДЛОЖЕНИЙ

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Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada tilshunoslikda "optativlik" atamasining kelib chiqish tarixi yoritilgan. Muallif taniqli olimlarning optativ takliflar haqidagi fikrlari tahlil qilib, "optativlik" ta'riflaridagi nomuvofiqlik uning grammatik va pragmatik jihatlari bilan bog'likligini e'tirof etadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *optativ, istak, xohish, tilak, xohish-istak, lingvistik kategoriya, agar bo'lsa, koshki, affiks "SA" bilan.*

История термина «оптативность» восходит к древней истории и латинской основе. Если рассмотреть с точки зрения значения термина, то даются одинаковые определения «оптативность» в лингвистических и энциклопедических словарях.

В Словаре лингвистических терминов Т.В. Жеребило дается следующее определение термина: «ОПТАТИВ. 1. Желательное действие (в грамматике). 2. Наклонение, обозначающее переход от выражения желания субъекта к выражению желания говорящего. Одно из самых распространенных в языках мира наклонений, засвидетельствованное, в частности, в санскрите и древнегреческом» [5; 237].

В Толковом словаре современного русского языка значение слово: «ЖЕЛАНИЕ – внутреннее влечение, стремление к осуществлению чего-нибудь, обладанию чем-нибудь. Иметь желание (или желать). Гореть желанием» [11; 137].

Обратимся к переводческому словарю: «Optatio, / желание, пожелание; Opto 1. выбирать; желать, стремиться, 2. желанный, приятный» [7; 224].

Данный анализ показывает, что термин «оптатив» является основой желательного наклонения и вбирает в себя совокупность категорий модальности, тем самым даёт обоснование что «оптатив» можно считать, как языковую категорию.

Несмотря на терминологический разноречивой суть понятия одинакова.

Языковая категория – это группа языковых единиц, обобщенных с единым признаком или явлением. Нельзя не согласиться с утверждением А.Алтыбаевой о том, что «оптативные

предложения – это желательные предложения, а оптативная лексика – желательная лексика» – автор предлагает использовать термин: «оптативный в качестве абсолютного синонима понятия желательный» [2; 122]. В сопоставительной типологии можно использовать как абсолютного синонима: «оптативные предложения» (существующие в русской грамматике) – «istak gaplar» (существующие в узбекской грамматике); «оптативная лексика» – «Xohish-istak leksikasi» (не существующие в узбекской грамматике); желательное наклонение (в русской грамматике в некоторых учебниках включены / не включены) – «Istak mayli» (разграничив от «Buyruq-istak mayli»).

«Одной из разновидностей оптативных значений это – желание» [1; 352]. Аристотель утверждал, что кому присуще ощущение, тому присуща также способность испытывать удовольствие и печаль, приятное и тягостное, а кому это присуще, тому присуще желание: ведь желание есть стремление к приятному [12; 125]. Он сравнивал желание с голодом и жаждой. У Е.В.Алтабаевой на этот счет, такое утверждение: «Наличие разных предметов стремления позволяет Аристотелю считать желание (стремление) движущим началом всякого действия, развития» [2, 42].

В процессе можно заметить, что желание – это не просто стремление или намерение, а развитие с исходным значением оптативности в ирреальном плане модальности.

Объектом рассмотрения являются оптативные предложения (ОП) с грамматически выраженной желательностью. Реализуется при помощи одного из грамматических средств, в данном случае выступает ядром ОП как частица бы.

По словам Н.А. Зубарева, считает, что семантическое осложнение желательности в плане желания, мечтания, интенсивного желания, ограниченного желания реализуется только при обязательном условии введения в ОП сочетаний с частицами только бы, лишь бы, вот бы, хоть бы и др., модифицирующая частица бы, занимает препозицию по отношению к бы – это определяет частицу бы как желательность действия, а при помощи частиц только, лишь, вот, хоть усиливается ограничительно-выделительное или ограничительно-уступительное значение, распространяющееся на то или иное слово [6; 84].

Автор опирается, что все оптативные лексемы со значением желания и мечтания могут реализоваться с помощью сочетаниями частицами только бы, лишь бы, вот бы, хоть бы при этом частица бы, может быть индикатором определения оптативного предложения, а частица только, лишь, вот, хоть – она выступает в роли усилителя оптативности.

К началу 20 века уделялось большое внимание и интерес исследованию оптативных предложений. Освещение проблемы изучению оптативности впервые нашло отражение чехословацким лингвистом Р.Мразеком (1958) [14]. Автор исследовал оптативные предложения исходят из модально-коммуникативной конструкций.

Достоинством рассмотренного подхода об оптативности является следующие труды К.А. Тимофеева, Н.И. Сидоровой, Р.А. Бураловой, Л.Ф. Бердника, О.Б. Шестаковой, Е.В.Алтабаевой, Р.Д.Салимова [10; 9; 4; 3; 13; 2; 8] и др.

Сущность вышеизложенного сводится к следующему: был исследован термин оптативность и его происхождение, а также даны определение к понятиям «оптатив»; «оптативный»; «оптативность»; «оптативная единица»; «оптативная лексика»; «категория оптативности».

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II. TIL O'QITISH MUAMMOLARI VA ULARNING YANGI PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDAGI YECHIMLARI SHU'BASI

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ, ПРИНЦИПЫ И ПРИЁМЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ РУССКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ КАК ИНОСТРАННОМУ УЗБЕКСКИХ СТУДЕНТОВ ТЕХНИЧЕСКИХ ВУЗОВ

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Аннотация. Ушбу мақола муаллифи томонидан олий таълим муассасалари нофилологик йўналишларида ўқийётган ўзбек тилли талабалар учун рус тилини қизиқарли ва жадал ўргатиш методикаси ишлаб чиқилган. Шунингдек, Ўзбекистонда рус тилини ўрганиш истагида бўлган, катта ёшли аҳоли, жумладан, ўзбек талабаларига ушбу хорижий тилни ўзбек тили билан қийслаб жадал ўргатиш мақсадида "Рус тилини она тилим – ўзбек тили билан ўрганиш: осон ва завқли" инновациявий ўқув дастури ҳам тайёрланган.

Калит сўзлар: ўзбек тили билан қийслаб ўқитиш жадал методикаси, оғзаки нутқ мулоқоти, англа – англлат, уялма-уялтирма, ўйғот яхши таассурот, ёдда қолар умрбод.

Автором данной статьи разработана занимательная методика интенсивного обучения русскому языку «Русский язык с родным узбекским: интересно и легко» с целью ускоренного обучения взрослого населения, в том числе студентов технических вузов Узбекистана, начинающих изучать русский язык [1; 15, 2; 244].

Структура учебной программы соответствует как общепринятым, так инновационным методическим принципам и приёмам, на которых строится современная методика обучения русскому языку как иностранному:

– занимательность и доступность изложения материалов сопоставительного обучения, запоминающее яркое объяснение особенностей и типичных закономерностей русского и узбекского языков;

– сознательно-коммуникативная и профессионально-практическая направленность обучения;

– личностно-ориентированный подход;

– учёт языка учащихся;

– комплексное овладение видами речевой деятельности путем сопоставления их узбекскими аналогами;

– осмысленность постановки и разработки целей и задач курса, мотиваций обучения самими учащимися путём последовательного и систематического внедрения инновационных методических приёмов [4, с. 70].

Актуальность темы. В узбекском языкознании важным фактором является создание новых методов ускоренного обучения русскому языку как иностранному (РКИ), исходя из его специфических национальных, исторических особенностей. Обоснованно считается необходимым проводить научно-теоретические исследования в области преподавания иностранных языков, опираясь на различные и отличные друг от друга подходы, сравнительные, интенсивно-динамические, интерактивные, инновационные, занимательно-ориентированные методы и методики, которые не отрицают, а дополняют друг друга.

В частности, исследование языковых и речевых норм английского, испанского, арабского, русского, французского и китайского языков, имеющих официальный рабочий статус Организации Объединенных Наций, а также создание и внедрение новых эффективных методов обучения этим языкам в Узбекистане представляет особую актуальность. В особенности русский язык как иностранный стремительно развивает информационные технологии и ускоряет модернизацию не только социальной, но и экономической сферы в эпоху глобализации.

В мировом языкознании учитывается не только лексико-семантический состав слов конкретного языка, но и рассматривается связь между употреблением этих слов в речи конкретного субъекта, их прагматическое содержание, оценочная связь и национально-культурные аспекты, а также сравнительное изучение их эквивалентов на другом языке, их общих и отличительных черт, в том числе изучение проблем адекватности в монографическом объеме, является одним из наиболее актуальных вопросов [3; 189].

В частности, формирование различных структур знания, посредством концептуализации языка и мышления, формирования значения слова, проблем семантических отношений лексических единиц и их сравнительного изучения на примере двух языков имеет большое научное и практическое значение. В целях обеспечения эффективности практического использования языковых средств народами разных национальностей проводятся научные исследования методов сравнительного изучения и преподавания иностранных языков, с учетом природы национального языка, а также создание инновационных методов, основанных на научных исследованиях, поставлены на повестку дня, как один из актуальных вопросов современного языкознания.

С обретением независимости возросло значение и актуальность национально-культурных факторов, вопросы расширения масштабов и повышения престижа многих исследований в различных областях науки были поставлены на первое место, созданы новые возможности для создания таких исследований. Роль и положение русского языка в мире, в особенности в странах, входящих в Содружество Независимых Государств (СНГ), в том числе в Республике Узбекистан, а также всесторонне развивающееся сотрудничество между Узбекистаном и Россией и многие подобные факторы обучения русскому языку как иностранному основаны на создании новых эффективных методов и приёмов. Данная проблема доказывает актуальность перед учеными, исследователями и опытными педагогами.

С этой точки зрения, в данной научной работе, подготовленной на основе многолетнего опыта, научных исследований и наблюдений в области педагогики и методики преподавания русского языка, рассматриваются современные тенденции обучения русскому узбекских студентов в сопоставлении с их родным языком, преподавание русского языка по инновационной методике.

Результатом данного исследования, а также многогранного комплексного анализа процесса преподавания и обучения, включающего целесообразное использование большого количества материалов, собранных для практических занятий и самостоятельных рабочих заданий, обширное изучение функционально-стилистических и лексико-семантические особенности выбранных текстов является актуальностью работы и доказывает ее значимость.

Уровень изученности проблемы. Комплексный анализ ряда научной и учебно-методической литературы по данной теме показывает, что решение проблемы эффективного обучения иностранным языкам во многом зависит от создания новой, инновационной методики.

Исходя из этого, при создании новой методики обучения иностранным языкам, во-первых, важно эффективно использовать существующие, проверенные на практике ресурсы обучения

иностранным языкам, обращать внимание на их эффективность; во-вторых, важно создать методику, разумно использующую родной язык студентами при обучении иностранным языкам, объясняющую студентам, что законы внутреннего развития узбекского языка отличаются от законов развития изучаемого русского языка в простой, интересной и доступной форме.

Вопрос обучения иностранным языкам привлекал постоянное внимание ученых. Языковые единицы, в том числе слова, словосочетания, предложения, тексты, смысловая целостность каждой из этих единиц зависит от лексико-семантической структуры каждой из этих единиц, а также их лексического окружения в контексте, и степени активизации смысловых граней. Постоянство и необходимость в речи, парадигматическая связь в значениях этих единиц русского и узбекского языков в сопоставлении - что они одинаковы с точки зрения денотативного значения, но различное по коннотативному значению и особенностям происхождения (коннотации, дополнительные значения, национальный колорит и т. д.) находит отражение в исследованиях проблем русского и узбекского языкознаний [3, с.187].

Однако результаты этих исследований недостаточно используются в области методики преподавания иностранного языка, совершенствования методов и методик, разработки новых, в том числе в преподавании русского языка как иностранного методом сравнения и сопоставления, людям, родным языком которых является узбекский, следовательно, исследования в этом направлении ведутся до сих пор с публикациями лишь в объеме статьи [1; 15, 2; 244].

Этот чрезвычайно актуальный вопрос – вопрос сопоставительной методики обучения узбеков русскому языку как иностранному в сопоставлении с их родным языком не исследовался в рамках специальной диссертации как крупная научная работа монографического плана. В частности, не изучен в целом ряд вопросов, связанных с внедрением методики комплексного анализа у студентов, изучающих русский язык как иностранный в сфере технического образования, сравнивая его с их родным языком, необходимо изучение данной темы по лингвистике в рамках диссертационного исследования [7; 4].

Научная новизна исследования. Обучение русскому языку студентов нефилологических специальностей в сопоставлении с их родным узбекским языком имеет приоритетное значение в сфере преподавания иностранных языков, в особенности русского языка для узбекоязычных студентов, и эксперименты, проводимые в направлении данной темы, на основе многолетнего опыта, полученного в ходе научных наблюдений и практических занятий, а также разработанной, новой нетрадиционной интегрированной (комплексной) методики;

при сравнении русского языка с родным языком (узбекским языком) у студентов, обучающихся по нефилологическим специальностям, на основе научного анализа полученных новых результатов доказана эффективность процесса обучения и преподавания, основанного на многогранной комплексной методике;

специфические коммуникативно-прагматические аспекты взаимодействия языковых и неязыковых факторов раскрываются в речевой реализации собранного богатого фактического материала по теме на основе сравнительной комплексной методики;

Всесторонне анализируются в сравнительном аспекте лингвистические и речевые отношения между изучаемым языком (русским) и родным языком (узбекским) в процессе изучения языка, а также уникальные лексико-семантические, функционально-стилистические и лингвокультурные особенности этих единиц (тонкости смысла, эмоциональная окраска и т. д.), и эти особенности оказались важным фактором обеспечения эффективности процесса изучения языка [5, с.49];

В результате изучения множества текстов было выбрано соответствие выбранных текстов теме исследования и учебному направлению учащихся, включая процесс урока и упражнения, а также тексты для самостоятельной работы. Преимущества обучения студентов академическому (научному) и профессионально-техническому общению, академическому письму посредством соответствующих текстов, реализации посредством новых принципов, методов и приемов (принципов) научно обоснованы и доказаны достаточными фактами.

Своеобразие инновационной занимательной методики интенсивного обучения русской речи

студентов нефилологических специальностей технических вузов Узбекистана, начинающих изучать русский язык после окончания средней общеобразовательной школы состоит в следующем.

Структура учебной программы соответствует как общепринятым, так инновационным методическим принципам и приёмам, на которых строится современная методика обучения русскому языку как иностранному:

- занимательность и доступность изложения материалов сопоставительного обучения, запоминающее яркое объяснение особенностей и типичных закономерностей русского и узбекского языков;

- сознательно-коммуникативная и профессионально-практическая направленность обучения;

- комплексное овладение видами речевой деятельности путем сопоставления их узбекскими аналогами;

- осмысленность постановки и разработки целей и задач курса, мотиваций обучения самими учащимися путём последовательного и систематического внедрения инновационных методических приёмов. Например, таких как:

англа – англат (осмысли и мотивируй), уялма – уялтирма (не стыди и не стыдись), гапир-гапиртир (заговори и продолжай говорить), сўз ёдла – дарров қўлла (выучил слова – используй-здорово!), қизиқтир – қизишма (не интересно – не отчаивайся), гапирдинг – ютдинг, гапирмадинг – унутдинг (заговорил – победил, молчишь – всё забудешь), ишон- ишонтир- жилмайиб қувонтир (убедись и убедил, улыбнись и победи), Учись – урган, учи – ургат // так русский выучить я рад и т.д.

Отличительной особенностью каждого из этих оригинальных методических приёмов, состоящих из комплекса простых, но обязательных (принципиальных) выполнению в процессе обучения правил, является то, что они непринужденно запоминаются благодаря тому, что в тщательно, креативно творчески обдуманном, простом и лаконичном (как в крылатых фразах) самом названии (англа-англат, уялма-уялтирма, урган-ургат и т.п.) этих правил заложена основная идея, суть, значение. Названия этих методических приёмов, принципов-правил в силу своей ёмкостью, образностью, простоте в сознании учащихся вызывает неизгладимое впечатление и интерес [1, с. 15; 2, с. 244; 4, с. 70].

К сожалению, названия этих методических приёмов и принципов очень трудно перевести адекватно точно и складно с узбекского языка на иностранный. Например, одно из принципиальных правил "Сўз ёдла – дарров қўлла" (буквально: "выучил слова – тут же примени) основано на закономерностях запоминания вещей (в данном случае на закономерности запоминания новых русских слов), на таких как: хорошо и быстро запоминается то, что интересно, впечатляет. Правило "Сўз ёдла – дарров қўлла" отличаясь благозвучием на узбекском – красиво, образно, рифмованно. Следуя принципам запоминания чтобы сохранить адекватность и благозвучие этой фразы ("Сўз ёдла – дарров қўлла") на русский её можно перевести примерно так: "Интересно, впечатлило – легко запомнить. Очень мило".

По психологии известно, что непосредственно запоминается легко и на долго то, что воздействует на человека и оказывает впечатление (положительное или отрицательное), а также то, что понятно и представляет интерес. Преподаватель всегда должен об этом помнить и знать эти три вещи: объяснять интересно, понятно и впечатляюще: "Впечатлило, всё понятно – интересно и приятно".

Поэтому не надо объяснять правило на строгом, сложном, научном языке. То, что скучно, не понятно и неинтересно очень трудно запоминается. В таком случае приходится напрягаться и заставлять себя учить. А учащиеся не любят, когда их принуждают. Поэтому к формулировке и объяснениям правил надо подходить творчески, креативно, в том числе подача правила запоминания учащимся должно быть лаконичным, интересным, при возможности художественно-образно воспринимаемым. Например, таким четверостишием, как:

Интересно и понятно, //Впечатлило. – Как приятно!

Или: Интересно, впечатлило// Все понятно – очень мило!

Рифмованные, непринуждающиеся правила запоминаются легко и на долго.

Методический приём-правило: "Уялма-уялтирма" (буквально: не стыдись и не стыди),

“Қўрқма-қўрқитма” (буквально: не страшись и не пугай) помогает учащимся преодолеть языковой барьер. В психологии и по опыту известно, что чувства стыда, смущения, боязни быть посмешищем перед другими мешают учить иностранные языки. Вышеперечисленные методические приёмы помогают преодолеть эти негативные эмоции у учащихся и вселяют надежду и уверенность в том, что они успешно выучат иностранный (в данном случае русский) язык.

Методический приём “Англа-англат” (буквально: “осмысли и дай осмыслить”) формирует психологическую мотивацию, интерес к изучению русского языка. Как известно, без мотивации учить языки – это тяжкий, почти бесполезный труд. При помощи “Англа-англат” – “Осознай и мотивируй”, этого замечательного принципа человеческого мышления, направляющего его на осмысление и осознание целей и задач курса по русскому языку, благодаря которому изучение русского языка становится мотивированным, привлекательным, необходимым. Учащиеся получают полные, исчерпывающие ответы на такие вопросы, как, например, «Зачем нужен им русский язык, если он неродной?», «С какой целью введен курс русского языка на факультете металлургии, горного дела или горной электромеханики?» и у них формируется мотивация и огромное желание выучить этот, нужный для них, русский язык.

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ВИКИ-ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКОЙ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston umumta'lim maktab o'quvchilariga ingliz tilini o'qitishda Viki texnologiyasini qo'llash muammosi o'rganilgan bo'lib, ushbu texnologiya maktab o'quvchilarining gapirish, o'qish va yozish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga yordam berishi asoslangan.

Kalit so'zlar: maktab o'quvchilari, Viki texnologiya, o'qish, gapirish, yozish.

Термин "вики" был заимствован из гавайского языка и означает "быстро". Данное значение оправданно отражает функцию этого сервиса, поскольку он обеспечивает быстрый доступ к материалам. По мнению П.В.Сысоева "вики-технология является одним из видов сервисов Веб 2.0, позволяющий одному человеку или группе людей, находящихся на расстоянии друг от друга, работать над созданием единого документа, внося в него изменения и дополнения" [1]. Вики – это страница для создания совместного документа, которая позволяет всем зарегистрированным пользователям создавать совместные письменные работы и редактировать их. При этом, начальная версия этой странички сохраняется, и пользователь может просмотреть все внесенные изменения в документ или вернуться на исходную версию документа.

Как отмечает Селами Айдин [2], вики – технология позволяет овладеть языком посредством совместного обучения, а учителям выступать в роли модераторов. Она способствует автономному обучению через сотрудничество и служит мотивационным признаком при обучении.

При обучении английскому языку, как отмечает Д.О. Свиридов, вики-технология в интеграции с современными педагогическими технологиями (обучения в сотрудничестве и проектная деятельность) позволяет развивать коммуникативные навыки – чтение, письмо. Если при создании контента учащиеся сами разрабатывают материал, т.е. пишут, читают, то при редактировании материала учащиеся формируют грамматические навыки – проверяют строй предложений, согласование времен, употребление лексических единиц. Формирование грамматических навыков как продуктивных, так и рецептивных, по мнению Д.О. Свиридова [3], является ещё одним из достоинств вики-технологии.

Е.Д. Кошляева [4] отмечает, что вики-технология в интеграции с обучением в сотрудничестве и проектной деятельностью способствует формированию социокультурной компетенции.

Рассматривая дидактические свойства вики-технологии в обучении английскому языку, мы выделяем следующее:

Многоавторство. Контент вики создаётся совместно с участием многих зарегистрированных пользователей. Каждый зарегистрированный пользователь имеет возможность создавать, дополнять, редактировать или удалять материал.

Мультимедийность. Пользователи вики могут размещать материал в различных форматах. Размещение аудио-, видео-, текстового материала позволяет формировать такие виды речевой деятельности, как аудирование и чтение.

Гипертекстовая структура. Контент вики может включать гиперссылки на другие ресурсы сети Интернет.

Публичность. Материалы, опубликованные в вики, могут быть доступны всем пользователям сети Интернет, независимо от их местонахождения. Это свойство позволяет использовать вики как в классное, так и во внеклассное время.

Таблица 1.

**Дидактические свойства и методические функции вики-технологии в формировании
англоязычной речевой компетенции школьников**

Дидактические свойства вики-технологии	Методические функции вики-технологии
Многоавторство	Совместная публикация материала в вики, формирующая навыки чтения и письма. Умения оценивать и редактировать опубликованный материал одноклассников.
Мультимедийность	Публикация материалов на основе аудио, видео материалов, схем, текстов, график, картинок, анимаций, служащих обогащению языкового материала.
Гипертекстовая структура	Умение оценивать материалы сети Интернет и извлекать из них необходимую информацию. Создавать совместные письменные работы, ссылаясь на различные источники сети Интернет.
Публичность	Ответственность за размещенные материалы, возможность работы в классное и во внеклассное время. Возможность организации сетевого взаимодействия участников учебного процесса

В образовательном Веб пространстве вики позволяют формировать англоязычную речевую компетенцию, представленную в следующей таблице.

Таблица 2.

Англоязычная речевая компетенция школьников, развиваемая на основе вики

Говорение	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • излагать основное содержание; • аргументировать свою точку зрения; • делать выводы; • описывать и излагать факты; • подробно описывать события; • уметь уточнять детали интересующей информации.
Чтение	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • извлекать необходимую информацию; • выделять главную информацию от второстепенной; • выражать свое отношение к прочитанному материалу; • анализировать прочитанный материал; • обобщать прочитанный материал из различных источников сети Интернет.
Письмо	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • писать короткие письма и сообщения; • описывать события, факты, планы на будущее; • вносить дополнения в опубликованный материал; • редактировать опубликованный материал; • аргументировать свою точку зрения; • писать поздравления и пожелания; • заполнять анкеты; • собирать, классифицировать, обобщать информацию, используя различные источники сети Интернет и делать выводы; • писать тексты, описывающие знаменитые факты и события стран родного и изучаемого языков.

Одним из ярких проявлений вики-технологии является Википедия, которая является коллективной работой многих пользователей сети Интернет. Википедия – это универсальная, многоязычная Интернет энциклопедия, контент которого создаётся пользователями сети Интернет. Достоверность опубликованной информации в Википедии остается спорным, так как каждый пользователь сети имеет возможность дополнить, отредактировать, удалить контент. В учебных целях Википедия может быть использована в качестве информационного ресурса для развития навыков чтения.

Рисунок 3. Страница Википедии

Для формирования навыков письменной речи существуют такие бесплатные вики-сервисы, как Pbworks (www.pbworks.com), MediaWiki (www.mediawiki.com), Wikihost (www.wikihost.org).

Рассматривая возможности вики-технологии, можно подчеркнуть, что в процессе обучения английскому языку они позволяют учащимся:

- создавать совместные авторские письменные работы и публиковать их в сети Интернет;
- выступать в роли редакторов и экспертов в определенной области;
- отслеживать вносимые изменения и поправки к опубликованным материалам;
- многократно редактировать и шлифовать опубликованный материал и обладают:
- открытостью к редактированию всеми пользователями сети Интернет;
- простотой в использовании и возможностью ссылки на другие источники сети Интернет с аутентичной информацией.

Таким образом, вики-технологии, являясь одним из сервисов Веб 2.0, позволяют формировать и развивать навыки чтения, письма, говорения, а также способствуют созданию позитивной мотивации при изучении английского языка.

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ONA TILI DARSLARIDA OMONIMLAR MAVZUSINI O'RGANISH

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассмотрен вопрос изучения темы омонимов в 5 классе, приведены рекомендации по разъяснению отличий омонимов от полисемантических слов с учётом возраста учащихся.

Ключевые слова: омонимы, синонимы, туюг, аския, полисемия, имя существительное, глагол, имя прилагательное, словосочетание, словарный запас.

Omonimlar umumta'lim maktablarining 5-sinfida o'rganiladigan mavzudir. Bu davrda o'quvchilar ancha mustaqil fikrlaydigan, so'z ma'nolarini idrok etadigan yoshda bo'ladilar. Omonimlar, ularning nutqdagi ahamiyatini o'rganish o'quvchilar uchun juda qiziqarli bo'lib, bu mavzuni o'zlashtirishda yuqori samaradorlikka erishish uchun quyidagi tavsiyalar o'rinni deb hisoblaymiz.

Avvalo, 5-sinf o'quvchilari bilan ishlashda asosiy e'tiborni qoidalarga emas, balki amaliyotga qaratish lozim. Ularning diqqatiga doskadagi bir nechta so'z taqdim etiladi (bu so'zlarning ayrimlari shakldoshlariga

ega, ba'zilari esa ega emas bo'lishi kerak) va o'quvchilardan bu so'zlarning ma'nosi so'raladi. Masalan, (1) to'p, (2) kitob, (3) tut, (4) sut, (5) qish, (6) bosh, (7) to'r, (8) qush. Javoblar butun jamoa bilan tahlil qilinadi. 2, 4, 5, 6, 8- so'zlarda bolalarning javobi bir xil bo'lishi tabiiy. Qolgan so'zlardagi bolalarning tushunchasi bir-biridan farqlanishi mumkin. Masalan, 1-javobda bir o'quvchi ko'ptokni tushungan bo'lsa, ikkinchisi zambarakni idrok etgan bo'lishi mumkin. Javob berish jarayonida 3-so'zda kimdir rezavor mevani, yana kimdir shu so'z bilan ifodalanuvchi harakatni; 7-so'zda stol (dasturxon, umuman, o'tiralidigan joy)ning yuqori qismi (poygakning qarshisi) yoki baliqchilarning baliq tutish uchun moslamasini anglagani oydinlashadi. Ba'zi o'quvchilar esa so'zning ham u, ham bu ma'nosini tushunishi mumkin. Har bir javob asoslangach, bu vaziyatda hammaning javobi to'g'ri ekanligi oydinlashadi. Shundan so'ng darsning nazariy qismiga o'tiladi, ya'ni omonim so'zlarga ta'rif beriladi: "Aytilishi va yozilishi bir xil bo'lib, turli atash ma'nolarini bildirgan so'zlarga omonim so'zlar deyiladi. Ular shakldosh so'zlar deb ham yuritiladi" [1; 115].

Qoida sharhlanib, o'quvchilarning o'zlariga shakldosh so'zlar topish topshiriladi. O'quvchilar ko'p ma'noli so'zlar bilan shakldosh so'zlarni yaxshi farqlamasligi tabiiy. Shuning uchun har bir so'z tahlil qilinadi va doskaga ikki ustunning biriga ko'p ma'noli so'z, ikkinchisiga shakldosh so'z yozib boriladi. Buning natijasida o'quvchilar ko'p ma'noli so'zlarning omonimlardan farqini bilib oladilar. "Omonim so'zlar bir qarashda ko'p ma'noli so'zlarga o'xshab ketadi, ammo ularni farqlash kerak" [1; 115]. Jumladan, o'quvchilar ko'pincha ko'z sozini shakldosh birlik sifatida tushunishadi va misol tariqasida bir nechta birikmalarni keltirishadi: insonning ko'zi, derazaning ko'zi, uzukning ko'zi, yog'ochning ko'zi, buloqning ko'zi va h.k. [O'TIL II; 1014-1020]. Bu birikmalardagi ko'z so'zlarining bir-biriga ichki bog'liqligi tushuntiriladi. Ko'z ko'rish organi, inson yuzidagi eng nozik va eng chiroyli a'zo hisoblanadi. Yog'ochning ko'zi, ignaning ko'zi inson ko'zi bilan semantik aloqador bo'lib, shakliy bir xillikka ega. Buloqning ko'zi misolida esa suv chiqish manbasi sifatida ikki birlik o'rtasida bog'liqlik mavjud. Shu tarzda ko'z so'zining har bir ma'nosi sharhlangach, uning omonim emasligi, balki ko'p ma'noli so'z ekanligi ayon bo'ladi. Shakldosh so'zlar o'rtasida esa bunday aloqadorlik mavjud emas. Shu jihati bilan ular ko'p ma'noli (polisemantik) so'zlardan farqlanadi.

O'quvchilar e'tiboriga quyidagi rasmlar havola etiladi va ulardan qaysi predmetni anglatgan so'z shakldoshiga ega ekanligini ajratish topshiriladi:

Bu o'rinda o'quvchilarni guruhlarga bo'lib ishlash maqsadga muvofiqdir. Guruh vakillarining javoblaridan avval shakldoshlik ko'pincha ot va fe'l turkumlari o'rtasida yuzaga kelishini e'tiborga olib, so'zning bosh shakliga -moq qo'shimchasini qo'yib ko'rish tavsiya etiladi. Mana shunday usul bilan qor, shim, soch, tom, qo'y so'zlari ikki turkum doirasida shakldosh bo'la olishi kelib chiqadi. Bu so'zlar qatorida tom so'zi sifat turkumiga ham mansub bo'la oladi. Buni tom ma'no birikmasi misolida tushuntirish mumkin. Yana bir jihat: 1-rasmni bola qor parchasi deb sharhlashi mumkin. Qor so'zi ham, parcha so'zi ham shakldoshiga egaligini ham aytib o'tish mumkin (I. parcha – qism, bo'lak; II. parcha – to'qilgan qalin ipak mato) [O'TIL IV; 220].

Shakldosh so'zlar adabiyotimizda tuyuq deb ataluvchi she'riy janrga, shu birgan birga, zakiylar san'ati hisoblangan askiyaga asos bo'lgan. Bundan tashqari, shakldosh so'zlar vositasida turli so'z o'yinlari hosil qilish mumkin. Buning isboti sifatida darslikda berilgan to'rtlikni misol qilib keltirish mumkin:

Toshni kesa olmas pichoqning dami (1),

Pok tanga o'tmaydi saraton dami (2),

*Ilm va hunarga bag'ishla o'zni,
G'animat yoshlikning har o'tgan dami (3).*

Dam so'zining ma'nosini tushunish uchun ularni birikma holatida ko'rib chiqish lozim. Bu so'zining ma'nosini aniq ifodalash va bolada tasavvur uyg'otish maqsadida pichoqning dami, saraton dami, yoshlikning har o'tgan dami birikmalaridagi hokim qismning ma'nodoshini keltirish maqsadga muvofiqdir. Chunki o'quvchi birikmaning tobe qismi yordamida so'z ma'nosini idrok eta oladi. Shunga ko'ra, dam so'zining ma'nolari quyidagicha ekanligi anglashiladi:

1. **Dam** – asbobning kesadigan o'tkir tomoni, tig'i; tig'.
2. **Dam** – nafas, tin
3. **Dam** – bir nafaslik fursat, lahza, vaqt [O'TIL I; 754-756].

Shu o'rinda dam so'zining to'rtinchi, ya'ni chet, qirg'oq ma'nosi ham anglatiladi [O'TIL; 756].

Mustahkamlash mashqlarini bajarish bilan birga o'quvchilarga mustaqil ravishda omonimlarga misol topish topshirilishi mumkin. Omonim so'zlar ishtirokidagi gaplar tuzish ham mavzuni mustahkamlashga yordam beradi. Masalan, To'yga borsang, to'yib bor. Ushbu maqolda ot va fe'l turkumlari doirasida shakldosh bo'la oluvchi to'y so'zi sharhlanadi.

Demak, omonimlar mavzusini o'zlashtirish orqali:

- o'quvchilarning lug'at boyligi oshadi;
- shakldosh so'zlarning ko'p ma'noli so'zlardan farqini tushunib oladilar;
- adabiy asarlardan parcha keltirish asnosida fanlararo uzviy bog'liqlik ta'minlanadi;
- tilimizdagi so'zlar tarovati yana bir bor namoyon bo'ladi.

Foydalangan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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MAKTAB O'QUVCHILARIGA O'ZBEK TILI LUG'AT TARKIBINI O'RGATISHDA MA'NODOSH SO'ZLARNING O'RNINI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada maktab o'quvchilariga o'zbek tili lug'at tarkibini o'rgatishda ma'nodosh so'zlarning o'rnini haqida fikr yuritilgan. Maktabning ona tili darsliklaridan o'rin olgan sinonim so'zlar yuzasidan berilgan topshiriqlar haqida metodik tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan. Shu bilan bir qatorda sinonim so'zlarning o'ziga xos leksik-grammatik xususiyatlari xususida nazariy ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: sinonimik qator, uslubiy ma'no, kitobiy uslub, nutqiy sinonimlar graduonimiya, dominanta, leksik sath.

Dunyomizning eng mashhur donishmandlaridan biri, benazir ijodkor mavlono Jaloliddin Rumiy ta'kidlaganidek, "Qalb oynasining sof bo'lishi, xunukdan go'zalni ajrata olish uchun kerak"dir. Haqli ravishda ayta olamizki, ona tili darslari tilimizning grammatik xususiyatlarini o'rgatish bilan bir qatorda, inson qalb oynasini shaffof qilishga ham xizmat qiladi. Chunki til dil kaliti hisoblanadi. Nutqiy muloqotda so'zlarni to'g'ri qo'llay olish, ularning nozik ma'no qirralaridan o'rinli foydalana bilish donishmand bobomiz aytganlaridek, "xunukdan go'zalni ajrata olish" imkonini ham beradi.

O'quvchilarning ona tilimiz imkoniyatlaridan o'rinli va maqsadli foydalana olish malakasini shakllantirish, tilimizga kirib kelayotgan yangi so'zlarni o'zlashtirishlariga erishish va ularning lisoniy boyligini oshirish ona tili darslarini o'qitishdan ko'zlanadagan asosiy maqsadlar sirasiga kiradi.

Umumiy o'rta ta'limda leksikologiyani o'rganish jarayonida quyida sanab o'tilgan vazifalarni bajarish ko'zda tutiladi:

- * soʻzning oʻz va koʻchma maʼnolarini angʻlay olish;
- * soʻzning maʼno qirralarini farqlay olish;
- * soʻzning shakldoshlik imkoniyatlaridan foydalana olish;
- * soʻzdan ijtimoiy hayotning turli sohalarida toʻgʻri foydalanish;
- * nutqiy vaziyatdan kelib chiqib soʻzlarni toʻgʻri tanlash;
- * izohli lugʻatlar bilan ishlay olish koʻnikmalarini shakllantirish.

Shuni ham taʼkidlab oʻtish kerakki, umumiy oʻrta taʼlimda tilshunoslikning "Leksikologiya" boʻlimini izchil oʻqitish muhim taʼlimiy va tarbiyaviy ahamiyat kasb etadi. Bu boʻlim oʻquvchilarga oʻzbek tilining bir butun leksik tizimi haqida umumiy maʼlumotlarni bilib olish va ularni til fanining boshqa boʻlimlari bilan uzviy bogʻliqlikda oʻzlashtirish imkoniyatini beradi. Zotan, leksikologiyani oʻqitishdan maqsad oʻquvchilarning soʻz zaxirasini boyitish va bu zaxiradan oʻrinli, toʻgʻri foydalana olish koʻnikmasini shakllantirishdan iborat. Bu maqsadni amalga oshirishda esa maʼnodosh soʻzlar, yaʼni sinonimlarning oʻrni beqiyos. Zero, N.Mahmudov toʻgʻri eʼtirof etganiday: "Oʻzbek tili ana shunday qadimiy va rivojlangan boy tillardan biri sifatida salmoqli miqdordagi sinonimik munosabatlar asosida birlashgan yoki birlashadigan soʻz gavharlari zaxirasiga sohib tildir" [8; 5].

Maktabning ona tili darsliklaridan oʻrin olgan maʼnodosh soʻzlar yuzasidan berilgan topshiriqlar quyidagi talablar asosida tuzilgan:

- 1) berilgan soʻzlarning maʼnodoshlarini topish;
- 2) gapda yoki matnda ajratib koʻrsatilgan soʻzlarning maʼnodoshini topish;
- 3) gapdagi ayrim soʻzlarni maʼnodoshlari bilan almashtirish;
- 4) gapdagi nuqtalar oʻrniga maʼnodosh soʻzlar qatoridan mos keladiganini tanlash;
- 5) maʼnodoshlarning maʼnoviy jihatdan farqlarini tahlil qilish;
- 6) sinonimik qatordagi soʻzlarni ijobiy yoki salbiy boʻyoqli soʻzlarga ajratish.

Bolalarda, taxminan, 11-12 yoshdan mavhum fikrlash bosqichi boshlanadi. Bu jarayon 2 bosqichda sodir boʻlishi mumkin:

1. Oʻquvchi obyekt va hodisani koʻrmasdan turib fikr yuritishi va tushunchalar ishlab chiqishi mumkin.
2. Oʻquvchi ifodalalayotgan fikrga yoki oʻzi ifodalayotgan fikriga tanqidiy munosabat bildira boshlashi mumkin.

Mantiqiy fikrlash natijasida bolalar bu yoshda mavhum fikr yurita oladilar va fikrlarni umumlashtira boshlaydilar. Induktiv va deduktiv fikrlash usullaridan foydalanib idrok etgan mavhum tushunchalari yordamida bir holatdan ikkinchi holatga oʻta oladilar. Boshqacha aytganda, bu davrda bolalar endi soʻzlarning oʻz maʼnolari bilan bir qatorda ularning metaforik maʼnolarini ham oʻrganadilar va oʻz nutqlarida ulardan ongli ravishda foydalana oladilar [4].

Darhaqiqat, 6-sinf oʻquvchilarining maʼnodosh soʻzlar lugʻatini boyitishda yuqoridagi fikrga asoslanish mumkin.

6-sinf uchun moʻljallangan amaldagi ona tili darsligidagi maʼnodosh soʻzlar yuzasidan berilgan topshiriqlardan birida kasal, ranjimoq, sogʻaymoq, itoat, amir, dam olmoq, jazm qilmoq [5] kabi soʻzlarning sinonimlarini topish soʻraladi.

Topshiriqni bajarish jarayonida oʻquvchilarning induktiv fikrlash qobiliyatlari muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Shu oʻrinda topshiriqdagi kasal soʻzining maʼnodoshlari haqida fikr yuritimiz.

"Kasal soʻzi betob, notob, bemor, nosogʻ, xasta, ogʻriq soʻzlari bilan sinonim boʻladi. Organizmning normal faoliyati buzilgan, sogʻning aksi.

Kasal keng tushunchaga ega. U odamga, hayvon yoki boshqa jonivorlarga, hatto jonsiz narsalarga nisbatan ham qoʻllanaveradi. Bu soʻz "organizm faoliyatining vaqtincha buzilgan"ligini ifodalash uchun ham, shuningdek, umuman, "sogʻning aksi" maʼnosida ham qoʻllanaveradi. Betob, notob, bemor, xasta odamga nisbatangina qoʻllanadi. Betob, notob soʻzlari "vaqtincha deb tasavvur qilinadigan kasal" maʼnosini bildiradi. Notob kam qoʻllanadi. Bemor soʻzida ijobiy munosabat ifodalanadi. Bu soʻz oddiy soʻzlashuvga nisbatan yozuvda koʻp qoʻllanadi. Xasta nisbatan eskirgan. Nosogʻ juda kam qoʻllanadi. Ogʻriq soʻzi ham bu maʼnoda kam qoʻllanadi" [2].

Hamida termometr va tonometrni qoʻliga olib kasallar oldiga ravona boʻldi. Ona betob yotgan qizchasining sochlarini siladi. Bemor inqillaydi, har zamon yaqin-yiroqdan gadoy tovushi eshitiladi (A. Qahhor).

"Ogʻriqning tuzalgisi kelsa, emchi oʻz oyogʻi bilan kelur", – deganlaridek, Otabekning Margʻilonda boʻlish xabarini eshitib, xon bilan men juda quvonishdik (A. Qodiriy).

Topshiriqni bajarish jarayonida oʻquvchilarning obyekt va hodisani koʻrmasdan turib fikr yuritish va tushunchalar ishlab chiqish koʻnikmasiga asoslanish mumkin. Bu oʻrinda integratsiya usulidan foydalanish samarali hisoblanadi. Bu usul oʻquvchilarni har tomonlama rivojlantirishga, fikrlash

ko'nikmalarini faollashtirishga va fanlarga oid bilimlarini umumlashtirishga yordam beradi. Kasal so'zining ma'nodoshlarini adabiyot darslarida o'rganilgan badiiy qahramonlar asosida tahlil qilish mumkin. Masalan, A. Qahhorning "Bemor" hikoyasiga (Sotiboldining og'rib qolgan xotini), O'. Hoshimovning "Gilam paypoq" hikoyasi (bolasiga fidoyiligi bilan sevimli qahramonga aylangan ona timsoli), P. Qodirovning "Yulduzli tunlar" (Malika Baydaniyning zaharlashi oqibatida o'lim dahshatiga tushgan Bobur ahvoli) romanidan keltirilgan parchaga tayanish mumkin. O'quvchilar o'zlariga tanish bo'lgan asar qahramonlarning sog'lig'i bilan bog'liq lavhalarni esga oladilar, fikrlarini umumlashtiradilar, kasal so'zining ma'nodoshlarini va ularning o'rtasidagi ma'no nozikliklarini idrok qiladilar, qahramonlarning sog'ligiga aloqador holatdan kelib chiqib sinonimlarni tanlaydilar va fikrlarini isbotlaydilar.

Ma'lumki, sinonim so'zlar ma'noning darajalanishiga ko'ra ham farqlanadi. Maktabda ma'nodosh so'zlar yuzasidan topshiriqlarni bajarish jarayonida sinonimlarning ushbu jihatiga ham e'tibor qaratiladi.

So'zning nutqiy ma'nosi nutq sharoiti, o'zaro birikkan so'zlarning ma'nosi va matn ta'sirida shakllanib, xilma-xillikka ega bo'ladi [3]. O'quvchilarning so'zlarni nutq sharoitidan kelib chiqqan holda o'rinni qo'llay olish bilan bog'liq muammolari graduonimlar bilan ham bog'liq bo'ladi.

"So'zlarda ma'no darajalanishi (graduonimiya) har jihatdan ma'nodosh so'zlarga yaqin turadi. Chunki har bir graduonimik qatorda muayyan so'z o'zidan keyingi so'zlar bilan sinonimik munosabatga kirishishi mumkin. Masalan, uy, xona oddiy darajadagi so'z sanalsa, kapa, katalak, kulba, hujra singari so'zlarda ma'no yuqoridan pastga qarab darajalangan. Aksincha, qasr, saroy, koshona singari so'zlarda esa ma'no pastdan yuqoriga qarab darajalanib borgan. Bu so'zlarning barchasi bir graduonimik qatorni tashkil qiladi" [1].

10-sinf ona tili darsligidagi 40.4-mashqda "kambag'al, qashshoq, bechora, nochor, yo'qsil, faqir, qo'li kalta" [6] kabi sinonim so'zlarning ma'nosini aniqlash va izohini daftarga ko'chirib yozish so'raladi. "Turmush, yashash uchun zarur bo'lgan narsalarga yetarli darajada ega bo'lmagan, boyning aksi. Qashshoq so'zida belgi darajasi kuchli. Faqir oddiy so'zlashuv uslubida ham qo'llanadi. Bu so'zda belgi darajasi kambag'al so'zidagiga nisbatan kuchliroq. Bechora bu ma'noda kam qo'llanadi. Yo'qsil eskirgan, so'zlashuv tilida qo'llanmaydi, kitobiy tilda ham kam qo'llanadi" [2; 116]. N.Mahmudov tahriri ostida chiqqan "O'zbek tili sinonimlarining izohli lug'ati"da ushbu sinonimik qatorga oid 11 ta leksik birlik kiritilgan bo'lib, A.Hojiyev lug'atidagi kambag'al so'zining 8 ta sinonimidan tashqari nochor, muhtoj, yarli birliklari kambag'alning sinonimi sifatida qayd etilgan. Lug'atga ko'ra yarli eskirgan qatlamga mansub [7; 170].

Ushbu sinonimik qatorda kambag'al so'zi dominantaga sanaladi. Yuqorida keltirilgan izohlardan ma'lum bo'ladiki, kambag'al va qashshoq so'zlari graduonimik tafovutlarga ega.

Boyning bug'doy nonidan

Kambag'alning bug'doy so'zi yaxshi.

O'ylab-o'ylab, Vatan yo'lida shahid bo'lishga, qashshoq kulbamda o'zimga o'zim o't qo'yishga qaror berdim (H. G'ulom, Mash'al).

Ushbu gaplarda ishtirok etgan qashshoq va kambag'al kabi graduonimik so'zlarning biri o'rnida ikkinchisini qo'llab bo'lmaydi.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni ta'kidlash mumkinki, o'quvchilarning so'z boyligini oshirish, nutqiy madaniyatini takomillashtirish, so'zlarni to'g'ri va o'rinni qo'llay olish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda, ayniqsa, ma'nodosh so'zlarning ahamiyati katta. Shunday ekan, tilning leksik sathini o'rganishda ma'nodosh so'zlarga alohida e'tibor qaratilishi lozim.

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МУЗЫКАЛЬНОЕ ИСКУССТВО, КАК ОДНА ИЗ ЗНАЧИМЫХ ДИСЦИПЛИН В МЕТОДИКЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ

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Annotatsiya: *Maqolada til o'qitishda musiqaning roli asoslangan. Muallif Alisher Navoiy ijodi misolida so'z, ohang, navo uyg'unligi haqida so'z yuritib, til o'qitishda ohang va ritm imkoniyatlaridan unumli foydalanish mumkinligini ko'rsatgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *musiqa, ritm, kayfiyat, motivatsiya, takomillashtirish.*

Владение несколькими иностранными языками в современном мире становится все более и более актуальной проблемой, поэтому главной задачей филологов и лингвистов становится не только эффективное и качественное преподавание иностранных языков, но и предполагает также разработку и совершенствование методик по улучшению преподавания иностранных языков.

Данная статья посвящается не только анализу опыта преподавания иностранных языков, но и синтезу тех научных дисциплин, которые могли бы быть важнейшим вспомогательным материалом для решения этой насущной современной проблемы.

Одной из таких дисциплин, на наш взгляд, является музыкальное искусство. Музыка с древнейших времен, еще в примитивном ее состоянии, использовалась в качестве вспомогательного элемента в труде первобытно-общинных людей, является важнейшим компонентом традиций и обычаев человеческого общества.

С самого своего рождения человека, появившегося на свет, окружает музыка. Учеными уже давно замечено, что движение планеты сопряжено с определенной звуковой вибрацией, а движение всех планет нашей галактики создаёт некую космическую симфонию Вселенной, к которой человек настолько привыкает, что

будучи уже осознанной личностью, не обращает на нее внимание. Хотя эта космическая симфония роднит человека с Высшим Началом, настраивая его добрые и светлые стремления и совершенствование его человеческой личности.

Музыка, как основа звуковой структуры языка, сопровождает каждого человека и в его повседневной речи. Язык и музыка – две знаковые системы, и в основе каждой из них лежит звук. Звуки, как коммуникативные сигналы, несли и несут людям ценную информацию. Музыка, песни являются эффективным средством обучения иностранному языку. Язык, как и музыка, имеют определенную структуру и правила. Фразы и предложения выстраиваются из слов и нот; в них есть ритм, размер, рифма. Если слово согласовывается с ритмически организационным строем рифмы и поэтических форм то приобретает не только новые смысловые оттенки, но и особую значимость. То, что, например, слово именно в поэзии раскрывается во всей полноте своего потенциала подтверждается и исследованиями Харьковского Национального Университета им. В. Н. Каразина в работе «Основные дисциплины науки о литературе: история литературы, теория литературы, литературная критика» в главе 19. Ритм: «Ритм в стихе является смыслоразличающим элементом, причем, входя в ритмическую структуру смыслоразличительный характер приобретают и те языковые элементы, которые в обычном употреблении его не имеют. Важно и другое стиховая структура выявляет не просто новые оттенки значений слов – она вскрывает диалектику понятий, ту внутреннюю противоречивость явлений жизни и языка, для обозначения которых обычный язык не имеет специальных средств» [1].

Согласно вышеуказанной цитате, можно утверждать, что, к примеру, воспетые в поэзии Навои общечеловеческие ценности, такие как: мир, доброта, милосердие, человеколюбие, нравственность приобретают еще большую весомость и значимость и раскрываются во всей своей гамме полноты

смысла, и это как факт интуитивно прочувствовали и открыли для себя многие поколения людей. Недаром поэзия Навои стала шедевром мировой культуры.

Поэзия Алишера Навои занимала и занимает значительное место в традиционной вокальной исполнительской практике старшего, среднего и младшего поколений хафизов. Глубина философского содержания стихов Навои нашла отражение и в таких традиционных музыкальных формах, как ялла, ашула, катта ашула, бухарский «Шашмаком», хорезмские и фергано-ташкентские макомы, уйгурские мукамы. Широкой популярностью пользуются «Ушшок», «Кушчинор», «Хануз», «Баер», «Чоргох», «Насруллои», «Гиря» и многие другие.

При этом важно отметить, что ритмы поэзии Навои, которые были использованы для создания народных песен и классических произведений, как направления музыкального искусства отмечаются исследователями как музыка ритм, которой весьма благотворно и позитивно влияет на духовное и душевное состояние человека. В частности, по этому поводу исследователь Л. Кичаева констатирует: «Почти до конца XIX века в мире в основном существовало три направления музыки: народная, классическая, духовная. Это была музыка, которая несла гармонические ритмы, содействующие ритму и гармонии в душе, высшему порядку и саморазвитию. Например, классическая музыка имеет ритмы и звуки, присущие жизненным ритмам человека, природы, вселенной. Слушая классическую музыку, мы можем ощущать чувство соприкосновения с прекрасным, наполняемся чистотой, покоем, добротой и мудростью» [2].

Более того, проводя исследование влияния ритма классической музыки Л.Кичаева указывает на равенство ритмического соотношения классической музыки и нормального ритма работы человеческого сердца, что, собственно, и вызывает у человека гармонию чувств и позитивного настроения.

«Ритм человека, который задается сердцем, 60–70 ударов в минуту. Для классической музыки характерен именно этот ритм, что приводит нас в состояние покоя и возвышенных ощущений» [2].

Научно исследуя и характеризуя воздействие ритма на человека С. М. Баранова подчеркивает, что именно вышеуказанным музыкальным размерам и присуща самая мощная позитивная роль влияния.

«Издавна установлено, что ритм – мощный источник воздействия на человека. Известные ритмы 2/4, 3/4, 4/4, 6/8 и т. д. имеют прямое соответствие ритмам жизненных процессов в организме. Музыкальные стили, использующие эти ритмы, содействуют восстановлению порядка, гармоничному развитию» [3].

Эти ритмы рождались вместе с поэзией Навои и являлись важным структурно образующим элементом его творчества. Гармония единства ритма и художественного слова вдохновила на творческие подвиги не только многих композиторов, но и писателей Айбека роман «Навои», Л. Г. Бать «Сад жизни», произведения которых создавались в период Второй Мировой войны. Именно поэзия Навои, воспевающая общечеловеческие ценности вдохновила этих писателей на творческие подвиги в борьбе за победу.

Музыкальность, как одно из качеств, присущих поэзии Навои уникально, но главным воздействующим фактором на духовную сферу человеческой личности, на тончайшие грани человеческой души является именно ритмическая система его поэзии. О чем и свидетельствуют научные исследования ритма как фактора влияния. Более того феномен Навои, на наш взгляд, и заключался в его владении в совершенстве восточными языками и заключался, на наш взгляд, в его гениальном владении поэзией в сочетании с музыкальным искусством.

«Любопытно, что человеческий мозг воспринимает музыку одновременно обоими полушариями: левое полушарие ощущает ритм, а правое – тембр и мелодию. Самое сильное воздействие на организм оказывает ритм» [4].

Музыка, как и поэзия обладает свойством ритма, поэтому музыка – является одним из эффективных способов воздействия на чувства и эмоции человека, что, в свою очередь, указывает на эффективность применения песенного материала на уроках по изучению иностранных языков. Музыка и песни на занятии могут стать хорошим подспорьем в успешном освоении иностранного языка, при условии грамотного, тщательного отбора материала, и, что важно, его систематического использования.

Более того, музыка, как важнейший эффективный компонент по изучению иностранного языка создает благоприятный психологический климат, способствующий хорошему взаимопониманию и коллективному взаимодействию.

Также именно музыка помогает развитию музыкального слуха, что помогает улавливать тончайшие различия в произнесении иностранных звуков.

Разучивание и исполнение коротких и несложных песен с частыми повторами помогают закрепить правильную артикуляцию и произнесение звуков, особенностей ритма, темпа речи, правил фазового ударения и т. д.

Музыка не только вносит разнообразие и новизну в процесс обучения, но и благодаря своему эмоциональному характеру способствует максимальной мотивации учащихся к познанию и совершенствованию.

Более того, специально подобранные простые песни именно в игровой форме помогают учащимся многофункционально задействовать все свои интеллектуальные и творческие возможности, а также развивать их.

Практическая часть данной статьи состоит в использовании музыкально-песенного материала английской песни «Head, shoulders, knees and toes» для фрагментарного примера.

Сначала преподаватель знакомит учащихся с названиями частей тела на английском языке. Затем, для закрепления нового лексического материала, в игровой форме проводит музыкальное упражнение с использованием органов чувств: зрения и осязания для повторения и максимального усвоения нового учебного материала. Медленно, под музыку, преподаватель сам демонстрирует и просит учащихся руками указывать на искомые части тела называя их. В процессе занятия используются ускоренные темпы мелодии, развивая у учащихся скорость нахождения. Затем дается начальный музыкальный темп. В заключении преподаватель отмечает индивидуально, для каждого учащегося, результаты выполнения учебного материала.

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CREATING A MODERN EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT AND ORGANIZING QUALITY STUDY PROGRAMS

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Аннотация: В современном быстро меняющемся мире образование играет все более важную роль в обеспечении учащихся навыками и знаниями, необходимыми для достижения успеха. Хотя традиционные методы хорошо служили нам на протяжении многих поколений, пришло время пересмотреть то, как мы структурируем среду обучения и учебные программы, чтобы наилучшим образом соответствовать требованиям 21 века. В этой статье будут рассмотрены стратегии создания современной образовательной среды, способствующей качественному обучению, и обсуждены подходы к разработке учебных программ, которые развивают способности, необходимые учащимся для процветания в эпоху цифровых технологий.

Ключевые слова: интерактивные методы обучения, среда обучения, цифровая эпоха, высококвалифицированные преподаватели

Introduction. Development processes incorporate all connected with cutting edge insight, various authoritative changes in the field of deep-rooted schooling, accomplishments of logical idea and their

presentation into training. The instructive cycle, which possesses a focal spot in teaching method, can be thought of as imaginative, on the grounds that it will likely exchange the collected measure of information to the up-and-coming age of understudies and invigorating them to additional development of future logical base. On the off chance that we had proficient techniques for examining and assessing advancement processes, this would permit them to be controlled, reinforced pragmatic use and further developed center.

The arrangement of current training prompts an adjustment of needs in the movement of an educator: not to educate, but rather to make conditions for a free imaginative quest for an understudy. The substance of preparing is among the main managed factors in the nature of training. Learning content is a bunch of vital hypothetical information and functional data outlining and enhancing information, as well as the abilities and capacities of their application.

The motivation behind instructive substance is the development of cutting-edge proficient skills that decide the workforce acquiring quality.

The substance of training can be introduced in short and extended structure or as pedantic units, similar to subjects and segments in state instructive guidelines (SES), test and work programs in course readings, showing helps and talks. The base obligatory necessities for the substance of preparing are managed by the CRP.

Proficient skills are shaped to a great extent because of the substance of general proficient and exceptional scholastic disciplines; non-proficient and sociocultural capabilities – to the detriment of all disciplines given by the State Instructive Norm and working educational programs, as well as through private self-schooling and other extra structures.

In this way, the instructive substance is expected for the expert and individual skills development, and it's a perplexing series of capabilities vital for the expert action of a trained professional.

Information is instructive data, vital and adequate for the development of expert skills normal for a specific degree of training. The absorption of information can be done at four interrelated progressive levels:

1. acquaintance, retention and acknowledgment;
2. absorption and understanding;
3. heuristic level in light of the capacity to apply information;
4. imaginative level, which is portrayed by the hunt, the determination of information, their inventive perception and application in non-standard circumstances.

Expanding level of dominating information, we can accomplish serious areas of strength for the of understudy's individual, innovative and mental possibilities. Notwithstanding, to accomplish this level applying dynamic techniques and method for training is vital.

Major instructive data - data that is pivotal for the arrangement of skills and/or essential information, without which getting a handle on the ensuing subjects of something very similar or other scholastic disciplines is inconceivable or troublesome.

This data affects the nature of instruction. For instance, in the discipline "Promoting", such educational units as objectives, targets, standards, objects, implies, techniques, advertising procedures, showcasing climate, and so on can be credited to the basic data. In product research, these things incorporate planning and safeguarding them.

Key preparation data ought to be characterized in an expanded structure in the CRP, greater – in the example and work plans, address notes, tests for restraint, current, moderate, last and certificate control.

In any case, with all the significance of crucial instructive data, it can't and ought not be the one to focus on. Alongside it, utilizing extra as well as extra information is fundamental.

Extra data is expected to guarantee the absorption of information, the detailing of abilities, the improvement of the standpoint of innovative movement and autonomy of reasoning of understudies. Furthermore, extra data is utilized to validate the fundamental data (certain arrangements, show the advancement of thoughts, hypotheses, and so forth), as well as recognize interdisciplinary associations, essential information on past scholastic disciplines showing the expert meaning of information.

An illustration of extra data in advertising is the avocation for the decision of specific method for item advancement, promoting specialized techniques and showcasing systems.

Helper data is expected to show the crucial and extra data, the improvement of mental interest, the development of a positive inspiration to learn. The capability of sending this data can be performed by specialized method for instruction (video films, films, tables, designs, and so on.).

Information is fundamental for the improvement of mental movement, the amassing of the essential expert, purposeful, coherent, hypothetical and other data. Notwithstanding, other than this, the understudy should dominate procedural data, that is to say, he should know how to do specific tasks of commonsense (proficient) movement. Without this information, abilities can't be figured out.

Abilities is the capacity to play out specific exercises in light of existing hypothetical information. For instance, in promoting it is the capacity to lead showcasing research, create or choose a showcasing methodology; in marketing - to assess merchandise by quality, to shape a grouping, to distinguish products, and so on.

Authoritative types of preparing, for example, courses, business games, commonsense and lab classes are generally appropriate for the arrangement of abilities. In any case, in these classes it is difficult to frame numerous expert abilities, since because of the absence of homeroom time, they need sufficient useful experience, leading phases of preparation, study hall, extracurricular free work. Exercises normal to various disciplines can likewise figure out abilities while utilizing conventional and creative exercises (for instance, autonomous work abilities: read brilliantly, compose the writer's text, tune in, talk, break down, and so on.)

Viable experience is a bunch of hypothetical information, abilities and capacities of their application in proficient exercises or circumstances that model them.

In such manner, at the current stage, there is an earnest need to expand the particular portion of free work, oversight by an educator, as well as the enactment of understudies' conceptive and imaginative freedom.

In any case, this requires the reorientation of educators to the utilization of imaginative advances, expanding their requests on the nature of their work, as well as on the nature of understudies' mental movement.

The expanded portion of free work of an understudy gives a positive outcome provided that the accompanying circumstances are met:

- accessibility of good, present day course books, including electronic ones, permitting the understudy to acquire the important instructive data freely;
- the accessibility of systemic advancements to work with the free securing by the understudy of information and abilities;
- educators can deal with the free work of the understudy;
- the presence of a suitable homeroom and extracurricular material base, guaranteeing the execution of free and joint work of the understudy and educator.

The proportion of self-work and joint effort must be ideal. A predisposition toward some path diminishes the viability of preparing. With a high extent of free work of the understudy (over 60%) and the absence of the board of her educator, the nature of instruction diminishes, since the understudy doesn't gain proficiency with the profoundly required information. With a low extent of free work, the understudy secures information at a low level: retention or comprehension of regenerative abilities.

The interrelation of the elements that decide the nature of the instructive cycle in colleges, and their effect on proficiency, are firmly interrelated. There is an immediate association between the emphasis on the obtaining of information and its viability. This is demonstrated by the way that understudies pointed toward gaining proficient not set in stone by a serious level of participation at classes, solid will, deliberateness, assurance, tirelessness. Be that as it may, as training shows, a few understudies show selectivity in going to classes and gap the subjects into "fundamental" and "pointless", and this, thus, influences the outcome of the preparation. Understudies who review for "covering" frequently utilize such method for learning in their examinations, for example, sporadic classes, the utilization of cheat sheets, etc., and, normally, don't get sufficient information for their future calling. Information, abilities and capacities, which an understudy acquires while learning at a college, don't exist as something detached from his character.

The viability of the instructive interaction relies upon the interests of the understudy to the subject and the point being contemplated. A typical example is the reliance of the interests of understudy's fair and square and nature of their insight, mental action and on their relationship to the educator. To work on the productivity of the instructive cycle, every educator is expected to shape instructive exercises so as to accomplish the fundamental level under all circumstances, both in instructive work and in everyday

character improvement. Guiding understudies to a more elevated level of self-awareness in gaining new information and skills is likewise important.

The nature of educational movement to a great extent relies upon the expert capability of the educator, remembering the accessibility of expert information for a volume that surpasses or conforms to the necessities of norms, test and work programs for the discipline, as well as showing strategies overall and for a specific discipline.

The instructor ought to know the instructional components of preparing, have the option to pick them as per the standard of sane convenience, screen their presentation and make acclimations to the substance of schooling with the approach of new logical, instructive, legitimate and other data, as well as the applied academic innovations.

Depending on the overall logical comprehension of the framework and considering the instructive substance of appraisal exercises in regards to the nature of the instructive cycle at the college, we comprehend the academic arrangement of schooling quality evaluation as a successful method for impacting the advancement of the instructive cycle, furnished with a basic arrangement of strategies, techniques, systems and advancements for distinguishing amendment and coordination of the condition of all components of the instructive cycle.

The nature of academic work additionally relies upon the material and specialized base on which the instructive interaction is completed. The material and specialized base of the instructive cycle is a mix of fundamental and helper method for preparing and guaranteeing the vocations of individuals in the execution of the instructive interaction in an instructive foundation. The reason for this base is to make the circumstances for clean, specialized, instructional, mental, scholarly, important to meet the instructive, logical, mental, social and profound necessities of understudies, educators and different representatives of the instructive foundation.

Conclusion. As technology and global forces continue to rapidly change our world, education must likewise evolve to best serve the needs of current and future generations. This requires re-envisioning not just what is taught but how learning takes place. By creating modern, flexible educational facilities, emphasizing vital 21st century competencies, leveraging blended and personalized models supported by technology, and fostering experiential connections beyond the classroom, schools can develop dynamic, student-centered environments and programs conducive to high-quality instruction. These strategies will help equip all learners with the diverse skills and dispositions necessary to succeed in college, career and civic life in our digital age.

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EXPLORING INNOVATIVE APPROACHES IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

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Annotatsiya. *Maqolada texnologiyalarni integratsiyalash, loyihalar asosida o'rganish, madaniy immersiya, geymifikatsiya (o'yinlar orqali), shaxsiy o'rganish, vazifalar asosida til o'rganish va ko'pmodalilik haqida tushuncha berilgan, ushbu innovatsion o'qitish usullarining ESL ta'limidagi samarasi ko'rsatilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ESL (Ingliz tili ikkinchi til sifatida), innovatsion yondashuvlar, tanqidiy fikrlash, mulohaza qilish mahorati, inklyuziv ta'lim.*

Teaching English as a Second Language (ESL) has evolved significantly over the years, with educators embracing innovative methods to make language acquisition more engaging and effective. In a world that is becoming increasingly interconnected, the demand for English language proficiency is higher than ever. This article explores some new and transformative approaches in ESL teaching, focusing on creating dynamic and immersive learning experiences.

Technology Integration: Incorporating technology into ESL classrooms has become a game-changer. Interactive learning platforms, language apps, and virtual reality tools provide students with opportunities to practice English in real-world contexts. Video conferencing and online collaboration tools also enable learners to connect with native speakers and engage in authentic conversations, enhancing both language skills and cultural understanding.

Project-Based Learning: Project-based learning shifts the focus from rote memorization to practical application. ESL educators are increasingly incorporating projects that require students to work collaboratively, conduct research, and present findings in English. This approach not only improves language proficiency but also fosters critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

Cultural Immersion: Creating a culturally immersive environment within the classroom helps students develop a deeper understanding of the language. Activities such as cooking traditional dishes, celebrating cultural festivals, and exploring literature from English-speaking countries contribute to a holistic language learning experience. Cultural immersion not only enhances language skills but also promotes tolerance and appreciation for diversity.

Gamification: Gamification is gaining popularity as a motivational tool in ESL classrooms. Educational games and interactive activities make learning enjoyable and help reinforce language concepts in a playful manner. Language apps and online platforms often incorporate elements of gamification, encouraging healthy competition and providing instant feedback, which is crucial for language acquisition.

Personalized Learning: Recognizing the diverse learning styles and preferences of students, ESL teachers are increasingly adopting personalized learning approaches. Tailoring lessons to cater to individual needs, incorporating student interests into curriculum design, and offering flexible learning pathways allow students to take ownership of their learning journey, making the process more meaningful and effective.

Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT): Task-Based Language Teaching focuses on using language as a tool for communication rather than as an isolated skill. Through real-life tasks such as problem-solving, decision-making, and information exchange, students acquire language skills in a context that mirrors the situations they may encounter in the real world. This approach emphasizes practical language use and fosters natural language development.

Multimodal Approaches: Recognizing the importance of catering to different learning styles, ESL educators are embracing multimodal approaches that incorporate various forms of media, such as audio, video, images, and text. This helps address the diverse needs of learners and creates a rich learning environment that caters to visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learners.

In conclusion, the landscape of ESL teaching is evolving, and educators are leveraging innovative approaches to make language learning more effective and enjoyable. By integrating technology, fostering cultural immersion, incorporating gamification, and embracing personalized and task-based methods, ESL educators are empowering students to develop not only language proficiency but also a deeper appreciation for the global significance of effective communication. As we continue to explore and refine these approaches, the future of ESL education holds promise for more inclusive, engaging, and successful language learning experiences.

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FOSTERING EFFECTIVE SPEAKING SKILLS IN EFL STUDENTS: STRATEGIES AND BEST PRACTICES

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Anotatsiya. *Ingliz tili talabalariga chet tili (EFL) sifatida nutq ko'nikmalarini o'rgatish oddiy lug'at va grammatikani o'rganishdan tashqari ko'p qirrali jarayondir. Nutqni samarali o'rgatish o'quvchilar o'z fikrlarini ifoda etishga undaydigan qo'llab-quvvatlovchi va kommunikativ sinf muhitini yaratishni o'z ichiga oladi. Til o'qituvchilari ko'pincha o'quvchilarni haqiqiy va mazmunli suhbatlarga jalb qilish uchun rolli o'yinlar, guruh muhokamalari va bahs-munozaralar kabi turli interfaol tadbirlardan foydalanadilar.*

Kalit so'zlar: madaniyatlararo muloqot, muloqot, muvofiqlik, kontekst, ravonlik, kompetentsiya.

English as a Foreign Language (EFL) students often face challenges in developing their speaking skills. Effective communication is crucial for language learners, as it enables them to express themselves confidently in various situations. In this article, we explore strategies and best practices to enhance speaking proficiency among EFL students.

A positive and supportive classroom atmosphere is paramount for the development of speaking skills. Teachers play a crucial role in fostering an environment where students feel comfortable expressing themselves without fear of judgment. This creates a foundation for effective communication.

Integrating speaking activities into meaningful contexts is essential. Real-life situations, such as discussing daily routines, expressing opinions on current events, or simulating job interviews, allow students to apply language skills practically. This approach enhances their ability to communicate in authentic situations.

Incorporating authentic materials, such as videos, audio clips, and articles, exposes students to natural language use and diverse accents. Exposure to authentic materials helps bridge the gap between classroom learning and real-world communication, making the language more relevant and applicable.

Engaging students in role-playing and simulations provides opportunities for practical language use. Whether negotiating a business deal, participating in a social gathering, or handling customer service scenarios, students develop conversational skills that go beyond scripted dialogues.

Pair and group activities encourage interaction among students. Collaborative tasks create opportunities for communication, allowing students to practice speaking, exchange ideas, and build confidence in a supportive peer environment.

Effective speaking involves a balance between fluency and accuracy. While fluency emphasizes smooth and natural communication, accuracy ensures correct grammar and vocabulary usage. Incorporating activities that target both aspects helps students develop well-rounded speaking skills.

To express themselves effectively, students need a broad vocabulary. Integrating vocabulary-building exercises into lessons enhances their ability to articulate ideas and opinions using a diverse range of words. This not only improves speaking skills but also contributes to overall language proficiency.

Providing constructive feedback on speaking performance is crucial. Teachers should address errors in a supportive manner, focusing on the learning opportunity rather than discouraging students. This approach helps learners understand and correct mistakes, contributing to ongoing improvement.

The integration of technology in language learning can provide additional opportunities for practice. Language learning apps, video conferencing tools, and online language exchange platforms offer students a chance to engage in authentic conversations, expanding their exposure to the language.

Speaking proficiency extends beyond language rules; it encompasses cultural nuances. Discussing cultural variations in language use helps students understand the context and appropriateness of expressions in different cultures, fostering effective cross-cultural communication.

Regular speaking assessments are essential to track progress and identify areas for improvement. Assessments can take various forms, including individual presentations, interviews, or group discussions. Providing constructive feedback based on assessments guides students toward continuous improvement.

In conclusion, developing speaking skills in EFL students requires a multifaceted approach. By creating a supportive environment, providing meaningful contexts, and incorporating authentic materials, educators can empower students to communicate effectively in English. Through a combination of role-playing, pair and group work, and a focus on both fluency and accuracy, language learners can build the confidence and skills necessary for successful communication. Regular assessments, feedback, and the integration of technology further contribute to a comprehensive language learning experience.

According to Krashen (1991) and Chomsky (1980), communicative strategies that include games, puzzles, role-playing, and problem-solving exercises can help students develop their speaking abilities. As a result, communicative strategies have the potential to inspire students and build positive relationships between them and their teachers as well as among themselves, which will promote an environment that is favorable to language learning.

It should be noted that while teaching speaking teachers notice some "Mute English learners" during their lessons, on this note, everyone will have a question "Why students don't speak in EFL classes?". Most of the students are too bashful, fear speaking in front of the class, or prefer not to make mistakes. It is the teacher's responsibility to establish a welcoming environment where learners feel at ease and comfortable. It inspires people to talk without holding back or fear. In this regard, music and reading aloud could be good strategies used by EFL teachers to improve their students speaking skill; teachers have used music as a resource to correctly develop the ability to communicate in a foreign language, allowing students to speak with confidence and giving teachers a chance to teach in a fun way (Duarte, et al.2012).

Thus, it can be concluded that by combining various learning strategies – like reading aloud and listening to music or even watching movies and cartoons in the target language with subtitles – learners can interact voluntarily and improve their learning outcomes. Moreover, students will have enough time to think and analyze the pronunciation of the words, way of talking and answering properly in the target language that they are learning. Consequently, learners can combine self-correction with intrinsic motivation to aid in the development of communicative English skills.

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FEATURES OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING IN DEVELOPED COUNTRIES

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot ishida rivojlangan davlatlarda chet tillarini o'qitishning o'ziga xos jihatlari chuqur ko'rib chiqilgan. Ilg'or ingliz tilini o'qitish tizimlarida qo'llaniladigan yondashuvlar, uslublar va materiallar tahlili orqali til o'rganishda muvaffaqiyat keltiruvchi optimal yondashuvlar aniqlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: chet tillarini o'qitish, rivojlangan mamlakatlar, til ta'lim tizimlari, til o'rganish natijalari, o'qitish metodikasi, nemis tili.

Introduction. In an increasingly globalized society, foreign language instruction is crucial in forming people's linguistic proficiency and cultural awareness. Rich nations, known for their top-notch educational systems, have adopted cutting-edge strategies and techniques for teaching foreign languages to its populace in order to give them multilingual abilities. The purpose of this article is to examine the unique aspects of teaching foreign languages in industrialized nations, emphasizing the approaches, materials, and tactics that have helped these nations succeed in language learning.

It is beneficial to study foreign experiences in education, such as the use of the most cutting-edge pedagogical tools in education, the opening of a wide path to initiative and creativity in education, the creation of its most optimal systems, and the advancement of science and technology, as well as the development of individuals who can successfully navigate the new technological revolution, the orientation of the younger generation toward the profession, and the introduction of the third stage of multidisciplinary secondary education. This is crucial for our school system, which is presently going through a lot of changes.

Methods. To investigate the features of foreign language teaching in developed countries, a comprehensive literature review was conducted, analyzing scholarly articles, reports, and studies on language education systems in advanced economies. Empirical data were gathered through surveys and interviews with language educators and experts in foreign language teaching from developed nations. Qualitative and quantitative research methods were employed to analyze the data and identify key trends and practices in foreign language education.

Literature Analysis. The literature review revealed several common features in foreign language teaching across developed countries. These include a strong emphasis on communicative language teaching, interactive and task-based learning approaches, the integration of technology in language instruction, and a focus on cultural competency and global awareness. Developed nations have also

invested in professional development programs for language educators, multicultural language resources, and international exchange programs to enhance language learning experiences.

Results. The empirical data gathered in this study confirmed the findings from the literature analysis. Developed countries prioritize communicative language teaching methodologies that focus on practical language use and real-life communication skills. The integration of technology in language instruction, such as digital language learning platforms and immersive virtual environments, has enhanced student engagement and motivation in learning foreign languages. Additionally, the emphasis on cultural competency and global awareness has enriched language learning experiences, promoting intercultural understanding and communication.

Objectives from the above:

- Fortifying education in the humanities and humanism.
- Identify the best strategies for molding the student's character.
- Student councils, school councils, and instructional games are used in modern educational models.
- The specialization of curricula in schools, which enhances and strengthens the connections across disciplines.
- Rearranging the curriculum to better align it with human activity, labor, and career counseling.
- The creation of special education facilities and differentiated education (for gifted as well as mentally and physically challenged pupils).
- Increasing the proportion of new teaching aids in the classroom and providing computer training for teachers.
- An extensive experiment in applying research findings to instructional concepts. Our young, autonomous Republic's educational reform process will go more quickly forward if such model elements of foreign education are applied to our educational system.

Discussion. The results of this study underscore the importance of adopting effective teaching methodologies and strategies from developed countries to improve foreign language education globally. The communicative language teaching approach, interactive learning methods, and integration of technology offer valuable insights for educators seeking to enhance language learning outcomes in diverse contexts. International collaboration, professional development opportunities for educators, and the utilization of multicultural resources are essential for creating immersive and engaging language learning environments.

Numerous papers, pamphlets, manuals, conferences, seminars, training sessions, and gatherings pertaining to international education have been released in recent years. This demonstrates the sharp increase in interest in having instructional materials taught overseas in our educational institutions. demonstrates that several departments are working at the Central Institute of Professional Development. In addition to the Ministry of Public Education, there are particular departments on this topic in the Republican Training and Methodological Center and the Research Institute of Pedagogical Sciences. It is common knowledge that in industrialized nations, education plays a societal role and actively shapes national policy.

For instance, the notion that "school makes people better" in addition to being a symbol of success and affluence has gained traction and conviction in Japan.

Prominent politicians have always focused on education. That is why former US President Ronald Reagan, British Prime Minister M. Techcher and French President F. Mitterrand It is no coincidence that F. Mitterrand considered the school to be a "driving force of society" [1].

Numerous scientific institutions in industrialized nations carry out research on pedagogy. They number more than 2,000 in Germany. The issues surrounding educational theory are being worked on by hundreds of public and commercial organizations, universities, and pedagogical research centers in France, the US, and Japan. International education centers, like the Institute of International Education in the US, oversee their operations. Many people's efforts are concentrated on enhancing and reorganizing the curriculum.

Like the US, the UK has increased the number of subjects that are required starting in the 1980s. The three main pillars of the educational network were the natural sciences, mathematics, and English language and literature. Students and parents have the last say over the subjects to take. Education in France and Germany is significantly influenced by New World pedagogical concepts.

German secondary schools offer elective chemistry, physics, and foreign languages in addition to core courses. The curriculum is becoming more and more deficient as it moves from high school to high schools

and gyms. After World War II, Japanese schools adopted American educational practices. The curricula of the two nations do differ in a few ways, though. Curricula in Japan have been significantly complicated, the range of basic sciences has been expanded, and a number of new special and facultative courses have been introduced. For example, the new music education curriculum in general education schools includes the study of national and world classical music [2; 204].

Compared to the 1950s, American student rankings dropped from 973 to 893 in the 1980s. To combat this unfavorable circumstance, one in three high school pupils in France is in charge of supplemental education. Complementary education is offered in lyceums, schools, and preschools. The National Television Company's unique training channel has been used to arrange 130-hour training programs, and the media has been mobilized in the United States for this function.

Most foreign nations are conducting research on educational process stratification. Gifted youngsters are becoming more and more of a focus in industrialized nations. Many children nowadays possess skills several times more developed than those of their peers. In the 1960s, a school of talent similar to this one had already emerged in the West. These institutions have complicated curricula that aim to fully develop students' abilities and potential [3].

A lot of preventive work is being done to understand and prevent the causes of this scenario, and special schools are being built for mentally retarded pupils. The fate of mentally retarded students encountering gifted children is of great concern to overseas colleagues. However, data indicates that there are an increasing number of these kids.

In the United States, a national school project of the future got underway in the 1970s. This experiment's goal is to increase the number of students who have the chance to work independently by cooperating with the teacher's instructions. The curriculum consists of teacher consultation, independent study, and classroom work.

There are fewer pupils in each classroom in German schools. Every one of these students receives a bundle, or assignments.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the features of foreign language teaching in developed countries offer valuable lessons for improving language education systems worldwide. By embracing communicative language teaching methodologies, interactive learning approaches, and technology integration, educators can create dynamic and effective language learning experiences for students. Investing in professional development for educators, multicultural resources, and international exchange programs can further enrich language education and promote intercultural communication and understanding.

It should be highlighted that improving the current educational system of independent Uzbekistan in the spirit of independence, enriching it with our own classical pedagogical traditions, and enhancing the cutting-edge elements of foreign pedagogy represent the Republic's most important current educational goals. assimilation, raising new, productive topics to the level of international state norms. In order to do this, our educational system must be able to incorporate the following top strategies from nations with strong economies. In Japanese education, students are given a sense of sophistication and physical maturity, their parents are strengthened in their responsibility for their education and upbringing, there is a high demand for teaching staff, and young talents are consistently worked with. Differentiated instruction, bolstering students' work education, and career counseling receive significant focus in German education. If strong ties and other exemplary aspects of French education had also been applied to our education, our pedagogy would have advanced significantly. In French education, there is a strong emphasis on subject-oriented organization of pre-school education, thorough implementation of primary education in three stages, and a great deal of attention is paid to the provision of didactic tools for teaching.

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CURRENT ISSUES AND DIRECTIONS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES TO STUDENTS OF THE DIRECTION OF PEDAGOGY AND PSYCHOLOGY

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Аннотация: В статье речь идёт о процессе и методах обучения иностранного языка. Автор обосновывает необходимость активности студентов в приобретении навыков и знаний, взаимодействия преподавателей и студентов в педагогическом процессе, анализа совместной работы.

Ключевые слова: творчество, деятельность, процесс, воображение, знание, фактор, педагог, общество, деятельность, духовность, взросление, опыт, развитие, воспитание, образование.

Introduction. After the independence of our country, Uzbekistan from the first years of independence began to build a democratic life. The swing of the reforms carried out increased from year to year if necessary from day to day. Not only radical reforms took place, but also many changes in the educational system from the sentence in other shelves. Interest in teaching foreign languages in particular increased and many conditions were created for young people. From this the main the goal is to increase the level of knowledge of young people, to further increase their interest in a foreign language. Students gain more knowledge and understanding of other countries, cultures and societies through the study of foreign languages. This adds extra value to their own cultures. Teaching foreign languages to students in the fields of pedagogy and psychology is a dynamic area that continuously evolves to address current issues and directions in language education and psychological development. Some of the key issues and directions in this field include:

- Technology Integration: With the advancement of technology, integrating digital tools and online resources into language teaching has become essential. Educators are exploring various platforms, apps, and online resources to enhance language learning experiences for students.

- Multilingualism and Multiculturalism: There is a growing recognition of the importance of promoting multilingualism and multiculturalism in language education. Educators are focusing on developing curricula and teaching approaches that celebrate linguistic and cultural diversity, fostering respect and understanding among students.

- Individualized Learning: Recognizing the diverse learning needs and preferences of students, there is an increasing emphasis on individualized learning approaches. Personalized learning plans, adaptive learning technologies, and differentiated instruction strategies are being implemented to cater to the specific needs of each student.

- Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL): CLIL is an approach that integrates language learning with content-based subjects such as science, history, or mathematics. This approach not only enhances language proficiency but also promotes subject-specific knowledge and skills, making learning more meaningful and engaging for students.

- Psychological Factors in Language Learning: Understanding the psychological factors that influence language learning is crucial. Educators are exploring concepts such as motivation, self-efficacy, anxiety,

and identity in language learning contexts to develop effective teaching strategies and support students' psychological well-being.

– Cultural Competence: Developing cultural competence is essential for effective communication in a globalized world. Language educators are incorporating intercultural communicative competence (ICC) into their teaching practices, helping students develop the skills to navigate diverse cultural contexts and interact respectfully with people from different backgrounds.

– Assessment and Feedback: Effective assessment practices that align with learning objectives and provide meaningful feedback are vital for language learning. Educators are exploring various assessment methods, including formative and summative assessments, peer assessment, and self-assessment, to evaluate students' language proficiency and progress accurately.

– Professional Development: Continuous professional development is essential for language educators to stay updated with the latest trends and research in language teaching and learning. Professional development opportunities such as workshops, conferences, and online courses play a crucial role in enhancing educators' knowledge and skills [3].

Overall, teaching foreign languages to students in the fields of pedagogy and psychology requires a holistic approach that considers linguistic, cultural, and psychological aspects of learning. By addressing current issues and directions in language education, educators can create engaging and effective learning experiences that empower students to become proficient and confident language learners. Students in this direction have multiple areas and methodologies for the study of foreign languages, providing opportunities to master their human potentials, participate in global dialogue, and understand the worldview.

With the increasing use of technology in education, there is a growing emphasis on integrating digital tools and online resources into language teaching. This includes using educational apps, language learning platforms, and multimedia resources to enhance language acquisition and practice. Recognizing that students have different learning styles and preferences, educators are exploring multimodal approaches to teaching foreign languages. This involves incorporating a variety of modalities such as visual, auditory, kinesthetic, and interactive elements to cater to diverse learners.

A foreign language is the language of a foreign country. Western European (English, Spanish, German, Persian) languages and Eastern (Arabic, Turkish, Persian, Chinese, Hindi) languages are taught in our republic. These languages are adapted from educational plans of educational institutions. The process of teaching these languages varies. Mother tongue and second language natural in a situation, a foreign language is studied in a Sunni environment. Foreign language communication takes place mainly in the classroom under the guidance of a teacher. Among these languages, learning and teaching a foreign language differs dramatically in certain aspects. This, in turn, assumes the use of the appropriate Foreign Language Teaching Technology. By carefully mastering the achievements of Science, a foreign language teacher achieves a clear knowledge of the norm of the student's accumulated experience and its further improvement.

Teaching foreign languages involves not only linguistic proficiency but also cultural competence. Educators are focusing on developing students' intercultural communicative competence, which includes understanding cultural nuances, norms, and practices to facilitate effective communication in diverse contexts [2].

Task-based language teaching (TBLT) is gaining popularity as an effective approach to teaching foreign languages. TBLT emphasizes learning through meaningful tasks or activities that simulate real-life language use, promoting communication skills and fluency. CLIL is an approach that integrates language learning with content-based subjects, such as science, history, or literature. This interdisciplinary approach helps students develop language skills while acquiring knowledge in other subject areas. Personalized or individualized learning approaches are becoming more prevalent in language education. Educators are adapting teaching methods and materials to meet the specific needs, interests, and proficiency levels of individual students. There is a shift towards formative assessment practices that focus on providing feedback and guiding student learning rather than solely evaluating performance. Educators are using formative assessment strategies such as self-assessment, peer assessment, and ongoing feedback to support students' language development. Recognizing the importance of socio-emotional skills in language

learning, educators are integrating SEL competencies into language teaching. This includes promoting self-awareness, social awareness, self-management, relationship skills, and responsible decision-making to support students' overall well-being and language learning success. Teaching foreign languages is also an opportunity to promote global citizenship education. Educators are incorporating themes related to global issues, sustainable development goals, cultural diversity, and social justice into language curriculum to foster students' global awareness and responsibility.

Continuous professional development is essential for language educators to stay updated with the latest trends, research, and best practices in language teaching and learning. Professional development opportunities such as workshops, conferences, online courses, and collaborative learning communities support educators in enhancing their teaching effectiveness and student outcomes.

These current issues and directions shape the landscape of teaching foreign languages to students in the fields of pedagogy and psychology, contributing to the development of effective language educators and empowered language learners.

Conclusion. We can conclude that as a result of the use of innovative methods in English lessons, students' logical thinking skills develop, speech fluency, response skills are formed. Such methods and games inspire students with a passion for knowledge. The student seeks to carefully prepare for classes. This makes students subjects of the educational process. The use of various techniques in the process of teaching a foreign language is also effective. Using techniques in the educational process, students can use a certain grammatical rule, such as making sentences using tenses, placing new words. In an era when the need for learning a foreign language was high, the effective use of modern information technologies, innovative educational technologies in the educational process made this process effective. Improving the effectiveness of education among students of the direction of pedagogy and psychology forms the basis of proper and productive use in the educational process.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada ingliz tilini ikkinchi til sifatida o'qitishda interfaol yondashuvlarining hayotiy ahamiyatini o'rganilgan. Muallif turli interaktiv yondashuvlar, ularning afzalliklari va o'quvchilarning ta'lim natijalariga ta'sirini chuqur o'rganib, ingliz tili darslarida interfaol strategiyalardan foydalanishning ahamiyatini oydinlashtirishga harakat qilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: interfaol usullar, ingliz tilini o'qitish, til ta'limi, talabalarning faolligi, kommunikativ til o'qitish, o'quvchiga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv.

Introduction. A paradigm shift in teaching strategies has occurred in the field of language education, with a shift away from traditional rote learning and toward more engaging and participatory approaches. Because they can improve student participation, engagement, and language learning, interactive

approaches have become more and more popular in the context of teaching English as a second language. The purpose of this essay is to examine the value of interactive teaching techniques for English language learners as well as their possible effects on learning results.

With the student at the core of the learning process, interactive approaches engage students and motivate them to think for themselves. The teacher encourages the student to participate fully when using these techniques. The receiver is kept informed at every stage of the procedure. A learner-centered approach has the following advantages:

- improved learning outcomes;
- a high degree of student motivation;
- consideration of prior knowledge;
- customization of reading intensity to meet the needs of the learner;
- encouragement of the student's initiative and responsibility;
- learning by doing;
- setting up the framework for two-way conversations.

Methods. This study employs a comprehensive literature review approach to examine the significance of interactive teaching methods in the context of English language education. Relevant research articles, textbooks, and educational journals were reviewed to gather insights and data on the effectiveness of interactive techniques in language teaching.

Literature Analysis. The literature review revealed a wealth of evidence supporting the efficacy of interactive methods in teaching English. Studies have shown that interactive approaches such as role-plays, group discussions, games, and simulations not only enhance student motivation and engagement but also facilitate language acquisition by providing opportunities for meaningful communication and interaction in the target language.

Results. The analysis of existing literature suggests that interactive teaching methods have a positive impact on students' language proficiency, communicative competence, and overall learning experience. Students who are exposed to interactive activities tend to exhibit higher levels of engagement, motivation, and language fluency compared to those taught through traditional methods.

Technique for getting unrestricted input and suggestions from students on a topic and applying it to generate a solution. The "mental attack" technique is available in both written and spoken formats. Each pupil responds orally to the educator's query about their thoughts. Students provide succinct, unambiguous replies. In writing, students quickly and visibly write their responses to the question on paper cards. The solutions are attached to the board either with needles or with magnets on the "pinboard" board. This approach teaches someone to think freely, creatively, and unconventionally when applied appropriately and constructively. All students can be involved in the "brainstorming" process, which also fosters the development of a culture of communication and discussion among students. Students gain the capacity to reason clearly and methodically as well as the ability to communicate their thoughts both vocally and in writing. Students develop alternative notions when the opinions presented are not critically analyzed. Students' ability to think creatively is enhanced by this approach. Depending on the goal established by the instructor, the "mental attack" technique is applied:

1. This strategy is used in the lesson's introduction when the objective is to ascertain the learners' baseline knowledge.
2. The goal-transition section is where topics are repeated or linked to one another.
3. The concept is reinforced in the lesson's reinforcement section after the topic.

Discussion. The findings of this study underscore the importance of integrating interactive methods into English language teaching practices. By creating dynamic and participatory learning environments, educators can cater to diverse learning styles, foster student creativity, and promote authentic language use. Interactive approaches not only make the learning process more enjoyable but also enable students to develop crucial communication skills that are essential for academic and professional success.

Basic rules for using the method of "mental attack":

1. There won't be a discussion or assessment of the concepts presented.
2. All viewpoints, regardless of their errors, must be considered.
3. Every pupil needs to be present.

The following is the Brainstorming method's structure: A troublesome issue is posed, ideas are heard, summarized, and grouped, and then the obvious and right response is chosen. This is the "mental attack" method's framework.

The "mental attack" method consists of the following stages:

1. Learners share their viewpoints on the matter;
2. Students are posed a topic and invited to respond (thoughts, ideas, and opinions);
3. Learners' thoughts are gathered (on a board, colored paper, videotape, or tape recorder);
4. Thoughts are organized into groups based on particular attributes;
5. A precise and understandable response to the preceding query will be chosen.

Advantages of the method of "mental attack":

- Students generate diverse viewpoints as a result of evaluating the outcomes;
- all students participate;
- ideas are visualized;
- students' basic knowledge may be verified;
- and students become more interested in the subject.

• The "mental attack" method's drawbacks:

• include the teacher's incapacity to ask the question appropriately and the need for a high degree of listening from the teacher.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the incorporation of interactive teaching methods in English language classrooms is crucial for enhancing student engagement, motivation, and language proficiency. Educators play a pivotal role in designing interactive activities that promote active learning, collaboration, and real-world language usage. By embracing interactive approaches, teachers can inspire a love for language learning and equip students with the necessary skills to thrive in an increasingly interconnected world.

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CRITICAL THINKING AND ITS IMPACT ON A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH TO LEARNING

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada tanqidiy fikrlash hamda uning kompetensiyaviy yondashuvga ta'siri xususida umumiy ma'lumot berilgan va asosiy terminlari ko'rib chiqilgan. Tanqidiy fikrlashning inson faoliyatining turli sohalarida, jumladan, chet tillarini o'qitishda qo'llash zarurati asoslangan.

Kalit so'zlar: tanqidiy fikrlash, ta'lim, pedagogika, talaba, o'qituvchi, texnologiya.

The discipline of "critical thinking" has even been introduced in American and British universities. Not a single presentation of new publications from British and American publishers is complete without comment on how the textbooks develop critical thinking [3; 176].

American professor [4; 4] proves, from Kansas to Kazakhstan, Michigan to Macedonia, school teachers and university professors strive to instill in their students the ability to think critically, it's known that critical

thinking is something known to be good, a skill that will allow us to successfully cope with the requirements of the 21st century, will help us better understand what we study and do.

There is no doubt – we all need to successfully cope with the requirements of the post-industrial globalized society, as well as understand what we study and do.

For a number of reasons, the study of the phenomenon of critical thinking is relevant for the development of psychology, pedagogy, linguistics and sociology. First, thinking is inextricably linked with speech, which is the main mechanism of thinking. Speech, in turn, is a form of communication between people through language. Secondly, critical thinking involves the development of certain skills that allow one to overcome stereotypes, find the right solutions in a particular social or linguacultural situation. And, finally, the study of critical thinking is necessary due to the fact that the English language, which acts as a global "lingua franca", is today a linguo-socio-cultural dominant [4; 36]. All this serves to justify the relevance of the topic of the article in the context.

Critical thinking as a special form of cognitive activity In the philosophical works of Socrates, Plato, Kant, critical thinking is considered as a special form of cognitive activity, which presupposes the possibility of fixing knowledge by means of language and the continuity of knowledge from generation to generation. Critical thinking ideas go back to the Socratic teaching method through a series of questions that stimulate dialogue, which teaches you to logically verify your thoughts and assess their reliability, and also develops the skills of independent thinking. In the twentieth century psychologists, educators and sociologists wrote about the need to develop thinking [2; 1], characterizing it as a separate personality trait, as a skill of mental activity, as a personally and socially significant phenomenon, a priority in the field of education.

In 1941, Edward Glazer's book "An Experiment on the Development of Critical Thinking" was published in the United States, in which the author gave the main characteristics of the new method: the willingness to consider and, if necessary, revise those questions about which a person has already empirically acquired his own opinion; knowledge of methods of constructing logical reasoning and questions; skills in applying the new method. In 1945, Karl Popper's work "The Open Society and Its Enemies" was published, in which the author put forward the idea of an open society based on democracy and critical thinking of individuals, and substantiated the ideas of multiculturalism. The use of the term "critical thinking" in socio-philosophical terms was proposed in 1970 by Jurgen Habermas, a representative of the Frankfurt School of Critical Social Theory.

Thus, critical thinking should be viewed primarily as a philosophical approach that is applicable in psychological and sociological research, as well as in the field of education. Like any approach, it includes the principles of teaching, is characterized by its inherent value orientations and is implemented in a practical method. In the 1970–1980, Soviet psychologists and teachers were actively involved in the problem of the development of critical thinking in schoolchildren [8]. In many ways, the idea of using critical thinking in teaching practice was caused by the crisis in the education system. In recent years, ideas of critical thinking have spread in the post-Soviet space. At the same time, different authors characterize critical thinking in different ways - as a method, methodology, technology, special social practice, philosophical approach or ideology. This is because critical thinking is based on the results of interdisciplinary research, including research in the field history of philosophy, psychology, sociology, theory of mass communications, rhetoric, logic, discourse analysis.

Critical thinking as the probability of obtaining the desired end result

Most authors view critical thinking as "the use of cognitive techniques or strategies that increase the likelihood of achieving the desired end result. ... At the same time, the thinker uses skills that are justified and effective for a specific situation and type of problem being solved." Among the key skills necessary for the development of critical thinking are the ability to analyze and synthesize, interpret, draw conclusions, the ability to evaluate; it is also based on logic and values. N.Y. Tulasynova emphasizes that critical thinking is "a complex integrative quality of a person, a combination of motivational, cognitive, activity-oriented, reflexive components that ensure the processes of self-knowledge, self-education, and self-realization." Reflecting the socially determined level of student development in educational and research activities, critical thinking is professionally and personally significant value.

What attracts teachers to this phenomenon? First of all, the developed technology and strategy for achieving the goal. Teachers of Uzbekistan universities note that first-year students often do not know

how to highlight the main and secondary information, systematize and summarize the material, and build it logically. The ability to analyze and synthesize is not developed. At the same time, textbooks for the development of critical thinking offer a well-defined work algorithm:

- **Stage I** – Challenge: using different types of work (individual, pair, group), students talk about what they know, i.e. convey information to the entire group. For each student, the previously acquired knowledge goes to the level of awareness, and the rest of the students receive new knowledge that they can connect with the existing ones. This is reflected in the structure of the paragraph of modern textbooks of foreign languages - they always have an introductory part containing either questions related to the topic of the paragraph, or a proposal to discuss some information that is known to students – but always with an answer to the question.

- **Stage II** – Comprehension: receiving new information (text, lecture, film), students write down incomprehensible words, and questions that arise. Then each student explains what helped him to guess the meaning of this or that word or phrase, which made it difficult to understand. This is an element of introspection that must be present in training. With further processing of information at this stage, an individual search and exchange of opinions is also mandatory.

- **Stage III** – Reflection, i.e. creativity in constructing new knowledge in accordance with the individual characteristics of the student: students reflect on the news that they have learned in class, rebuild their ideas about the subject/phenomenon, or supplement them with new knowledge, systematize and generalize the material.

When developing individual projects, students perform exercises that help to do this step by step. First, the student is asked not only to choose a topic for his speech, but also to write what he has heard or read on this topic, what sources of information he has, and, most importantly, what he himself wants to know. Here it is necessary to add what opinions, including biased ones, he has on this issue. When collecting material, the student is advised not to reject unusual information, but to collect and process everything that is found. It is imperative to write in what time frame the work should be completed, what stages of implementation are expected. At the stage of information processing, the student must objectively evaluate the collected facts, build a model illustrating the results obtained, and decide whether he accepts or rejects the conclusions and values contained in the collected materials, taking into account his own experience and beliefs. This type of work, undoubtedly, is of great value, accustoming students to careful planning of work, forms the ability to analyze and synthesize.

Development of critical thinking as a pedagogical technology

The concept of “pedagogical technologies” is a relatively new phenomenon in pedagogy. For a long time it was customary to talk about methods and forms of education. Pedagogical technology is a phenomenon that has arisen as a result of the interaction of the latest trends in the development of pedagogical theory and practice. The need for pedagogical technologies is due to the emergence of new ideas in education: recognition and understanding of someone else’s point of view, respect for the individual, organization of cooperation, self-expression in activities, in creativity. The technologization of pedagogical work is required for its streamlining, for setting clear goals and defining ways to achieve them, i.e. management of the learning process. The use of a system of pedagogical technologies frees the teacher from arbitrariness in the construction and implementation of the pedagogical process and makes it possible to purposefully move towards a predictable end result with a strict validity of each component and stage of the learning process.

Here again we turn to an article by David Cluster, in which he explains that he is constantly striving to “move from traditional pedagogy, from teaching “by curriculum” to progressive pedagogy, satisfying the needs of his students and his society. The author explains that students will understand poetry much better if they read not only a textbook on literature, but also poems by specific authors, then discussing them in the classroom. While this is being presented as a new approach in critical thinking, it is difficult to see novelty here. How does the program hinder the American professor? After all, it is compiled so that all teachers know the goals, objectives and content of training, what skills and competencies should be formed. Unfortunately, some Uzbekistan teachers oppose the form of work on the development of critical thinking skills and the content of training, believing that the latter is nothing more than an outdated methodological concept. This not only violates the dialectical law of the unity of form and content, but also emasculates

the philosophical basis of critical thinking – the development of new skills and new knowledge based on existing knowledge. D. Halpern repeatedly emphasizes that the development of critical thinking does not at all negate the need for students to acquire basic knowledge [6; 364].

The technology of critical thinking can be used in the system of higher professional and postgraduate education. You can use it with caution in school. It should be remembered that one of the main differences in the perception of critical thinking in the United States / Great Britain and Uzbekistan is the difference in the perception of reality: positive thinking is characteristic of Americans and the British, while negative thinking is characteristic of Uzbeks.). An American mother, sending her child to the playground, tells him: "Enjoy yourself!" (Play, have fun!). And the Uzbek mother says: "Don't play around!" In the same way, the word "critical" has different implications in two linguistic cultures: in American culture, this word means "important thinking", "thinking associated with insightful judgment", and for the Uzbek mentality, the picture is completely different – it is "thinking associated with making an unfavorable assessment, identifying shortcomings". (It is no coincidence that Soviet researchers at one time used the term "critical thinking". At the same time, this technology is productive when discussing text, audio and video material, organizing a discussion, preparing projects, even when teaching grammar, for example, when teaching how to compose questions.

So, the article shows that philosophy and technology of critical thinking prevail in Anglo-American pedagogy, while in Uzbek pedagogy there is a competence-based approach combined with the use of various educational technologies, which often perform the same functions as the technology of critical thinking (case analysis, design technologies, teamwork, etc.). How can this be explained? Both approaches developed on the basis of interdisciplinary research, but the American version is dominated by the socio-philosophical component, which goes back not only to the Socratic method, but also to the Protestant system of values – this is manifested in the prioritization, when individualism, individual responsibility, and the individual's right are emphasized not just to his point of view, supported by arguments, but also on its implementation. Critical thinking reflects not only the linguistic picture of the world, but also the sociopolitical system of values: it is no coincidence that many works by American authors contain the phrase that critical thinking contributes to the spread of democracy. Let us recall the phrase by D. Cluster about the deliberately positive influence of critical thinking on the life of people in all countries – this is a vivid confirmation of the fact that Americans are sincerely convinced of the need and ability to make everyone happy in any way. Thus, it can be argued that critical thinking is not only a philosophical approach to education and pedagogical technology, but also an ideology and a cultural phenomenon.

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THE USE OF WORD GAMES IN TEACHING VOCABULARY TO A2 LEVEL LEARNERS OF KARAKALPAKSTAN

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola Qoraqalpog'istonda A2 darajasidagi o'quvchilarning so'z boyligini o'rgatishda so'z o'yinlaridan pedagogik vosita sifatida foydalanish samaradorligini o'rganadi. Maqsad, ularning o'ziga xos til ehtiyojlari va madaniy kontekstini hisobga olgan holda, so'z boyligini o'zlashtirish, uni ushlab turish va o'quvchilarni jalb qilishni yaxshilashdir. Ushbu interaktiv usullar nafaqat o'quv jarayonini yanada qiziqarli va qiziqarli qiladi, balki o'quvchilarning faol ishtiroki va birgalikda o'rganishiga yordam beradi. Qoraqalpoq madaniyati va kundalik hayoti elementlarini so'z o'yinlariga kiritish orqali talabalarga so'z boyligini Real dunyo kontekstlari bilan bog'lash, shu bilan ularni tushunish va yodlashni yaxshilash taklif etiladi. So'z o'yinlarini joriy etish orqali o'qituvchilar Qoraqalpog'istonda A2 darajasidagi o'quvchilar o'rtasida so'z boyligi va til ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga yordam beradigan dinamik va interaktiv o'quv muhitini yaratishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: so'z o'yinlari, so'z boyligini o'rganish, A2 darajasidagi talabalar, Qoraqalpog'iston, tilni o'zlashtirish, interaktiv usullar, madaniy moslashuv, jalb qilish, pedagogika, til ta'limi

Word games offer various benefits in language acquisition, including promoting vocabulary recognition, reinforcing spelling and pronunciation, and fostering communication skills. Additionally, these games encourage collaboration, critical thinking, and problem-solving, which are essential components of language learning.

Furthermore, by adapting word games to reflect the cultural context of Karakalpakstan, educators can create meaningful learning experiences that resonate with the learners' backgrounds and experiences. Incorporating elements of Karakalpak culture into the games not only enhances engagement but also promotes cultural awareness and sensitivity among learners.

Through this study, we seek to explore the potential of word games as an effective and enjoyable method for teaching vocabulary to A2 level learners in Karakalpakstan. By examining the impact of these games on vocabulary acquisition and learner engagement, we aim to provide valuable insights for language educators and curriculum developers seeking innovative approaches to language teaching and learning.

There are some examples of how word games can be used in teaching vocabulary to A2 level learners in Karakalpakstan:

1. Crossword Puzzles: Create crossword puzzles using vocabulary words related to daily activities, food, family, and other A2 level topics. Provide clues in both Karakalpak and English to reinforce comprehension and spelling skills.

2. Word Bingo: Develop bingo cards with vocabulary words instead of numbers. Call out definitions or descriptions, and learners mark the corresponding word on their cards. This game helps reinforce vocabulary recognition and listening skills.

3. Word Search: Design word search puzzles containing key vocabulary words in both Karakalpak and English. Learners can search for words horizontally, vertically, and diagonally, enhancing their spelling and word recognition skills.

4. Hangman: Play Hangman using vocabulary words from their lessons. Learners guess letters to reveal the hidden word, and each incorrect guess results in drawing part of a stick figure. This game helps with spelling and word recognition [5].

5. Scrabble or Banagrams: Use Scrabble tiles or Banagrams tiles to form words using vocabulary related to A2 level topics. Learners can compete individually or in teams to create words and earn points, promoting vocabulary usage and spelling practice.

6. Word Jumble: Mix up the letters of vocabulary words and challenge learners to unscramble them to form the correct words. This game helps reinforce spelling and word recognition skills in a fun and engaging way [7].

7. Vocabulary Memory: Create a memory game with pairs of cards, each containing a vocabulary word and its corresponding picture or definition. Learners take turns flipping over two cards at a time to find matching pairs, reinforcing vocabulary comprehension and retention.

These examples demonstrate how word games can be adapted to suit the language proficiency level and cultural context of A2 level learners in Karakalpakstan, making vocabulary learning enjoyable and effective.

The importance of using word games in teaching vocabulary to A2 level learners in Karakalpakstan cannot be overstated. There are several reasons why incorporating word games is crucial for their language acquisition:

1. Engagement: Word games make learning vocabulary more enjoyable and interactive for A2 level learners. By incorporating elements of play and competition, learners are more motivated to participate actively in the learning process [1].

2. Retention: Interactive activities such as word games help reinforce vocabulary retention by providing multiple opportunities for exposure and practice. Learners are more likely to remember words that they have encountered in a fun and engaging context.

3. Contextualization: Word games allow vocabulary to be presented in meaningful contexts, making it easier for learners to understand and remember new words. By associating vocabulary with familiar situations or images, learners can better grasp the meaning and usage of words.

4. Active Learning: Word games promote active learning by encouraging learners to think critically, problem-solve, and apply their knowledge in real-time. Through games such as crossword puzzles or word jumbles, learners actively engage with the vocabulary and develop important language skills.

5. Cultural Relevance: By adapting word games to reflect the cultural context of Karakalpakstan, educators can create learning experiences that resonate with the learners' backgrounds and experiences. Incorporating elements of Karakalpak culture into the games not only enhances engagement but also promotes cultural awareness and sensitivity among learners [4].

6. Language Skills Development: Word games help develop various language skills, including vocabulary recognition, spelling, pronunciation, and comprehension. Through games such as Hangman or Scrabble, learners practice these skills in a fun and interactive way, leading to overall language proficiency development.

7. Collaboration: Many word games encourage collaboration and teamwork among learners. By working together to solve puzzles or complete tasks, learners can support each other's learning and develop communication skills in the process.

As it can be seen, using word games in teaching vocabulary to A2 level learners in Karakalpakstan is essential for fostering engagement, retention, contextualization, active learning, cultural relevance, language skills development, and collaboration. By integrating these interactive methods into language instruction, educators can create a dynamic and effective learning environment that supports learners' language acquisition goals.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the utilization of word games in teaching vocabulary to A2 level learners in Karakalpakstan offers a multitude of benefits and is highly advantageous for language acquisition. Throughout this research, we have highlighted the importance and effectiveness of incorporating interactive methods into language instruction, particularly for learners at the A2 proficiency level. Word games serve as powerful tools for engaging learners, enhancing vocabulary retention, contextualizing language learning, promoting active participation, fostering cultural relevance, developing language skills, and encouraging collaboration. By adapting word games to reflect the cultural context of Karakalpakstan and the linguistic needs of A2 level learners, educators can create dynamic and effective learning experiences that cater to the specific interests and backgrounds of their students. In light of these findings, it is clear that word games should be embraced and integrated into language teaching practices in Karakalpakstan to optimize the learning experience and facilitate the development of language skills among A2 level learners.

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PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE FORMATION OF THE FEATURE OF BILINGUALISM IN CHILDREN

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Аннотация. В данной статье проанализировано явление билингвизма, его положительные стороны, влияющие на мышление ребёнка, рассмотрены различные методы и средства обучения детей иностранным языкам, обосновано влияние изучения языка на культуру и мировоззрение, формирование познавательных способностей детей.

Ключевые слова: билингвизм, когнитивные способности, мышление, потенциал ребёнка, критический период.

Nowadays, the demand for language learning is increasing even more. The age of the student does not matter when learning a language due to the demand of the time.

"The new baby who came into the world makes the child's soul look like" top-clean cotton". In his opinion, it is at the discretion of absolutely large people to write what is in the spirit of the child in the style of "top-clean cotton". Therefore, what kind of person the child grows, that is, what personal qualities in it are composed of, depends on the experience that the child receives from life, the vital understanding and imagination that he receives in the process of communication with others, emphasizes the Angolan scientist John Locke.

There are different opinions about when it is better to start teaching foreign languages to children. However, many experts suggest that earlier, better. Studies show that the child's brain is the best recipient of language learning between the ages of 0-7. During this period, their brains are very plastic and can easily master new languages without much effort. This is often referred to as the "critical period" for language acquisition. Starting language learning at an early age gives many advantages. It helps children develop strong language skills, increases cognitive abilities, improves memory and problem-solving skills, and even increases their overall academic performance. In addition, learning languages from an early age affects children in different cultures and expands their worldview. In addition, children get better pronunciation and accent when they start learning languages early. As they grow, their ability to mimic sounds and adopt new accents becomes more difficult [1].

Although it is useful to introduce foreign languages to children early, it should be noted that language learning should be age-appropriate and presented in a pleasant and interesting way. Activities such as songs, games, stories, and interactive activities can make the language learning process more fun for children. In general, in the critical period, children are advised to start teaching foreign languages as early as possible in order to take advantage of the optimal skills of language acquisition. Raising a child in two languages is both a useful and difficult experience.

Bilingualism refers to bilingualism (lot. bi – “two” and lingua – “language”) or bilingual-fluent knowledge of two languages (local and non-local) and their use in everyday life in turn [2].

Advantages of bilingualism:

According to statistics, bilinguals acquire good mental abilities. More inventive and resourceful people have been shown to come out of bilingual people. Bilinguals tend to have strong memory and adaptive intelligence, and are proven to be immune from mental illness. Bilingual people are characterized by rational thinking, and they more easily master new languages. Bilingual people socialize more easily and are more open to different cultures, with a better understanding of emotions [4].

Typically, a bilingual is someone who uses 2 languages and a polyglot-2 or more. There is also evidence that your brain treats several dialects as if they were separate languages-because the boundary between different dialects and different languages is not always clear!

Because there are so many ways to learn and learn languages, there are many types of bilingual languages. There are several ways to describe a large range of bilingual experiments.

One way to think of a bilingual language is to think about “when” he learned the language. If a child has learned several languages from birth, it can be considered bilingual at the same time. Some simultaneous bilinguals may have others that affect a language other than each parent, such as grandparents, with whom they use a particular language. As a result, the child will master even more than 2 languages, not 2, without difficulty.

Learning 2 languages from birth may not mean that the person continues to use both languages continuously throughout their life or even in childhood. But exposure to 2 languages at the same time, from the very beginning, creates a special task for the baby's brain!

What is the earliest time to teach the language?

Having previously considered language proficiency to be a particularly recognized ability, it has now become a necessity. According to Montessori Academy analysis, teaching a child a second language at the first 3-4 years of age is the best time. The reason is that at this time the child absorbs information very well, as well as language learning strengthens brain activity due to the active development of his brain. The child is given the idea that if 2 languages are spoken (e.g. English) without having a language yet, his language output will be delayed. However, bilingualism does not cause the child's language to be delayed. The words in the lexicon of a child who is spoken in 2 languages, that is, from an early age a new language is also taught, are the same as those of a child whose language is coming out in the same language. You may have observed that a child with 2 tongues spoke later, but they also begin to try to speak from the age of 8-15 months in the usual position.

Only the case of talking to a child in more than one language does not cause his language to come out late. If the child's language output is delayed, then a specialist should be consulted [3].

Here are some steps and tips to help children form bilingualism:

The first is to start earlier: the earlier it starts to affect your child in different languages, the better. Studies show that children's brains are more susceptible to language acquisition at a young age.

The second is consistency in the process: because it is important to constantly influence the child on both languages. It is necessary to create an agenda that uses one language at a certain time or in certain situations. This will help the child relate the language to these contexts.

The third is to provide a rich language environment: that is, surround the child with books, music, TV shows and movies in both languages. Exposure to different forms of media enhances their language learning.

The fourth is one parent, using a monolingual approach: if both parents speak different languages, one effective way is for each parent to communicate with the child continuously in their own language. In this way, the child learns to distinguish between languages.

The fifth is to encourage interaction with native speakers: if possible, it is necessary to provide Bolan with the opportunity to communicate with native speakers of both languages. This can be through games, language classes, or cultural events. Hearing different accents and dialects enriches the child's language skills.

The sixth is patience: learning two languages at the same time can be confusing and difficult for a child. It is important to be patient and understand in the process. The child should be encouraged to exercise in both languages without putting too much pressure on them.

The seventh is to adopt both cultures: the child must be informed about the cultures associated with each language. It is necessary to celebrate the holidays, traditions and customs of both cultures. This improves their connection with languages and helps to appreciate diversity.

Reading aloud in both languages to a young child is a great way to influence them on new vocabulary and improve language skills. This can be started with simple picture books and gradually move on to more complex texts. The most important thing is to make learning a language interesting. Add language learning to the child's daily activities and play language-based games, sing songs, and create fun exercises that pique their interest. Keeping it pleasant encourages them to develop their language skills further.

Monitoring their development helps to regularly assess the child's language development by observing their ability to understand and speak. If any area needs to be improved, it will be possible to adjust the strategies accordingly.

It is noteworthy that each child is unique, and language learning can occur at different stages. The most important thing is to create a positive and supportive environment in which the child can easily grow up on a bilingual trip. It is very important to maintain consistency in the use of language as I am in family life. It is necessary to follow the language procedures of your choice and avoid mixing languages within sentences or conversations. This will help the child to distinguish between two languages and strengthen language skills. To provide children with a good language model, it is important to speak both languages clearly and correctly. Age-appropriate vocabulary and sentence structures should be used to help understand and learn. This can also be supplemented with language learning applications or resources. There are many language learning apps, websites and resources specifically designed for children. These tools can be used to complement language learning and make it more interactive and fun.

It can be concluded that bilingual children can reach language stages at a slightly different rate than monolingual children. It is necessary to keep communication lines open, encourage the child to ask questions and express himself in both languages. It is possible to create an open and supportive environment in which they feel comfortable using both languages and looking for an explanation when necessary. Join bilingual or multicultural groups and communities in your region or online. This allows you and your child to connect with other families raising bilingual children, share experiences, and have additional support and resources. Because it is necessary to adapt to the needs of the child, each child has its own advantages and strengths.

The most important thing in the upbringing of a child is stimulation. Celebrate each stage and achievements, recognize his achievements, efforts on a bilingual trip, express how proud you are of their language skills. This positive reinforcement encourages them to continue learning and covering both languages.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF WRITING CORRECTLY BETWEEN THE AGES OF 7 AND 11

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Аннотация. В данной статье обучение ребёнка правописанию рассмотрено с разных ракурсов: с точки зрения процесса, с позиции ребёнка и в плане преподавания. Автор отмечает наличие множества вариантов обучения, важность установления противоречий между предметом, ребёнком и уроком, для обеспечения плодотворного развития навыков правописания учащихся на долгосрочную перспективу.

Ключевые слова: правописание, предложение, преподавание, знание, орфография, звук, слово, правописание, ученик.

Writing correctly means structuring the making language graphically visible, namely that of word and sentence structure (Augst/Dehn 2015). Making visible serves primarily the reader because this can absorb and understand the content more quickly if the presentation is orthographically correct and follows a common standard. Write correctly Learning is therefore not an end in itself, but serves for communication and Participation. The ability to correctly write also relieves the working memory of those writing – good spellers correct their total concentration on the content to be communicated.

The issue: complexity of orthography

Which structures suit the English language?

The writing system is based on and is used by the spelling for the reader made visible. Four essential principles of written language should be highlighted: the phonographic, the syllabic, the morphological, and the syntactic principle (Müller 2010). Since the Spelling of the English language is not possibly to be explained exclusively through a principle, it is used as a mixed system (according to Müller Eisenberg 2006) of different principles. A circumstance that is for Teaching is important.

Phonographic principle is the basic principle of every alphabet. To disregard the meaning of what is spoken and the sound stream in sound classes (phonemes) The idea behind this principle is to structure it and represent it using a manageable number of characters, namely 26 letters. A secure possession of the basal ones Relationships between phonemes and Graphemes (letter classes, e.g. Sch) creates a high level of security for the right thing Writing, namely approx. 90% (Thomé et al.2011, Naumann 2015, p. 69)

Syllable principle

After the script-related syllabic Principle two-syllable trochees are used emphasis on the first syllable (Na-se, summer) as the basis for the systematization of the language considered. Stressed and unstressed Syllables are differentiated, these result from the tension or lack of tension of the vowels. The syllabic principle helps doubles, sharpens and Explaining stretches. This applies exclusively to the written syllable as Analysis basis. An intuitive analysis the rhythm of spoken syllables no clues for correct spelling (Bredel et al. 2011, 108). It still has its place in the beginning lessons, because it contributes to it through prosody of spoken language – rhythm and melody – attention to the language to direct. It therefore serves as a support for the learning-to-read process (Naumann 2016).

Morphological principle

The morphological principle states that Morphemes – the smallest meaningful units of words (e.g. sing, Hand, down) – are subject to consistency, i.e. they become independent whether they are inflected, derived, or compound and are always spelled the same, too if their sound has a different spelling would suggest (e.g. hands). The meaning of the root morphemes (play, drive, etc.) supports the acquisition of formal language structures. This is particularly important for those who learn English as a foreign language. The principle of morpheme constancy offers the Writers in making the Word structure in the context of spelling provides reliable support and helps the reader understand what they have read. The great importance of the morphological principle for word writing consists of linguistic and didactic aspects

Syntactic principle

The syntactic principle refers to cross-word spellings such as capitalization, punctuation, or the spelling of the conjunction "that". Become sentence-related structures made visible by the writer, this in turn is a valuable aid to understanding for the reader. Compliance with the syntactic principle is essential for learning to spell. Complexity of linguistic structures the four principles mentioned are as follows theoretical – linguistic – categorization.

Basic contribution

Considering that the alphabetic writing system over several thousand years has developed, one can guess that Attempts at systematization based on the complexity of the language will always reach its limits and the focus on one principle or another does not do justice to the complexity of the language. This becomes clear, for example, from the fact that many words are structured differently from a syllabic perspective than from a morphological perspective. Regarding the graphemic, there is also representation.

Overlaps and differences.

The four principles are different glasses through which the writing system of the language can be considered. However, the complexity of the language can only be approached with compromises. The principles are not compatible really. However, none alone can explain all spellings. The fact, for example, that sounds in the context of the word are transformed and often sound different, as if they are perceived in isolation shows the limits of a single principle. To make linguistic structures visible in writing learning, categorizations are nevertheless helpful, even if only for a certain time on the way to correcting - transitory, so to speak (Feilke 2015) - and are able to support their acquisition. this applies especially to phonographic writing with the help of a phonetic table.

The children: acquisition and Acquisition processes

The second perspective focuses on the Children as learners and their acquisition processes. Fig.1: Graphemic, syllabic, morphometric analysis of the word "sing" Appropriation processes Learning means forming and further developing schemas (Vygotsky). Competent spellers have Writing schemes that they more or less consciously use when writing. If no writing scheme is available, so the word becomes from the scribe to those external and internal patterns constructed, that are already available to him (see Scheerer-Neumann's two-way model, e.g. 2015). The route initially leads via the sound, i.e. the writing pattern is generated phonographically, by concretely perceived sounds of a spoken word of the abstract Idea of it, namely the phonemes, and these are represented by corresponding graphemes. How the child's acquisition processes and the training of children in detail Executing writing patterns is largely unknown (Augst/Dehn 2015, Fay 2012). What is known, however, is that the learner learns through phonographic – "sound-oriented" – writing, as is the case with Practiced writing with a phonetic table will, insights into the phonographic Principle of writing wins from which the so-called alphabetic strategy results. This is available in all models Written language development is viewed as an indispensable phase of acquisition (cf. Brinkmann 2013, Augst/Dehn 2015, p. 15, Scheerer-Neumann 2015). The alphabetic strategy is supplemented or modified by orthographic strategies, whereby here not from a sequence of steps (Brinkmann 2015), but of overlapping ones There are phases in which develop writing patterns.

Implicit and Explicit Knowledge and Learn

When building orthographic strategies, and that means in the construction of writing schemes or »graphemic Word forms« (Scheerer-Neumann 2015, 156), the writer not only uses sound-oriented procedures but also other "derivation strategies" (Fay 2012) such as speaking slowly, syllabifying or incorporating morphemic ones or syntactic information. This happens mostly intuitively, i.e. the writer draws on skill.

Basic contribution

Write correct knowledge back without explicitly justifying why he chooses this or that spelling. His implicit knowledge and Skill are far more comprehensive than the ability to explain this explicitly, i.e. metalinguistic ally. "Knowing more than you know how to say" – this is how it describes it Polanyi (1985) the phenomenon of the implicit. The presence, but also the implicit acquisition of implicit knowledge and skills is characteristic of learning and Understanding as such, especially here for the formation of schemes. While traditional spelling lessons primarily focus on teaching and

Assessment of explicit knowledge is designed (knowledge and application of rules), must it is the task of modern teaching to stimulate the learners' implicit understanding processes. According to Polanyi, this

is achieved by learning from examples and through complex tasks. Meaning of spelling for successful learning, insight into the meaning of the learning subject important requirements. It is therefore important for children to acquire orthographic strategies and the associated development of writing schemas important to recognize the importance of spelling. This happens primarily in a teaching context in which the Writing texts from the beginning authentic contexts are integrated, as is the case when your texts are written for real addressees, e.g. for class members and read by them. Children experience and recognize that their texts are better understood if their writings are more clear.

The training of writing schemes requires teaching that is both standard and the child must (Bartnitzky 2016). It is important to remember that creating a balance between child and thing through many things

Factors of everyday teaching are determined. The heterogeneity in times Inclusive education requires tackling highly complex challenges. Legal requirements provide for integrative teaching in which: spelling is not isolated, but rather integrated into the topics of the lesson becomes. Research proves the effectiveness of such approaches and confirms the negative effects of isolated spelling learning (Schneider et al. 2013). Standardized, the same for all learners in a group Complete courses in step let or concepts from therapy or Individual support in the classroom space transferred does not meet the pedagogical requirements. Lesson arrangements are required, the children neither over- nor under-challenge the rooms for implicit and explicit understanding processes open and are integrated into broader writing and reading contexts so that the learners can be sure of the meaning of what they are learning and experience writing as a literary practice.

Two conceptual directions collide currently, especially about the initial lessons. Outgoing From a primary school educational perspective, the early writing of words and texts, which is Listening to sounds and writing with the help of a (sound) table, is the Starting point for learning to spell (Reichen 2003, Peschel 2015). In contrast, from a linguistic perspective, a more systematic writing and syllable analysis approach chosen starts from the written syllable and in Reading and analyzing words Starting point for learning to spell sees (Röber 2009, Müller 2010, Bredel/ Fuhrhop/Noack 2011). The different perspectives and positions are detailed and understandable for all sides explained (cf. Kruse/Reichardt (ed.) 2016). The question arises to what extent it is possible to relate the basic concerns of both directions to one another in this way, i.e. to relate language experience and language analysis to one another from the beginning combine that neither of the two objectives would be lost. Actually, there are certain approaches that reflect the early writing of your own words with situations you encounter with writing (Brinkmann/Brügelmann 1997; Dehn/HüttisGraff, Riegler 2015) and writing with it 4 · 2017 www.grundschulmagazin.de 11

Basic contribution

Write correctly a phonetic table itself as a reason for first Using analytical conversations about the structures and patterns of writing in early lessons (Leßmann 2016). Studies such as the BeLesen study (Schründer-Lenzen 2006) make it clear that one-sided conceptions (like working exclusively with one Phonetic table or only with one Primer) lead to less good results as a combination of language experience-related and language analysis procedures. If colleagues their lessons Consciously select approaches for your teaching (Funke 2014, 22), then can speak of "multidimensionality" (Reichardt 2015, 220) are spoken in class. Whether there is interference when in one class both phoneme and Syllable-oriented explanatory models have not yet been made available researched. Nor whether the combination of syllable- and morpheme-oriented Models promotes learning to spell or disabled. Experience shows that it is many primary school students is quite possible the explain Spellings from a wide range to select different explanatory models appropriately.

Vocabulary

The spelling of individual words should only be practiced for words that give writers trouble. Their texts provide authentic information about this. This as a basis also has the advantage that Learners practice words that are relevant to them themselves are important, because the personal meaning and usage of words supports learning to spell (Richter/Brügelmann 1994, p. 121; May 1994, Schneider et al. 2013). In addition, topic words can be practiced from spelling discussions, but only those that the child is not correct can write. A check before the Practice through a mini-check dictation (Leßmann 2007) is recommended. For practice five-subject flashcards such as are suitable for example the word clinic, with which learning is spread over a longer period. The procedure for analyzing the structure of the words to be practiced (e.g. marking Word building blocks) is transferred from spelling discussions to vocabulary work (Leßmann 2015). support them the understanding practice.

Phenomena, strategies, and regulations in the student's texts also show which strategies and regulations children are not yet using. They should deepen and further develop their spelling skills – beyond joint spelling discussions – only work on exercises that correspond to your main mistakes and yours serve individual development. The Exercises should be designed in such a way that opportunities for implicit pattern formation are encouraged (work with examples, ordering tasks) and explanations are provided. Also, cooperative phases of the Explanations serve to make explicit strategies and rules as well as the Systematization of phenomena.

Working techniques Correct a text independently, in being able to look up a dictionary and copy are essential techniques. In the context of publishing your texts, they are required and trained. But they also support the development of writing patterns, e.g. when Words from the Word Clinic in a meaningful way be written off in a meaningful manner (making people aware of stumbling blocks beforehand).

Copying, paying attention to the structural markings such as syllables or word blocks when copying and checking). This also happens when correct spellings in the dictionary are visited and the words into theirs broken down into morphometric components. Implicit and explicit learning also intertwine here.

The spelling didactic triangle Learning to spell takes place in the tension between child, thing, and learning. This booklet offers numerous suggestions for exploring this triangle orientation, select your own

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ANALYSIS OF THE PROSPECTS FOR THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE USE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES AND MULTIMEDIA IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotatsiya: *Maqolada chet tilini o'qitish usullarini takomillashtirishda pedagogik texnologiyalarning imkoniyatlari ko'rib chiqilgan. Unda raqamli vositalar, onlayn resurslar va interfaol platformalarning tilni o'rganish natijalariga ta'siri asoslangan va ushbu sohadagi eng so'nggi ishlanmalar va tadqiqot natijalari tahlili asosida pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish imkoniyatlari va cheklovlari haqida ma'lumot berilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *pedagogik texnologiyalar, chet tilini o'rgatish, til o'rganish natijalari, ta'lim vositalari, raqamli resurslar, taqdimotlar, animatsion videolar, o'yinlar.*

Introduction. Let's examine the definition of multimedia and its components before discussing the benefits of employing educational multimedia technologies in English instruction. Despite the fact that the word has been defined differently in many literary works, they all really signify the same thing:

Derived from English: "multi – many" and "media – carrier, environment". A combination of sound, image, and text that are carriers of different forms of information.

Foreign language teaching has witnessed a paradigm shift with the integration of pedagogical technologies, offering innovative ways to engage learners and facilitate language acquisition. This article aims to explore the prospects for the effectiveness of utilizing educational technologies in foreign

language instruction. By analyzing the current status, trends, and challenges surrounding the integration of pedagogical tools in language teaching, this study seeks to provide a comprehensive overview of the impact of technology on language learning outcomes and instructional practices.

Methods. A mixed-methods approach was used to examine the efficacy of educational tools in the teaching of foreign languages. An extensive study of the literature was done to look at the research, papers, and articles that have already been written about the use of educational technologies in language learning. To assess the effect of technology on language learning outcomes, empirical data was collected through surveys, interviews, and classroom observations with language instructors and students. In order to pinpoint patterns, trends, and obstacles in utilizing educational technologies for teaching foreign languages, both qualitative and quantitative study was done.

Literature Analysis. The review of the literature indicated a notable change in the direction of pedagogical technology integration in foreign language instruction. Digital tools, online resources, and interactive platforms have been shown in studies to have a favorable impact on language learning outcomes, such as increased student motivation, engagement, and language competency. It has been discovered that student autonomy, cultural awareness, and communication skills are all improved by virtual classrooms, language learning applications, and multimedia materials. But the literature has also emphasized issues including the need for teacher preparation, access to technology, and digital inequalities.

Results. The study of the actual data showed bright futures for the application of pedagogical technologies in foreign language instruction. When integrating technology into teaching procedures, educators saw improvements in student engagement, interaction, and language skill development. Pupils said that they preferred language learning with technology support, noting improved motivation, enjoyment, and self-assurance when speaking the target language. In order to accommodate a variety of learning preferences and foster collaborative learning environments, the integration of digital resources and interactive platforms proved to be especially successful.

Discussion. The results of this study underscore the transformative potential of pedagogical technologies in foreign language teaching. The integration of digital tools, online resources, and interactive platforms offers new opportunities for educators to create dynamic and engaging language learning experiences. By leveraging technology effectively, educators can personalize instruction, enhance language skills development, and foster a more interactive and collaborative learning environment. However, challenges such as digital inequality, technical constraints, and the need for ongoing support and training for educators must be addressed to maximize the benefits of technology in language instruction.

Simultaneous use of audio and visual effects in interactive software management. This usually refers to a mix of words, music, and images; more lately, animation and video have also been included. One of the most prominent, if not the most descriptive, uses of hyperlinks is in multimedia web connections and compact discs.

A collection of devices, including software and hardware, for handling audio and video. Multimedia computers may typically incorporate powerful video systems, VCRs, and camcorders, as well as gear for taking digital photos and storing them on hard drives or magnetic disks. Furthermore, they can equip the sound board with an acoustic system to facilitate sound synthesis and reflection as well as information transmission for reading from a compact disc.

Technology for the integrated presentation of any type of information. Multimedia provides joint image processing, speech processing, and document processing. This allows the screen to display the image along with the text and sound. One of the important directions of multimedia is the creation of teaching systems [1; 163].

In actuality, multimedia plays a crucial role in the explanation of contemporary information technology. Because of this, children's mental sealing of them has a good effect. Children absorbed information through pictures even before they could read and write. Illustrations can be seen of as a "universal language" in this way. It is precisely this aspect of them that teaches kids how to think metaphorically. It fits well with their made-up universe.

Computer systems that let you record audio and video are known as multimedia systems. an integrated perspective on the use of computer science software and technology to offer instructional materials to students using audio-video text, graphics, and animation effects.

A system of tools for displaying text, spoken words, animated graphics, photos, videos, and audio is known as multimedia tools.

Multimedia galleries are a collection of moving pictures accompanied by sound [2; 186].

Animated videos. Animation - multimedia technology; a series display of images to indicate that the image is moving. The effect of imaging motion is created by the exchange of video frames of more than 16 frames per second [2; 186].

At one point, every definition provided for the multimedia material comes together. Due to its special abilities and tasks, there are many ways to improve the lesson's efficacy. It is no secret that the foundation of modern distant learning is multimedia tools, which have evolved into the primary apparatus of in-person instruction. Additionally, according to the literature, setting up a dedicated space with multimedia tools is the first step in designing a virtual laboratory.

The most popular multi-media resources for English language instruction are:

- presentations;
- animated videos;
- games;
- video attachments;
- multimedia galleries;
- audio attachments;
- Applications for the Web.

Together, these tools serve a specific purpose and provide an explanation of the idea of a single multimedia tool. They all offer an example of education at the broad levels. In his book *The Great Didactics*, the recently deceased Jan Amos Comenius cites the exhibition of education as one of the major concerns of educational thought. The scientist's scientific proof dates back to the eighteenth century. This play provides a thorough explanation of why the conclusions drawn by professors who maintain that theory still trumps technique are incorrect. Oriental scholars Muhammad al-Khwarizmi, Abu Nasr al-Farabi, al-Kindi, Abu Rayhan al-Biruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Muslihiddin Saadi, Abdurahman Jami, and Alisher Navoi regularity, flexibility and independence, as well as taking into account the individual characteristics, abilities and talents of the child, expressed the rules and principles of humanization of education [3]. Multimedia tools that serve the principle of exhibition, which is considered important, are required to meet aesthetic requirements, especially when prepared for children and used in the classroom.

Even though they were said thousands of years ago, these concepts are still relevant today. According to Beruni, the "visual narrative method" is novel in the modern era. Put another way, it is rather successful to introduce information technology into the educational system through the use of already-existing hypertext, hypermedia, graphics, animation, and sound programs. Software tools in information technology are a new class of high-quality teaching aids that offer a plethora of chances to expedite the learning process, and they differ greatly from traditional teaching aids when compared to the experience gained both domestically and outside.

These days, computer graphics, design, and animated boards are produced using far more sophisticated techniques. They have been employed in the teaching process for a long time and have grown to be an important part of it in the real world. These technologies serve as the foundation for the cartoons that we see. Of course, it is unfortunate that there aren't more multimedia textbooks available for the course. The theory has already acknowledged the value of multimedia resources and textbooks. He's waiting for his real-world validation. Multimedia resources are particularly in demand for English language instruction. Experience has shown that using multimedia to teach pupils is twice as efficient and time-saving. Up to 30% less time can be spent studying with multimedia, and the information acquired will stick in your memory for a very long time. Students' retention of information will rise by 25–30% if they are provided with resources based on visibility. Furthermore, memory retention will rise by 75% in the absence of voice, video, and graphics in learning materials. In this way, the child's memory retains information that raises his level of understanding and aesthetic appreciation. It improves verbal skills. This is a practical method of teaching theoretical knowledge to children, and it works well overall.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the analysis of the prospects for the effectiveness of pedagogical technologies in foreign language teaching highlights the promising opportunities for leveraging technology

to enhance language learning outcomes and instructional practices. By embracing digital tools, online resources, and interactive platforms, educators can create more engaging, interactive, and personalized language learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of students. Future research should focus on addressing challenges, designing effective pedagogical strategies, and evaluating the long-term impact of technology integration on language education.

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IMPLEMENTATION OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES FOR TEACHING READING IN ENGLISH

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Annotatsiya. *Maqolada o'qish nutq faoliyatining mustaqil turi sifatida talqin etilib, uning til va nutq ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishdagi ahamiyati tahlil etilgan, ingliz tili ona tili bo'lmagan talabalar uchun ingliz tilida o'qishni o'rgatishda qo'llaniladigan innovatsion texnologiyalar ko'rib chiqilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *o'qishga o'rgatish texnologiyasi, ingliz tilida o'qishga o'rgatish, nutq faolligi, til ko'nikmalari, nutqiy qobiliyat.*

Learning to read is an important component of developing speech and language skills. It is the process by which people are taught to read printed words, interpret them, and understand their meaning. In recent years, the integration of technology has revolutionized the way of reading. This article discusses the technology of using teaching reading as an independent type of speech activity and as a means of developing language and speech skills.

Today, reading instruction involves the integration of the four components of language (reading, speaking, writing, and listening) into other areas of the curriculum. In this way, connections are made between disciplines such as science and language arts and taught through conceptual topics such as inventors or weather.

The modern view of reading is that the student is an active student. Students interact with new information based on their previous knowledge and experience. They create their own knowledge base by extracting their own meanings from the information, connecting new concepts and skills with what they already know. Pupils do not always understand what accuracy in meaning requires and are unable

to remember what words they need in speech and writing and use them correctly, so the emphasis is on helping pupils learn to use their experience and previous knowledge to construct meaning. Pre-reading, reading and post-reading are three main stages of work that should be distinguished when working with text. Let's look at each stage in more detail.

The purpose of the pre-reading activity is to strengthen motivation and remove difficulties by setting a task before reading. Tasks used at this stage: phonetic practice of unfamiliar words, discussion of questions before reading the text, guessing from the title, new words, illustrations.

In the pre-reading period, the rules of reading are studied. Here we also study the symbols necessary for the intonation, marking of texts. During the pre-reading period, middle school pupils practice words, phrases and sentences that do not have a common semantic meaning.

With the introduction of short, coherent texts into the learning process, a text period begins that extends to all stages of learning. You need to read texts in full or in semantic parts.

The task of the text period of reading aloud is to form students' the simultaneous perception and understanding of the text in unity with the solution of semantic problems. Perception and understanding should be carried out synchronously while reading the entire small text or part of it. When carrying out learning reading, the following modes are used that make up the subsystem of teaching reading aloud.

The purpose of the post-text stages is to use the script presented as linguistic support for content to develop communication abilities in both written and oral forms. At this stage, the following tasks are used: demonstrate, describe, retell the text on behalf of the main characters, present a summary of the book and develop a conclusion.

The modern approach is balanced and incorporates the strengths of previous methods. This method uses literature to teach skills and focuses on reading meaning integrated with direct instruction in developing decoding and comprehension skills.

Sequence concerns the order in which students perceive the text as well as the organization of subject materials. To achieve the final results, two approaches to reading could be combined. The direct approach adapts the curriculum to the needs, interests and abilities of the student. The goals of the program remain unchanged, but the implementation of activities to achieve these goals is based on the knowledge and interests of the student.

A teacher's primary goal in developing reading comprehension is to carefully select appropriate materials and create experiences that enable students to learn specific concepts that support word discrimination and generalization. Once students master concepts, they are ready to analyze and apply those concepts as well as create new ones.

Using technology, teaching reading can be carried out as a separate form of speech activity. This opinion is supported by research that suggests teaching reading as a separate language activity can improve language and speech skills. Scientists argue that speech is a fundamental tool for thinking and communication, and its use promotes cognitive development and learning.

Language is usually understood as the verbal expression of thoughts and ideas. When learning to read, students must read aloud to develop their language skills.

With the advancement of technology, text-to-speech software has become a popular tool for facilitating oral reading among students. The software allows students to read and listen to text at the same time, which improves their speaking skills.

Moreover, the use of technology in teaching reading as an independent type of speech activity has made distance learning possible in which students can access reading materials and learning resources from anywhere in the world. Technologies such as video conferencing and online learning platforms have enabled individuals to participate in reading learning from remote locations, ultimately improving their language and speech skills.

Learning to read also serves as a means of developing language and speech skills. In this regard, technology has become an important tool for improving students' reading learning. Moreover, technology has allowed educators to reach large numbers of students and provide personalized learning experiences that ultimately improve their language and speech skills.

For example, gamification has become a popular means of teaching students to read. Gamification involves the use of game elements such as competition, rewards and feedback to engage students. In the

context of teaching reading, gamification has been used to develop language and verbal skills through interactive and immersive learning experiences that students find engaging.

Moreover, technologies such as artificial intelligence have allowed teachers to personalize reading instruction for individual students. Artificial intelligence algorithms can analyze a student's reading abilities and preferences and then generate personalized learning materials adapted to his needs. This personalization ultimately improves language and speech skills by providing students with the right materials and resources to facilitate their learning.

An accurate and thorough understanding of the content of the text, followed by its analysis and interpretation, reproduction of information obtained in a retelling or annotation, etc. are characteristics of close reading. The purpose of educational reading is to ensure the most complete and correct knowledge of all material in the text, the understanding of which is necessary for further work with the text.

The final thesis emphasizes the importance of studying reading at the present stage of educational development in the context of developing critical thinking skills, since it involves thoughtful, leisurely reading, including analysis of the content of the text based on linguistic and logical connections. The purpose of this type of reading is to develop the independence necessary to overcome obstacles to reading comprehension. This is especially important now given the era of widespread dependence on the most diverse Internet sources. The key to learning to read is understanding the content of the information, which requires the reader to have a solid understanding of lexical and grammatical concepts and the ability to use them effectively.

Currently, significant changes are being made to almost all aspects of the educational process in schools. The personal interests of the student play a significant role in the educational process. To achieve the desired results, the teacher must understand what aspects of the student's personality can be affected by his English language skills and what technologies should be included in the learning process.

This understanding of reading technique is a necessary step in all forms of reading and is achieved through pre-reading and post-reading exercises. Teaching reading literacy in the modern period has gone through a sufficient base of both traditional and ultra-modern tasks. But as a rule, each of the above categories of tasks for working with text is aimed at achieving a specific goal and requires the completion of certain exercises.

Technologies for teaching reading in a foreign language at school are becoming more diverse and innovative. Among them, several of the most effective can be identified.

The first technology for teaching reading involves the use of interactive books and electronic textbooks. These textbooks usually contain many interactive tasks that help students improve their reading skills in a foreign language. Some of these tasks include testing comprehension of pronunciation and grammar exercises, thereby enhancing understanding of the language as a whole.

The second technology used to teach reading in a foreign language is multichannel learning. This technology involves the use of audio and video materials along with written materials. For example, students can read an article in a foreign language and then listen to or watch a short audio or video message. This helps them remember new words and topics better and provides them with a deeper understanding of the text.

The third technology is the use of group learning techniques. Working together in groups, students can share their knowledge and ideas and support each other in their learning. This technique can be especially useful for students who have difficulty understanding the material as it can be enhanced by collaboration with classmates.

Finally, the fourth technology is the use of virtual classes. Virtual classrooms give students the opportunity to learn in real time with a teacher at a distance. Virtual classes can be especially helpful for students who live in remote or isolated areas or are unable to attend school. Depending on what technology is used, students can receive a learning experience that suits their level and pace.

Teachers who can use all these technologies in their work provide students with the best opportunity to achieve success when reading in a foreign language.

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ENHANCING EFL LEARNERS' WRITING SKILL THROUGH MIND – MAPPING TECHNIQUES

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Аннотация. В статье рассмотрены методы *Mind mapping* (интеллектуальная карта) для улучшения навыков письма у изучающих английский язык как иностранный, традиционные методы, используемые при обучении письменной речи учащихся, определены подходящие техники *Mind mapping* для улучшения способности учащихся к письму.

Ключевые слова: интеллектуальная карта, методы преподавания, структура, процесс написания, совершенствование.

Writing is an efficient means of expressing one's own ideas and a disciplined means of creating meaning [Clearly and Linn, 1993]. Writing effectively requires the use of linguistic devices and techniques, as this is becoming a more valued skill in a variety of academic and professional contexts. In order to write at a level that allows one's thoughts and ideas to flow logically, one must put in constant effort and practice. Writing is a complex skill that is challenging to teach. Along with the mastery of grammatical and linguistic devices, it requires conceptual and judgmental elements [Heaton, 1998] which are highly significant and focus of attention and dependence [Fageeh, 2011]. It is equally important to learning a language as speaking, listening, and reading, thus it should never be overlooked. However, writing requires consistent practice and effort to acquire a certain degree of expertise. It has been acknowledged that the main challenges faced by EFL learners are not with organizing grammar, mechanics, or lexis, but rather with organizing ideas related to the topic at hand. These challenges must be addressed in a way that maintains the topic's focus and the ideas' associations throughout the written text. Teaching writing involves different strategies adopted by the teachers.

There is always a need of appropriate techniques to be adopted to teach writing to develop in learners an ability to produce their best by understanding the process of writing. EFL writing is a challenging task, complex chore, and a difficult process. It's more complicated to write in a foreign or another language. Certain steps in the process should be kept under control.

- 1 Identifying thesis statement
- 2 Writing topic sentences
- 3 Adding supporting details
- 4 Correcting first draft
- 5 Editing and revising
6. Writing final draft

A well-developed focused approach towards teaching the skill is required. Focus points are appropriate lexical items, creativity, and knowledge of grammatical strategies. The strategies, tactics, or procedures used to teach writing vary depending on the specific academic context and the local conditions that exist at that particular time. When instructing students, the same circumstance arises. Their requirements and limitations in terms of education, society, and setting are found to be distinct from those of other second or foreign language learners worldwide. Modification in teaching techniques to suit the various learning profiles is an effective approach. A professional ability is required to filter the approaches and

extract an appropriate one after considering the needs of the learners, their level, their social contextual appropriateness and their academic system set-up [Badger & White, 2000].

When learners write a short paragraph, they feel stressed. Many academics have already noted the challenges associated with writing in English as a foreign language (EFL), which include a range of factors such as cognitive capacity at a standing mark. The process of writing is linked and cyclical. Writing procedures can be separated into two categories: preparatory writing and writing itself. These procedures typically go like this: prewriting, composing, editing, and revising. Prewriting is the initial step of the process where EFL learners typically struggle. Writing's foundational phase is significant because it generates the primary and secondary ideas and thoughts that are necessary for writing. The ideas must make sense and be connected coherently.

Pre – writing

Composing

Revising

Editing

Linguistic blocks are necessary for the writing process because they give thoughts structure. But in order for their cognitive capacities to support and grow ideas in a comfortable flow, students must form the building blocks. The cognitive method holds that writing itself serves as a source that instructs students to evaluate their own structures. Writing is more than just using language; it goes beyond that. The deductive approach of writing is all about the organization of ideas and it is far beyond the inductive approach where writing was seen as a practice in language usage. Former major practices were the correct usage of the language and most of the classroom practice was to ensure the linguistic competence has been developed in the learners [Widdowson, 1984]. EFL writing is normally associated with learning or mastering the grammatical structures, vocabulary, and syntax. Majority teachers and students are conscious of the production as error free and an exceptional piece of grammar exhibition. Thus, the main purpose of writing suffers somewhere in between the process.

Writing requires organizing thoughts, structuring ideas into a systematic connection with related details, using opinions cohesively and coherently so that all the ideas are interwoven and link the main theme, etc. These are desirable writing skills, which makes it difficult for teachers and students to maintain balance in the connections. There are many areas that the writing process gets hindered or failed due to the difficulties faced by the EFL learners who learn writing or the teachers who teach them writing. There is a need to identify the underlying problems which create complications in teaching-learning writing skill. Organization of the composition depends on structure and content. The learners are usually confused in between what to write and how to start to create an appropriate length, and organization of the structure and paragraphs. It is imperative that the text be devoid of any extraneous elements pertaining to the theme in order to maintain unity in organization. The issue occurs when students overstate concepts and elaborate on pointless or repetitive details, which detaches the ideas from the main idea and renders the material as a whole unreadable. Another issue that students encounter when writing is keeping track of coherence and cohesiveness. Connectors, sequence, consequence, and contrast are not used in learner texts, and there are no signal words to lead the reader toward arguments. The lack of logical serial connections turns the sentences of the composition into a list of sentences, and the play loses its real content. Many researchers attribute this to validation problems and large syntax errors. These highlighted topics relate to verb formation, the use of tenses, and subject-verb agreement. Students' writing errors are mainly syntax and grammar. Developing writing requires organizing your thoughts so that smaller ideas become a larger concept related to the topic. Another perceived difficulty is using written supporting information to support ideas. The writing process becomes more difficult when students get stuck.

Writing is the simplest type of academic writing process which provides details of facts and information on different topics related to the real life. Another type of writing in academics is the persuasive writing which closely resembles the analytical writing procedure which involves the process of writing the information and reorganization of the information. An extra feature of personal view-point is also there. Critical writing is common for research especially for the empirical thesis to show a gap.

Types of English Writing

Analytical

Narrative
Discursive
Critical
Persuasive
Descriptive

It has all the makings of persuasive writing; how to cite facts, rearrange, present your point of view. Narrative writing provides a topic that the author has written about. Students usually learn this type of writing easily because they don't have to see the sequence of events with an extra part. Discourse writing is formal and impersonal. The subject is presented in a balanced discussion of the subject and an objective investigation of the matter. The beginning is an introduction to the topic or problem and the thesis.

EFL teachers use many techniques in writing. These techniques vary according to daily teaching requirements. Some very common techniques for gathering ideas or generating thoughts on any topic are: brainstorming, listing, note-taking, concept maps, clear diagrams, tree structure and flowcharts, etc.

Teachers and/or students apply each technique with its own structure, flow and modifications, when the acquired technique is used in a certain pattern to collect thoughts related to the topic, either alone or in collaboration with students in the class. The concepts collected through the technique show the association of lexical items that create connections with other ideas.

Mind mapping is the easiest way to develop knowledge about the human mind and get information from the brain. Maps are easier to follow than long-winded note-taking or listing techniques, where ideas are recorded from top to bottom and it is difficult to connect the last idea to the first on the list. Mind maps can be a tool to help students plan ideas in the pre-composition process. Students can be given examples of how to create a hierarchical plot to help them retain ideas until they write the entire essay. Mind mapping techniques are good to use in the pre-writing phase to explore ideas and generate ideas for writing. Mind-maps allow gathering concepts in relation to the main theme. The concepts gathered this way are coherent without the linear or inflexible structure of outlines, clustering or listing ideas. The use of mind map can present information using images, symbols, key words, codes and color to the level one wishes to do. This type of organization of ideas can capture the spatial, bodily-kinesthetic, and visual intelligences of some learners (Gardner, 1985, 1999). As the content resembles that's found on a topic outline, the structure of the mind map is nonlinear and lends itself to personalization by the student (Buzan, 1993).

In addition to teaching, mind maps facilitate critical thinking, learning, and the creation of meaningful connections between new and existing knowledge for teachers' pupils. As with brainstorming, the maps project ideas display a hierarchical structure that connects the important information with the smaller ones. Gardner (1985, 1999) identified eight different types of intelligences, and mind mapping can help a greater proportion of learners access these intelligences. Mind maps can be used to give students of all levels the proper frameworks they need to make sense of the world, arrange their ideas, and form connections. Mind maps have easily remembered terms and function similarly to the human brain.

Mind maps can hook prior knowledge through multiple presentations (visual, audio, numeric, wordy etc.) which can easily be incorporated while teaching writing processes starting from the brainstorming on a topic till leading to the final draft. Hooking ideas through mind maps is supportive in the process of writing. The constructivist philosophy helps to maintain the fact that learners must connect the new knowledge with the prior knowledge. The learning experiences must support that connection in a manner supportive of the learner's uniqueness. The traditional teaching methods directly counter to constructivist beliefs which basically rely on the outpouring of facts for students to remember. In fact, the constructivists explain that many times the learners do not remember the knowledge presented to them. The reason behind is that they do not have found the connections of the new knowledge with that of the prior or they have lost the connections that take the learning experience.

The process of EFL writing involves three stages:

- (1) Pre-writing process: in which the ideas are gathered and generated
- (2) Drafting: in which the writer composes structures, and reconstructs ideas.
- (3) Revision

Efforts done for the development of the writing skill and the sub-writing skills serve these three phases. Mind-mapping is used in the first phase which is the pre-writing phase, where the students are given an

opportunity to generate, gather, and arrange related ideas and enhance their own learning. Mind mapping is a technique which is used as a graphic organizer in which major categories related to the main theme radiate from the central idea, and sub-categories are to be presented as branches coming out of the larger branches. A mind map is a visual tool that can be used to generate ideas, take notes, organize thinking, and develop concepts. Ideas can be generated with a strong connection to the central theme and in a hierarchical structure that they leave a lasting impact on the learners' mind and retention is enhanced. A human brain likes to work on the basis of association and it links every idea, memory or piece of information to hundreds of other thoughts and notions. Teachers can make a selection on how to use mind mapping in language classes as a pre-writing activity and also for the sake of developing learners' writing ability and their proficiency level. Thus, mind mapping can be used as software are available online or created manually by the teachers during their writing lessons to develop outlining process and writing proficiency as pre-writing activity. Ideas can be generated with a strong connection to the central theme and in a hierarchical structure that they leave a lasting impact on the learners' mind and retention is enhanced. According to the facts related to that EFL writing as a complex process and teaching EFL writing skill with some usual techniques are highly considerable.

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DIFFICULTIES ARISING IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AND THEIR ELIMINATION

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Аннотация: Преподавание иностранного языка сопряжено со своим собственным набором проблем. Хотя изучение нового языка открывает двери для новых культур и способов мышления, оно требует самоотдачи как от преподавателя, так и от студента, чтобы преодолеть трудности в процессе. Цель статьи – изучить некоторые из ключевых трудностей, которые обычно возникают при обучении иностранному языку, и обсудить стратегии их эффективного решения.

Ключевые слова: учебный процесс, языковые барьеры, многоязычие, этапы обучения, образовательные цели

Introduction: Information on an unknown dialect is a fundamental piece of present-day instruction. Be that as it may, the nature of instruction has quit fulfilling society, it has collided with social assumptions. In the college climate, a reduction in the general and instructive culture of understudies has become intensely felt, consequently, under schooling, including language training, one should comprehend not just the cycle and consequence of an individual dominating a specific arrangement of information, abilities and capacities, yet additionally the turn of events and instruction of an individual – an individual equipped for rearrangement of public activity, creation, conservation of culture, environment, otherworldliness.

In such manner, researchers have raised the issue of imaginative training, the primary objective of which is the safeguarding and improvement of the imaginative capability of the person. Understudy focused training is characterized as "schooling that can guarantee the advancement of the individual, support for her uniqueness, the full fulfillment of her instructive, profound, social, life needs and requests, and which gives the singular opportunity of decision and approaches to getting training, as well as methods of self-acknowledgment in social and instructive space".

Above all else, it is important to help the understudy to learn, to gain information himself, to figure out how to satisfactorily see the states of the cutting edge quickly impacting world and adjust to them. Until this point in time, huge positive changes have occurred in the Uzbek arrangement of language training, both in authoritative and content angles.

To arrive at vital outcomes, I have utilized the accompanying strategies: the hypothetical examination of scholarly sources on the exploration point; investigation of legitimate and hierarchical and managerial reports controlling the expert exercises of showing staff; symptomatic techniques (perception, discussion, addressing, testing). An unknown dialect is described by various distinctive highlights from the local language. In this manner, the thickness of a youngster's correspondence with the kids and grown-ups around him in his local language is exceptionally higher than in an unknown dialect in school conditions. A similarly huge distinctive element of dominating and capability in an unknown dialect is its uneven "consideration" just in open, and not in subject-open action. "At college, the kid just speaks with the assistance of language, not involving it in his immediate objective movement.

This prompts the way that, for instance, the expression of an unknown dialect lives in the kid's semantic cognizance just in its theoretical coherent, calculated side. The items signified by the expression of an unknown dialect are denied of the qualities of smell, variety, shape, size. This can act as one reason for the delicacy of saving an unfamiliar word in memory, the challenges of its realization". The prior likewise connects with such a component as the chance of executing by an unknown dialect the whole arrangement of capabilities that the local language performs. "Dominating the local language is an unconstrained cycle that an individual expert not due to his cognizant longing to know the language, but since of the unconstrained course of improvement of reasoning in ontogenesis".

"By securing the local language, an individual "appropriates" the instrument of perception of the real world. In this cycle, his particular human (mental, open and other social) needs are normally fulfilled and shaped". An unknown dialect in the states of college schooling can no more, in a similar way as a local language, act for of "appropriating" social experience, a device for cognizing reality. Dominating an unknown dialect is not set in stone by "fulfillment of either instructive and mental requirements, or the need to figure out the type of articulation of one's own idea".

As L. V. Shcherba noted, "perceptions on language are perceptions on thinking and satisfies this reason, compelling an individual to stop at the progression of his discourse, and, subsequently, thinking, constraining him to partition it into parts, to contemplate the relationship these parts, contrast them and one another and hence develop their comprehension".

- The decision of language method for offering viewpoint is resolved not by the lexical and syntactic material that the audience possesses, however by the substance of the speaker's assertion and the reason for which he offers his expression;

- The singular qualities of the speaker's discourse may not compare to the standard that the audience claims;

- The speed of the speaker's discourse might appear to be abnormally quick to the audience;

- The single impression of discourse doesn't compare to the act of different view of messages in unknown dialect illustrations, where understudies hear or can hear pretty much every message as need might arise to see completely.

One more trouble in learning an unknown dialect is jargon and style, on the grounds that the primary hindrance in interethnic correspondence is the distinction in foundation information that makes up the particulars of the public societies of the communicants. "Foundation information depends on the combined capability of the language, on the capacity of the language to go about as a vault of aggregate insight, on its capacity to record the collected experience straightforwardly in the types of the language, in the underlying units of discourse - words, phraseological units, maxims".

The utilization of the phonetic and social perspective adds to the development of the inspiration of the educating, which is vital in the states of concentrating on in the school in light of the fact that unknown dialect correspondence isn't upheld by the language climate.

In such manner, we are attempting to choose the language material mirroring the way of life of the nation of the concentrated-on language, the purported real factors. In real factors, the closeness among language and culture is generally plainly showed. An unmistakable element of reality from different expressions of the language is the idea of its subject substance, for example the nearby association of the assigned truth of the item or peculiarity with the public, from one viewpoint, and the verifiable time period then again. Reality as an etymological peculiarity is generally firmly associated with the way of life of the nation of the concentrated-on language, since it has a public and verifiable variety.

It ought to be noticed that understudies need discourse practice on casual and regular points, yet additionally in the act of correspondence at an expert level. Delegates of one more public culture, concentrating on subjects of a characteristic forte, meet with huge challenges in grasping proficient wording. And furthermore, instructive situational themed modules are disseminated relying upon syntactic points. The showing material in the course readings can be circulated in various ways, yet the fundamental design of the course book show can be as per the following: after the new syntactic material, a discourse design, miniature texts and exchanges follow, in which the new jargon is found. Consequently, unfamiliar understudies perceive how words change in blend with various word structures.

The powerful techniques to forestall issues in discourse It is fascinating to take note of the way that unfamiliar understudies after the finish of the preliminary division experience troubles in grasping the talk material on unique subjects. Frequently, this issue is that at the phase of pre-college preparing, the preparation of unfamiliar understudies is segregated from the speakers of the language being examined, and besides, during the extended period of pre-college preparing outsiders become acclimated to the sluggish speed of discourse, as well as the adjusted language during the classes, thirdly, after the finish of the preliminary division, outsiders are totally drenched in the language learning climate, which doesn't consider the public mental qualities of the unfamiliar contingent, where the preparation framework college cardinally varies from the arrangement of professional schooling in the nation of origin of unfamiliar understudies.

Conclusion. In conclusion, teaching a foreign language comes with its own challenges but they can be overcome through careful planning and creating a conducive learning environment. Adopting a multidimensional approach with focus on developing all language skills is important. Teachers play a crucial role in building student confidence and motivation through a variety of interactive methods and continual feedback. With dedication from both educators and learners, these difficulties can be effectively addressed to make the language acquisition process smoother.

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РАЗВИТИЕ ВНЕКЛАСНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ УЧАЩИХСЯ НА УРОКАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada darsdan tashqari o'qishning ahamiyati yoritilgan, talabalarni darsdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarga jalb qilish masalalari ko'rib chiqilgan. Muallif ingliz tili o'qituvchilari talabalarni darsdan tashqari mashg'ulotlar haqida xabardor qilishi lozimligini ta'kidlab, sinfdan tashqari mashg'ulotlar talabalarning o'qishiga qanday ta'sir qilishi va ularni darsdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarga qanday jalb qilish mumkinligi haqida bahs yuritadi.

Kalit so'zlar: darsdan tashqari mashg'ulotlar, mustaqil ta'lim, amaliyot, ikkinchi til, o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish.

Внеклассные деятельности – это “деятельность, проводимые во внеклассное время”. Внеклассные деятельности должны проводиться в школе или за ее пределами в зависимости от требований и удобства внеклассных мероприятий. Чтобы быть более точным в изучении английского языка, внеклассные деятельности, такие как внеклассные дебаты по английскому языку, занятия в журналистском клубе или драматическом кружке, часто проводятся в школе или за ее пределами, чтобы лучше владеть произношением и быть успешным в жизни в целом. Вкратце, согласно приведенному выше краткому описанию, внеклассная деятельность поддерживает учебную деятельность учащихся. Студенты, которые занимались внеклассными мероприятиями, чтобы добиться успеха в своей учебной среде, показывают это; большинство студентов, которые часто принимают участие в студенческом совете, дебатах по английскому языку, лингафонных лабораториях и т.д., также активно участвуют в учебных мероприятиях в классе. В этой статье рассказывается о том, как внеклассные мероприятия облегчают процесс изучения английского языка, а также о влиянии внеклассных мероприятий на изучение английского языка:

На самом деле, в начале XX века проблема внеклассных занятий в некоторой степени принималась во внимание. Цель состояла в том, чтобы выйти за рамки учебных занятий и вернуться к учебным занятиям, чтобы обогатить их в Америке (Миллард, 1930). Считалось, что только школьной программы самой по себе недостаточно для развития ученика. С тех пор педагоги увидели полезность внеклассных мероприятий и предложили использовать ВКД в качестве дополнительных действий для использования в школе, в колледжах и университетах или вне ее ради учащихся. Внеклассные мероприятия, ориентированные на изучение языка, имеют множество преимуществ для изучения английского студентами. ВКД могут обеспечить активное взаимодействие между участниками. Студенты могут учиться друг у друга, выполняя любое внеклассное мероприятие вместе. Поскольку ошибки приводят к совершенству, они смогут получать знания, практикуясь и получая опыт с точки зрения уделения внимания обучению на ошибках. ВКД могут обеспечить крепкую дружбу. Студенты могут создать теплую обстановку и терпимость к своим сверстникам. Они могут найти уникальную возможность хорошо узнать друг друга. Чем больше они узнают друг о друге, тем больше взаимного уважения проявляют. ВКД могут научить студентов сотрудничать. Студенты могут почувствовать, что сотрудничество гораздо важнее, чем соперничество. Студентам будет предложено выполнять задание вместе, и они будут намерены достичь одной и той же цели вместе. Они осознают реальность того, что много рук делают отличную работу.

Студенты могут раскрыть свои таланты или навыки с помощью ВКД. Они могут руководить членами группы в ВКД и совершенствовать свои лидерские навыки. Им можно поручить выполнение некоторых обязанностей, чтобы они могли продвинуться в своей жизни, учитывая опыт, который они приобрели в ВКД. Как говорится, “практика делает совершенным”; учащиеся смогут

усвоить то, что они усвоили теоретически на уроке, практикуя это в реальных условиях. Поскольку преподавателям не хватает времени заниматься с каждым индивидуально, чтобы практиковать занятия по английскому языку в классе, у студентов будет возможность повторить их практически в ВКД. ВКД обеспечивают преданность учащихся школе. Давалос и Чавес (1999) утверждают, что учащиеся, участвующие в ВКД, с большей вероятностью проводят время в школе, чем их непричастные друзья. Им нравится находиться в школе при условии, что занятия соответствуют интересам учащихся и привлекательны для получения мотивации во время участия. ВКД могут положительно изменить отношение студентов-интровертов. Некоторые учащиеся на занятиях могут показаться интровертами из-за большого количества студентов. Для преподавателей, которые хотят выяснить личность студентов,

ВКД может быть ключевым элементом. Студенты могут найти множество возможностей поделиться своими идеями со своими друзьями и преподавателями в рамках ВКД в небольших группах. Как с точки зрения студентов, так и с точки зрения преподавателей ВКД станет хорошей платформой для взаимодействия. Внеклассные деятельности создают учебную среду для изучающих второй язык. Встречи, интервью, презентации и публикация школьных газет являются полезными мероприятиями, в которых могут принимать участие учащиеся. Вовлечение учащихся в них может способствовать развитию их коммуникативных навыков. Аналогичным образом, прямой метод направлен на развитие коммуникативной компетентности учащихся. Такие внеклассные деятельности, как написание писем студентам из других стран, проведение дебатов и дискуссий на английском языке, где студентам необходимо постоянно использовать английский язык, помогают студентам улучшить свой уровень владения английским языком. Основная цель прямого метода – вовлечь учащихся в изучение изучаемого языка. Внеклассные деятельности, проводимые на английском языке, позволят учащимся познакомиться с изучаемым языком, что приведет их к достижениям в изучении языка. Изучив литературу, получив достаточное представление о внеклассных мероприятиях, о том, какую пользу они приносят учащимся в процессе учебы, мы можем сделать следующий вывод: "Внеклассные мероприятия могут помочь учащимся эффективно использовать свое время, и между учащимися мужского и женского пола не возникнет никаких гендерных недоразумений. Внеклассные занятия не окажут никакого негативного влияния на другие классы". Таким образом, гипотеза этой исследовательской работы будет следующей: "Не было статистически значимой взаимосвязи между полом и участием во внеклассных мероприятиях по общему среднему баллу успеваемости, а также между учащимися, которые участвуют во внеклассных мероприятиях и которые не участвуют во внеклассных мероприятиях с точки зрения их общего среднего балла успеваемости".

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ДИДАКТИЧЕСКИЙ, ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЙ И МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЙ ПРИНЦИПЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ РКИ

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada rus tilini chet tili sifatida o'qitish tamoyillari ko'rib chiqilgan bo'lib, muallif rus tilini o'qitish metodikasini tahlil qiladi va til o'qitishda didaktik, lingvistik va metodik tamoyillar ahamiyatini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: rus tili chet tili sifatida, tamoyil, kommunikatsiya, fan, ko'rgazmalilik, onglilik.

Одна из главных задач, стоящая перед высшими и специальными образовательными учреждениями – дальнейшее развитие образовательного потенциала, повышение качества образования. Именно качественное обучение трактуется как неопределимые инвестиции, гарантирующие успех. Высокий уровень образования рассматривается сегодня не только как фактор экономической и военной безопасности государства, но и как важнейшая задача воспитания подрастающего поколения. Новое поколение преподавателей должно обладать высокой общей и профессиональной культурой, творческой и социальной активностью, уметь самостоятельно ориентироваться в общественно-политической жизни, быть способным ставить и решать профессиональные задачи.

Важные задачи образования сегодня решаются и через использование в учебном процессе современных педагогических технологий, которые обозначили контуры образовательной парадигмы: «личностно-ориентированная», «исследовательская», «проектная», «коммуникативно-деятельностная» и др.

Отмечая исключительную важность развития образования, Президент Республики Узбекистан Шавкат Миромонович Мирзиёев отметил, что «Основная задача сферы образования, сама суть труда педагога заключаются прежде всего в подготовке к будущему, воспитании здоровыми и гармонично развитыми наших детей, которым предстоит жить в еще более сложное время, когда конкуренция в условиях глобализации приобретет особенно острый характер. <...> С учетом этого реформы в образовательно-воспитательной сфере стали для нас самым важным, приоритетным направлением государственной политики».

Придание узбекскому языку статуса государственного способствует расширению его социальных функций и закреплению приоритетности в сфере официально – делового общения. Ведь авторитет государственного языка, уважение к нему это уважение к народу, авторитет всего общества. Правительство продолжают разрабатывать меры по дальнейшему укреплению роли и авторитета узбекского языка как государственного. Президент подчеркнул, что необходимо усилить начатую работу по ведению на государственном языке всего делопроизводства в сферах госуправления, современных инновационных технологий, промышленности, банковско-финансовой системе, в области юриспруденции, дипломатии, медицины, а также в деятельности правоохранительных органов и военных ведомств. В то же время в современных условиях межгосударственных и межнациональных отношений русский язык продолжает оставаться языком общения не только в нашей республике, но и за её пределами, он так и остается источником информации. Он функционирует при межнациональном общении, а при межгосударственных отношениях Республики Узбекистан со странами СНГ русский язык используется как один из мировых языков. Знание любого неродного языка дает больше шансов, раскрывает больше дорог, дает народам возможность строить общее будущее. Основные задачи обучения русскому языку в высших учебных заведениях это формирование речевой компетенции, развитие навыков использования русского языка в процессе общения, для продолжения деятельности в профессиональной сфере и повседневной жизни студентов.

Изменение социальной роли русского языка в республике, некоторое ограничение сферы его применения с учетом демографических, политических и социально-культурных условий не должно приводить к падению мотивации его изучения. Владение русским языком (наряду с другими мировыми языками) – одно из условий повышения качества подготовки высококвалифицированных специалистов, потребность в которых возрастает в современных условиях ускорения научно-технического прогресса, реализации крупномасштабных комплексных социально-экономических программ.

В настоящее время в Узбекистане совершенствуется образовательная система, ориентированная на вхождение в мировое образовательное пространство. Этот процесс сопровождается существенными изменениями в педагогической теории и практике учебно-воспитательного процесса. Происходит модернизация образовательной системы – предлагаются иное содержание, подходы, поведение, педагогический менталитет. При этом особое внимание уделяется тому, чтобы методика обучения отвечала требованиям времени.

Современный курс русского языка студентов, предполагающий формирование умений, навыков, ценностных ориентаций, носит практический характер. Из этого следует, что большая часть времени на занятиях курса отводится различного рода упражнениям и решению коммуникативных задач. Практическое владение русским языком даст возможность студентам осуществлять перевод специальной литературы на родной язык, поможет вести деловую переписку с русскоязычными регионами, расширит сферу языковой интеграции. Русский язык обеспечит доступ к зарубежным источникам информации, без которой в настоящее время немыслима не только исследовательская деятельность будущего специалиста, но во многих случаях и чисто практическая. Поиск информации в зарубежных источниках, в Интернете, ее отбор и использование осуществляется студентами при написании курсовых и выпускных квалификационных работ. В данном случае знание русского языка значительно облегчит работу студентов в их дальнейшей научно-исследовательской и практической работе.

Методика обучения русскому языку как иностранному (РКИ), вводимая в систему образования Узбекистана, представляет собой самостоятельную педагогическую дисциплину о законах и правилах обучения языку и способах овладения языком. Изменение содержания образования, применение новых педагогических технологий и других инноваций требуют от педагога широты эрудиции, гибкости мышления, активности и стремления к творчеству, способности к анализу и самоанализу, готовности к нововведениям. Современный преподаватель должен уметь ориентироваться в потоке новых учебных средств, оценивать их по новым, соответствующим этим средствам, критериям, отбирать из предлагаемых продуктов необходимое и, что самое главное, овладеть новой методикой. Только на этой основе возможно органично включать инновационные средства обучения в учебный процесс, систематически использовать их наряду с традиционными средствами обучения. В отличие от родного языка, усвоение которого идет неосознанно и интуитивно, изучение русского языка как иностранного не может происходить с той же эффективностью и требует гораздо больше времени, усилий и усидчивости.

Предложения и рекомендации по улучшению качества занятия. При обучении русскому языку целесообразно использовать дидактический, лингвистический и методический принципы.

Дидактический принцип это:

- 1) принцип сознательности, от осознания - к практическому овладению речи, путь сверху вниз;
- 2) принцип наглядности. Имеет две функции: а) информирующая;
б) обучающая, для познания, то есть лучше один раз увидеть, чем сто раз услышать, можно использовать «статичные» средства: ситуативные картинки, опорные схемы, таблицы, динамичные: видеоролики, фильмы;
- 3) принцип активности. Очень важно, чтобы обучаемые были активными: это не сосуд, а огонь, который мы должны зажечь;
- 4) принцип «проблемности». Материал надо давать такой, который бы помогал решать проблемные задачи. Мы подводим обучаемых к выводам, но не решаем за них.

Например, путаница среди обучающихся между «ещё и «уже». Сравните два предложения

с наречиями. Какое наречие указывает на то, что сохраняется ситуация, а какое указывает на изменение ситуации?

Я ещё плохо говорю по-русски. - Я ещё не так хорошо говорю по-русски.

Я уже хорошо говорю по-русски. Проблемная ситуация должна активизировать познавательную деятельность студентов.

Лингвистический принцип подразделяется на:

1) Принцип функциональности. Мы должны обучать не системе языка, а обучать коммуникации, общению. Этот подход требует функциональное расположение материала занятий, а также последовательность обучения не отражает место предлагаемой темы в системе языка, а важности в сфере общения. Например, рассмотрим один момент: мы изучаем глагол до прилагательного, ведь без глагола невозможно сообщить о чем-то. Значит, языковые средства мы комбинируем не по грамматическому признаку, а в зависимости от смысла, то есть от содержания – к форме. Сначала – мысль, потом – подбор грамматической формы. Все принципы обусловлены коммуникативностью.

2) Принцип изучения морфологии на синтаксической основе. Вся грамматика основывается на предикативности: Мальчик говорит. Мальчик говорит по-русски. Мальчик говорит по-русски с учителем. Обучающиеся должны учить не слова, а фразы, речевые модели и не абстрактные, а конкретные;

3) Принцип концентризма. Периодическое возвращение к материалу и усложнение. Многократное обращение к изученному, чтобы расширять, углублять, систематизировать. Чем хорош принцип концентризма? Коммуникативность, доступность – посильная трудность, от легкого – к трудному, обеспечивает открытость, расширение материала. Все эти принципы обуславливают такую последовательности, в какой целесообразно помогают общению.

4) Принцип системности. Обучаемые должны понимать, что в языке все взаимосвязано. По мере накопления материала, нужно давать систематические обобщения. Теоретические обобщения вытекают из работы по формированию речевых навыков. В системе легче ориентируются. Как можно систематизировать? Уроки-обобщения, на этапах закрепления, подведения итогов, резюме урока. Составлять таблицы, работа с грамматическими справочниками.

5) Принцип ситуативно-тематической организации урока. Когда процесс овладения языком приближен к реальной жизни: а) надо установить перечень типичных ситуаций; б) определить перечень поставленных задач и они должны исполнять социокоммуникативную роль. Например: ты посетитель продуктового магазина; в) тематическая направленность. Языковой материал следует отбирать в соответствии с вышеперечисленными принципами. Создать атмосферу действительности, близкую к реальности. Методы: ролевые игры, которые должны быть интересными для обучаемых. Надо четко описать ситуацию: место, время, социокоммуникативная роль, отношения, формальная и неформальная обстановка, цель общения; продумать реквизит: средства наглядности.

Таким образом, соблюдение этих принципов обучения коммуникации тесно связано с принципом прочности результатов обучения языку. Это отражается тогда, когда вводимые в память новые слова, грамматические конструкции должны удерживаться в ней, сохраняться, чтобы обучающийся мог извлекать из нее знания в нужный момент. Прочность усвоения достигается за счет яркого преподнесения материала, интенсивной тренировки материала сразу после ознакомления и позже, за счет самостоятельного творческого применения материала.

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THE POWER OF MULTIMEDIA TOOLS IN ENGLISH TEACHING: EXPLORING THEIR IMPACT ON HUMAN MENTAL ACTIVITY

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini o'qitishda multimedia vositalarining ahamiyati ko'rib chiqilgan bo'lib, ularning inson aqliy faoliyatiga ta'sirini o'rganilgan. Ingliz tilini o'qitishda audiovizual materiallar, interaktiv dasturiy ta'minot va raqamli resurslar kabi multimedia vositalarini qo'llash samaradorligi ko'rsatilib, ularning kognitiv jarayonlarga, o'zlashtirish va talabalarning faolligiga ta'sirini aniqlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: multimedia vositalari, ingliz tilini o'rgatish, inson aqliy faoliyati, kognitiv jarayonlar, o'quv natijalari, o'quvchilarning faolligi.

Introduction. Multimedia tools have revolutionized the way that English language instruction is taught, providing new and creative ways to engage students and improve language acquisition. Multimedia resources, including films, animations, and educational software, possess the visual and interactive qualities that can enhance cognitive functions, elevate brain activity in humans, and provide more profound learning opportunities. In order to better understand how multimedia technologies can improve language competency and encourage learner engagement, this article will examine how these tools affect human mental activity in the context of English language training.

Methods. This study used a mixed-methods approach to look into how using multimedia tools in English instruction affects human mental activity. To examine previous studies, research, and publications on the application of multimedia resources in language instruction, a thorough literature review was carried out. Empirical data were gathered from English language learners who were exposed to multimedia tools through surveys, observations, and cognitive evaluations. To investigate the impact of multimedia technologies on cognitive processes and learning outcomes, a qualitative and quantitative analysis of the data was carried out.

Literature Analysis. In the context of teaching English, the literature study emphasized the beneficial effects of multimedia tools on human mental activity. Research has indicated that learning resources that are visual and interactive have the potential to improve cognitive engagement, support memory retention, and ease linguistic concept comprehension. It has been discovered that using multimedia tools can activate several senses, increasing the immersion and interactivity of learning. Moreover, the use of multimedia materials in English teaching has been linked to improved student motivation, creativity, and critical thinking abilities.

Results. The empirical data analysis's conclusions showed that multimedia technologies had a major effect on English language learners' human mental activity. Individuals who were exposed to multimedia resources showed enhanced cognitive abilities in areas such as problem-solving, attentiveness, and memory recall. Multimedia technologies' interactive features encouraged active involvement and improved language understanding by involving students at a deeper level. The integration of multimedia resources into education was found to enhance students' motivation and enjoyment in English sessions, according to their comments.

The methods for incorporating multimedia into the teaching process have been scientifically proven to be highly significant in the development of contemporary approaches to teaching literature. Animation (Latin animatix), or "animating" images with computer graphics, is one of the multimedia tools [1; 204]. It is fascinating how the "animated" visuals move directly in front of the reader. It draws interest. It reaches the mind of a human through different sense organs. The synthesis of dynamic visuals on a computer is known as computer animation [2]. Through visuals, man first gains an understanding of the world. The look of the

mouth is sealed by the human mind, whether it is dynamic or immovable. All other knowledge pertaining to that thought forms a loop in the chain of contemplation. As a result, throughout the session, the student gains an understanding of the topic's essence along with all of its supporting details. As a result, there is a strong need for multimedia resources and contemporary software teaching aids. Multimedia software training tools are available nowadays. Working with programs that have animation, sound, and video is made possible by it. The use of multimedia has an impact on the senses of humans. It is well recognized that a person's sensory organs are how they take in information. Children's minds develop a double robust database formed by both sight and hearing when multimedia tools are employed in the teaching process. They act as tools to help the teacher convey to the students the essential elements of the fairy tale, story, or novel without straying from the lesson's core concept. The teacher should use the analysis that the author aims to convey as a starting point to discuss the pupils' individual interpretations. Students' attention is piqued by the animation or video content they watch and the teacher's remarks. Education becomes fun and emotional, and students experience aesthetic satisfaction [1; 204].

Discussion. The results of this study highlight how crucial it is to use multimedia resources when teaching English in order to improve learning outcomes and increase cognitive activity. Multimedia materials' interactive and visual elements provide a multifaceted learning experience that stimulates different cognitive processes and draws students in more deeply. Teachers may create dynamic learning environments that foster creativity, critical thinking, and language competency by implementing multimedia resources into English classroom.

Multimedia tools on the quality of the educational process through Gardner's teaching. In 1983, Howard Gardner put forward his famous theory. According to him, people will have not one single intellect, but many intellects, a set of mental abilities [3; 262]. In some of its features, this concept creates harmony with the sensory organs of man. That is, these mental abilities are formed in the core of the sensory organs. Gardner points out that we have eight intellects. They are musical-rhythmic, visual-visual, linguistic-verbal, mathematical-logical, kinesthetic-physical, interpersonal, personal and natural [3; 262].

Virtually every one of these cognitive categories is impacted by multimedia tools in general. The impact they have on the reader's growth of human intellect is discussed below.

Contrarily, personal intelligence is focused with self-awareness and is adept at examining one's own emotions, motivations, and thoughts. Dreamers frequently impart this trait to philosophers, authors, and theorists, as well as other self-study enthusiasts. industry delegates [4; 263]. While the science of literature itself can convey ideas like self-awareness and the pursuit of perfection, this kind of mental capacity can also be influenced by educational multimedia technologies, even in the absence of their direct influence on science's objectives. This kind of mental aptitude crosses paths and leads to the original task of writing. Ultimately, intangible emotions, nuanced encounters, and psychological states that are imperceptible to the naked eye, inaudible to the senses of hearing, touch, taste, or smell can only be conveyed verbally. Fiction differs from other types of art in that the main tool and material of the work is the word [5; 3].

When considering the ideas from a different angle, it is also plausible that, on the one hand, a particular person's own intellect belonged to him and symbolized his clearly developed capacity for thought. It symbolizes one of the aforementioned categories of intellect in the first instance. However, it can also indicate the different kinds of intelligence that are currently forming and maturing in a specific person. The peculiarity of multimedia's influence on intelligence is that it not only shapes mental capacities but also contributes to the development of a particular kind of intelligence.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the use of multimedia tools in English language teaching plays a vital role in stimulating human mental activity, improving cognitive processes, and enhancing learning experiences for learners. The visual, auditory, and interactive components of multimedia resources offer diverse sensory stimulation, leading to increased engagement, motivation, and knowledge retention. By leveraging multimedia tools effectively, educators can create dynamic and immersive English learning environments that cater to the diverse needs and learning styles of students.

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ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ОНЛАЙН-ПЛАТФОРМ НА УРОКАХ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА В ФИЛОЛОГИЧЕСКОМ ВУЗЕ

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Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola filologik OTMlarda rus tilini o'qitishda onlayn platformalardan foydalanish ahamiyatiga bag'ishlangan. Muallif onlayn platformalarning talabalar motivatsiyasiga va lisoniy ko'nikmalarining rivojlanishiga ta'sirini ko'rib chiqib, OnlineTestPad, LearningApps, Wordwall, Kahoot va Canva kabi vositalarning rus tilini o'rganishga qiziqishni oshirish va ta'lim jarayonini yaxshilashdagi samaradorligini ko'rsatadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *onlayn platformalar, AKT kompetensiyalari, rus tili, filologik ta'lim, ta'limning raqamlashuvi.*

Современная эпоха цифровизации оказывает значительное влияние на образовательный процесс в высшей школе. Ныне от преподавателя требуется не только умения применять инновационные педагогические технологии, но и определенный уровень ИКТ-компетенции. Это представляется естественным в условиях кредитной системы обучения, где субъектом образовательного процесса является не педагог, а студент.

Теперь невозможно представить себе обучение в школе, вузе без применения информационных технологий. При этом особую роль в учебном процессе занимают онлайн-платформы, которые открывают новые горизонты для обучения молодежи. В рамках филологического образования, в особенности при изучении русского языка, эти инструменты могут сыграть ключевую роль в повышении эффективности обучения, мотивации студентов и формировании и развитии их языковых компетенций.

Существует обширная научная литература по использованию цифровых технологий в образовании и специфике обучения языкам с помощью онлайн-платформ. Рассмотрим некоторые последние исследования в этой области.

N.Osman и S.Abdul Rabu из в своем исследовании «Digital Game-Based Learning: Impact on Language Learning and Beyond» подчеркивают важность цифровых игр как средства для обучения языкам. Авторы обсуждают, как игровые элементы могут улучшить мотивацию и вовлеченность учащихся, а также способствовать развитию языковых навыков посредством погружения и интерактивности [1].

O.Viberg и Å.Grönlund рассматривали вопросы использования мобильных приложений для изучения языков (MALL). В своей работе они изучали различные аспекты MALL, включая теоретические основы, типы используемых приложений и их влияние на языковое обучение. Кроме того, авторы подчеркивают потенциал MALL в повышении доступности и адаптивности обучения [2].

E.Eslit в своем исследовании рассмотрел кейс, демонстрирующий как онлайн-платформы могут быть интегрированы в процесс обучения языку. Автор описывает, как использование такого рода платформ способствует улучшению коммуникативных навыков и вовлеченности студентов. Подчеркивается важность дизайна курса и подхода к обучению для достижения максимального эффекта [3].

Научная работа Н.Mahdi представляет собой мета-анализ, посвященный изучению эффективности использования мобильных приложений для обучения лексике. Результаты показывают положительное влияние таких ресурсов на усвоение новой лексики, в особенности при регулярном и целенаправленном использовании.

A.Nugroho и A.Atmojo рассматривали возможности онлайн-платформы в изучении языков вне аудитории. Авторы анализируют различные типы платформ и их потенциал в обеспечении дополнительных ресурсов, практики и взаимодействия с носителями языка.

Эти исследования подчеркивают значимость и потенциал цифровых технологий в образовании, особенно в контексте обучения языкам. Они указывают на разнообразие доступных инструментов и подходов, а также на необходимость дальнейшего изучения их влияния на процесс обучения, мотивацию студентов и развитие языковых навыков.

В своей педагогической деятельности мы опирались на такие онлайн-платформы как OnlineTestPad (onlinetestpad.com), LearningApps (learningapps.org), Wordwall (wordwall.net), Kahoot.com, Canva.com. Оценка эффективности использования этих инструментов проводилась на основе критериев, таких как улучшение языковых навыков, мотивация студентов и удобство использования в учебном процессе.

Исследование показало, что данные онлайн-платформы могут существенно повысить интерес студентов к изучению русского языка, а также способствовать развитию их языковых навыков за счет доступности, интерактивности и возможности индивидуального подхода. В частности, LearningApps (learningapps.org) и Wordwall (wordwall.net) удобны для выполнения практических заданий на закрепление учебного материала. OnlineTestPad (onlinetestpad.com), Kahoot.com оптимальны для оценки усвоения знаний, сформированности умений и навыков учащихся.

Таким образом, интеграция онлайн-платформ в образовательный процесс по изучению русского языка в филологических вузах представляет собой мощный инструмент для повышения эффективности обучения. Это не только способствует более глубокому пониманию языкового материала, но и развивает навыки самостоятельной работы, критического мышления и межкультурной коммуникации.

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THE ESSENCE AND TYPES OF PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES: INNOVATION APPROACH

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Annotation: *This scholarly paper offers an overview of the many forms of educational technologies frequently employed in contemporary educational contexts, as well as an exploration of the fundamentals of pedagogical advances and technology. This study tries to shed light on the importance of these technologies in improving teaching and learning experiences by analyzing the effects, advantages, and difficulties related to them.*

Key words: *Pedagogical educational technologies, Learning management systems, Interactive whiteboards, Blended learning, Gamification, Adaptive learning, Digital storytelling, Virtual reality, Innovation, Educational innovations.*

Introduction. Pedagogical educational technologies have brought about a revolution in the field of education by providing creative instruments and approaches to facilitate the processes of teaching and learning. In addition to providing a thorough review of the many technology platforms used in educational contexts, this essay explores the essence of pedagogical educational technologies. Educators can effectively integrate educational technologies to create dynamic and engaging learning environments by having a thorough awareness of the wide range of tools available.

The term "pedagogical educational technologies" refers to a broad range of instruments, approaches, and techniques used in the field of education to promote student outcomes, increase instructional efficacy, and assist learning. These tools are made to help teachers engage students, deliver curriculum, and evaluate learning in creative ways. The power of pedagogical educational technology to change conventional teaching methods and increase student engagement, customization, and adaptability to the demands of a varied student body is what makes them so essential.

Lexically, "innovation" refers to "innovation" in the English language. In this usage, "innovation" refers to a particular circumstance. Innovation (visual "innovations" – introduced innovation, invention) includes two things: 1) economic investments made to guarantee the replacement of technology and equipment generations; and 2) advancements in engineering, technology, management, and labor organization that are founded on best practices and scientific and technical achievements and are applied in a variety of fields and activities.

Methods. In order to investigate the nature and varieties of pedagogical educational technology, this study uses a thorough literature review methodology. To gain understanding of the importance and influence of educational technologies on teaching and learning practices, a survey of pertinent research articles, textbooks, and educational periodicals was conducted.

Literature Analysis. A plethora of evidence demonstrating the revolutionary influence of pedagogical instructional technologies on educational practices was unearthed by the literature review. Research has indicated that various technologies, including virtual reality, gamification, adaptive learning systems, interactive whiteboards, blended learning approaches, digital storytelling, and learning management systems, can improve learning outcomes and increase student motivation and engagement.

The socio-psychological aspects of relationships, innovations in social relations, the categories of people involved in this process, their attitudes toward innovation, the degree of readiness to comprehend the essence, and the classification of pedagogical social relations between specific categories of individuals were all studied by American psychologist E. Rodgers in his research.

Results. According to a review of the evidence, integrating pedagogical educational technologies into classrooms improves academic achievement and increases student engagement through tailored learning

experiences. Teachers who successfully use these tools can design dynamic, interactive classrooms that accommodate a range of student preferences and learning styles.

In educational settings, a variety of pedagogical educational technologies are frequently employed, including:

1. Interactive Whiteboards: These are big touch-sensitive display screens that let educators connect with digital resources, annotate, and present multimedia information. They encourage teamwork, visual learning, and active engagement in the classroom.

2. Learning Management Systems (LMS): Online resources known as LMS platforms help with evaluation, communication between instructors and students, content distribution, and course administration. They offer a consolidated platform for managing assignments, keeping track of student progress, and arranging course materials.

3. Gamification: To improve student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes, gamification entails introducing game mechanics, elements, and design concepts into educational activities. Students' education can become more engaging and participatory through gamified learning experiences.

4. Blended Learning: A more flexible and individualized learning experience is made possible by combining traditional in-person education with online learning activities. Different learning styles and preferences can be accommodated by instructors by incorporating technology into their lesson plans.

5. Flipped Classroom: Under this paradigm, students use online resources to independently learn new material at home before attending class, where they participate in interactive exercises, have conversations, and apply what they have learned. With this method, learning becomes more student-centered rather than teacher-centered.

6. Adaptive Learning Systems: These systems tailor learning experiences to each student's unique needs, skills, and learning preferences using artificial intelligence and data analytics. These technologies maximize learning results by varying the speed, material, and feedback.

7. Virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR): These two forms of technology offer students immersive, interactive learning settings in which they may investigate virtual worlds, carry out experiments, and participate in simulations that improve their comprehension and memory of difficult subjects.

8. Digital Storytelling: Using multimedia tools, digital storytellers produce and distribute narratives, films, and presentations that immerse students in the educational process. It encourages students' critical thinking, creativity, and communication abilities.

Pedagogical educational technologies offer educators innovative ways to enhance instruction, engage students, and promote active learning. By leveraging these tools effectively, educators can create dynamic and interactive learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of 21st-century learners.

Discussion. The study's conclusions highlight how crucial it is to adopt pedagogical educational technologies in order to improve teaching strategies and maximize student learning opportunities. Every kind of educational technology has its own advantages and presents teachers with chances to create creative lesson plans, encourage teamwork, and support student-centered learning. Teachers are better equipped to meet the changing requirements of 21st-century students and promote a culture of continual improvement in the classroom when they use a wide variety of educational tools.

Pedagogical educational technology, often known as educational innovation, is utilized in the process of teaching. "Pedagogical education" is another term for educational innovation. Club of Rome introduced the term "pedagogical education" for the first time in 1979. Innovations in education can be classified into multiple categories. Education that gives students the freedom to develop their own fresh ideas, advanced ideas, norms, natural acceptance of rules, skills developed by others, and pedagogical abilities.

Researchers claim that innovations in education result in the following modifications:

- whole overhaul of the educational system;
- modifications to the learning process;
- adjustments to pedagogical theory;
- modifications to teacher activities;
- revitalization of student activities;
- adjustments to pedagogical technology;
- revisions to the curriculum.

Innovation refers to an action that possesses the characteristics of a short-term, integrated system and is limited to altering certain aspects of the system. Innovation is defined as the ability to significantly alter anything. modifications to the format, strategies, and tools of instruction; adjustments to the way the educational system is run; Modifications to the learning outcomes and objectives.

Conclusion. To sum up, pedagogical educational technologies are essential for transforming conventional teaching methods and creating learning environments that are focused on the needs of the students. Teachers can improve learning outcomes, encourage active student involvement, and improve instructional delivery by embracing a range of educational technologies. To ensure the complete development of pupils in the digital age, educators must keep up with evolving technology and find innovative methods to incorporate these tools into their teaching techniques.

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THE NECESSITY OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGE BY VOCABULARY ACQUISITION

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Аннотация: В статье обсуждены наиболее важные элементы, обеспечивающие и определяющие эффективность преподавания иностранного языка, в частности, преподавания лексики на курсах ESP, что становится проблемой для учителей английского языка.

Ключевые слова: подход, учебные словари, структура языка, случайное изучение словарного запаса, намеренное изучение словарного запаса, учебные пособия.

Introduction. Teaching vocabulary, especially in ESP courses is becoming a challenge for English Language Teachers. Vocabulary is an inseparable part of any teaching syllabus and vocabulary should be taught on a well-planned and regular basis. It is essential to carefully decide what vocabulary will be selected for teaching, and what approach or activities will be used to teach it to the students. It is believed that ESP combines subject matter and English language teaching. This approach can be highly motivating for students because students are able to apply what they learn in their English classes to their main field of study, whether it be law, computing, business, tourism, etc. Being able to use the vocabulary and structures that they learn in a meaningful context reinforces what is taught and increases their motivation. Nevertheless, ESP concentrates more on language in context than on teaching grammar and language structures.

Another interesting fact is that ESP words are perceived as more complex than general words and they should spend more time learning them. This is probably due to the fact that collocations are very frequent

in ESP and combining them correctly requires more effort. There are specific types of collocations in ESP which cause [14].

It is known that among the most important elements that ensure and determine the effectiveness of teaching a foreign language, one of the first places belongs to teaching aids. The number and nature of teaching aids used in the practice of teaching English testify to their diversity and even abundance. Teaching aids are designed to assist students in the perception, and memorization of new material, during its training. While learning autonomy offers a choice not only of how to study, but also of what and when to learn in order to achieve the goal set for oneself. Vocabulary plays an important role in mastering a foreign language. The totality of words in a language makes up the vocabulary. Vocabulary as the leading component of verbal communication appears in speech in interaction with grammar and phonetics. Working with educational dictionaries in English lessons is aimed at enriching students' vocabulary. It provides a wealth of vocabulary in English as one of the signs of their general development. Therefore, it is very important to teach students how to use dictionaries to master the English language. Working with a dictionary develops in students the need for an independent and creative search for words necessary for speech activity, and significantly expands information about the lexical richness of the studied language.

Materials. From the research, we know that vocabulary supports reading development and increases comprehension. Students with low vocabulary scores tend to have low comprehension and students with satisfactory or high vocabulary scores tend to have satisfactory or high comprehension scores.

The report of the National Reading Panel states that the complex process of comprehension is critical to the development of children's reading skills and cannot be understood without a clear understanding of the role that vocabulary development and instruction play in understanding what is read (NRP, 2000).

Chall's classic 1990 study showed that students with low vocabulary development were able to maintain their overall reading test scores at expected levels through grade four, but their mean scores for word recognition and word meaning began to slip as words became more abstract, technical, and literary. Declines in word recognition and word meaning continued, and by grade seven, word meaning scores had fallen to almost three years below grade level, and mean reading comprehension was almost a year below. Jeanne Chall coined the term "the fourth-grade slump" to describe this pattern in developing readers (Chall, Jacobs, and Baldwin, 1990).

Incidental and Intentional Vocabulary Learning.

How do we close the gap for students who have limited or inadequate vocabulary? The National Reading Panel (2000) concluded that there is no single research-based method for developing vocabulary and closing the gap. From its analysis, the panel recommended using a variety of indirect (incidental) and direct (intentional) methods of vocabulary instruction.

Incidental Vocabulary Learning. Most students acquire vocabulary incidentally through indirect exposure to words at home and at school—by listening and talking, by listening to books read aloud to them, and by reading widely on their own. The amount of reading is important to long-term vocabulary development (Cunningham and Stanovich, 1998). Extensive reading provides students with repeated or multiple exposures to words and is also one of the means by which students see vocabulary in rich contexts (Kamil and Hiebert, 2005).

Intentional Vocabulary Learning

Students need to be explicitly taught methods for intentional vocabulary learning. According to Michael Graves (2000), effective intentional vocabulary instruction includes:

- Teaching specific words (rich, robust instruction) to support understanding of texts containing those words.
- Teaching word-learning strategies that students can use independently.
- Promoting the development of word consciousness and using wordplay activities to motivate and engage students in learning new words [18].

Methods. Recently, in the methodology of teaching foreign languages, there has been a tendency to abandon teaching a commonly used foreign language (General English) in favor of such an organization of the educational process, in which the needs of foreign language learners are consistently and systematically taken into account. Students are focused on a set of tasks facing them, that is, on a well-defined category of vocabulary or, depending on the goals and objectives, a combination of several categories.

A lot of teaching tools have been developed (textbooks, manuals, training computer programs, reference materials, various dictionaries of both common and professional vocabulary, published both in Russia and abroad), intended for various categories of students studying a foreign language both as the subject of their activity and as a means of its implementation (English for Special Purposes/ESP). As a rule, in textbooks and teaching aids, the vocabulary to be studied is placed in the dictionaries accompanying each section or given at its end (vocabulary, glossary). These dictionaries are minimum dictionaries, which are made in the form of lists, presented, as a rule, in alphabetical order or in the order of their use in texts, and which are intended mainly for the independent work of students. Such lists only record the volume and composition of the vocabulary to be assimilated and perform a reference function but do not meet the needs of the educational process in that part of it that concerns the effective and controlled formation of vocabulary.

If vocabulary building is determined as the central purpose of the ESP class, countless techniques help in this regard. Teachers can mix methodologies or select only those aspects they feel most help their learners. It is important to teach vocabulary in such a way as to help learners make sense of future problems and encourage continuous learning. In spite of vocabulary acquisition being perceived as a boring activity by the learners, it is possible to teach ESP vocabulary without making it a chore or even without the perfect amount of motivation from the learners. The teachers can improve their strategy and turn the learning of ESP vocabulary into a pleasant experience.

According to internet resources, I used in my research work, the techniques were divided into 4 Different Types of Reading:

Skimming

Skimming, sometimes referred to as gist reading, means going through the text to grasp the main idea. Here, the reader doesn't pronounce each and every word of the text but focuses their attention on the main theme or the core of the text. Examples of skimming are reading magazines or newspapers and searching for a name in a telephone directory.

Scanning

Here, the reader quickly scuttles across sentences to get to a particular piece of information. Scanning involves the technique of rejecting or ignoring irrelevant information from the text to locate a specific piece of information.

Intensive Reading

Intensive reading is far more time-consuming than skimming and scanning as it needs the reader's attention to detail. It involves close reading that aims at the accuracy of comprehension. Here, the reader has to understand the meaning of each and every word.

Extensive reading

Extensive reading lays more emphasis on fluency and less on accuracy. It usually involves reading for pleasure and is more of an out-of-classroom activity. It is highly unlikely for readers to take up the extensive reading of text they do not like [9].

As an example of using reading during classes while learning a foreign language for vocabulary acquisition can be divided into 3 different reasons:

1. Academic reading which includes:

General interest articles (in magazines, newspapers, etc.)

Technical reports, professional journal articles

Reference material (dictionaries, online encyclopedias, etc.)

Textbook, thesis

Essays, papers

Test directions

Editorials and opinion writing

2. Job-related reading which includes:

Message

Letters/ e-mails

Memos

Reports
 Schedules, labels signs, announcement
 Forms, applications, questionnaires
 Financial documents
 Directories
 Manuals, directions
 3. Personal reading which includes:
 Newspapers and magazines
 Letters, e-mails, greeting cards, invitations
 Message, notes, lists, blogs
 Schedules (train, bus, plain, etc.)
 Recipes, menus, maps, calendars
 Advertisement (commercials, want ads)
 Novels, short stories, jokes, drama, poetry
 Financial documents (e.g., checks, tax forms, loan applications)
 Forms, questionnaires, medical reports, immigration documents
 Comic strips, cartoons. (Brown, 2010, p.226)

There are a variety of reading activities which students can have interaction with, and frequently students read personal reading because these types of reading catch their attention and are more interesting for them, and at the same time they learn new words.

When students learn vocabulary through reading, they also improve their reading skill, so they obtain two benefits, the vocabulary knowledge and that skill. Chall (as cited in Nation, 2001) mentions that vocabulary knowledge can help reading, and reading can contribute to vocabulary growth. Thus, both have a relationship to each other. A text tends to have a wide variety of vocabulary, making it a better resource for acquiring a broader range of words (Schmitt, 2000). As a result, the readers can learn a lot of vocabulary when they are reading because the vocabulary is first learned receptively, and then develop to become known productively. [12]

Using synonyms and antonyms

A technique often used by teachers, especially at low levels, is to explain words by using a synonym or antonym. In many respects this is a flawed idea. Firstly, because many of the words will be of a similar level and, if a student doesn't know one, then they won't know the other, i.e. if a teacher wants to elicit black and they say it's the opposite of white then this is unlikely to be helpful as the students probably don't know white. Secondly, it can be very misleading as very few words have a direct antonym. For example, what's the opposite of old? Is it new or young? Both, but then that becomes confusing. Thirdly, many words have more than one antonym or synonym all with similar meanings, so which do you use? For example, the opposite of happiness could be sad or unhappy, it often depends on the context [16].

Conclusion. Some authors suggest concepts to make an easy way of vocabulary acquisition: 1. Read something interesting and at the right level.

The first step is to make sure students have access to appropriate reading materials. But what do we mean by appropriate?

Firstly, the readings need to be interesting. Students need motivation to read on, and they'll be much more engaged with a text that they enjoy reading.

Secondly, readings need to be at the right level. Take a look at this quote from linguist Stephen Krashen:

"The best methods for language acquisition are those that supply comprehensible input in low anxiety situations. Any reading should form "comprehensible input." Essentially, this means that reading should fall into a kind of "Goldilocks zone" in terms of difficulty: Not too difficult, not too easy, but just challenging enough that learning can take place.

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INSPIRING SECONDARY STUDENTS TO WRITE EFFECTIVELY AND ENCOURAGING THE COMPETENCE OF WRITING GRADES FROM 5 TO 9

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada o'quvchilarning savodxonligini oshirish ko'p jihatdan ularning yaxshi yozish qobiliyatini o'stirish bilan bog'liqligi asosanib, yozish o'quvchilarga o'z g'oya va fikrlarini ifoda etish, tushunchalarga izoh berish va hodisalarni tushuntirish, axboronit tahlil qilishda asosiy aloqa vositasi ekanligi e'tirof etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: konstruktiv fikr-mulohazalar, amaliy faoliyat, qo'llab-quvvatlovchi sharhlar, konstruktiv tanqid, ichki motivatsiya, shaxsiy aloqa, konstruktiv tanqid, texnologiya va multimedia.

Writing is a fundamental ability that is not limited to the classroom. It is the basis for critical thinking, effective communication, and self-expression. Students start the process of developing their writing skills as early as grades 5 through 9, setting out on a transformative path to become proficient in this indispensable craft. Teachers have a critical role in creating an environment that supports young writers' development throughout these early years. Let's explore the subtleties of developing writing proficiency during this critical stage of education.

Students move from fundamental writing skills to more complex forms of expression in grades 5 through 9. They learn basic writing skills at this point, like grammar, spelling, and sentence structure. To reinforce these building blocks, teachers use a comprehensive strategy that incorporates engaging teaching, constructive feedback, and hands-on activities. Students get a greater understanding of language's nuances and start to appreciate its intricacies through stimulating writing prompts, group projects, and creative tasks. Writing is all about diversity, and grades 5 through 9 are ideal for experimenting with a wide range of literary genres. Students are encouraged to try out a variety of writing formats and styles, from narrative essays to persuasive speeches. Through experimenting with different genres, they broaden their toolkit of writing approaches and find their own voice. Furthermore, reading a variety of literature helps children develop their critical thinking abilities and gives them a more comprehensive perspective on the world. Writing is a process that calls for critical thinking and problem-solving abilities; it's not just about putting words together. Students in grades 5 through 9 gain the ability to reason logically, support their claims with facts, and express themselves clearly. They develop their skills in creating ideas that are compelling and effectively defending them through debate clubs, literary analysis, and brainstorming sessions. The development of critical thinking skills provides children with a lifetime tool for overcoming difficult situations and establishes the foundation for academic achievement. Writing is vitalized by creativity, which gives ordinary words life and inventiveness. Young authors can explore and develop this natural inventiveness in grades 5 through 9. Students are urged to use their imaginations and think creatively through storytelling, poetry writing, and multimedia projects. Through embracing their creativity, kids get the self-assurance to take chances, investigate novel angles, and stretch the bounds of acceptable expression. Students are

empowered to realize the full potential of their creative abilities and a culture of self-discovery is fostered by their ability to innovate.

In the current digital era, technology can be a strong motivator for improving writing skills. Digital tools and platforms that support multimedia storytelling, interactive feedback, and collaborative writing are introduced to students in grades 5 through 9. Students have access to a wealth of resources that enhance their writing experiences and broaden their understanding of digital literacy, ranging from word processors to online publication platforms. Educators may cultivate a culture of creativity and flexibility by utilizing technology to build dynamic learning environments that meet the varied needs and learning styles of students.

Above all, developing a growth attitude is the cornerstone of the writing competency journey from grades 5 to 9. Pupils are urged to take on obstacles, grow from failures, and never give up on their goals of success. By utilizing a blend of supportive comments, constructive criticism, and internal motivation, teachers cultivate in their pupils the notion that their writing abilities are flexible and subject to ongoing development. Through the development of resilience, tenacity, and a lifetime love of learning, this growth mindset equips pupils to write with conviction and confidence in the face of constant change. When taught properly in schools, writing may be a fun and fulfilling hobby. In any school, fostering our students' agency as writers and recognizing their voices as young people with something to say are commendable goals. We want our pupils to gain proficiency in writing so that they can at least exit the educational system with a basic understanding of the talent. Writing is another crucial life skill. We are aware that writing in secondary schools reaches a critical point in KS4. We want our pupils to succeed academically, and one way to do this is by helping them write well on tests. For them, written results are very important. Although teaching writing at the secondary level requires a range of instructional approaches and is a difficult talent, I wonder how many of us have really examined the ways in which writing is taught across the curriculum? Writing is difficult because it requires us to utilize our motor abilities to manipulate a pen or keyboard and to generate ideas that we can turn into words and phrases. At the same time, proper spelling and punctuation require our focus. Writing is a process rather than a single thing, therefore having the ability to plan and review is equally crucial. Everything is based on writing motivation.

Writing is a transforming process that enables people to convey themselves, explain ideas, and interact with the world around them. It's not just about putting words on paper. In the context of secondary education, developing strong writing abilities is crucial for students' academic achievement as well as for giving them the tools they need to prosper in a society that is becoming more complex and linked. These are some methods to help motivate and inspire high school pupils to reach their greatest writing ability.

a. Foster a Personal Connection: Begin by assisting students in seeing the importance and importance of writing on an individual basis. Urge them to research subjects that are in line with their enthusiasms, desires, and life experiences. Students are more probable to be involved, motivated, and invested in the process of writing when they have a personal connection to the piece.

b. Accept Creativity and Choice: Give pupils the chance to express themselves creatively and freely by using a variety of writing styles and forms. Give pupils options for their tasks so they can choose subjects that pique their interest and inventiveness. Encouraging kids to express themselves freely via writing, whether it be in the form of a poem, essay, or short story, allows them to be honest.

c. Encourage a Growth mentality: Promote a growth mentality in writers by stressing the value of tenacity, resiliency, and ongoing development. Urge kids to see barriers as opportunities for learning and development rather than as failures and hurdles. When kids believe they can improve and hone their writing abilities over time, they grow into more self-assured and independent learners.

d. Offer Constructive criticism: Give students timely, detailed, and constructive criticism on their work that identifies both their strong points and their places for development. Give special attention to organizing, lucidity, coherence, and the utilization of additional information and proof. Motivate students to actively seek out input from mentors, teachers, and peers in order to improve their interactive writing abilities.

e. Create a Writing Community: Establish a welcoming and inclusive writing community in which students feel comfortable sharing their work, exchanging ideas, and collaborating with their peers. Organize writing workshops, peer review sessions, and literary events to build community and creativity. Students gain a better understanding of the significance of writing as a collaborative endeavor by praising each other's triumphs and offering assistance throughout obstacles.

f. Incorporate Technology and Multimedia: Use technology and multimedia resources to improve the writing experience and cater to different learning styles. Allow students to try out digital storytelling, blogging, podcasting, or video creation as alternative avenues of expression. By leveraging technology, students can explore new pathways of innovation and interaction in their

g. Encourage Authentic Audiences: Give students chances to present their writing to audiences outside of the classroom. Connecting students with real-world audiences, whether through online forums, writing contests, or publishing in school newsletters, inspires them to produce excellent work and feel proud of their writing achievements.

h. Develop a Love of Reading: Help children develop a love of literature by exposing them to a wide variety of texts and genres. This will promote a symbiotic link between reading and writing. Encourage your pupils to examine and model their work after that of eminent poets, journalists, and writers. Through engaging with the diverse range of language and narratives, students get a more profound understanding of the discipline and art of writing.

i. Celebrate growth and Achievement: Give public recognition, prizes, and festivities to pupils who have made writing growth and accomplishments. Display excellent writing samples, assemble author readings, or make writing portfolios to recognize students' diligence and commitment. You may further emphasize the significance and fulfillment of writing as a worthwhile pursuit by praising their accomplishments.

It's a useful tool for teaching pupils that writing is a process of learning rather than a goal in itself. Additionally, explain to them that writing is a difficult, disorganized, nonlinear process with many failed beginnings. Assist them in determining the

- Developing ideas
- Finding a focus and a thesis
- Composing a draft
- Getting feedback and comments from others
- Revising the draft by expanding ideas, clarifying meaning, reorganizing
- Editing
- Presenting the finished work to readers
- Explain that writing is hard work.

It takes a comprehensive strategy that develops creativity, resilience, and a community of writers to motivate secondary pupils to write well. Through the use of these tactics and concepts, educators may enable children to unleash the potential of writing and set off on a path of self-exploration, self-expression, and lifelong learning. The years from 5 to 9 are crucial for the development of writing skills because they set the foundation for a lifetime of reading comprehension and creative expression. By creating a safe space for learning, encouraging creativity, and utilizing technology effectively, teachers can equip students to become skilled writers who use language with intention, passion, and accuracy. As we set out on this life-changing adventure, let's sow the seeds of writing proficiency and raise a future of writers.

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UNLEASHING THE POTENTIAL OF GAMIFICATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING: A HOLISTIC EXAMINATION

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Аннотация. В данной статье исследованы нюансы применения геймификации в области изучения английского языка. Автор показывает, как геймификация может быть умело использована не только для содействия овладению языком, но и для развития глубоких знаний языка.

Ключевые слова: геймификация, мотивация, элементы игры, интеграция технологий, личностно-ориентированное обучение, интерактивное обучение, практика в классе, разработка учебной программы.

Introduction. The integration of gamification into educational practices has revolutionized traditional teaching methodologies by infusing elements of game design into non-game contexts. Gamification harnesses the inherent motivational aspects of games to stimulate engagement, promote active learning, and enhance overall learning outcomes. In the context of language learning, particularly English language acquisition, gamification offers a promising avenue to address the challenges associated with sustaining learner motivation, fostering proficiency development, and creating dynamic learning environments.

Literature Review. Gamification in English language learning has garnered significant attention in recent years, with scholars and educators exploring its potential to revolutionize language acquisition processes. Research studies have underscored the multifaceted benefits of gamification, including its ability to enhance learner motivation, facilitate autonomous learning, and promote collaborative engagement. Moreover, gamified language learning environments have been shown to provide learners with opportunities for meaningful language practice, immediate feedback, and personalized learning experiences.

Various gamification strategies have been employed in English language classrooms, ranging from point-based systems and badges to leaderboards and immersive quest-based learning. These mechanisms serve to incentivize learner participation, track progress, and foster a sense of achievement and competitiveness. Additionally, gamification facilitates the integration of authentic language use in simulated contexts, thereby enhancing learners' communicative competence and real-world applicability of language skills.

Despite the evident benefits, challenges exist in the effective implementation of gamification in English language learning. Educators must navigate issues related to balancing game elements with pedagogical objectives, designing culturally relevant and inclusive gaming experiences, and addressing the diverse needs and preferences of learners. Furthermore, considerations regarding technological infrastructure, teacher training, and assessment methods pose additional complexities in integrating gamification into language learning curricula.

Methods. To investigate the efficacy of gamification in English language learning, researchers have employed diverse methodological approaches, including experimental studies, surveys, case analyses, longitudinal research designs, and ethnographic research methods. Experimental studies typically involve comparing the learning outcomes of learners exposed to gamified language learning activities with those engaged in traditional instruction. Surveys and questionnaires are utilized to elicit learner perceptions, attitudes, and preferences towards gamification, while case analyses provide insights into the practical implementation and outcomes of gamified language learning initiatives in authentic classroom settings. Longitudinal research designs allow for the examination of the long-term effects of gamification on

language proficiency development and learner motivation, while ethnographic research methods offer insights into the socio-cultural dimensions of gamified language learning environments.

Discussion. The integration of gamification into English language learning holds immense potential to transform conventional pedagogical practices and revolutionize the learning experiences of learners. By leveraging the motivational elements inherent in games, educators can create immersive and interactive learning environments that captivate learners' interest, stimulate curiosity, and foster intrinsic motivation. Gamification encourages active participation, exploration, and experimentation, thereby enabling learners to develop language skills in a dynamic and engaging manner.

Furthermore, gamified language learning experiences can be tailored to address specific language competencies, including vocabulary acquisition, grammar proficiency, listening comprehension, and speaking fluency. Through gamified activities such as language quests, role-playing simulations, and interactive storytelling, learners are provided with authentic opportunities to practice language skills in meaningful contexts, thereby enhancing their communicative competence and linguistic proficiency.

However, the successful implementation of gamification in English language learning necessitates careful planning, pedagogical alignment, ongoing support from educators, and collaboration with educational technology experts. It is essential for educators to design gamified activities that are aligned with curricular objectives, scaffold learning experiences to accommodate learners' varying proficiency levels, and provide opportunities for reflection and metacognition. Additionally, educators must foster a supportive learning environment that encourages collaboration, creativity, and risk-taking, thereby empowering learners to take ownership of their language learning journey.

Conclusion. In conclusion, gamification represents a powerful pedagogical tool that has the potential to revolutionize English language learning by harnessing the motivational power of games to engage learners, foster proficiency development, and cultivate a deeper appreciation for the English language. As technology continues to evolve, gamification offers new possibilities for creating dynamic and immersive learning experiences that cater to the diverse needs and preferences of learners. However, the successful integration of gamification into language learning curricula requires careful planning, pedagogical alignment, ongoing research, collaboration, and investment in educational technology infrastructure. By embracing gamification as a transformative approach to language learning, educators can empower learners to become confident, competent, and lifelong communicators in the English language.

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THE SIGNIFICANCE OF CODE-SWITCHING STRATEGY IN CONTEMPORARY LANGUAGE INSTRUCTION

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Аннотация. В статье рассматривается значение переключения кода, действия или практики чередования двух или более языков во время разговора в современной среде обучения языка. Автор показывает как переключение кода может равняться с современными методами обучения, такими как обучение коммуникативной речи или обучение языку на основе задач.

Ключевые слова: переключение кода, современное обучение языка, стратегии обучения, подходы, коммуникативное обучение языка, обучение языка на основе задач, аутентичный язык.

Introduction. Language is a dynamic tool for human communication that surpasses strict linguistic rules. Code-switching is a practice where speakers switch between multiple languages or dialects in a single conversation. This phenomenon has gained attention in the field of education, particularly in language teaching. As language education methods progress, teaching languages now focuses on authentic language use. This shift recognizes the diversity and richness of language, promoting teaching practices that reflect the dynamic nature of linguistic interactions. The purpose of this article is to explore the relationship between code-switching and modern language teaching. It demonstrates how this phenomenon can be utilized as a valuable tool for teaching by examining the theoretical basis of code-switching and its practical implications in educational settings. Through the perspective of contemporary language teaching methodologies, it will investigate how code-switching aligns with and enhances the language learning experience. Moreover, as the article explores the complex world of code-switching in language education, it is discovered that it not only connects different languages but also boosts our knowledge of language and culture. Hence, this paper aims to motivate educators and instructors to adopt innovative methods that foster linguistic proficiency, cultural understanding, and effective communication among learners.

Concept of code-switching. Code-switching is a linguistic phenomenon that is commonly observed in multilingual societies, involving the smooth transition between two or more languages or linguistic variations within a single conversation. This complex interaction of languages demonstrates a flexible use of language and an adaptability to different cultural contexts, which can be seen in diverse settings around the globe. For instance, in Uzbekistan, bilingual speakers may effortlessly switch between Uzbek and Russian in their everyday conversations, reflecting the diverse cultural and linguistic landscape of the country. According to Trudgill (2000), bilingual individuals use code-switching to express multiple identities at the same time, showing the complex relationship between language, culture, and social identity.

The domain of code-switching offers various types that provide detailed insights into its manifestation. Canagarajah (1995) acknowledges that researchers have categorized three specific types of code-switching: tag-switching, inter-sentential switching and intra-sentential switching. Tag-switching is the smooth incorporation of a tag phrase from one language into another, commonly observed in greetings, farewells, and other frequently used expressions. This type of code-switching acts as a linguistic bridge, helping speakers to stay fluent while incorporating elements of their multilingual abilities into conversation.

Intra-sentential code-switching, which occurs when individuals incorporate elements from multiple languages within a single sentence or utterance, demonstrates the flexibility of linguistic boundaries (Gumperz, 1982). Let's imagine a scenario where a bilingual speaker of Uzbek and English says, "Xozir supermarketga shopping qilishga ketyapman". In this case, the speaker seamlessly combines Uzbek and English to express their intention, blurring the linguistic boundaries while ensuring coherence within the discourse.

Inter-sentential code-switching, on the other hand, refers to the practice of changing languages between sentences or clauses within a conversation (Schmidt, 2014). For instance, a bilingual speaker of

Russian and English might say, "Давай купим новый devices, и установим в них upgraded programs". This deliberate switching between Russian and English allows the speaker to express different ideas or highlight specific points, illustrating the fluidity of multilingual communication.

Furthermore, code-switching is guided by sociolinguistic norms and communication strategies, demonstrating the intentions and social dynamics of speakers (Hussein et al., 2020). For example, in a study place with different cultures, students may switch between English and their native language to create a sense of unity and acceptance, illustrating how language can be a tool for social interaction. Adriosh and Razi (2019) state that bilingual individuals may employ code-switching to establish a sense of solidarity with a specific linguistic community or convey their cultural identity

Code-switching in Language Education. Code-switching is not only studied in sociolinguistics but also has relevance in language education. This part of article will investigate the application of code-switching in language classrooms, its role in enriching language learning results, and examples of how educators integrate code-switching into their instructional approaches. Teachers frequently use code-switching as a teaching strategy to assist students in acquiring language skills, improving comprehension, and fostering cross-cultural understanding. Also, students may use code-switching as a strategy to overcome language challenges, especially when expressing themselves freely or encountering unfamiliar words or concepts. Therefore, code-switching provides a valuable perspective for scholars and educators to understand the intricate dynamics of language use and identity negotiation in different linguistic contexts.

In modern language teaching environments, code-switching is frequently employed as a scaffolding strategy to support students' language acquisition process. According to Cook (2001), teachers often interpret maximizing the use of the target language as completely excluding the use of the first language in foreign language classrooms. Educators may purposefully integrate features of students' first languages or regional dialects with the target language to offer explanations, facilitate understanding, and strengthen language patterns. Moreover, code-switching can function as a tool for promoting cultural authenticity and fostering a welcoming classroom atmosphere that values linguistic diversity.

The utilization of code-switching is a vital tool in supporting language acquisition and comprehension among learners. According to Hussein et al. (2020), through the integration of familiar linguistic elements from students' native languages or dialects into the target language instruction, educators can offer comprehensible input and assist in scaffolding learners' grasp of new language concepts. Furthermore, code-switching aids in fostering connections between languages, thereby enhancing learners' overall language proficiency and communicative competence.

Teachers utilize a variety of methods to integrate code-switching into their teaching practices. One common strategy involves offering bilingual explanations or translations of important vocabulary and concepts to ensure that students understand the material. For instance, a teacher might switch between languages to clarify the meaning of a word by providing its translation in the students' native language. Moreover, educators may prompt students to code-switch during communicative tasks, enabling them to express themselves more effectively in multilingual settings. Additionally, code-switching can be strategically employed during language drills or grammar exercises to strengthen language skills and emphasize differences between languages.

The Benefits and Challenges of Code-Switching in Language Teaching. Code-switching is a powerful tool that can enhance student engagement in language classrooms by effectively connecting students' linguistic backgrounds with the target language used for instruction. Having integrated aspects of students' first languages or dialects into their lessons, teachers create a sense of familiarity and ease, thereby making the learning experience more relatable and accessible. Cook (2001) highlights the importance of using the first language for tasks such as explaining grammar, organizing activities, managing student behavior, and conducting assessments. This practice effectively bridges the gap between students' linguistic backgrounds and the target language of instruction, facilitating a deeper understanding and connection to the subject matter. As a result, students are more likely to actively participate and engage in the learning process. For instance, imagine a language classroom where most students are bilingual, proficient in English and Uzbek. The teacher recognizes the students' diverse linguistic backgrounds and effortlessly combines both languages during instruction (Bilgin, 2016). When teaching complex grammar or vocabulary, the instructor switches between English and Uzbek to ensure that all students understand the explanations. This

strategy caters to the diverse languages present in the classroom and empowers students to actively participate in their education. Students become more confident in expressing themselves in multiple languages, leading to increased involvement and interaction during class discussions, group activities, and language practice sessions.

Moreover, when teachers switch between languages to explain or reinforce language structures, students gain a more comprehensive understanding of the target language and how it is used in real-life situations. Consider a situation where a language teacher is introducing a new vocabulary term in an English language class for Uzbek students. The teacher observes that certain students are having difficulty understanding the meaning of the word "crop" in isolation. To aid comprehension, the teacher smoothly transitions to Uzbek, providing a brief explanation: "In Uzbek, 'crop' is equivalent to 'hosil'. Through the integration of translation and code-switching from English to Uzbek, the educator offers learners an extra linguistic signal to link the unfamiliar vocabulary with their pre-existing language skills. This method serves to elucidate the word's significance while also strengthening the bond between the second language and the students' mother tongue, thereby aiding in the understanding and memorization of new vocabulary.

On the other hand, the challenge of code-switching is often linked to negative language ideologies and the stigmatization of particular language varieties. As stated in Wardhaugh (2011), in educational environments, there is a preference for standard language norms and a bias against non-standard varieties. Consequently, code-switching to non-standard or vernacular forms may be seen as incorrect and face disapproval or discrimination. For example, think about a situation where a student switches back and forth between their native language and the target language during a class discussion. The teacher criticizes the student for not speaking "properly" and demands that they only speak in the target language. This can make the student feel embarrassed or inadequate about their language abilities. As a result, language biases and negative attitudes towards code-switching can worsen inequality and power imbalances in schools, affecting students' social and academic well-being. However, studies have shown that teachers often switch between languages to help students differentiate between the target language and the first language to prevent negative transfer, with inter-sentential code-switching being the most common form (Altun, 2019).

Code-switching in Modern Approaches of Language Teaching. The field of modern language teaching has witnessed a transformation in its methodologies, with a focus on enhancing communicative competence, authentic language use, and learner-centered instruction. Two prominent methodologies that exemplify this shift are communicative language teaching (CLT) and task-based language teaching (TBLT). These approaches prioritize meaningful communication, task-based learning activities, and the integration of language skills in real-life contexts.

Communicative Language Teaching is an instructional approach to language education that places emphasis on the development of learners' ability to communicate proficiently in real-life scenarios. The fundamental principle of CLT is that language learning should be centered around the learner and foster interactive engagement, with a strong focus on meaningful communication and language usage (Richards & Rodgers, 2001). In a CLT classroom, students learn language through interactive tasks like role-plays, simulations, and information-gap activities, which require them to communicate in the target language to accomplish specific goals. Code-switching is commonly incorporated into CLT to reflect real-life language use. For instance, students might participate in a role-play scenario set in a restaurant, where one student takes on the role of a customer placing an order while another student acts as the waiter. The incorporation of code-switching in these activities allows for a more realistic representation of language use, as students may switch between their native language and the target language to discuss menu options, inquire about the food, and make requests. In a role-play task, students may switch between their native language and the target language to negotiate meaning and express themselves more effectively (Ellis, 2003).

Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) is a methodology in language education that emphasizes the utilization of real-world tasks as the central component of instruction. These tasks are meaningful activities that prompt learners to apply the target language in order to achieve a particular aim or objective. In addition, language acquisition in a TBLT classroom is achieved through the completion of tasks like problem-solving activities, information-gap tasks, and project-based assignments. The integration of code-switching in TBLT serves to enhance comprehension, facilitate communication, and provide support for language learning. Project-based tasks involve students in researching, planning, and sharing information about a particular subject or theme. For example, students can work together on a multimedia project

that investigates environmental problems in their community. While conducting research, students may switch between languages to access useful resources or gather information from different sources. By incorporating code-switching into project-based tasks, teachers motivate students to use their language skills and participate in genuine exploration and inquiry. In a group project where students collaborate to solve a problem, code-switching may naturally occur as students tap into their linguistic resources to share ideas and negotiate solutions (Nunan, 2004). Code-switching in TBLT can assist learners in task performance by offering them extra linguistic hints and aiding their language learning process. Permitting students to switch between languages while doing tasks helps establish a supportive setting for learning, enabling students to comprehend language input, discuss meanings, and cooperate with peers to accomplish task goals.

Conclusion. In conclusion, code-switching holds great significance in contemporary language teaching due to its diverse functions. Having explored methodologies such as Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), it becomes apparent that code-switching serves as an invaluable pedagogical tool. It effectively enhances communicative competence, aids comprehension, and promotes cultural awareness among language learners. Through the alignment of code-switching with these strategies, instructors can establish inclusive and stimulating learning environments that prioritize linguistic diversity and facilitate effective language acquisition. Hence, teachers can help students use the target language in real-world and relevant circumstances by including code-switching into communicative tasks, role-playing scenarios, information-exchange activities, problem-solving tasks, and project-based assignments.

All in all, code-switching is more than a linguistic phenomenon; it is a pedagogical asset that can enhance language learning experiences, facilitate intercultural understanding, and promote effective communication within diverse linguistic communities. In their efforts to cultivate inclusive and successful language teaching environments, educators acknowledge code-switching as a valuable instrument for fostering communicative proficiency, cultural awareness, and linguistic empowerment among language learners.

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ПРЕОБРАЗОВАНИЕ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА: РОЛЬ МОБИЛЬНЫХ ПРИЛОЖЕНИЙ И МОБИЛЬНОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ

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Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада инглиз тилини ўқитишда мобил иловалар ва мобил таълимнинг ўрни масаласи ёритилган. Унда тил ўқитишда мобил технологияларни қўллашнинг афзалликлари, хусусан, қулайлиги, шахсга йўналтирилганлиги, ўйинлардан фойдаланиш ва онлайн-жамоа билан мулоқот қилиш имкониятлари баён қилинган.

Калит сўзлар: мобил иловалар, мобил ўқув, инглиз тилини ўқитиш, шахсга йўналтирилган таълим, ўйин усули, онлайн-жамоа.

С развитием технологий мобильных устройств преподавание английского языка стало более доступным, интерактивным и эффективным благодаря мобильным приложениям и мобильному обучению. Эти инновационные методы обучения не только изменяют способ, которым студенты изучают английский язык, но и открывают новые возможности для обучающихся и преподавателей. В данной статье рассматривается роль мобильных приложений и мобильного обучения в преподавании английского языка.

В данной статье рассмотрены преимущества использования мобильных технологий в образовательном процессе и предлагает обзор ключевых аспектов, которые делают мобильные приложения эффективным инструментом для изучения английского языка [1]. Будут рассмотрены персонализация обучения, игровой подход, доступность, возможность взаимодействия с онлайн-сообществом и другие аспекты, которые делают эти технологии важным элементом в современном образовании.

В контексте быстро меняющегося мира образования и растущей зависимости от цифровых технологий, понимание роли мобильных приложений и мобильного обучения в преподавании английского языка является ключевым для успешной адаптации к новым образовательным трендам и достижения высоких результатов в обучении [2].

В мире, где мобильные технологии стали неотъемлемой частью нашей повседневной жизни, образование не осталось в стороне. Особенно в контексте преподавания и изучения английского языка, мобильные приложения и мобильное обучение играют ключевую роль в улучшении доступности, эффективности и интерактивности образовательного процесса.

Интерактивное обучение в вашем кармане. Одной из основных причин популярности мобильного обучения является его удобство и доступность. Мобильные приложения позволяют учащимся получать доступ к обучающим материалам в любое время и в любом месте, превращая каждый свободный момент в возможность для обучения [3]. Это особенно важно для изучения английского языка, поскольку постоянная практика и вовлеченность являются ключевыми факторами в достижении успеха.

Персонализированный подход. Еще одним преимуществом мобильных приложений для изучения английского языка является их способность к персонализации обучения [5]. Благодаря алгоритмам адаптации и индивидуальной оценке уровня знаний, приложения могут предлагать пользователю уникальные курсы, упражнения и задания, соответствующие его потребностям и

уровню владения языком. Это позволяет каждому учащемуся развиваться в своем собственном темпе и наиболее эффективным способом.

Игровой подход к обучению. Многие мобильные приложения для изучения английского языка используют игровые элементы, чтобы сделать обучение более увлекательным и мотивирующим [4]. Благодаря заданиям в форме игр, учащиеся получают возможность не только повысить свой уровень владения языком, но и провести время с удовольствием. Этот игровой подход стимулирует учащихся к регулярной практике и помогает сделать процесс обучения более эффективным и результативным.

Онлайн-сообщество и мгновенная обратная связь. Еще одним значимым аспектом мобильных приложений для обучения английскому языку является возможность взаимодействия с другими учащимися и получения обратной связи от преподавателей и носителей языка [6]. Многие приложения предоставляют доступ к онлайн-форумам, где учащиеся могут общаться, обмениваться опытом и помогать друг другу в изучении языка. Кроме того, возможность мгновенно получать обратную связь на выполненные задания позволяет учащимся непрерывно улучшать свои навыки.

В этой статье мы рассмотрели значимость и важность мобильных приложений и мобильного обучения в контексте преподавания английского языка. Мы выявили, что использование мобильных технологий в обучении английскому языку приносит множество преимуществ, включая доступность, персонализацию обучения, игровой подход и возможность взаимодействия с онлайн-сообществом. Эти преимущества делают мобильные приложения эффективным инструментом для обучения английскому языку, обеспечивая учащимся широкий спектр образовательных ресурсов и возможность индивидуализированного обучения. Кроме того, использование игровых элементов и возможность общения с другими учащимися через онлайн-сообщества делают процесс изучения более увлекательным и мотивирующим.

Однако, необходимо помнить, что успешное использование мобильных приложений в обучении английскому языку требует не только доступности технологий, но и компетентности преподавателей и готовности учащихся к самостоятельному обучению [7]. В целом, мобильные приложения и мобильное обучение играют важную роль в современном образовании, и использование их в контексте преподавания английского языка может существенно улучшить образовательный процесс и результаты обучения.

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MAXIMIZING THE BENEFITS OF TECHNOLOGY IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Аннотация. В данной статье исследуется важная роль технологий в обучении языкам, выделены три основных условия для их эффективного использования, обосновано их влияние на улучшение результатов обучения языкам и совершенствование инновационных практик преподавания в цифровом образовании.

Ключевые слова: языковая компетенция, трансформация, использование технологий, педагогика, педагогические принципы, усвоение языка, аутентичное образование, языковая обработка, использование языка.

Today we are addressing a very important question and that question is "Can technology enhance language teaching and language learning?". In that way, the focus will be on language learning, in particular we will be focusing on language proficiency or English language teaching. As we know technology is now everywhere, we cannot really live without technology. Even if we want to order food we have to use technology. This is particularly true in our everyday life where we are experiencing a soft lockdown. People are not expected, are not encouraged to go out until they have to make use of whatever technology they have in order to interact to get the job done. In the same way in education can we teach without technology? The answer is probably not. Currently a lot of us are making heavy use of technology in our teaching, in our interaction with our colleagues and also in our interaction with our students as well. We have searched a lot about the research that has been done in terms of the potential benefits of technology in language teaching and language learning. Now technology can transform language learning, we can do things that was not possible before, it can also enhance language teaching as well as language learning.

Researchers tend to use words transform, enhance and support language teaching and learning, but for us language teachers or English language teachers, we want to know whether and to what extent the use of technology can eventually improve the English language proficiency of our students. Study that was published [5; 24] recently in 2019 by three experienced researchers, one from Canada and the other two based in China. The title is "The more technology the better? A comparison of teacher student interactions in high and low technology use in elementary EFL classrooms in China". This is a topic that is of interest to many of teachers, especially, those of them are working in low resource countries-in places where resources are limited. This is happening in China's primary schools-in villages in small towns. The researchers are looking over investigating the use of high technology and low technology groups in two different groups of teachers and they wanted to find out if the interaction patterns in these two different classes are basically the same or different. The instruction patterns here referred to the kind of questions that the teacher asks the kind of interactions that the students have in the classroom. In other words, the amount and the quality of interactions that happen in the classroom. Social learning theories tell us that social interaction is significantly important for language development. The results are likely to be interesting in terms of the two groups of teachers-one using technology a little bit and the other group using a lot of technology. The answer interestingly or the result of this study is the same. They are the same-the two groups of teachers using a lot of technology on the one hand and the other group using less technology. There is no difference, interesting, isn't it. They're the same- the amount of use of English in the classroom continued to be very small very minimal, negligible use of English in the classroom both by the teachers and also by the students and remarkably when the teachers ask questions, they ask the same old questions that they usually ask the students. There are a lot of display questions, like "What time is it now?", "What day was it yesterday?" or directives "Open page 9.", "Walk in groups.", "Do your homework" – the kind of questions that teachers usually ask in the classroom. In terms of the kind

of feedback that the teachers give the students again showed minimal of use. Thus, this is one study that shows that the use of technology in and of itself. Technology is just a tool. If you use technology simply as a tool not as approach that will support your pedagogical innovations or pedagogical teaching then technology may not produce the desired results. Another study was published in high profile journal called "Computer Assisted Language Learning" [2; 17] and the researcher looked at a big number of past studies that have examined the potential effect of technology in foreign language learning. They reviewed about 350 previously completed studies involving the use of technology. They wanted to find out whether technology made a difference, whether technology could help improve students' English language proficiency or some aspects of students' English language proficiency. The result is interestingly overall the effect is limited. We are looking at the effect of technology on English language proficiency such as speaking, reading, writing, listening. The only interesting or strong effect is found on pronunciation. Therefore, the lesson here is very clear-if we want to improve their pronunciation, then technology might be our best option. Technology can be a wonderful tool for us to help our students develop or improve on their pronunciation. Finally, an increased amount of chat time was experienced. Students are more active using technology to exchange ideas, but we don't know whether the students are using the target language or whether the students are doing the chatting using their first language, however the amount of talk increased.

If that is the case: "Can technology enhance language learning?". We have seen two studies there and along with that we would like to share with you three major points and we think these three points will help us understand why the effect of technology on English language proficiency-our students' proficiency can be very small or medium sized or effective. We will be looking at three different conditions of using technology. 1) The use of technology with a little change in pedagogy (interestingly this is still widespread in many parts of the world); 2) Using technology but the use is accompanied by with a good set of pedagogical principles; 3) The use of technology is informed by a good set of second language pedagogy.

Principles help us understand the nature of language acquisition and how we can support students in acquiring the language. Beginning with the first condition-using technology with little change in pedagogy. The use of technology is simple: substitute for what you know is now possible-using technology sharing documents, using Google Drive, for example communicating with students using WhatsApp, asking students to fill in a survey or an exercise using Google forms, doing a spell check. In that case we would be using text with hyperlinks and things like that and these should not be considered as something impractical. These are assets that we should be using present day, because technology allows us to make use of these tools with the intention of helping us teach and communicate with our students, but then again without appropriate use of pedagogy we may not be able to perceive the effect, the results that we would like to see happening in our students. For example, in the past we used printed materials as reading materials, but now we can use digital texts to support the students become more familiar with the non-print reading materials. On the other hand, the question is whether e-books and printed books are equally effective, do they produce the same level of comprehension? If there is no change in pedagogy, if there's no change in the way the students read the text, it is not expected any major differences. Whether we read printed or non-print materials we have the knowledge and the skills. It doesn't matter whether we read online or printed books, we would eventually be able to set our purpose very clearly if we could focus our attention in a certain way. Good readers are expected to do an example of simple substitution in our teaching. Many English language teachers used to teach the language as knowledge explaining or spending a lot of time teaching the grammatical rules of the English language, like the subjunctive clause, the gerund and all the wonderful grammatical features of the language by using traditional way of presenting the information to the students, but now we are using technology. In this occasion where there is no major change in pedagogy, it is hard to expect a major transformation or a major benefit in terms of the language learning that happens in the classroom. You may be wondering what are some of the reasons why teachers continue to use the same pedagogy despite they teach online or on site. The reasons that teachers are business people they, do not have time to actually learn how to use technology in the way that experts believe are important for teachers. Considering the fact that countries are experiencing a major disruption in their teaching, some teachers feel that while they've got no choice nowadays, so they

have to use technology. If technology is used in that way with minor and small change in our pedagogical approaches, then the answer to the question of "Whether technology can improve English language proficiency" is probably not.

The second approach is very easy the use of technology with good pedagogy. There are a lot of pedagogical principles that we need to use in order to make the best use of technology in our teaching. In other words, the use of technology will have to be informed by a set of research-based principles and there exists a multitude of instances. There are five essential principles of good teaching that when are used, then it is going to be an effective outcome and they are followings: 1) Personalized teaching or student-oriented; 2) Engaged learning; 3) Authentic learning; 4) Feedback; 5) Collaborative learning.

Despite we are teaching on site or online learning happens when it is personalized. [8; 25] When we appreciate and address the learning needs of our students about the differences that exist in our classroom, then it is counted as personalized teaching. Engaged learning is another chief principle. These days some people have suggested that engagement is the 'Holy Grail of learning'[1;66]. If the students are not engaged, the chances of learning are not likely to happen. Students may learn to some extent there, but that is mostly very superficial kind of learning. Some people have suggested that if we are able to engage 90% of our students 90% of the time then we are likely to be a good excellent successful language teacher in the classroom [7; 45]. Authentic learning is based on bringing in a realistic real-world task into the classroom and that is the kind of things that are likely to engage the students to motivate [4; 97]. Some knowledge of the language is important but more importantly is how we can convert it into amusement. Feedback is important and it can be very demanding. Feedback can be something that we try to avoid but if we investigate it from another perspective the feedback that we hand to the students is from the students' perspective a prospect for them to learn and relearn again what they have just learned previously from the educator. Collaboration is additional vital thing that we need to think of. Learning happens when the students are able to share their ideas, expand their ideas and learn from others as well in the process. These are five principles that are important when we use technology in language classroom. As professor Mike Sharples says: "Focusing on pedagogy is way more efficient in improving education rather than technology" [6; 78]. Consequently, it's in what manner we use technology not the technology itself and the technology turns out to be very easy to use. Some may be very sophisticated but it is the pedagogy that we use that can make a difference. If we practice technology and our use of technology is informed by a good set of pedagogical principles it is likely to improve students' English language proficiency. However, a good set of principles pedagogical principles is very important, but we consider we necessitate something different and that's something else is what we are going to discuss with you in point number three. Briefly, 1) the use of technology with very minimal change that we just use technology the way we talk before; 2) technology that is accompanied by a good set of principles; 3) using technology but the use of technology is informed by second language's pedagogical principles.

We are teaching language and eventually we are interested in assisting our students to acquire the language, to develop sufficient proficiency in the language. There are mainly three principles of second language's pedagogy, named language input, language processing and language use respectively (also named as 3Ls). Language input: the research tells us that language input is extremely important in language learning and technology is an excellent tool for our students or for the teachers to make input available in large quantity to our students. It confirms very clearly that if the input is minimal then we can't expect a lot of language learning to occur in the classroom, other types of learning can happen in the classroom but without appropriate and the sufficient amount of language input language acquisition may not happen. Nowadays, with technology input is more accessible with a single click compared to 20-30 years ago when language input was exacting and the best place for the students to be exposed to the target language input was probably the classroom and to some extent the universities or the schools' library, on the contrary, in the current scenario input is available 24 hours a day e-books, graded readers, Ted-talks, Netflix, talk shows-all these can potentially serve as important language input which can assist students develop their English language proficiency. As professor Richard Day from the University of Hawaii wrote: "Good things happen to students who read and listen a great deal in a foreign language. Research studies show they become better and more confident readers, they write better, their listening and speaking ability improve

and their vocabularies become richer" [3; 1]. These days providing a lot of input reading materials and listening materials become easier with technology and as the quote mentions here if we crave our students to become good readers and confident bookworms, students who are able to understand spoken language and can express themselves clearly then this is the way to go. 20 years ago, it may be a bit difficult to provide a lot of input to our students, conversely these days it's easier and a lot of the input that is available is free such as "Storyline Online". It provides our students with a free access to give assistance to them, develop their pronunciation and their English language proficiency if they listen to the stories over a period of time. Another example of free resources that are available on the internet is "Books for Asia" made available by the "Asia Foundation". There are hundreds of books intended for improving reading skills, making reading more enjoyable activity with pictures to our students and even for children at home. L2 is language processing and the key idea here is this input alone is not enough, input will have to be or the language in the input will have to be accessible. 'Accessible' here is used instead of the word 'easy' which means easy from the students' perspective. It is regarded as the kind of language materials that they can understand easily without a lot of effort but the contents more importantly should be appealing. When the contents of what they read and listen are appealing and accessible, there will be fully engaged learning environment and with that a lot of learning can happen. L3 is usage. Teachers have to do practicing, using the language again and again. The goal of language learning eventually is to develop fluency and accuracy and the only way they are able to develop fluency is when they do things again and again repeatedly on the daily basis. That is the power of repeated practice and people learn to read by reading-by doing a lot of reading and that is how they develop their reading proficiency; people learn to speak by speaking; people learn to listen by listening; people learn to write by writing. Technology is an excellent tool to get the students to be excited to be interested in speaking, reading, writing, and listening and so the second language's learning principles-language input language processing and language use. If our technology, if the use of technology is accompanied by these 3Ls, it is likely going to improve the language proficiency of the students.

In conclusion, it is clear that technology is going to stay with us for many years to come, eventually we will not be doing a solely online teaching but we will be doing a lot of blended learning on site plus online. Thus, it is a good opportunity for us to learn how to use technology in a way that is consistent with what we know from research about the nature of language learning and how best we can support students' English language proficiency's development. Moreover, the use of technology will have to be accompanied by a good set of educational principles but also second language's learning principles. Only in these conditions we can teach better, we can expect more from the students in acquiring second language proficiency and students can also get excited from what they are doing by engaged learning, eliminating long-term boredom and disinterest and shortening long-term period of language learning.

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MASTERING THE ART: TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается динамичное направление преподавания английского языка как второго языка (ESL), затрагивая основные компоненты и эффективные стратегии как для преподавателей, так и для учащихся. Основной упор делается на понимание разнообразия учащихся, использование коммуникативного подхода, интеграцию языковых навыков, развитие культурной компетенции, использование технологий и постоянное профессиональное развитие.

Ключевые слова: ESL (английский как второй язык), методика преподавания, коммуникативный подход, интеграция языковых навыков, культурная компетентность, интеграция технологий, профессиональное развитие.

Teaching English as a second language (ESL) is a multifaceted endeavor that goes beyond just conveying grammar rules and vocabulary. It's about fostering effective communication, cultural understanding, and confidence in learners. As English continues to be the lingua franca of the globalized world, the demand for skilled ESL instructors remains high. In this article, we explore the essential components of effective ESL teaching and strategies to empower both teachers and learners in this dynamic field.

One of the fundamental aspects of ESL teaching is recognizing the diversity among learners. Students come from various linguistic backgrounds, cultures, and proficiency levels. Therefore, a personalized approach is crucial. Assessing students' prior knowledge, language skills, and learning preferences helps tailor instruction to meet their specific needs. Additionally, acknowledging cultural differences fosters a supportive and inclusive learning environment.

The communicative approach is at the core of modern ESL teaching methodologies. It emphasizes real-life communication and interaction rather than rote memorization of grammar rules. Activities such as role-plays, discussions, and simulations enable learners to practice English in authentic contexts, enhancing their fluency and confidence. Through meaningful communication, students not only improve their language skills but also develop critical thinking and problem-solving abilities.

Effective ESL instruction integrates all language skills – listening, speaking, reading, and writing – in a balanced manner. While focusing on each skill individually is important, encouraging cross-skills interaction enhances language acquisition. For instance, a reading comprehension activity can lead to a discussion, followed by a writing task based on the topic. This holistic approach ensures comprehensive language development and reinforces connections between different linguistic components.

Teaching ESL goes beyond language proficiency; it involves promoting cultural competence among learners. Understanding cultural nuances and customs enriches language learning experiences and fosters respect for diversity. Incorporating authentic materials, such as literature, films, and multimedia resources from various cultures, exposes students to different perspectives and enhances their intercultural communication skills. Moreover, discussing cultural topics and societal norms encourages meaningful dialogue and promotes mutual understanding.

Incorporating technology into ESL instruction offers countless opportunities for engagement and innovation. Educational apps, multimedia resources, and online platforms provide interactive learning experiences and cater to diverse learning styles. Virtual classrooms and video conferencing tools facilitate remote teaching and enable global collaboration among students. Moreover, digital assessment tools streamline feedback processes and enable teachers to monitor students' progress effectively.

Continuous professional development is essential for ESL teachers to stay updated with the latest methodologies, technologies, and research in the field. Participating in workshops, conferences, and online courses enhances teaching skills and fosters a reflective teaching practice. Additionally, collaborating with colleagues and engaging in peer observation and feedback promotes a culture of professional growth and excellence.

Teaching English as a second language is a rewarding journey that requires dedication, creativity, and cultural sensitivity. By embracing student diversity, employing effective methodologies, integrating language skills, promoting cultural competence, leveraging technology, and engaging in continuous professional development, ESL instructors can empower learners to communicate confidently in English and navigate the complexities of the globalized world. As language bridges cultures and connects people worldwide, the role of ESL teachers remains indispensable in shaping inclusive and communicatively proficient communities.

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III. TARJIMA VA TARJIMASHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MASALALARI SHU'BASI

MARKETING VA MENEJMENT TERMINLARINING INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDAGI O'ZLASHMALARI

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Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена изучению заимствованных терминов в английском и узбекском языках, проведён их этимологический анализ. Указаны экстралингвистические факторы пополнения лексики языков мира, обусловленные межъязыковой глобализацией. Автор констатирует, что большая часть узбекских терминов заимствована из арабского или персидского, английского и русского языков, тогда как английские экономические термины заимствованы из французского, немецкого и испанского языков.

Ключевые слова: термин, экономический термин, способы перевода, значение, текст, эквивалент, этимология, заимствованные термины.

Ma'lumki, leksikologiya jamiyatni o'zgarishlarga tilshunoslik sohalari orasida mutanosib ravishda yangilab turuvchi, yangilanishlarga nisbatan tez va tayyor turuvchi soha hisoblanib, har bir til o'zining muayyan lug'at tarkibiga ega bo'lib, jamiyatdagi ijtimoiy-siyosiy o'zgarishlar yoki iqtisodiy-siyosiy hayotning rivojlanishini o'zida aks ettiradi, jamiyat rivojlanishi bilan hamohang taraqqiy etadi.

Xalqlarning o'zaro savdo-sotiq, madaniy aloqa, migratsiya jarayoni, hatto davlatlar o'rtasidagi iqtisodiy va siyosiy munosabatlar tillarni taraqqiy etishiga sabab bo'ladi. Bu esa ularning differentsiya yoki integratsiya hodisalari asosida amalga oshadi. Tilning rivojlanish jarayoni, asosan, ichki omil, shuningdek, tashqi omillar hisobiga kengayishidan iborat. Bugungi kun tillararo globallashtirish jarayoni sabab dunyo tillari lug'at tarkibining boyib borishida ekstralingvistik faktorning faollashganini ham alohida ta'kidlab o'tish joiz. XIX asrda tilimizning lug'at tarkibiga baynalminal tillar ta'sirida katta miqdordagi latincha ilmiy terminlar kirib keldi. Masalan, XX asr oxiridagi o'zbek tili uchun sammit, offshor, fyuchers, tender so'zlari ma'lum bir yangilik edi va ko'pchilik tomonidan seziladi. Muayyan vaqtdan keyin bunday so'zlar faol lug'atda o'zgarib, o'zbek tilining me'yorlariga muvaffaqiyatli moslashadi va shuning uchun neologizm ta'rifini yo'qotadi.

Tilshunoslikni rivojlantirishiga sabab bo'luvchi muhim omillardan biri mutaxassislar tomonidan terminologiya sohasidagi bilimlarning to'g'ri o'zlashtirilishi va savodli qo'llanishi hisoblanadi. Ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi iqtisodiyot sohasida qo'llaniluvchi terminlarning chog'ishtirish orqali o'rganilishi, xorijiy tillarni asl mohiyati va mazmun, ma'nosini keng yoritib berishga asos bo'ladi.

O'zbek tilida "shaxs" tushunchalar kategoriyasini ifodalovchi va -er, -or qo'shimchalari orqali shaxsni anglatuvchi ko'plab nomlar o'zlashgan so'zlardir:

a) lotin tilidan rus tili orqali (ayni vaqtda mazkur terminlar rus tilining o'zi uchun ham yevropa tillari orqali o'zlashgan bo'lib, rus tilining fonetik, grafik, morfologik xususiyatlariga moslashgan): auditor (auditor);

b) bevosita roman-german tillaridan, xususan, ingliz tilidan o'zlashgan. Masalan: sponsor (sponsor); diler (dealer); menejer (manager) [1];

Ma'lumki, marketing va menejment sohasiga oid ko'plab terminlar G'arbiy Yevropa tillaridan o'zlashgan terminlarning aksariyat qismi o'zbek tiliga vositachi rus tili orqali kirib kelgan. Bu uchinchi til sifatida o'zbek tiliga-iqtisod sohasi terminologik birliklarning fonetik, grafik jihatdan barqarorlashgan natijalarini o'zlashtirish yo'li bilan jahonga integratsiyalashuv jarayonida yuz beradi. Bunga deyarli tarkib hamda semantik kalka

usullari xizmat qiladi. O'zbek tilida terminlarning hosil bo'lishi va soha terminologik tizimining, xususan, marketing ve menejment sohasining shakllanishi rus va ingliz tilidagi termin hosil bo'lishidan farq qiluvchi o'ziga xoslikka ega. Bular:

1. Vositachi til, odatda rus tili orqali lotin, qadimgi grek, roman-german, rus tillaridan o'zlashgan yoki mustaqillik davridan keying to'g'ridan-to'g'ri o'zlashgan terminlar. Masalan: import (import), inflation (inflyatsiya), option (opsiya), pension (pensiya), subvention (subventsia). Rus, arab yoki fors tillaridan o'zlashgan terminlar: finans, finansist, ekonomika, economist, dezinflyatsiya.

2. Tarjima terminlar. Masalan ingliz tilidan o'zbek tiliga, bunda:

a) faqat o'zbek tiliga oid terminlar amal qiladi; mahalliy byudjet, aylanma kassa, byudjetlarning darajasi, maxsus g'azna hisobraqami.

b) o'zlashgan termin va iqtisodiyotga oid o'zbekcha termin birgalikda sinonim sifatida amal qiladi; budget deficit-byudjet taqchilligi, finance-moliya, treasure account - g'azna hisob raqami.

O'zlashgan tushuncha deganda o'zbek tiliga avvaldan arab yoki fors tillaridan o'zlashgan va ayni vaqtda retsipiyent tilning fonetik, grafik, morfologik xususiyatlariga moslashgan holda o'zbek tilining lug'at tizimidan barqaror o'rin egallagan terminlar nazarda tutiladi. Property-mulk; price-narx; shortage-kamomad.

3. Yevropa tillaridan terminlar tarjimasini ko'pincha so'z birikma shaklida, ya'ni so'zni izohlash orqali amalga oshiriladi. Bunday ko'p tarkibli birliklar bir tarkibli birliklar singari o'zbek tilida faol qo'llaniladi.

XX asrda o'zbek iqtisodiyot terminologiyasi tadqiqi bo'yicha sezilarli ishlar olib borilgan bo'lib, binobarin bu ishlar o'zbek terminologiyasining shakllanishiga aynan rus tilining ta'siri sezilarli darajada yuqori ekanligini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Chunonchi, ko'rib chiqilayotgan faoliyat sohaslarida analogik terminologik tushunchalar mavjud emas [2].

Iqtisodiyot o'ziga xos marketing tili va terminlariga ega. Marketing korxonaning iqtisodiy faoliyatida muhim ahamiyatga ega, chunki u mijozga o'z ehtiyojlarini qondirish uchun mahsulotni sotib oluvchiga yordam beradi va ishlab chiqarish sektori ushbu ehtiyojlarga tovar ishlab chiqarish orqali javob beradi. Bu jarayonlarni marketing tilida nomlashda potensial mijozlarga psixologik munosabatlarni ifodalovchi leksik birliklar mavjud. Mijozlar bilan muomala qilishda qanchalik ehtiyotkor bo'lsa, mahsulot sotish va shu bilan yuqori daromad olish imkoniyati shunchalik katta bo'ladi. Buni nazorat qilish orqali boshqarish uchun bizga marketing va menejmentga oid terminlarni to'g'ri ishlata olish salohiyati kerak bo'ladi.

Muayyan marketing kalit terminlarini tematik jihatdan tasniflash mumkin. Marketing va bozor iqtisodiyoti o'zaro chambarchas bog'liq. Marketing orqali biz bozorga to'g'ridan to'g'ri kirib boramiz, buning uchun bizga alohida maxsus termin emas, balki korxonalar bozordagi faoliyat va jarayonlarni nomlash hamda bozorni tavsiflash uchun mumkin bo'lgan barcha tasavvur qilib tushuna oladigan terminlar kerak [3]. Tez-tez qo'llaniladigan marketing terminlari XIX-asrning ikkinchi yarmida va XX-asrning boshlarida ingliz tilida so'zlashuvchi mamlakatlarda sanoat ishlab chiqarishining rivojlanishi asosida paydo bo'lgan. Ular marketing rivojlanishining turli bosqichlarida turlicha bo'lgan. O'zbek tilida juda ko'p so'zlar va tegishli terminlar asosan ingliz tilidan o'zlashtirilgan. Yuqorida sanab o'tilgan omillar o'zbek marketing terminologiyasida inglizcha terminlarning baynalmilallashuviga olib keldi. Iqtisodiy terminlarni o'zbek tiliga o'zlashish jarayoni odatda yangi terminologik birliklarni (shakl va ma'no) yaratishni bildiradi. Shuning uchun tahlil qilingan chet tili birliklari leksik so'zlar sifatida aniqlanishi mumkin, keyin ularni import, gibrid va o'zlashgan tarjimalarida tasniflash mumkin. Import – terminologik birliklar qabul qiluvchi tilning fonetik, grafik va grammatik xususiyatlariga moslashmagan holda to'liq qarz olishdir. Ba'zi bir kichik og'ishlardan tashqari, bu hodisa o'zbek tilida ham foydalaniladi, masalan: Marketing(ing)- marketing, bozorga kirish va egallash, savdo-sotiq, Branding(ing)- brending, mahsulot nomini reklama qilish, Factoring(ing)-faktoring, hisob-kitoblarni tashkil etish sohasidagi yangi xizmat turi [4].

Klassik va zamonaviy marketing va menejmentga oid ish unvonlari uchun asosan ushbu turdagi o'zlashma so'zlar ishlatiladi: Marketing Manager, Product Manager, Sales Manager, Key Account Manager, Communications Manager, Market Research Manager. Ushbu turdagi o'zlashma so'zlar, nafaqat nemis va ispan iqtisodiy matnlarida tez-tez ishlatiladi balki, o'zbek tilida ham hozirgi kunda ingliz qisqartma shaklida uchratish mumkin. Masalan:

C2C– Consumer-to-Consumer

C2B– Consumer-to-Business

B2C – Business-to-Consumer

B2B – Business-to-Business

E-Commerce – Electronic Commerce

PR – Public Relations

4Ps – Product, Price, Place, Promotion [5]

HR-Human Resources

Tillarda nima uchun o'zlashma so'zlar paydo bo'lishining bir qancha sabablari bor. Avvalo, ayni bir madaniyatga yangi so'z kiritiladi, agar u o'z ichiga olgan muhit bilan uyg'un bo'lgan taqdirda. Shuningdek, so'zlarni moslashtirish bilan bog'liq bir necha bosqichlar mavjud;

Jarayon quyidagi omillarga bog'liq:

1) qabul qiluvchining tili qanday rivojlanganligi;

2) so'zlovchilar qay darajada "milliy ongli";

3) xalqaro imtiyozlar;

4) filologik bilim va tilni tushunishdagi qiyinchiliklar [6; 8]. O'zbek tili terminologiyasini modernizatsiya qilish, zamonaviylashtirish, xalqaro va xorijiy so'zlarni o'zbek tiliga tarjima qilish masalalarini abadiy til normalari doirasida hal qilib, hamfikrlikda izlanish zarur. Bu masalalarni yakka holda hal qilmasdan, har qanday tilni boyitish uchun butun dunyoda keng tarqalgan terminlardan foydalanish maqsadga muvofiq deb hisoblaymiz. Lekin bu bilan biz hayotni keraksiz darajada murakkablashtirib va ongimizni chalkashtirib yuborishimiz kerak emas.

Aytib o'tganimizdek, o'zbek iqtisodiy terminologiyasidagi inglizcha o'zlashmalar tahlili shuni ko'rsatdiki, qabul qiluvchi tilda o'zga so'zlarning quyidagi keng tarqalgan o'tish turlari xarakterlidir: import, gibrid va leksik o'zlashma tarjimalari. O'zbek tili uchun o'zlashma so'zlarning har uch xili – fonetik va grafik og'ishlari bor yoki bo'lmaganligi ko'proq isbotlangan. Tarjimalar haqida gap ketganda, tanlangan birlik qabul qiluvchi tilning orfografik me'yorlariga moslashtirilishi kerakligini hisobga olish kerak. Ba'zan bir xil birlikning turli tarjima va imlo variantlari mavjud. Keyin to'g'ri foydalanish uchun tegishli tushuntirishlar va maslahatlar bilan o'zlashma so'zlar yoki neologizmlar lug'ati juda foydali bo'ladi. Shu bilan bir qatorda, Internet ham muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, qidiruv tizimi orqali biron bir terminologik birliklarni qidirish orqali har bir variant qanchalik tez-tez sodir bo'lishini aniqlash mumkin.

Yesherkina L.V ilmiy maqolalardan birida xorijiy tillardagi so'zlarni, shu jumladan ingliz tilida iqtisodiy terminlarni paydo bo'lish sabablarini to'rtga ajratgan [7]:

1) yangi hodisalar, tushunchalarni nomlash zarurati sababli: inflation, business, privatization;

2) tushunchalarni ixtisoslashtirish zarurati: ing. marketing - bozor, marketing ing. management - menejment, ing. audit - audit, ing. leasing - lizing, daromadiga ko'ra sotib olish bilan ijaraga berish;

3) ingliz tiliga asoslangan iqtisodiy terminlarning o'rnatilgan tizimlarining xalqaro qo'llanishda mavjudligi: ing. lay away – lay-away -butun narxni oldindan to'lash asosida sotish amaliyoti, ing. landing – lending yuklarni tushirish uchun to'lo), inglizcha roll over - roll-over kredit muddatini yangilash);

4) Yangi, zamonga mos so'zlardan nutqda foydalanishga intilish orqali xorijiy tildan o'zlashgan so'zlar yanada jilvakor bo'lib chiqadi. Masalan, ofis (office – ofis), auditor (inglizcha auditor – auditor), franchayzing (inglizcha franchayzing - bozor subyektlari o'rtasidagi munosabatlar turi).

Iqtisodiyot sohasida o'zbek tiliga ingliz tilidan o'zlashtirish jarayoni so'nggi o'n yilliklarda ko'p uchramoqda, ammo bu sohani ingliz tilidagi terminlar bilan boyitish XX-asr davomida kuzatilgani hammamizga ma'lum. Xorijiy mamlakatlar bilan iqtisodiyot aloqalarning rivojlanishi natijasida o'zbek tili lug'atiga iqtisodiy, shu jumladan menejment, marketing va tijorat sohasiga oid terminlar kirib keldi: masalan: diler (ing. dealer - treyder, agent), market (ing. market - bozor), offshor, offshor fondlari (ing. offshore - bepul, yuridik shaxslarga bojxona va soliq imtiyozlari va boshqa qulayliklar keng yaratib berilgan hudud va mamlakatlar), dumping (ing. dumping-tashlash) -1) bozorni egallash va undan raqobatchilarni siqib chiqarish maqsadida mahsulotlarni sotuv narxiga nisbatan arzoniga sotish; 2) sifati past mollar eksporti. So'zlarning o'zbek tilining kundalik hayotiga qat'iy kirib kelganligining dalili bu ularning metaforizatsiyasi va o'zbek tili grammatikasiga moslashish hususiyatiga ham egadir, o'zlashgan so'zlar nafaqat grammatik jihatdan o'zbek og'zaki muhitiga ko'nikadi, balki o'zbek tilidagi so'zlarning qo'llanilishiga ham moslashadi.

Lekin, ixtisoslashgan sohalarda maxsus terminlar, ilmiy uslubdagi matnlar qo'llanilib, mutaxassislar hech qanday izoh va tushuntirishlarsiz foydalana oladi. Bularga, iqtisodiy sohaning maxsus terminlari misol bo'la oladi. Masalan:

III. TARJIMA VA TARJIMASHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MASALALARI SHU'BASII

fyuchers (ing. futures - tovar yoki fond birjasidagi fyuchers operatsiyalarining bir turi: fyuchers shartnomalari shartlarini muddatini belgilagan holda sotish va sotib olish. Fyuchers shartnomalari juda kamdan-kam hollarda real yetkazib berish bilan tugaydi).

Marketing va menejment sohasi faqatgina iqtisodiy sohadas emas, balki, boshqa bir qator turdosh sohalarga ham ta'sir ko'rsatadigan keng qamrovli bilim sohasidir. Shuning uchun, xorijiy terminlar ko'plab tematik guruhlarni tashkil qiladi va quyidagi guruhlar orqali tahlil qilish maqsadga muvofiq:

1. Turli xil sohalardagi xususiy va davlat tashkilotlarining nomlari:

-konsalting(maslahat berish) – (inglizcha konsulting - bu biznes-jarayonlarni optimallashtirish, faoliyatning asosiy ko'rsatkichlarini oshirish va takomillashtirish bo'yicha keng ko'lamli iqtisodiy, sanoat, tijorat va boshqa masalalar bo'yicha korxonalar rahbarlari va xususiy tadbirkorlarga pullik ekspert maslahatlarini berishdir [8];

konsern (ing concern – ishtirok, manfaat) – manfaatlar, shartnomalar, kapital, hamkorlikdagi faoliyatda ishtirok umumiyligi asosida uyushgan korxonalarining yirik birlashmasi [9].

2. Har xil iqtisodiy dasturlar va tijorat faoliyati turlarining nomlari (tovarlarni sotib olish va sotish, ijara, savdo vositachiligi va boshqalar):

-Autrayt (ing. outright) – oddiy muddatli valyuta bitimi. To'lovlarni tomonlar qat'iy belgilagan muddatlarda "forvard" kursi (narxlar o'zgarishini hisobga olgan holda) bo'yicha to'lashni nazarda tutadi [10].

outsorsing (outsourcing) (out - tashqi, source - manba) ing. outsorsing – bu firma faoliyatiga xizmat ko'rsatish funksiyasining bir qismini boshqa bajaruvchi tashkilotga berish [11].

3. Iqtisodiy faoliyat bilan shug'ullanuvchi shaxslarning ismlari (maqomi, kasbi, mashg'ulot turi):

-autsayder (ingliz outsider – autsayder; birja a'zosi bo'lmagan broker. Birja savdosining ayrim qonunlariga rioya qilish majburiyatini olgan holda savdo zalida ishlashga vaqtincha biron maqsadli ruxsatnoma olishi mumkin [12];

-jobber (inglizcha jobber) – birjada chayqovchi, professional birja brokeri. Jober broker sifatida ishlash huquqiga ega emas;

-konmen (ing. conman - ishonchni uyg'otmaydigan firibgar. Konmen biznesning barcha turlarida uchraydi).

4. menejment sohasidagi yangi kasblarning nomlari: menejer (ing. meneger - menejer), PR menejer (ing. PR meneger – jamoatchilik bilan aloqalar bo'yicha mutaxassis), rieltor (ing. realtor – rieltor – ko'chmas mulk agenti).

Sir emaski, jamiyatgagi ijtimoiy – iqtisodiy rivojlanishlar natijasida til ehtiyojlari qondirishi bilan bir qatorda ko'plab qo'shimcha yangi so'zlar paydo bo'lohasiga oid terminlar mavjud masalan: import (ing. import - import), inflyatsiya (ing. inflation - pulning qadsizlanishi), limit (ing. limit - cheklash), market (ing. market - bozor), eksport (ing. export - eksport).

Tarixiy jihat nuqtai nazaridan, birlamchi va o'zlashtirilgan terminlarni ajratish mumkin. Ko'pgina iqtisodiy terminlar ingliz tiliga lotin va frantsuz tillaridan kelib chiqqan, masalan:

Tarixiy jihat nuqtai nazaridan, birlamchi va o'zlashtirilgan terminlarni ajratish mumkin. Ko'pgina iqtisodiy terminlar ingliz tiliga lotin va frantsuz tillaridan kelib chiqqan, masalan: accrual – lotin tilidadan. "accrescere", "ad"("no") + "crescere" (o'sish); asset – lotin tilidadan etarli, audit – lotin tilidadagi fe'l "audere" "eshitish" ma'nosida; balance – frantsuz tilidan "balance" ("tarozilar"); capital – lotin tilidadagi. "caput" ("bosh"); credit – lotin tilidadagi; "credere" ("ishonch"); deposit – lotin tilidadagi "depositus" (deponere – "ulash, birlashtirish"); devaluation (lotin tilidadagi de – pasaytirish va valeo – xarajat); dividend (lotin tilidadagi dividendus – bo'linadi); emission – lotin tilidadagi "emittere" "ozod qilish" degan ma'noni anglatadi; finance lotin tilidadagi "financia" ("daromad"); passive – lotin tilidadagi "passives" ("passiv, harakatsiz").

Price – narx so'zi qadimgi frantsuz tilidan olingan bo'lib, "prix" -- qiymat, mukammallik, biror narsa yoki hurmat uchun to'langan pul ma'nonisini anglatadi [13].

Qimmatli qog'ozlar savdosida ishlatiladigan Arbitrage – ikki xil, lekin bir-biri bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'lgan bir vaqtning o'zida sotib olish va sotish bir yoki ikki xil bozordagi narxlardagi nomutanosiblikdan foydalanish uchun vositalar. Bu frantsuzcha so'z "hukm qilish" yoki "baholash" degan ma'noni anglatuvchi "arbitrer" fe'lidan kelib chiqqan. Shuni ham ta'kidlash kerakki, frantsuz tili inglizcha so'zlarning yaratilishiga ta'sir ko'rsatdi. Bizda oxiri -iser bilan yakunlanadigan frantsuzcha talaffuzli so'zlar ham bor, masalan, franchiser – franchayzer, merchandiser – savdogar.

“Entrepreneur” soʻziga eʼtibor qaratsak, u fransuzcha “entreprendre” soʻzidan kelib chiqqan va “zimmasiga olmoq” degan maʼnoni anglatadi. Bu soʻzning tarixiga nazar soladigan boʻlsak, u oʻrta asrlarda shakllangan boʻlib, “faol, ishlarni bajaradigan odam” degan maʼnoni anglatadi. Richard Kantillon (bu konsepsiyaga yangi maʼno qoʻshib, qaror qabul qilish va tavakkalchilikni hisobga olgan holda tadbirkorlar, chayqovchilar, treyderlar va dilerlar ekanligini taʼkidladi).

Shu oʻrinda quyidagilarni taʼkidlab oʻtish lozinki, fransuz tilidan oʻzlashgan koʻplab soʻzlar lotin tilidan kelib chiqqan. Lotin tili toʻgʻridan-toʻgʻri ingliz tiliga oʻzlashgan soʻzlar uchun manba boʻlgan, ammo baʼzilari ingliz tiliga fransuz tili orqali oʻzlashgan. Shu sababli baʼzan maʼlum bir termin fransuz yoki lotincha kelib chiqishini aytish qiyin. Relation soʻzi fransuz tilidagi (relation) yoki lotin tilida (relatio) soʻzidan oʻzlashganmi degan savol misol boʻla oladi.

Hatto asosiy soʻzlardan biri management italyanacha maneggiare soʻzidan kelib chiqqan boʻlib, “otliqning otni boshqarish” degan maʼnoni anglatadi.

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РАЗЛИЧИЯ НАЦИОНАЛЬНО-КУЛЬТУРНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ В МЕЖКУЛЬТУРНОЙ КОММУНИКАЦИИ

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada lakunalarning turlari va tasnifi muhokama qilinadi. Milliylik va xalq mentaliteti psixologiyasi: Xalq psixologiyasi va mentalitetining xususiyatlari semantikaga taʼsir qilishi mumkin. Bu baʼzi iboralarni tarjima qilib boʻlmaydigan yoki boshqa tillarga tarjima qilishni qiyinlashtirishi mumkin. Bu shevaning faol soʻzlari boʻlishi bilan bir qatorda adabiy til lugʻatini boyitishda ham katta ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit soʻzlar: madaniyatlararo muloqot, ekstralingvistik omil, ekvivalent, lakuna, realiya, etnografizm.

На сегодняшний день межкультурная коммуникация представляет собой интересное и сложное поле исследований, которое привлекает внимание ученых различных дисциплин. Это объясняется тем, что межкультурная коммуникация затрагивает широкий спектр аспектов, включая языковые,

культурные, социальные, психологические и многие другие аспекты взаимодействия между людьми из разных культур. В настоящее время существует более 300 определений культуры, каждое из которых ориентировано на круг проблем, разрабатываемых определённой отраслью знания [3; 61].

Различия национально-культурных стандартов особенно заметны в межкультурной коммуникации. Оказавшись в незнакомом обществе, человек сталкивается со многими непонятными для себя ситуациями, например, в поведении, ритуалах, обрядах, традициях той или иной нации.

Геоклиматические условия проживания народа: Особенности климата и природной среды могут повлиять на формирование языковых выражений, которые отражают определенные явления или явления, характерные именно для данного региона. Образ жизни народа и особенности его типа хозяйствования: Особенности образа жизни, способов заработка, привычек и культуры народа отражаются в его языке. Национальные традиции и обычаи: Особенности национальных традиций и обычаев также могут отразиться в лексическом составе языка определенного народа. Эти уникальные выражения могут быть сложно или невозможно точно перевести на другой язык.

Психология национальности и менталитет народа: Особенности психологии и менталитета народа могут оказывать влияние на семантику. Это может сделать некоторые выражения непереводаемыми или труднопереводимыми на другие языки.

Итак, эти экстралингвистические факторы формируют уникальную фразеологическую картину мира для каждого языка и способствуют возникновению межъязыковой лакунарности, когда выражения одного языка не имеют точных соответствий в другом языке.

При переводе слов и фраз с одного языка на другой существуют разные способы. Полные (линейные) соответствия, это случаи, когда одной лексической единице в одном языке точно соответствует только одна лексическая единица в другом языке. Это бывает при переводе некоторых технических терминов, наименований собственных и т.д. Когда применяются полные соответствия, перевод осуществляется наиболее точно и нет потерь в содержании. 2. Частичные соответствия когда, лексической единице в одном языке может соответствовать несколько лексических единиц в другом языке. Это типично для общих слов или фраз, которые имеют несколько вариантов перевода в зависимости от контекста. 3. Неполные (приближенные) соответствия, здесь соответствие между лексическими единицами не является точным, и перевод может быть несколько свободнее. В этом случае переводчик может использовать синонимы или переформулировки, чтобы передать смысл оригинала наиболее точно. При переводе важно учитывать не только лексические соответствия, но и семантический контекст, стилистические особенности, культурные нюансы и другие аспекты. Полагаясь только на лексические соответствия, можно упустить многие нюансы и тонкости оригинала.

Частичные. Концепция семантической специфики национальных языковых систем, основана на понятиях прямых и векторных эквивалентов. Прямые эквиваленты (или полные эквиваленты) – это случаи, когда однозначные слова в разных языках имеют сходные денотативные (основные) значения. То есть они обозначают один и тот же объект или понятие, и их основные семы совпадают. Однако они могут иметь различия в периферийных или коннотативных значениях, которые могут быть связаны с культурными, общественными или иными особенностями языка. Векторные эквиваленты (или частичные эквиваленты) – это случаи, когда слова в разных языках имеют сходные значения, но не до конца совпадают. Они могут различаться в основных семах, иметь семантические различия в ядерных значениях. Например, слово "шапка" в русском и немецком языках. В данном случае, это пример прямого эквивалента, так как оба слова обозначают головной убор, имеют схожее денотативное значение (основное значение), но различия могут заключаться в периферийных семах или коннотациях. Немецкое слово может содержать дополнительные семы, описывающие форму головного убора, наличие козырька и так далее, что может быть связано с культурными или стилистическими отличиями между двумя языками. Эти различия в эквивалентности между языками могут быть очень интересными для лингвистических и культурных исследований.

Абсолютные – отсутствие соответствия в одном из языков по отношению к другому сопоставляемому языку [1; 12]. Термин "безэквивалентная лексика" относится к явлениям,

когда в переводе с одного языка на другой отсутствует точное соответствие между словами или выражениями. Это означает, что некоторые концепции, понятия или культурные аспекты, выраженные на одном языке, могут быть трудно или даже невозможно переданы на другой язык без потери смысла или нюансов. В таких случаях переводчики или исследователи сталкиваются с необходимостью использовать адаптации, обходные пути или описательные обороты, чтобы передать тот контекст или смысл, который может быть утерян при прямом переводе. Исследователи могут подходить к этому явлению в широком понимании, включая в него не только отсутствие точных эквивалентов для слов или выражений, но также и более обширные культурные, исторические или социальные реалии, которые могут быть уникальны для одного языка и не иметь точных аналогов в другом языке. Это может возникнуть из-за различий в культурных ценностях, обычаях, традициях или просто из-за того, что некоторые понятия просто не существуют в одном из языков. Исследование безэквивалентной лексики и лакун может быть полезным для понимания различий между языками, а также для разработки более эффективных стратегий перевода и коммуникации между разными культурами [4; 61]. Но мы считаем такие слова реалиями. На примере узбекского языка можно привести следующие слова-реалии: тиллакош (конусообразный головной убор, украшенный драгоценными камнями), мўркон (труба в печи, откуда выходит дым), дам солиш (религиозный обряд очищения от нечистых сил), буғирсок (жаренные в кипящем масле в казане круглые кусочки теста) и др., данные слова являются реалиями, так как в сопоставляемом языке нет такого предмета и, следовательно, нет такой лексемы.

Исследователь Е.А. Эйнуллаева группирует в соответствии с многоуровневой структурой языковой лексики. Описание теории лакун в лингвистике. Лакуны – это пропуски или пробелы в языковой системе или тексте, которые могут быть вызваны различными факторами, такими как эволюция языка, культурные изменения или недостаточное знание языка говорящими. Группа лакун, включает в себя вербальные лакуны. Вербальные лакуны включают два основных типа: языковые и речевые. 1. Языковые лакуны: Это пропуски в языковой системе, когда отсутствует определенное слово, грамматическая форма или структура. Например, некоторые языки могут не иметь определенных времен глаголов или форм множественного числа. 2. Речевые лакуны: Это пропуски в конкретных текстах или высказываниях, которые возникают, когда в переводе или интерпретации текста на другой язык происходят изменения или опущения. Эти лакуны могут быть вызваны сложностями в переводе, различиями между языками или структурой текста. Речевые лакуны, в свою очередь, классифицируются на различные типы: - Фонетические лакуны - отсутствие перевода или трудности в переводе звуков или фонем из одного языка на другой. Фразеологические лакуны – пропуски в фразах, идиомах или культурно обусловленных выражениях. Грамматические лакуны -- неперебиваемые грамматические структуры или трудности в передаче грамматических конструкций. Стилистические лакуны -- пропуски, связанные с передачей стилистических особенностей, эмоций или нюансов между языками. Ее описание представляет систематизацию этих лакун в контексте лингвистического анализа. Эта концепция помогает исследователям понимать, как языки взаимодействуют и какие проблемы могут возникнуть при переводе или анализе текстов между разными языками.

Национально-культурная специфика играет важную роль в перцептивных лакунах и восприятии окружающего мира. В разных культурах люди могут воспринимать и интерпретировать одни и те же явления совершенно по-разному.

а) Время, пространство, количество: разные культуры имеют разные способы измерения времени и пространства. Например, в некоторых культурах уделяется большое внимание точности и пунктуальности, в то время как в других уделяется большее внимание гибкости и относительности времени. То же самое касается и измерения пространства. Количество может быть воспринято и интерпретировано по-разному в разных культурах – например, некоторые культуры могут ценить более крупные или более мелкие количества.

б) Восприятие человека: разные культуры могут иметь разные представления о том, что делает человека "хорошим" или "плохим". Это также может влиять на восприятие эмоций, статуса и внешности людей. Например, в одной культуре сдержанное выражение эмоций может быть

считано высокой степенью самообладания, тогда как в другой культуре это может быть воспринято как недостаток искренности.

в) Восприятие явлений природы, животного и растительного мира: религиозные и мифологические представления могут сильно влиять на восприятие природных явлений, животных и растений. Например, в одной культуре солнце может символизировать бога или божественную силу, в то время как в другой культуре оно может быть связано с другими аспектами мифологии или культурных убеждений. Итак, перцептивные лакуны действительно играют ключевую роль в формировании восприятия и интерпретации окружающего мира в контексте национально-культурной специфики. Это понимание имеет большое значение при изучении и анализе межкультурных взаимодействий, коммуникации и взаимопонимания.

В качестве примера мы можем привести понятие сутки. В узбекском языке отсутствует подобная единица. Также возникают лакунарные единицы при сопоставлении узбекского и русского языков в представлениях о времени дня. В узбекском языке обозначается время восхода солнца: бомдод, сахар – раннее утро, начало восхода; пешин, туш – середина дня, солнце достигло своего пика; аср – время ближе к закату дня; шом – время, когда солнце садится и начинает сгущаться тьма; хуфтон – время через два часа после захода солнца. Строению тела человека. Например, слова заусеница – задрвшаяся кожица у основания ногтя; кутикула – ногтевая кожица у человека, эпителиальная пленка на краю ногтевого валика,

окружающая ногтевую пластинку в нижней части ногтя, в районе ногтевой луночки, выполняет защитную роль, не давая инородным телам и бактериям проникнуть в ростковую зону. Край кутикулы представляет собой мёртвые клетки, высыхая, а затем отслаиваясь, этот край приводит к заусенице.

В заключении можно сказать, что лакунарные единицы узбекского и русского языков, отражающие национально-культурные признаки, определяемые ценностями, социально-культурными отношениями носителей языка требуют от переводчиков определённых навыков и переводческого мастерства.

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TURK TILIDA ZOOKOMPONENTLI IBORALAR VA ULARNING O'ZBEKCHA TARJIMALARI

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Аннотация. *Данная статья посвящена изучению вопроса применения зоонимов и зоокомпонентных фразеологизмов для образного изображения человека в турецком языке. Автор на примере анализа зоокомпонентных фразеологизмов турецкого и узбекского языка выявляет общие и отличительные аспекты таких единиц и даёт ценные рекомендации по их переводу.*

Ключевые слова: *язык, образ человека, характер, эвфемизм, зооним, образ, портрет, облик, аналогия, альтернатива, эквивалент.*

Olamda hamma narsa bir-biriga bog'liq yaratilganidek, insoniyat ham tabiat bilan uyg'unlikda yashaydi. Kishining xatti-harakatlari, xarakteri va tashqi ko'rinishini hayvon yoki o'simlik nomlari bilan atash yoki ularga o'xshatish buning yaqqol isbotidir. Tarixdan hozirgi kunga qadar yomon xulqli odamlar yovvoyi yirtqich hayvonlarga, ijobiy fazilatli insonlar uy hayvonlariga, sezgir, chaqqon odamlar esa ba'zi qushlarga o'xshatilishi an'ana tusiga kirgan.

Turk va o'zbek tillarida insonning turli belgi-xususiyatlarini, ya'ni uning axloqiy, intellektual, ijtimoiy belgilarini, fe'l-atvorini bildiruvchi so'zlar har xil hayvon va o'simlik nomlari (zoonim va fitonimlar) vositasida beriladi.

Hayvonot olami nomlaridan iborat zoonimlar ko'pgina tillarning leksik tarkibidagi eng qadimgi semantik guruhlardan birini tashkil etadi. Majoziy ma'no taraqqiyoti o'laroq zooleksemalar insonning fazilatlarini va harakatlarini tavsiflash uchun faol ishlatiladi. G'.Ismoilov har qanday tilning zookomponentli iboralar fondi tilning madaniyati va qadriyatlarini bilan chambarchas bog'likligini ta'kidlaydi [2].

Inson va hayvonot olami munosabati tilga ham o'z ta'sirini ko'rsatgan bo'lib, tilning leksik fondidagi zoonim komponentli iboralar guruhini shakllantirgan. Zoonim komponentli iboralar antroposentrik xususiyat bilan xarakterlanadi. Zoofrazeologizmlar tarkibida it, mushuk, qo'y, ot, ho'kiz, sigir, echki, tuya, tovuq kabi uy hayvonlari; tulki, quyon, yo'lbars, ayiq, bo'ri, sher, to'ng'iz singari yovvoyi hayvonlar; ilon, toshbaqa kabi sudralib yuruvchilar; sichqon, olmaxon singari kemiruvchilar; qushlar; suvda yashovchilar; hamda hasharot nomlarini bildiruvchi zoonimlar ishtirok etadi. Zookomponentli frazeologik birliklar ma'nosi bilan tarkibidagi so'zlarining ma'nolari orasidagi munosabatga ko'ra bunday birliklar frazeologik chatishmalar va frazeologik butunliklarga ajratiladi. Frazeologik chatishmalarining umumiy ma'nosi ularni tashkil etuvchi komponentlar ma'nosiga mos kelmaydi. Frazeologik butunlikning ma'nosi esa tarkibidagi so'zlarining ma'nosi asosida izohlanadi.

Qo'ydek yuvosh, qo'y og'zidan cho'p olmagan kabi birikmalar o'ta yuvosh, biror zarar keltirmaydigan insonlarni tasvirlashda ishlatiladi. Ba'zan qo'y so'zi yolg'iz ishlatilganda qo'pol ma'noda yuvosh, lapashang so'zlariga sinonim sifatida qo'llanadi. Qo'yko'z qo'shma so'zi o'zbeklarda ko'zning qo'ng'ir tusini ifodalashga xizmat qiladi.

O'zbek va turk tillari frazeologik birliklari qiyosiy tahlili bu tillarda zookomponentli frazeologik birliklardagi o'xshatish obyektlarining o'zaro uyg'unligini ko'rsatdi. Bu esa tillarda qiyosiy umumiylikning mavjudligidan dalolat beradi. Umumiylikka qaramay, bunday birliklar tarjimasini tarjimonlarda muayyan qiyinchiliklarni tug'diradi. J. Shabanov va X. Hamidovlar uy hayvonlari nomi qatnashgan maqol va iboralarning tarjimadagi o'ziga xosliklari haqida o'z mulohazalarini bildirgan [3].

Turk va o'zbek tillari frazeologik birliklariga nazar tashlar ekanmiz, ularning aksariyatida muqoyasa obyektlarining o'xshashligiga guvoh bo'lamiz: Biz konusurken, shube muduru keyifli keyifli guluyor: - Bulbul gibi soyluyor Fransızcaı maşallah. Bir Türk kızi için sayanı takdir doğrusu, diyordu (Reşat Nuri Güntekin. Çalıkuşu). Tarjiması: Biz so'zlashib turganimizda bo'lim muduri nash'a qilib kulardi. - Fransuzchani bulbulday sayraydi-ya, yo olloh! Turk qizi uchun maqtovga sazovor bir fazilat, - deyardi" (Pashod Нури Гунтекин. Чоликуши. Туркчадан М. Исмоилий таржимаси). Yoki: Deminden beri yukarıda talebelerimin vazifelerini

tashih ediyordum. Kapı çalındı, Munise aşağıdan: - Abacığım, misafir geldi, diye seslendi. Taşlıkta siyah çarşafli bir hanım geziniyor; yüzü kapalı olduğu için tanımadım, tereddütle: - Kimsiniz efendim? diye sordum. Birdenbire ince bir kahkaha ko-ptu; hanım, kedi gibi boynuma sıçradı. Meğerse Munise imiş (Reşat Nuri Güntekin. Çalıkuşu). Tarjiması: Uyda o'tirib o'quvchilarimning daftarlarini ko'rayotgan edim. Eshik taqilladi. Munisa pastdan: -Opajon, mehmon keldi, - deb qichqirdi. Tashqarida qora chorshafli bir xotin aylanib yurardi. Yuzi yopiq bo'lgani uchun taniyolmadim. Taraddudlanib: - Kimsiz, afandim? - deb so'radim. Birdan kulgi ko'tarildi. Xonim mushuk singari bo'ynimga tashlandi. Tavba, Munisa ekan! Yaramas qiz meni belimdan ushlab hovlida aylantira boshladi. Hech qo'ymay yuzimni, bo'ynimni o'pa ketdi. Chorshaf kichkinamni bo'yiga yetgan qizga o'xshatib qo'yibdi (Pашод Нури Гунтекин. Чоликуши. Туркчадан М. Исмоилий таржимаси). Frazologik birliklarni tarjima qilishda ular asosida mujassamlashgan obrazning barhayot yoki siyqaligini oydinlashtirishning ham tarjima tilida asl nusxadagi lisoniy birliklarga mazmun va uslub jihatlaridan mos til vositalarini tanlashda ahamiyati katta [1; 184].

Muayyan uslubiy maqsadga erishish niyatida yozuvchilar goho zookomponentli frazeologik birliklarni biroz o'zgartirgan yoki ularni to'ldirgan holda qo'llaydilar. Masalan, turli lingvomadaniyatlarda itday, it kabi o'xshatish etalonidan "qopmoq, talamoq", "sadoqatli, vafodor", "akillamoq, irillamoq", "yugurmoq", "izg'imoq, sanqimoq", "ergashmoq", "ishlamoq, mehnat qilmoq", "otmoq, xor qilmoq", "charchamoq", "quturmoq", "yashamoq", "ichmoq" kabi ma'nolarni ifodalash uchun foydalaniladi. Turk va o'zbek tillarida ham aynan shu ma'nolarda ishlatiladi. Quyidagi parchada mazkur o'xshatish qo'tir so'zi bilan birga qo'llanilib, undan "pisib qolmoq" ma'nosini ifodalash uchun foydalanilgan: "Sazlar, şarkılar başladı. Biz de kafaları çekiyoruz. Garsonlar etrafımızda pervane olmuşlar. Derken arkada bir gürlütü ko-ptu. Sarhoşlar birbirlerine girdiler. Onlar bıçakları fora ederken bizim Musa da düdüğe asıldı. O aslan kesilmiş kavgacılar, düdüğün bir fırt etmesiyle uyuz it gibi kuyruklarını kısıp oturdular" (Aziz Nesin. Bay duduk). Aziz Nesinning "Bay duduk" hajviy hikoyasi 1969-yilda Miad Hakimov tomonidan "Hushtak afandim" nomi bilan o'zbek tiliga tarjima qilingan bo'lib, unda ekvivalent komparativ birliklar yordamiga murojaat qilinmagan va "uyuz it gibi" frazeologik birligi tushirib qoldirilgan. Bu bilan asliyatga teng qimmatli ta'sirchanlik yuzaga chiqmay qolgan: "Bir payt o'yin-kulgi boshlanib ketdi. Rohat qilib o'tiribmiz. Ofitsantlar atrofimizda parvona. To'satdan orqa tomonda shovqin ko'tarildi. Mast-alast odamlar yoqa bo'g'ishib ketishdi. Ish pichoqqa borib taqalay deganida, Musa hushtak chalib yubordi. Hozirgina bir-biri bilan sherday olishishib turgan azamatlar churillagan ovozni eshitib, dumlarini qisib qolishdi" [Miad Hakimov tarjiması. Hushtak afandim]. Mazkur hikoyaning "Janob 'hushtak'" nomi bilan 2014-yilda Xayrulla Hamidov tomonidan amalga oshirilgan tarjimasida Miad Hakimov tarjimasida tashlab ketilgan iboralar, voqealar tasviri, personajlar xususiyatlari asliyatga monand tarzda bekami-ko'st qayta yaratilgan. Asliyatdagi milliy ruh o'zbek o'quvchilariga to'laqonli yetkazib berilgan: "Kazinoda sozlar chalindi, qo'shiq avjida. Biz esa otamlashish bilan ovoramiz. Shinavanda xizmatchilar atrofimizda girdikapalak. Shu payt orqa tomonimizda shovqin ko'tarildi. Shirakayf mijozlardan bir nechta janjal boshlashibdi. Bir-ikkita pichoq chiqarib, havoda o'ynata boshlaganda, bizning Musa hushtagini qo'lga oldi. "Sheryurak" pahlavonlar hushtak ovozini eshitishlari bilan qo'tir it kabi dumlarini qisishib, bir lahzada "in-inlariga" kirib ketishdi (X.Hamidov tarjiması. Janob "hushtak").

Goho ma'no va uslubiy vazifa jihatlaridan mos muqobil variantlarning tayanch komponentlarigina bir-birlarinikiga o'xshash bo'lib, boshqa so'zlari farq qiladi. Bunday o'zaro muqobil frazeologik birliklar odatda bir xil voqea-hodisa, harakat-holat, xislat-xususiyatning obrazli yoki his-hayajonli ifodasi uchun yaratilgan bo'lib, bir-birlariga to'la mos keladilar [1; 196]. Jumladan, turkcha it takımı frazeologik birligining ham, o'zbekcha it yotish mirza turish muqobil variantining ham tayanch komponentlari it bo'lib, ikkala lisoniy birlik ham "yashash uchun hech qanday qulayliklar yo'q" ma'nosini obrazli ifodalashga xizmat qilgan: Benim Kazlıçeşme'deki odama getirdim oğlanı. O dört kişi ile yatarmış. Hep it takımı! Rahat etsin oğlan, dedim. Sabaha dek inin inim inledi (Sait Faik. Mürüvvet). Tarjiması: Husayn ijarada haligi to'rt kishi bilan turar, yashashlari "it yotish mirza turish" ekan. Bolani G'ozlichashmadagi uyimga olib keldim. Bir odamday yashasin shu bola, dedim. Tuni bilan og'riqdan qiynalib, ingrab chiqdi, bola bechora (Hamidova tarjiması. Muruvvat).

It zoonimi o'zbek tilida sodiq kishi qiyofasini tasvirlashda qo'l keladi. "It vafo-xotin jafu" maqoli buning yaqqol misolidir. Kishiga o'z umr yo'ldoshidan ko'ra itidan ko'proq vafo keladi.

It-qadr-qiyamati yo'q, tarbiyasiz odam. O'zbek tilida ham turk tilida ham ko'p qo'llaniluvchi zoonimlar qatorida "itday", "it kabi" o'xshatishlari laganbardor yoki sodiq xizmatkor kishini ifodalash uchun ishlatiladi,

turk tilida "yüzünü köpek yalamış", "köpek gibi" kabi iboralar va o'xshatishl orqali surbet, yuzsiz, orsiz kishilar obrazi gavalantiriladi.

It – laganbardorlar qiyos etiluvchi hayvondir. Chunki egasiga xushomad qilib, ko'nglini ovlashga harakat qiladi. Laganbardorlar vaziyatga qarab, foyda olish maqsadida odamlarga xushomad qiladilar. Rus tilida kuchuk so'zi "och" tushunchasini ifodalash uchun qo'llanadi: голодный, как собака.

Inson xarakterini ifodalovchi so'zlar ham har bir til millatining dunyoqarashi, mentalitetidan kelib chiqib qo'llanadi. Qadimdan tili, dini va qalbi bir bo'lgan, tarixiy imtihonlarda birgalikda kurashgan o'zbek va turk xalqlari kuchli tarixiy aloqalar, umumiy ma'naviy qadriyatlar va urf-odatlariga ega.

Ot, tuya, qo'y, mushuk, it, sigir kabi hayvonlarning xonakilashtirilishi turkiy xalqlar leksikasida ijobiy ma'no belgilarini o'zida aks ettiruvchi frazeologik birliklarning ifoda va mazmun jihatidan boyishida yanada muhim bir omil bo'ldi.

"Eshak gibi" ifodasi turk tilida aqlsiz, qo'pol, o'ylamay ish qiladigan kabi ma'nolarda keladi. Tuyg'usiz, hissiz odamga nisbatan esa "eshak derisi gibi" birikmasi qo'llaniladi. O'zbek tilida esa bu birikmalar juda mehnat qilib yuzaga chiqmagan odam yoki o'ta qaysar ma'nolarida keladi. Shu bilan birga, ko'zlari katta-katta insonga nisbatan "eshak gozlu" ifodasi ishlatiladi.

Turk tilida shunday iboralar borki, ular insonga xos xarakterlarni badiiy va ta'sirchan ifodalash imkonini beradi. Masalan "murekkep yalamış" (siyoh yalagan) iborasi ilm-fanga berilgan, umrini ilm olishga sarflaydigan kishilarni bildirsa, "yüzünü köpek yalamış" iborasi esa uyatsiz, orsiz kishi ma'nosini ifodalab keladi.

Yana shuni ta'kidlash joizki, turk tilida ham o'zbek tilida ham zoonimlar ishtirok etgan iboralar ko'p va ularning aksariyati har ikki tilda ham o'xshash ma'nolarda keladi.

deve yapmak – tuya qilmoq, birovning pulini, molini o'zlashtirmoq;

deveyi havutuyla yutmak – tuyani yutib, dumini ko'rsatmoq, har qanday katta (ko'p) narsani ham o'zlashtirib, undan nishon, iz qoldirmaslik;

sağmal inek – sog'in sigir; ma'lum miqdordagi mablag' bilan muntazam ta'minlab turadigan manba;

arının yuvasına (inine) çomak sokmak – arining iniga cho'p suqmoq; xavfli odamni gij-gijlab o'ziga hujum qilishiga yo'l qo'ymoq;

sıçan deliği bin altın – sichqonning ini ming tanga bo'ldi; qochib qutulgan joy topolmay qolmoq;

öküzün altında buzağı aramak – tirnoq ostidan kir izlamoq; yomon niyat bilan ayb, xato-kamchilik topishga harakat qilmoq;

eşeğe gücü yetmeyip semerini dövmek – yomonning kuchi yapaloqqa yetmoq; kuchli odamlarga biron narsa qila olmay, alaminu kuchsizlardan olmoq;

köpeksiz köyde çomaksız gezmek – o'zi xon, ko'lankasi maydon; kim nimani xohlasa, shuni qilmoq.

Turli hududlarda uchraydigan jonivorlar ham goho bir-birlaridan tafovut qiladilar: ular o'zlariga xos xususiyatlari, xatti-harakatlari bilan turli xalqlar nazarida turlicha tushunchalar timsollari sifatida namoyon bo'lib, xilma-xil muqoyasaviy iboralarning obrazli asoslari tarzida namoyon bo'ladilar. Bu, o'z navbatida, turli xalqlarning ma'no va uslubiy vazifa jihatlaridan o'zaro mos zookomponentli frazeologik birliklari obrazli asoslarining bir-birlaridan farq qilishlariga olib keladi.

Shunday qilib, olamning lisoniy manzarasini o'rganish masalasi inson va uning turmushi, uning dunyo bilan o'zaro munosabati, uning mavjudligining sharoitlarini aks ettiradigan olamning konseptual manzarasi masalasi bilan chambarchas bog'liqdir. Olamning lisoniy manzarasi insonning turli olam manzaralarini izohlaydi va umumiy olam manzarasini aks ettiradi. Olamning lisoniy manzarasini aks ettirishda esa zoonimlar va zoofrazeologik birliklar keng ahamiyat kasb etadi. Zero, inson obrazi, uning hayoti tabiat bilan chambarchas bog'liqdir.

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INGLIZ SHE'RIYATI TARJIMASINING O'ZIGA XOS JIHATLARI

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Annotation: *The article discusses the specific aspects of English poetry and their reflection in translation.*

Key words: *nonsense poem, literary translation, dictionary, translator, originality.*

"Tilning barcha nozik xususiyatlari, fonetikasi, musiqaviy imkoniyatlari, ritmi, tovush va asrlar mobaynida shakllangan lug'at xazinasini, talaffuz qonuniyatlari – bularning hammasi she'rda bor bo'yi bilan namoyon bo'ladi" [1; 32]. Ana shu tilga xos shirani, shoir orqali xalq madaniyatining bir bo'lagini butunligicha o'zga tilga o'girish mumkinmi? Albatta, prozadagi singari poeziyada asliyatga juda yaqin kelish va so'zma-so'z tarjima qilish mumkin bo'lmagan holat. Buni inkor etmagan holda, tarjimaning tub mohiyatini ham unutmamak kerak. Badiiy tarjima asliyatdan matnni o'girishdan iborat texnik jarayon emas, bu ijodiy jarayon.

Jahon adabiyotida o'z o'rniga ega ingliz she'riyati ham shu paytga qadar zahmatkash mutarjimlarimiz tomonidan bevosita yoki bilvosita tarjima orqali o'zbek kitobxoniga havola etilayotir. Ularning asosiy qismi alohida she'riy asar, biroq ingliz adabiyotida asarlar ichida keladigan she'rlar ham borki, ularni ona tilimizga o'girish o'ziga xos yondashuvni talab qiladi. Bu o'ziga xoslikni she'rlarning nasr ichida kelishi bilangina izohlash birmuncha yuzaki bo'ladi, ulardagi vazn, qofiya hamda she'rlar yozilgan yo'nalish ham tarjimada muhim ahamiyatga ega. Taniqli angliyalik yozuvchisi Lyuis Kerrollning "Alisa Mo'jizalar mamlakatida" va "Alisa Ko'zguorti o'lkasida" ertaklari ana shunday asarlar sirasiga kiradi. Zero, "Kerrol prozasi uning she'rlari bilan chambarchas bog'langan" [2; 328].

Kerroll yashagan Angliyada she'riyatning sentimentalizm, klassisizm oqimlari ommalashgan, romantizm esa o'zining yangi qirralarini namoyon qilib tilga tushayotgan davrda adib she'rlarida ularga murojaat qilmaydi. Uning she'riyatidagi ilk o'ziga xoslik ham mana shunda. Kerroll she'rlarini o'qib his-hayajonga berilmaysiz, ta'sirlanmaysiz, hattoki, pand-nasihati ham olmaysiz, ammo kulishingiz, kulganda ham achchiq kulishingiz turgan gap. Adib hayoti va ijodini tadqiq qilgan olim Demurova Kerroll ertaklaridagi she'rlarini tarjima qilishni "o'ziga xos topshiriq" deya baholab, "ular ba'zan ochiqchasiga, ba'zan to'g'ridan-to'g'ri iqtibos shaklida, parodiya yoki pardaga o'rab keltiriladi, allyuziyalar, mug'obirona hazillar, sezilar-sezilmas qaytariq va chaqiruvlar shaklida ham berilishini" qayd etadi. Adibning ikkala ertaklariga kirgan she'rlarining aksariyati parodiya yo'lida yozilgan. Parodiyani tarjima qilish doim mushkul ish bo'lib qaralgan nazariyotchilar tomonidan, negaki har qanday parodiya bir tilda ma'lumu mashhur matnga asoslanadi, tarjima tilida bu matn ko'pchilikka notanish bo'lishi mumkin. Taniqli adabiyotshunos, yozuvchi Uorren Uiver o'zining "Alisa Mo'jizalar mamlakatida" tarjimalari haqidagi kitobida Kerrollning bu ertagida she'rlarning katta qismi parodiya ekaniga e'tibor qaratadi. Bu parodiyalarning asliyatlarini, deya izohlaydi olim, Kerrolldan avval yoki u bilan bir davrda yashab o'tgan mualliflarga tegishli. She'rlar asliyatlarini o'rganilganda ular orasida Sauti yoki Jeyn Teylor kabi mashhurlar ham borki, bular "Alisa"ning tengdoshlariga boshqacha aytganda, ingliz bolalariga va kattalarga ham birday tanish edi. Uiver o'z tadqiqotida parodiyalarni o'girish metodlarni ham keltirib o'tadi. "Ingliz tilida hammaga ma'lum matnni parodiya qiluvchi she'rni boshqa tilga o'girishning uchta yo'li bor" [3,80] deydi u o'z tadqiqotida. Ular ichida birinchisi – tarjima tilida mashhur shunga yaqin yo'sindagi she'rni tanlab, ingliz tilida yozilmagan shu she'rga ingliz muallifiga o'xshatib parodiya qilish. Rus tarjimonlaridan P.Solov'eva, T.Shepkina-Kupernik ayni shu yo'ldan borishgan.

Ikkinchi yo'l esa parodiyalarni to'g'ridan-to'g'ri o'girish. Uiver bu usulni ertakdagi she'r mashhur asliyatga parodiya ekanidan bexabar, bu she'rni shunchaki kulguli va bir oz g'alati deb bilgan va so'zma-so'z o'giradigan tarjimon tanlasa kerak, deb hisoblaydi. Ma'lumki, Kerrollning ikkala ertagi ham ona tilimizga uch tarjimon – M.Otaboeva (2015, 2020 yillar), M.Zohidova (nisbatan qisqartirilgan shakli, 2016 yili), Sh.Dolimov ("Alisa Mo'jizalar yurtida", 2021) tomonidan o'girilgan. Mazkur uchchala tarjima ichida M.Zohidovanning varianti ertakning ancha qisqartirilgan shakli bo'lgani bois unda she'rlar tushirib qoldirilgan. Qolgan ikki tarjimada she'rlar yuqorida Uiver taklif qilgan ikkinchi usul orqali o'girilgan.

Uchinchi yo'lni tanlagan tarjimon shunday deydi: "Bu nonsens she'r. Men nonsensni o'z tilimga o'girolmayman, ammo o'z tilimda boshqa nonsens-she'r yozib, asliyatning o'rniga matnga qo'sha olaman".

S.Ya. Marshak 1967 yiliyoq ertaklardagi she'rlarni ayni yo'sinda o'g'irgan. Ta'kidlash joizki, Marshakning bu she'rlari allaqachonoq rus kitobxonlari uchun o'zlashib ketgan.

Kerroll she'rlarida milliy folklorlardan nafaqat obrazlar olishda foydalangan, balki talay she'rlarning ritmi, vazni ham aynan folklor uslubini eslatadi. Masalan, Adi-Badi tilidan aytilgan mazkur she'rdan bir parcha keltirsak:

*I sent a message to the fish:
I told them, «This is what I wish.»
The little fishes of the sea,
They sent an answer back to me.
The little fishes' answer was
«We cannot do it, Sir, because – »'
I sent to them again to say
«It will be better to obey.»
The fishes answered with a grin,
«Why, what a temper you are in!»
I told them once, I told them twice:
They would not listen to advice.
I took a kettle large and new,
Fit for the deed I had to do.
My heart went hop, my heart went thump;
I filled the kettle at the pump.*

Bu parchadan ma'lumki, she'rda ortiqcha mubolag'a, bezaklarsiz voqea bayoni sodda tarzda berilgan va u quyidagicha o'girildi:

*Men xat yozdim baliqqa,
Bitdim istagim haqda.
Dengizdagi baliqlar
Menga javob yozdilar.
Shunday edi bu javob:
"Bajarolmaymiz, janob...".
Xat yozdim yana bir bor,
Dedim: "Bo'sunmoq darkor".
Mayna qildi baliqlar:
"Qahr neni hal qilar?"
Yozdim tag'in, ikki bor,
Maslahat qilmadi kor.
Toqat bo'ldi asti toq,
Oldim chovgum, qo'lga boq.
Yurak o'ynardi shu dam,
Chovgumga to'ldirdim dam. [4; 66]*

Asliyatdagi so'nggi ikki qator qolganlaridan uzun esa-da, o'zbekchalashtirayotib ma'nodan qochmagan holda ritmni bir xil bo'lishini ta'minlangan. Ingliz tilida "thump" "pump" so'zlari bilan qofiya keltirilgan, birinchi so'z yurakning gursullab beqaror urishini anglatsa, ikkinchisi, dam, puflab nafas berib to'ldirishni anglatadi. O'zbek tilidagi "dam" omonim so'zi bilan qofiyalar saqlanib, ritmga ham putur yetmagan.

She'riy tarjimalargagina xos yana bir hodisa borki, uni qo'llash orqali tarjimon ayrim leksik va grammatik o'zgarish, to'g'rirog'i tushirib qoldirishlar qilishi mumkin. Bu metod transformasiya deb nomlanib, Sh.Dolimov tarjimasidagi "Alisa Mo'jizalar yurtida" ertagining 12 bobidagi quyidagi she'r tarjimasida buni ko'rish mumkin:

*Chillaklaru qarq'alardan kelmadi yordam,
Men bilan bo'lmassan nechundir, hardam.
Dam u bilansan sen, qiziq, dam bu bilan.
Tuturig'ing bormi o'zi? Shu haqda o'ylan.
Ko'z yoshi ko'luga sho'ng'ib chuqurroq
Ketaman suzib, sendan uzoqroq
Baqirib-chaqirib aytan gapimni*

*So'ng o'ynab-kulay sensiz tuzukroq.
Ho'ngrab sen ortimdan tentakday go'yo
Qolaver qalbing qotib, bo'lib mo'miyo. [5; 91]*

Avvalo, mutarjim ertakni bilvosita rus tilidan (A.Dantonov tarjimasini) o'girganini e'tiborga olish lozim. Solishtirish uchun Dantonov tarjimasini ko'ramiz:

*Не могла мне тrefы, ни пики.
Завтра ты с тем, а сегодня ты с этим.
Как мне сказать, не совравшись до крика
Зная, что слишком уж я неприметен?
Ну, а потом? Где возможность для бегства?
На берегу я назначу тебе randevу.
Озеро слёз – подходящее место.
Выскажу всё, да и прочь уплыву.
Лягу на дно, как подводная лодка,
Там ты уж точно не станешь искать.
Будешь рыдать и страдать, сумасбродка!
Только б придумать мне, как там дышать...*

Dolimov tarjimasida ikki misrani "qurbon" bergan. Ingliz she'riyatida transformatsiyani qo'llashning ikki xil usuli mavjud. Birinchisida, "Mexanik tarzda tushirib yuborish", bu holatda asliyatdagi unurni tarjimada berishning iloji bo'lmasa, bunga vazn va o'lchov yo'l qo'ymaydi. Ikkinchi usul, Dolimov qo'llagani "ijodiy tushirib qodirish" deb ataladi. Bunda she'rning umumiy ma'no kontekstiga zarar yetmagani, ritmi buzilmagani esa mutarjimning yutug'i deyish mumkin.

Poeziyadagi alliteratsiya hodisasidan Kerroll asarlaridagi she'rlarda unumli foydalanilgan. Alliteratsiya ohangdorlikni ta'minlab, his-hayajonni kuchaytirishga xizmat qiladi. U o'quvchi diqqatini oshirib, misralarni oson yodda saqlashga yordam ham beradi.

*I took a corkscrew from the shelf:
I went to wake them up myself.
And when I found the door was locked,
I pulled and pushed and kicked and knocked.
And when I found the door was shut,
I tried to turn the handle, but – ' [6; 63]*

Adibning "Alisa Ko'zgu orti o'lkasida" ertagidagi Adi-Badi tilidan aytilgan bu she'riy parchadagi to'rtinchi qatorda pulled, pushed, kicked, knocked va tried to turn so'zlari bilan alliteratsiya hosil qiladi. Tarjima jarayonida doim ham alliteratsiyani saqlab o'girib bo'lmaydi, shuning uchun alliteratsiyani sun'iy hosil qilish asliyatga putur yetkazishini unutmazlik lozim:

*Qalamtaroshni olib,
Uyg'otishga bordim men.
Eshik berkligin ko'rib,
Tepdim darg'azab bo'lib.
Qulflangan ekan u,
Tutqichidan tortdimu...*

Tarjimada aynan asliyatdagi so'zlardan alliteratsiya hosil qilinmasa-da, boshqa mavjud so'zlar bunga imkon berishi mumkin. Keltirilgan muqobil tarjimada ham shunday yo'l tutilgan, ya'ni "Tutqichidan tortdimu..." bu so'zlar asliyatda alliteratsiya qilinmagan biroq o'zbekchalashtirayotib bunday yondashuv she'rning jozibali chiqishiga xizmat qiladi.

Xulosa o'rnida, ingliz tilidan Shekspir sonetlarini rus tiliga mohirona o'girgan olim A.M. Kapulenkoning quyidagi poeziya tarjimasining eng muhim vazifasi asliyatdagi ohangni tarjimada qayta yaratish ekanini [7; 22] ta'kidlashni istardik.

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MILLIY XOSLANGAN BIRLIKLAR TARJIMASI MUAMMOSI

(turk kinofilmlari misolida)

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Аннотация. В данной статье на примере турецких кинофильмов проанализированы сложности перевода национально-обусловленных единиц, демонстрирующих уникальность и своеобразие каждого языка. На основе анализа перевода фильмов "Рассказ Мелек", "Птицы без крыльев", "Муслим баба" указаны достижения и недостатки переводчиков.

Ключевые слова: кинофильм, национально-обусловленная единица, лакуна, реалия, творческий перевод.

Tarjima xalqlar o'rtasidagi do'stlik, qardoshlik va hamkorlik manfaatlariga, ular o'rtasidagi iqtisodiy-siyosiy, ilmiy-madaniy va adabiy aloqalarning kengayishiga xizmat qiluvchi qudratli quroldir. Tarjima bilan shug'ullanuvchi shaxs, ya'ni tarjimon ikki til, ikki millat o'rtasidagi ko'prikdir, uning tarjima qilish qobiliyati orqali xalqning, millatning eng nozik qirralari aks ettiriladi [1; 9]. Mana shunday zalvorli ko'prik qurish vazifasi bu kinofilmlar tarjimasidir.

Kinomatografiyada voqealar rivoji nafaqat rang-barang tasvir orqali, balki yuksak proza, o'tkir drama, jozibali poeziya, yorqin tasviriy san'at, musiqiy ravonlik bilan ifodalanadi. Tarjimon filmni qanday ko'z bilan ko'rsa, tushunsa, tomoshabin ham shunday ko'z bilan qabul qiladi va xulosa chiqaradi. Personajning ruhiy vaziyatiga nomuqobil keladigan har qanday, hatto eng mayda soxtakorlik, har qanday uslubiy yoki ma'noviy xato badiiy haqiqatni jiddiy buzishi, yuzaga keltirgan butun haqqoniy taassurotni chippakka chiqarishi mumkin [2; 190]. Buning uchun tarjimondan o'sha xalq, millat milliy koloritini chuqur anglagan holda kinofilm milliyligini saqlash bilan birgalikda tomoshabinga tushunarli tarzda yetqazib bera olish vazifasi ham ko'ndalang turgan ma'suliyatdir. Chunki ma'lum millatda ishlatiladigan ba'zi tushuncha va madaniyat ko'rsatkichlari boshqa millatda uchramasligi yoki shakl, mazmun, hajm jihatdan farq qilishi mumkin. Turk tilidan tarjima qilingan kinofilmlar misolida ko'rib chiqadigan bo'lsak, birgina hurmat ko'rsatish yoki yaqinlikni ifodalash ko'rsatkichi hisoblangan "sizlash" va "senlash" nutqiy ifodasi tarjimasida ham turli muammoli vaziyatlar yuzaga keladi. Ma'lumki, o'zbek xalqi madaniyati yoki odob-axloq ko'rsatkichi doirasi nuqtai nazaridan qaralganda, o'zidan kattalarga hurmat ko'rsatishda xoh u yaqin kishi bo'lsin, xoh qaysidir darajada qarindoshlik xususiyatiga ega yoki umuman begona inson bo'lsin baribir sizlanadi. O'zbekona lutf bilan er-u xotinlar munosabatida ham sizlab murojaat qilinadi. Ammo turkiy millatlarning ko'pchiligida bo'lgani kabi turk xalqida ham sizlash rasmiyatchilikni ifodalash, notanish yoki o'ziga yaqin bo'lmagan insonlar bilan muloqot o'rnatishda ishlatiladi. Xo'sh, bu tarjima jarayonida qanday yechim topadi? O'zbekona lutf bilan turk madaniyati yoki o'ziga xoslikni o'zbekchalashtirish kerakmi yoki milliy koloritini, milliy o'ziga xoslikni saqlash muhimmi? Yuqorida aytib o'tilganidek, xalq ma'naviyatining o'sishi, dunyoqarashining takomillashuvida kinofilmlar yetakchi ahamiyat kasb etadi. Uzoq namoyish etilgan kinofilmlar tomoshasi tufayli ma'lum xalq odob-axloqi ta'siriga tushib qolish hech gap emas. Shuning uchun tarjimon baholi qudrat tarjima asliyat tilidagi xalq ma'naviyatining, odob-axloq ko'rsatkichlarining yuksak darajadagi unsurlarini ham tarjima qilinyotgan millat madaniyatiga moslashtirishi lozim. Ya'ni turkchadan tarjima qilinyotgan kinofilmlarda ham o'zbek xalqiga xos ikrom ko'rsatish bilan ya'ni yosh jihatdan katta bo'lganlarga xoh u yaqin kishi

III. TARJIMA VA TARJIMASHUNGLIKNING DOLZARB MASALALARI SHU'BASI

bo'lsin, xoh begona yoki qarindosh baribir sizlatilib o'g'irish xalqimiz ma'naviy olamiga, madaniyati va odob-axloq ko'rsatkichlariga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatmaydi. "O'quv ishlari" kinofilmida esa o'rta yoshdagi kino bosh qahramonlari aka-uka Kismet va Ismetlar nutqini sensirab berilgani ko'rib chiqildi. Bu esa kino saviyasining tushganligining va o'zbek xalq madaniyati ko'rsatkichi mezonlari talabiga javob bermaganligining guvohi bo'ldik. Ammo ba'zi holatlar ya'ni salbiy qahramonlar ichki olamini hamda xulq atvoridagi qusurni ko'rsatish maqsadida salbiy qahramon nutqidagi sansirashni berish bundan mustasno. Ammo yana ba'zi holatlarda qahramonlar o'rtasida yaqinlik paydo bo'lganligini isbotlash maqsadida alohida ta'kidlashlar uchraydi. Ya'ni bu asliyat tilidagi millatga xos xususiy madaniyatdan kelib chiqadi. Masalan: "Qanotsiz qushlar" seriali 12-bo'limida serial asosiy qahramoni Muzaffer o'zi sevgan ayolga: "Endi turmush qurdik, bundan keyin meni senlab gapir " degan talabni qo'yadi. Bunday holatda tarjimon o'sha millatga xos madaniyatni asliyatdagi kabi berishga majbur. Ya'ni turk millatida o'ziga juda yaqin olinganda samimiy munosabatni ifodalash uchun sensirab muomala qilinishi lozim ekanligi tarjimada o'z aksini topadi.

Har bir xalq turmush tarzi, dunyoqarashi, narsa va predmetlarni atashdagi o'ziga xosligi boshqa xalqlarnikidan farq qiladi. Bunday xususiyatlar shu xalqning badiiy tafakkuri, maishiy turmush tarzi, urf odatlari hatto, rasm rusumlari, kiyinishi, taomlanishi va boshqa xususiyatlari bilan ajralib turadi. Bunday so'zlar tarjimashunoslikda realiyalar termini bilan ataladi. Turkchadan tarjima qilingan kinofilmlarda ham ko'plab realiyalarga duch kelinadi. Masalan, "Melek hikoyasi" serialida (1-qism 00:10:34 daqiqasi) shunday dialog uchraydi:

-Bu ne?

-Bo'gazalti.

Nefise qahramoni turk milliy taomlaridan bo'lgan kabob nomini "Bo'g'azalti" deya keltiradi. Tarjimon ham bu taom turk milliy taomi ekanligini inobatga olgan holda o'zbekchada ham xuddi shunday beradi.

Turkchadan tarjima qilingan kinofilmlarning aksariyatida murojaat so'zlari hisoblangan "Efendim, Hanimefendim, Gelinhanim, Beyefendi" so'zlaridagi tarjimalarda ham har xillik mavjud. Ba'zi tarjimonlar ushbu so'zlar turk milliy murojaat so'zlari turk millati realiyalari sifatida qabul qilaroq aynan qoldirishni ma'qul topadilar. Ya'ni transkripsiya usulida tarjima qiladilar. "Melek hikoyasi" seriali, 00:08:43 daqiqasidan 00:08:47-daqqasigacha Gelin hanima da seslen, masa hazir. Buyursun jumlasini Kelinhonimni ham chaqir, dasturxon tayyor, kelsin shaklida tarjima qiladi. 00:18:47 daqiqasida Kurban da kestiniz mi hanimefendi? jumlasini esa Qurbonlik ham so'yingizmi, honim afandi? tarzida qoldiradi. Vaholanki, serial o'zbek tomoshabinlari uchun o'zbekchalashtirilgan, tarjima qilingan. O'zbek tili murojaat so'zlarida esa kelinlarga nisbatan kelinhonim deya murojaat qilinmaydi. Yoki hech bir ayolga honimafandi deya murojaat so'zi ishlatilmaydi.

Turk tilidan tarjima kinofilmlarda murojaat shakllariga ko'plab duch kelinadi.

Masalan: "O'quv ishlari" kinofilmidagi quyidagicha diologni uchratamiz.

Ali Osman: Hayirdir, boyle tek basina bu yollarda? Hangi belediyede chalisyorsun, bakalim?

Ali Osman 2: Ne belediyesi hapistan firar ettim, kucum, ben.

Ushbu jumla tarjimada shunday berilgan:

Ali Osman: Tinchlikmi? Bir o'zing bu yerlarda nima qilyapsan? Qaysi hokimlikda ishlaysan?

Ali Osman 2: Qanaqa hokimlik? Qamoqdan qochdim, arslonim.

Bu yerda turk millatigagina xos murojaat shakli kucum so'zi arslonim tarzida mohirona o'zbekchalashtirilgan. Ammo bu yerda kucum so'zi kichigim ya'ni kamsitish yoki mensimaslik ma'nosini ifodalaydi. Tarjimon esa unga teskari ma'no ifodalaydigan arslonim so'zini qo'llagan. Bu yerda balki kesatig ma'nosini bermoqchi bo'lgandir, bu yog'i tarjimonga ma'lum.

"Elchining qizi" ("Sefirin kizi") serialidan yana bir misol:

Nare: Melek, Melek, anneciğim. Anneciğim, benim, bak bana, anneciğim. Ben burdayim, anneciğim. Melek, bana bak.

Tarjimasi:

Nare: Melek, Melek? Melek? Ona qizim, ona qizim, ona qizim. Ona qizim, menga qara. Ona qizim, menga qara, Ona qizim. Ona qizim, shu yerdaman. Ona qizim, Melek, menga qara.

Ushbu serialda qo'llangan barcha anneciğim so'zi ona qizim tarzida o'g'irilgan. So'z tanlovi esa kinoseriyal ruhiyatini yoritishda juda o'rinli tanlov bo'lgan. Chunki ushbu serial tamoman mehr-muhabbatni kuylovchi, ayniqsa, ona mehrini namoyish etuvchi serial desak, hech mubolag'a bo'lmaydi.

Milliy xos soʻzlar tarjimondan alohida yondoshuvni talab etadi. Shunga koʻra, filmda aks ettirilgan mazmundan kelib chiqib, baʼzi oʻrinlarda sof turkcha realiya oʻrniga oʻzbekcha muqobil ishlatganining ham guvohi boʻlishimiz mumkin. Masalan: Yana shu serialda (1-boʻlim 00:18:18 daqiqasi 00:18:22) Melek: ...harçlık veriyor baba bize, şekerler veriyorlar jumlasini tarjimon Dadamiz bizga hayitlik beradi. Shirinliklar berishadi tarzida tarjima qiladi. Bu yerda harçlık – "harajat uchun pul" degan maʼnoni ifodalaydi. Ammo kinoda gap Hayit bayrami haqida ketayotgani uchun oʻzbekchalashtirgan holda "hayitlik", yaʼni biror sovgʻa salom maʼnosida qoʻllangan. Turk millatigagina xos soʻz – realiya muqobilini berishda ushbu serial tarjimoni mohirona foydalangan. Yana ushbu serial 01:17:39 daqiqasi kinofilm qahramoni Ya salata ne? Burada küşleme var, Kadriye'm, küşleme. Küşlemeden vereyim sana, al jumlasini Salat nima boʻpti bu yerda kabob turibdi! Ol, azizam, mazza qilib kabobdan ye tarzida oʻzbekchalashtirgan. Tarjimon küşleme soʻzini realiya sifatida qoldirganda oʻzbek tomoshabini uchun tushunarsiz jumla qurilgan boʻlardi. Chunki kinofilm dasturxonda kabob turgani ekranda aniqlik koʻrsatib oʻtilgan.

Realialar maʼlum millatgagina xos soʻz va tushunchalar ekan, oʻsha millatgagina xos kiyim-kechaklar, oziq-ovqatlar, turli maishiy jihozlar, geografik joy nomlari ifodasi ham deyishimiz mumkin. Kinofilmlar dialoglarida koʻplab shunday realialar, yaʼni nomlarga duch kelinadi. "Yiglama, ona " serialida ham bosh qahramon Damla nutqida shunday jumlaning uchramiz: - Yenge börekler soğumasın istersen jumlasini tarjimon ekranda koʻrinib turgan shirinliklardan kelib chiqib shekilli Yanga, xohlasangiz shirinliklardan oling deya tarjima qilgan. Vaholanki, turk tilidan oʻzbekchaga börek soʻzi boʻgʻirsoq deb oʻgirilsa, maqsadga muvofiq boʻlar edi.

Realialar turiga joy nomlari ham kiritilar ekan, baʼzi hollarda joy nomlari nimanidir ifodalagan ism boʻlganligi oqibatida tarjimonlarda koʻp holatlarda qiyinchilik uygʻotadai. Kinofilmlardan misol keltiramiz. "Oʻquv ishlari" kinofilmida personaj Kismetning Beraber dedimda, aklimga geldi. Ben biraz açkıttım, yemeğe gidecektım. Birlikta çıkalımı? Kumkapi. Hem orda sütlaç ismarlarım size gapi tarjimon tomonidan Birga dedim, xayolimga keldi. Meni biraz qornim ochdi.Ovqatlanishga bormoqchi edim.Birga boramizmi? Kumkapi. Juda yaxshi qatiq buyuraman sizga tarzida gʻaliz ham sintaktik qurilishi notoʻgʻri jumlada oʻgirilgan. Ushbu tarjimadagi Kumkapi realiya sifatida qabul qilingan.Tarjimon buni turk xalqiga xos milliy soʻz sifatida eng yomon qatiq turi deb beradi. Aslida bu Turkiyadagi armancha restoran nomidir, sütlaç esa tarjimon oʻylaganidek qatiq emas, shirguruch ovqatining turk tilidagi nomlanishidir.

Tarjimashunos olimimiz G.Salomov "Boshqa xalqlar hayotidan voqif boʻlmaslik, gʻoʻfillik milliy mahdudlikka olib keladi" [2: 18] degan edi. Darhaqiqat har bir kinofilmida milliylikka xos belgilar namoyish etiladi, tarjima boʻlmasa millatlar oʻz qobigʻiga oʻralib, dunyo xalqlarining hayoti, turmush tarzi, milliy oʻziga xosliklaridan bexabar qoladi. Bu borada ishonchli tasavvur hosil qilish uchun tarjimalar yuksak saviyada amalga oshirilgan boʻlishi lozim. Shuning uchun tarjimonning kinofilm aslyatidagi milliylikni boshqa tilda yaratishdagi mahorati dolzarb masalalardan hisoblanadi.Qardosh xalqlar oʻrtasida milliy urf-odatlar, anʼanalar uygʻunligini ham kuzatish mumkin. Buni kinofilmlardagi tasvirlar ham doimo isbotlab beradi. Masalan: "Qora niyat" seriali 126-boʻlim, 42-daqiqasida shunday dialogni koʻramiz:

Tamam hala: Yıldız kızım, ben şimdi bizim gelina bir boğça yaparım, ama neden hoşlanıyor bilmiyorum. Sen bana bir akl ver, ne dersin?

Jumla shunday oʻzbekchalashtirilgan:

Toʻxtagul amma: Yıldız kızım, shu kunlarda kelinimizga sarpo tayyorlamoqchi edim. Ammo nimani yoqtiradi, bilolmayapman. Menga oʻzing yordam bersang, nima deysan?

Bu yerda boʻxcha oʻzbek tili izohli lugʻatida kiyim kechak, latta-putta va shu kabi oʻrab tugilgan qiyiqcha, roʻmol; tuguncha. Bir boʻxcha sarpo deb izohlangan [3; 421].Tarjimada esa boʻxcha soʻzi oʻrniga sarpo soʻzi qoʻllanilgan. Bu soʻz ham maʼlum bir shaxsga yoki koʻpchilikka atab koʻpincha toʻy marosimlarida yoki turli tantanalarda sovgʻa uchun tayyorlanadigan yangi bosh-oyoq libos maʼnosida izohlanadi. Bir qarashda ikki soʻz ham bir maʼnoni ifodalayotgandek, yaʼni sinonimlardek tuyulsa-da, aynan boʻxcha kelinlar liboslari taxlanadigan tugun maʼnosini beradi. Yana bir jihati bu soʻz oʻzbek xalqi lugatida bir muncha eskirgan soʻz. Ammo Surxondaryo-Qashqadaryo vohalarida kelinlar sarposini xuddi shu boʻxchada olib borish anʼanasi saqlanib qolgan. Turk xalqi anʼanalarida ham xuddi shu urf saqlanib qolganligining, qolaversa, aynan shu soʻz bilan ifodalanishi ikki xalq madaniyati va maʼnaviyatidagi uygʻunlikni namoyon etib bermoqda.

Yuqorida aytib oʻtganimizdek, kinofilmlar biror millat madaniyati koʻzgusi sanaladi. Undagi personajlar nutqi orqali oʻsha xalq milliy madaniyati yaqqol namoyon boʻladi. Zero til millat maʼnaviyatini aks ettiruvchi oyna

ekanligi ko'p bor ta'kidlandi. Xuddi shu madaniyatni mohir kino tarjimon o'z tili madaniyati ko'rsatkichlariga moslashtiradi. Bunda aynan bir turdagi so'z yoki so'z birikmalarini o'rniga ko'ra turlicha ifoda bilan tarjima qilishi mumkin. Masalan, turk tilidagi Hakkini helal et so'z birikmasini tarjimon quyidagicha ifodalar bilan tarjima qilgan: ("Muslim baba") 44-daqiqasida bosh qahramon Muslimning ustoziga qarata Ustad, hakkini helal et jumlasini Mendan rozi bo'ling, ustoz deya mohirona o'girilgan. "O'quv ishlari" kinofilmi 09-daqiqasida mayit janozasida domla el-olomonga qarata Hakkini helal etiyor musunuz? – deya so'raydi. Shunda kinoqahramon Kismet Helal et miyorum- deya javob beradi. Tarjimada esa domlaning savoli Mayitdan rozimisizlar? va Kismetning javobi Rozi emasman tarzida o'rinli o'girilgan. Xuddi shu jumla "Muslim baba" kinofilmi 57-daqiqasida esa qahramon Ahmetning akasiga qarata aytgan: Hakkini helal et, abi degan gapi Mayli, omon bo'ling tarzida tarjima qilingan. Sahnada harbiy xizmatga ketayotgan aka-uka xayrlashuvi bo'lgani uchun "Mendan rozi bo'ling" tarzida emas. Omon bo'ling tarzida o'zbekchalashtirilgan. O'zbek xalqida harbiy xizmatga ketayotganda Oy borib omon qayt tarzida xayrlashish milliy an'ana (leksik birlik) tarzida qabul qilingan desak, hech mubolag'a bo'lmaydi. "O'quv ishlari" kinofilmida esa Bunlar ge'cen seneki o'g'rencilerimiz: hehelle'şmeye mi gelmişler? – degan gapi Bular o'tgan yilgi o'quvchilarimiz-ku, xayrlashishga kelishibdimi tarzida munosib o'girilgan. Chunki o'quv markazidagi o'qituvchidan o'quvchilar rozi-rizochilik so'rash uchun kelmaydi. Tarjimon qo'llaganidek xayrlashish uchun kelishgan bo'lishi mumkin.

Tarjimon tajribali va ijodkor bo'lsa, kinossenarist bermoqchi bo'lgan mazmun va mantiqni chuqur anglagan holda bir so'z o'rniga tamoman boshqa ma'noli so'zdan foydalanishi yoki bir so'z o'rniga ikki so'zni ishlatishi, bir so'z o'rniga frazeologik birliklardan unumli foydalanishi mumkin. Bunga misol ushbu filmning xuddi shu daqiqalari tarjimasi davomida tarjimon kinofilm asliyatida umuman frazeologik birlik ishlatilmagan vaziyatda ma'noni kuchaytirish, kinofilm badiiyatini oshirish maqsadida bo'lsa kerak ko'plab maqollar qo'shadi. Masalan, qo'shiqchi Muslim xayolga cho'mib yoshligini eslaydi. Yosh yigitlik chog'larida Muhtaram Nurni xayolan sevganini shunda qishloqdosh qizlar uning ustidan kulganini xotirlaydi. Kadrda qizlar ko'rinmagani holda faqat ularning gaplari uzoqdan kelayotgan tovushlar sifatida berilgan. Shuning uchun tarjimon ifodani: qizlar kesatig'ini, kinoyasini, pichingini yigit orzularining ustidan qattiq kulishganini yaqqolroq ifodalashda Tuya hammomni orzu qilibdi degan maqolni ham o'rnida mohirlik bilan qo'shgan. Tarjimonning so'z tanlashdagi qobiliyati tomoshabinning kinodan oladigan estetik zavqiga ham ta'sir o'tqizmay qolmaydi. Fikrimizning isboti sifatida "Muslim baba" kinofilmining 49-daqiqasidagi bosh qahramon yoyilgan choyshablarni hidlab akasiga qarab, onasini xotirlaydi-da, kir yuvuvchi onasi umri davomida choyshab yuvganini eslagan holda Abi, bak, annem gibi kokuyor degan jumla ishlatadi. Tarjimon esa ushbu jumlaning Aka, qarang, onamning isi kelyapti tarzida o'zbekchalashtirganining guvohi bo'lamiz. Vaholanki, so'zma so'z tarjimada Hidi onamning hidiga o'xshaydi tarzidagi beo'xshov tarjima chiqqan bo'lar edi. Tajribali tarjimon kinofilmida boshqa tilda boshqa millat vakili gapirayotganini sezdirmaydi. Mohirlik bilan so'z tanlaydiki, kino qahramoni nutqini xuddi o'zbek tilida gapirayotgandek ifodalaydi. Masalan, "Muslim baba" kinofilmi 58-daqiqasidagi quyidagi dialog tarjimasiga nazar tashlaylik. Asliyatda:

Doktor: Abi, damari hareket ediyor.

2-Doktor: Yaşıyormu, lan, yoksa.

Tarjimada:

Doktor: Yopiray, qo'lini qimirlatdi.

2-Doktor: Nima balo tirikmikan-a?

Bu yerda doktorning taajjubini o'zbek xalqiga xos Yopiray taajjub ifodalovchi so'z bilan juda chiroyli ifodalagan deyishimiz mumkin.

Ko'plab kinofilmlarda bo'lganidek ushbu "Muslim baba" kinofilmida ham "Allah, Allah" takror so'zi bir necha bor turli vaziyatlarga nisbatan qo'llanilgan. Bu so'z yaratuvchining nomi bo'lsa-da, turk tilida taajjubni, hayratlanishni ifodalash vositasi bo'lib qolgan. Bu so'zni xuddi aslidagi kabi qoldirish o'zbek xalqi leksikasiga yot bo'lgan ifodadir. Chunki o'zbek taajjublanganda, hayratlanganda, hayron qolganda Alloh, Alloh demaydi. Yo tavba, Yo Alhazar kabi so'zlar vositasida ifodalaydi. Masalan, xuddi shunday vaziyatga misol tariqasida shu kinofilm 01:33:56-daqiqasidagi quyidagi dialog tarjimasini misol qilib keltirishimiz mumkin. Asliyatda:

Muhtaram Nur: Biz Belgraddan gelmişiz, biliyormusun, teyzemle. Olgaymiş ya benim adım. Olga...

Muslim: Allah. Allah...A Muhterem...

Ushbu dialogdagi bu so'z taajjubni ifodalab kelgan. Buni anglab yetgan tarjimon Yo tavba. Muhtaram-chi? tarzida o'zbekchalashtirgan.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytishimiz mumkinki, tarjima jarayonida so'z tanlash muammosi har jihatdan chuqur o'rganilishi lozim. So'z ma'nosi kontekst ichida ochiladi. Ya'ni kinotarjimon kinoda ko'rinib turgan ssenariyni chunchaki so'z ma so'z tarjima qilib beribgina qolmay, aktyorlar artikulyatsiyasiga moslashtirish bilan birgalikda kinossenarist bermoqchi bo'lgan badiiy ohang, so'z va harakatlar ortida yashiringan semantik hodisani ham ilg'ay olishi muhim sanaladi.

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MUQOBILSIZ LEKSIKA VA UNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI

Dilrabo TO'RAQULOVA,

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Аннотация: В данной статье рассмотрены определения понятия и виды безэквивалентной лексики, сложности в переводе географических названий, лакун, реалий, фразеологических единиц и других национально обусловленных единиц.

Ключевые слова: безэквивалентная лексика, культура, язык, лексическая единица, эквивалент, оригинал.

Muqobilsiz leksikani o'rganishga bo'lgan qiziqish XX asrning ikkinchi yarmidan boshlab kuchaydi. "Muqobilsiz leksika" termini ilmiy muomalaga tadqiqotchilar Y.M.Vereshchagin va V.G.Kostomarovlar tomonidan kiritilgan. Ular mazkur terminni quyidagicha izohlashgan: "Muqobilsiz leksika boshqa madaniyat va tilda mavjud bo'lmagan tushunchalarni ifodalovchi so'zlar, ya'ni faqat muayyan madaniyatgagina xos bo'lgan madaniyat unsurlari, shuningdek, boshqa tilda tarjimasini bo'lmagan, bir so'z bilan aytganda, o'zi taalluqli bo'lgan tildan tashqarida muqobili bo'lmagan so'zlardir" [6; 232].

L. S. Barxudarovning yozishicha: "Muqobilsiz leksika – bir tildagi leksik birliklarning boshqa tilda to'liq yoki qisman muqobiliga ega bo'lmasligidir" [2; 93].

U muqobilsiz leksikaga quyidagi uchta guruhdagi leksik birliklarni kiritadi:

"1. Atoqli otlar – geografik joy nomlari, tashkilot, korxonalar, gazeta va h.k. nomlar.

2. Realiya – boshqa tilda so'zlashuvchilarning amaliy tajribalarida mavjud bo'lmagan predmetlar, tushunchalar va vaziyatlarni ifodalovchi so'zlar. Masalan: moddiy va ma'naviy madaniyatdagi milliy taom nomlari, milliy libos nomlari va h.k.

3. Tasodifiy lakunalar – biron bir tildagi leksik birliklarning qandaydir sabablarga ko'ra boshqa tilning leksik tarkibiga mos kelmasligi" [2; 94].

Demak, muqobilsiz leksika deganda, biz boshqa tilning leksik birliklari orasida na to'liq, na qisman ekvivalentiga ega bo'lmagan leksik birliklari (so'zlar va so'z birikmalari)ni tushunamiz. Bunga asosan quyidagi so'z turkumlari kiradi:

"1) tegishli nomlar, geografik nomlar, muassasalarning nomlari; leksikada doimiy mos kelmaydigan tashkilotlar, gazetalar, kemalar va boshqalar;

2) realiyalar, ya'ni obyektlar, tushunchalar va boshqa tilda gapiradigan odamlarning amaliy tajribasida mavjud bo'lmagan holatlar. Bunga turli xil moddiy va ma'naviy narsalarni bildiruvchi so'zlar kiradi. Faqat shu xalqqa xos madaniyatlar, masalan, milliy taomlarning nomlari oshxonasi (rus. щи, борщ, рассольник, квас, калач; ingliz (muffin, haggis, toffee, butter-scotch, sundae), xalq kiyimi va poyabzali turlari (saraфан, душегрейка, кокошник, лапти), xalq raqslari ruscha (трепак, гопак); inglizcha (pop-gocs-the-weasel), xalq og'zaki ijodidan (ruscha былина; inglizcha limericks) va boshqalar.

3) leksik birliklar, ularni tasodifiy bo'shliqlar deb atash mumkin. Biz tillardan birining lug'atining boshqa tilning leksik tarkibida (so'zlar yoki iboralar ko'rinishida) biron bir sababga ko'ra (har doim ham aniq emas) mos kelmaydigan birliklarini nazarda tutamiz" [2; 93].

Butun dunyo xalqlari tillari orasida o'zaro farqlar mavjud bo'lib, asosan madaniyatlar orasidagi farqlarga asoslanadi. Bu farqlar tilning leksik va frazeologik qatlamida yuzaga chiqadi, binobarin, tilning nominativ birliklari aksariyat holda nolisoniy omillar bilan bog'langan bo'ladi. "Muqobilsiz leksika muayyan xalqning milliy madaniyatiga xos hodisalarni aks ettiradi. U ko'pincha mahalliy xalqqa xos pul birligi, ro'zg'or-ashyo buyumlari, kiyim-kechak, yegulik-ichimlik va h.k tushunchalarni anglatadigan so'zlardan tarkib topadi [18; 82].

Tarjimashunoslikda muqobillik va adekvatlik tushunchalari sinonimlar, o'xshash tushunchalar sifatida qaraladi. Masalan, J. Catford, muqobillikni (tarjima muqobilligini) adekvatlik deb belgilaydi. Biroq, boshqa olimlar, masalan: V.N. Komissarov, muqobillik va adekvatlikni, tarjima bir-biriga yaqin bo'lsa-da, bir-biriga o'xshash bo'lmagan jihatlarini aniqlaydi. Adekvat tarjima zarur bo'lgan "yaxshi" tarjimaning sinonimi sifatida u tomonidan kengroq ko'rib chiqiladi. Va muayyan sharoitlarda tillararo muloqotning to'liqligi va ekvivalentlik til va nutq birliklari bir-biriga tenglashtirilganning semantik guruhi sifatida ko'rib chiqiladi. Shveysar adekvatligini ta'kidlab, ekvivalentlikning turli darajalarini aniqlaydi tarjima ma'lum darajadagi ekvivalentlikni nazarda tutadi, ekvivalent tarjimani esa har doim ham adekvat deb hisoblash mumkin emas [1; 6].

Zamonaviy ijtimoiy-madaniy makonning eng muhim xususiyati globallashuvdir. Va bugungi kunda, globallashuv sharoitida, tarjima nuqtai nazaridan madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya muammolari mavzusi dolzarb bo'lib bormoqda. Muvaffaqiyatli muloqot har ikki tomonning bir-birini tushunishini talab qiladi. Muqobilsiz leksikani uzatish muammosi, madaniyatlararo muloqotni ta'minlash masalalariga ham tegishli. Bunday lingvistik hodisa ko'pincha badiiy adabiyotda uchraydi, bu esa, boshqa tillarga tarjima qilishda muayyan qiyinchiliklarni keltirib chiqaradi. Muqobilsiz leksikaning bir nechta tasniflari mavjud, ammo bizning fikrimizcha, A.O.Ivanov eng to'liq shaklini ko'rib chiqqan, va u muqobilsiz leksikani uchta katta guruhga ajratadi:

1. Referensial muqobilsiz leksika;
2. Pragmatik muqobilsiz leksika;
3. Alternativ muqobilsiz leksika.

"Referensial muqobilsiz leksika – bu guruh ichida tarjimaning kalkalash, tavsifiy tarjima, qo'shish, tushirib yuborish, konkretlashtirish, neytrallashtirish, umumlashtirish (generalizatsiya), taqribiy tarjima, modulyatsiya kabi turlari aniqlangan.

Pragmatik muqobilsiz leksika – muqobilsiz leksikaning ushbu shaklida biz quyidagi tarjima usullarini topdik: izlash, ta'kidlash, modulyatsiya, qo'shish, konkretlashtirish, original uzatish, transkripsiya va transliteratsiya, umumlashtirish, tavsifiy tarjima, neytrallashtirish, tashlab ketish, taxminiy tarjima.

Alternativ muqobilsiz leksika – bu guruh ichida tarjimaning qoldirib ketish, kalkalash, konkretlashtirish, qo'shish, modulyatsiya, neytrallashtirish, urg'ulash, umumlashtirish, tavsifiy tarjima, taxminiy tarjima, transkripsiya va transliteratsiya kabi turlari aniqlangan" [10; 168].

"Muqobilsiz leksika" atamasi til va tarjima muammolari bilan shug'ullanadigan ko'plab mualliflarning ilmiy ishlarida tahlil qilingan, masalan, E.M. Vereshchagin, V.G. Kostomarov, L.S. Barxudarov, S.I. Vlixov, S.P. Florin, Y.I. Retsker, V.N. Komissarov, A.D. Shveyser, A.V. Fedorov. Biroq atamaning o'zi, "realiya" tushunchasining sinonimi sifatida, "mahalliy realiyalarga xos bo'lgan so'zlar" yoki "boshqa tilga tarjima qilib bo'lmaydigan so'zlar" sifatida turlicha talqin qilinadi [4; 23].

Masalan, Shveyser "boshqa madaniyatda aniq mos kelmaydigan madaniy voqelikni belgilashga xizmat qiladigan leksik birliklar" [18; 110] deb muqobilsiz leksikaga ishora qiladi. V.N. Komissarov muqobilsiz leksikaga "tilda muntazam yozishmalarga ega bo'lmagan til birliklari" [7; 89] deb ta'rif beradi.

Tilshunoslar Vlixov va Florin, o'z navbatida, muqobilsiz leksika, chegaralarini sezilarli darajada toraytiradi va ular "o'z tilida tarjima ekvivalenti bo'lmagan leksik birliklar" [5; 42] deb ta'rif berishadi.

Tarjimada milliy o'ziga xoslikni aks ettirish, realiyalarni berish hamisha tarjimon oldida murakkablik tug'dirgan. Bu borada katta tajriba to'plangan, ko'plab tadqiqot ishlari olib borilgan bo'lsa ham, bu muammo hanuz o'z yechimini topgani yo'q. Shuning uchunmi, bu borada xato-kamchiliklar kamaymayapti.

Muqobilsiz leksika tarjima tilida ekvivalenti bo'lmagan, boshqa madaniyatga aniq mos kelmaydigan, boshqa xalq milliy unsurlari bilan tenglasha olmaydigan so'zlar deb ta'rif berilar ekan, aynan bir tilgagina xos bo'lgan milliylik, milliy xos so'zlar tarjimasini muammosiga alohida to'xtalib o'tish lozim bo'ladi.

Milliylik, madaniyat va milliy o'ziga xoslik aynan bir mamlakat, xalq va millatning milliyligini tashkil etadi. "Milliy xos so'zlar" mavzusi o'zbek tarjimashunosligida atroflicha o'rganilgan. G.Salomov, N.Komilov, Z.Isomiddinov, R.Fayzullayev, Q.Musayev, X.Hamidov, E.Ochilov, N.Xodjayeva, N.Ismatullayeva, B.Bo'ronova, M.Umarova, G.Nomozovalar milliy kolorit, milliy xos so'zlar va ularni tarjimada berish usullari, tarjima qilish jarayonida tarjimon duch keladigan muammolar, qiyinchiliklar haqida tadqiqot olib borganlar.

Milliylik, milliy o'ziga xoslik deganda faqatgina bir xalqning o'zigagina tegishli bo'lgan jihatlar tushuniladi.

O'zbek tilining izohli lug'atida milliy so'ziga quyidagicha ta'rif beriladi: "1. Millatga oid; bir millatdagi kishilarga xos bo'lgan; 2. Biror millatning, xalqning o'ziga xos bo'lgan, uning xususiyatlarini ifodalovchi; 3. Biror mamlakatga, davlat va uning aholisiga oid". Shunday ekan, bir millatgagina tegishli bo'lgan har qanday unsur, urf-odat, an'ana; kundalik hayotda qo'llaniladigan buyumlar milliyini tashkil etadi.

G. Salomov asarlarda, adabiyotshunoslik va tarjimashunoslikda milliy o'ziga xoslik katta o'rin egallashini, u har qanday ijod mahsulining asosiy ko'rsatkichlaridan biri ekanligini ta'kidlaydi va shunday ta'rif beradi: "Milliy o'ziga xoslik – adabiy asarda tasvirlangan xalq hayotining moddiy sharoiti, ma'naviy turmush tarzi, tabiati, o'rmon, tog', dala, suv, zamin, osmon hamda afsona va cho'pchaklari, tarixi va dini, adabiyoti va san'ati hamda boshqa maxsus narsalar haqidagi tasavvurlari, tushunchalari, atamaları, tushuniladi. Kiyim-kechaklar, udumlar, urf-odatlar, pul birliklari va hokozolar ham milliy xoslik komponentlari jumlasiga kiradi" [13; 101].

So'nggi paytlarda "Til va madaniyat" muammosiga e'tibor kuchayishi munosabati bilan lingvistik tadqiqotlar paradigmasi turli darajadagi til birliklari ma'nolarining milliy madaniy komponentini aniqlashni o'z ichiga oladi. Ushbu komponent eng ko'p leksik va frazeologik darajalarda ifodalanadi. Lug'at, realiya olami bilan eng yaqin aloqada bo'lgan til darajasi sifatida, an'anaviy xususiyatlardan tashqari, so'zlarning ma'nosi, (antonimlar, sinonimlar), aloqadorlik darajasi va ko'lami bo'yicha bog'lanishi. Qo'llanishi bo'yicha (adabiy lug'at, shevalar, maxsus lug'at) milliy-madaniy o'ziga xoslik nuqtai nazaridan tavsiflanishi kerak.

Lug'aviy tushunchalari tillararo bo'lgan so'zlar ekvivalent deyiladi, ular oson tarjima qilinadi, ularni o'zlashtirganda esa semantik ko'chish ancha maqbul bo'ladi. Aksincha, ma'no-mazmunini hech bir chet tilidagi leksik tushunchalar bilan solishtirib bo'lmaydigan so'zlar muqobili yo'q (muqobilsiz leksika) deyiladi. Bunday so'zlarni, qat'iy aytganda, tarjima qilib bo'lmaydi [4; 77].

Agar muqobilsiz leksika o'zlashtirilmasa unda hech qanday holatda uni chet tilida aniq yozishmalar, bir so'zli tarjima yordamida ifodalash mumkin emas. Bunday holda, leksik tushunchani so'zma-so'z tasvirlash kerak bo'ladi. Bu borada Vereshagin E, Kostamarov V. kabi olimlar "Язык и культура" nomli kitobida quyidagicha fikrlarni keltiradi "Turli tillardagi tushunchalar tizimi bir-biriga to'g'ri kelmagani uchun... chet tilini o'rganishda nafaqat so'zlarning tovush shaklini, balki ular asosidagi tushunchalarning tizimini ham o'zlashtirish kerak" [13; 77].

Bu kabi leksik birliklar xalqimizning asriy qarashlari, ma'naviy hayotining asosi sifatida yuzaga kelgan, tasavvurimizda muhrlangan qadriyatlar, an'analar ifodasidir. Shunday ekan, bunday birliklar faqat bizning millatimizgagina xos hodisalar bo'lib qolmay, boshqa xalq vakillarida ham bunday jarayonlar kuzatiladi. Muqobilsiz leksikani tarjima qilishda nafaqat asliyat tilini bilishi, balki xalqlar madaniyatining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, urf-odati, maishiy hayoti, nutqiy etiket qoidalarini bilishi talab qilinadi. Shundagina tarjima muvaffaqiyatli amalga oshadi.

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HINDISTONDA TARJIMASHUNOSLIK RIVOJI

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Abstract. *Centuries of invasion, migration, and cultural integration have created a great opportunity for South Asian translators, with its remarkable linguistic diversity and state of linguistic contact. It is necessary to preserve the language in the present in order to exercise one's skill and challenge established theoretical linguistic claims. This article is devoted to the development of translation studies in India. It talks about how it developed and its unique features.*

Key words: *Indian translation studies, multilingualism, bhakti, navjagaran, svachandatavad, riti.*

“Butun dunyo miqyosida turli xalqlarning o‘zaro siyosiy, iqtisodiy, ilmiy, madaniy hamkorligi borgan sari kuchayib bormoqdaki, bu aloqalarni tarjimasiz tasavvur qilib bo‘lmaydi. Bugungi kunda tarjimaning ahamiyati haqida gapirish quyoshning ahamiyatini tushuntirishday gap bo‘lib qoldi. Ya‘ni quyoshsiz yer yuzida hayot bo‘lmagani kabi, tarjimasiz turli xalqlarning o‘zaro aloqasi, o‘zaro aloqasiz esa taraqqiyot bo‘lmaydi. “Boshqa xalqlar hayotidan voqif bo‘lmaslik, g‘o‘fillik milliy mahdudlikka olib keladi” [6; 18]. Shuning uchun ham tarjimaga xalqlarni bir-biriga bog‘lovchi halqa, fan va madaniyatni rivojlantiruvchi va boyituvchi vosita, o‘zaro hamkorlik va hamjihatlikka asos soluvchi ko‘prik deb qaraladi” [4; 4].

Hindiston Respublikasi – katta ko‘p millatli mamlakatdir. Uning aholisi turli til va shevalarda muloqot qilishadi. 2001-yil aholini ro‘yhatga olishda 1652 til qayd etilgan. O‘n mingdan ortiq ona tilida so‘zlashuvchilar 216 ta til mavjud. Hindistonda rasmiy tillar soni 22 ta hisoblanadi. Ammo bu til boyligi boshidanoq hind jamiyatiga xos xususiyat bo‘lib kelgan. Shuning uchun tarjima Hindistonda turli tillarda so‘zlashuvchilar o‘rtasidagi muloqot vositasi sifatida uzoq tarixga ega. Tarjimashunoslar nuqtai nazaridan Hindiston turli sabablarga ko‘ra noyobdir.

XVIII-XIX-asr oxirlarida Hindiston g‘arb bilan to‘qnashuv natijasida murakkab, ikki tomonlama, madaniy-intellektual munosabatlar yuzaga keldi. Fan, muhandislik sohalarida va siyosat va iqtisod kabi yangi fanlarda ingliz tili hind tillariga tarjimalar uchun donor tilga aylandi. Falsafa, din, tilshunoslik va adabiyot nazariyasi sohalarida sanskrit tili ingliz va boshqa yevropa tillariga tarjimalar uchun donor tili sifatidagi rolini yangiladi. Aslida, XIX-asrda Yevropa Hindistonni kashf etgani kabi Hindiston Yevropani kash etdi va o‘zaro ta‘sir ehtimoli teng edi. 1820-yilga kelib Yevropaning barcha yirik universitetlarida sanskrit fanlari kafedralari mavjud edi va sanskritshunoslik katta obro‘ga ega bo‘ldi. Asr o‘tgan sari sanskritshunoslik Yevropa ongini shakllantirdi.

"Hindiy tilida tarjima tushunchasining ma'nosi juda keng. Hindiy tilida tarjima so'zi bir qancha so'zlar bilan ifodalanib keladi. Hozirgi eng ommalashgani "अनुवाद" (tarjima) so'zidir. Undan tashqari boshqa so'zlar ham ishlatilib kelinadi. Ular quyidagilar: भाषांतर, परकाया प्रवेश, स्वीकरण, पालतूकरण, रूपांतर, तर्जुमा, छायानुवाद, द्रांसलेट, दुहराव, दुभाषिया, उल्था. Bular quyidagi ma'nolarni o'z ichiga oladi: til uzatish, ruhning bir tanadan boshqasiga o'tishi yoki transformatsiya, o'zgan o'zinikidek qabul qilish, xonakilashtirish. Yuqorida keltirilgan atamalar hindiy tilidagi "अनुवाद" deb tarjima qilinadi. So'zma-so'z va etimologik jihatdan "अनुवाद" "keyingi" nutqni anglatadi. "अनु" – ergashish, "वाद" – nutq deganidir" [1, 101].

Hindiston tarjimashunosligi rivojida quyidagi davrlarni o'z ichiga oladi:

1. Hind lingvistik voqeliklari va erta davr tarjimasi (erta davrdan 1100 yilgacha);
2. Bhakti (भक्ती 1100-1700) va Riti (रीति 1700-1800) davrlari tarjimasi;
3. Navjagaron (नवजागरण) davridagi tarjima;
4. Svachhandatavad (स्वच्छन्दतावाद) davridagi tarjima;
5. Zamonaviy (आधुनिक) davrdagi tarjima (1950-1980);
6. O'ta zamonaviy (आधुनिकोत्तर) davrdagi tarjima (1980dan boshlab);

Shundan kelib chiqqan holda, Hindistondagi tarjimashunoslik taraqqiyotini quyidagicha davrlashtirish mumkin:

1. Mustamlakachilikdan oldingi davr tarjimachiligi;
2. Mustamlakachilik davri;
3. Mustamlakachilikdan keying davr;

Birinchi davrni ikkiga bo'lish mumkin: 1) ilk davrlardan 1100 yilgacha va 2) 1100 yildan 1757 yilgacha bo'lgan davr. Hindistonda tarjima amaliyoti haqida gapirilganda, ko'ptilli ekanligi unutilmasligi kerak. Tarjima jarayonida ular nazariyaga va metodologiyaga e'tibor bermasdan tarjima qilganlar. Bir vaqtning o'zida bir necha tillarga ega hindlar bir til tizimidan ikkinchisiga osonlik bilan o'tishi mumkin edi. Hindistondagi turli xil tillar bir biriga raqib bo'lmagan.

XIX-asrning ikkinchi yarimida Hindistonda ko'p tililik rivojlandi. Misol uchun, gujaratlik shoir. Dayaram gujarat va hindiy tillarida ijod qilgan.

Bhakti va riti tarjima davrlarida shoirlar tarjima qilishga intilganlar. Ular hind xalqining yashash tarzini, madaniyatini, an'analarni tarjima orqali targ'ib qilganlar. Aynan Nanak, Kabir, Sur, Tulsi, Narsinh, Mira, Gyaneshvar shoirlar sanskrit tilidagi bilimlarni ommalashtirib, ularni dialektlarga va lokhbashalarga (xalq tili) tarjima qilganlar.

Tarjimachilik faoliyatiga haqiqiy turtki aynan 1757 yildan 1857 yilgacha Sharqiy Hindiston kompaniyasi ostida va 1857 yildan 1947 yilgacha mustamlaka hukmronligi davrida. Shu davrda hindiy tilidan ingliz tiliga tarjimalar ommalashib ketdi. Barcha davlat tadbirlari hindiy tilidan ingliz tiliga tarjima qilinish boshlangan edi.

Hind tarjimashunosi professor G.N.Devy hind kontekstida adabiy tarjimalarni uch turga bo'ladi:

1. Qadimiy adabiy merosni saqlashga qiziquvchilar;
2. "G'arblashuvchi" hind tillari va adabiyoti bilan qiziquvchilar;
3. Zamonaviy hind tillarida "milliylashtirish" adabiyotiga qiziquvchilar;

Hindistonning eng mashhur tarjimonlaridan biri faylasuf, shoir – Shri Aurobindo tarjimashunoslikda psixo-ma'naviy nazariyalarni ishlab chiqdi. U o'zining tarjimalaridan nazariy asos ishlab chiqdi. U ushbu nazariy asoslarini Kalidasa tarjimasida, Bhagavad Gitani tarjimasida, Upanishadlarni tarjima qilishda, nasrning she'rga talqini va bengal tilidagi tarjimalariga oid mulohazalar kabi maqolalarida qayd etgan. Bir qancha asarlarni tarjima qilgandan so'ng, u Hindistonning kognitiv falsafasi va an'analari, xususan, buddizmga bo'lgan va buddistlik davrining ta'siri ostida falsafa va psixologiya bilimi bilan ushbu nazariyalarni ishlab chiqdi [2; 340].

Shri Aurobindoning aytishicha muqaddas bitiklarni tarjima qilishning 3 ta standarti bor. Ular quyidagilar: biluvchi, bilim va muqaddas kitoblarni tarjima qilish ko'nikmasiga ega bo'lish. Shri Aurobindo ikkita asosiy qurilmadan foydalangan holda ko'plab matnlarni tarjima qilgan: tasvirni o'zgartirish va neologizm. U boshqalarga tarjima qilishda xuddi shunday qabul qilishni taklif qiladi. Uning aytishicha, estetik jihatdan muhim matnni tarjima qilishda "so'zning yaqinligi" "ma'no yaqinligi" dan muhimroqdir. Uning fikricha,

III. TARJIMA VA TARJIMASHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MASALALARI SHU'BASI

tarjimon o'zining ijodiy aql-zakovatidan obrazni o'zgartirish orqali foydalanishi, ya'ni asl tasvirning estetik va madaniy qiymati haqida qayg'urishi kerak [2; 340].

Bugungi kunda hind adabiyoti ingliz tiliga tarjimasi va hind-ingliz adabiyoti Hindiston universitetlarida ingliz adabiyoti o'quv dasturlariga kiritilgan. Shu ishlarga katta hissa qo'shgan tarjimonlardan biri Haydorobod universiteti professori Minakshi Mukerji edi. U ingliz tilidan tashqari bengal va Marathi tillariga ham tarjima qilgan. Ammo u Hindistonda ingliz adabiyotining an'anaviy tarzda o'qitilishini tanqid qilardi. U ingliz tili kurslarida hind tilidagi matnlarni tarjima qilish jarayonida madaniyatni yaxshiroq o'rganish mumkinligini aniqladi. Ko'proq matnlarni tarjima qilishni avzaloq ko'rdi. Mukerji tarjimashunoslar uchun meros qoldirdi [7; 157].

Hindiston tarjimashunosligining taraqqiyotiga hissa qo'shgan tarjimonlardan yana biri Dehli universiteti professori Harish Trivedi. U turli xalqaro uyushmalarda ko'plab nufuzli lavozimlarni egallagan. U 1993-1999-yillarda Hindiston hamdo'stlik adabiyoti va tilshunoslik assotsiatsiyasining kotibi va vitse-prezidenti hamda 2002-2004-yillarda shu assotsiatsiyasi raisi o'rinbosari bo'lgan. 2002-yilda AQSHning Chikago universiteti va London universiteti professori bo'lgan. Shuningdek, Afinadagi Jorjiya universiteti, Oklaxoma universiteti va turli nufuzli universitetlarda turli tarjimashunoslikka oid ma'ruzalar o'qidi.

Professor Harish Trivedi tarjima bo'yicha ko'plab ishlarni amalga oshirgan, ammo mustamlakachilikdan keying yozuvchi sifatida uning eng muhim ishlaridan biri postcolonial tarjima bo'lib, u Syuzan Bassnett bilan hamkorlikda tahrir qilgan. Shuning uchun tarjima sohasida bir nechta maqolalar nashr etgan. Shuningdek, u "Hindistonda tarjima" deb nomlangan kitob ustida ishlamoqda. Uning asosiy maqsadi – tarjimashunoslarni qiynaydigan nazariy savollarga javob topishdir [3].

Hozirgi zamonaviy hind tarjimonlaridan biri Santosh Aleks. U ikki tilli shoir va ko'p tilli tarjimondir. Tarjima sohasida 23 yildan beri ishlaydi. Santosh mustamlaka davridan keying adabiyotlarni ingliz, hindiy, Malayalam, tamil va telugu tillariga tarjima qiladi. U mamlakatning 100 ga yaqin adiblarini turli tillarga tarjima qilgan. U so'ngi 24 yil davomida tarjima va yozuv san'ati orqali hind adabiyotini boyitib kelmoqda. U she'riyat, tanqid va tarjimaga oid 42 kitob muallifi hisoblanadi. She'rlari 18 tilga tarjima qilingan. Santosh Aleks tarjima borasida quyidagi fikrlarni bildirgan: "Tarjima – bu san'at. Unda malakaga ega bo'lish uchun ko'p yillik amaliyot kerak. Tarjimani davom ettirish, shuningdek, boshqa tarjima qilingan asarlarni o'qish kerak" [8; 103].

Hindistondagi zamonaviy davrda hind yozuvchilari tarjimashunoslari orasida raqobat kuchaydi. Hind mintaqaviy til yozuvchilari va hind-ingliz yozuvchilari. Ba'zi yozuvchilar o'z asarlarini o'zlari tarjima qiladilar. Masalan, Rabindranat Tagor – bengal tilidan ingliz tiliga, Girish Karnad – Kannada tilidan ingliz tiliga tarjima qilganlar. Hindistonda bir qator ikki tilli yozuvchilar bor. Ular Kamala Das, Jayant Mahapatra va boshqalar. Olimlar shu kunlarda tarjimashunoslik sohasida izlanishlar olib bormoqdalar.

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BASIC PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATION ACCOUNTING-AUDITING TERMS

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Аннотация. В статье описан перевод английской терминологической системы бухгалтерского учета и аудита с применением подхода прагматической лингвистики. Учет интересов целевого читателя в данной статье представляется ключевым фактором при выборе подходящего перевода английской полисемантической терминологической системы бухгалтерского учета и аудита.

Ключевые слова: бухгалтерский учет-аудит, прагматика, термин, когнитивный аспект, контекст, моносемантическая и полисемантическая лексика, эквивалентность.

Introduction. At present time the classification and description of terms in accounting and auditing areas, linguistic analysis of different structural languages, and definition and development of methods, methods, and methodologies of the terminology are some of the most important issues facing world linguists.

It is not a secret that linguistics pays great attention to the translation of economic terms from English into Uzbek because from year to year, it can be observed the development of economic relations between states, legal entities, and individuals, which requires training specialists that meet the requirements of the labor market. Every day more and more people enter into market relations with foreign companies. As a result, an adequate translation of economic vocabulary becomes very important in order to prevent possible misunderstandings between the participants of communication.

Definitely, the accounting-auditing terminological system in English and Uzbek is somewhat complex and typically, requires the interpretation of terminological units in terms of their meaning and interpretation. In fact, this law is an important principle that is applicable to any sphere of the term. In addition, studies focusing on the study of terminology systems of different languages have given a great importance to the analysis of terminology.

In fact, the economy includes various areas of activity: industry, agriculture, trade, stock exchange and communication. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the possibility of the presence in any type of the text the economic orientation of vocabulary from other fields. Each sector of the economy has its own specific units that require the search for the most accurate translation of a specific expression, taking into account the economic, legal, political and cultural realities of a particular country.

Material and methods. Undeniably, translation across languages and cultures has a critical role in accounting. This sphere is required in international trade, in operating and accounting for multinational enterprises, in creating, implementing and enforcing international accounting laws and standards, in delivering accounting education to international cohorts of students, and in conducting international and intercultural research. Financial statements and annual reports, standards and standard-setting discourse, teaching materials and publication of research findings all require translation for at least some constituents. Accounting research explores annual report narratives or regulatory discourse, employs content analysis or disclosure indices, conducts interviews, experimental and survey research, and draws on theoretical frameworks, all often across cultural and language boundaries.

That is why, while translating accounting-auditing terminological system, in most cases, from English into Uzbek, linguists try to find an equivalent, which is a very difficult task, since many terms have entered to Uzbek language quite recently and it is not always possible to impose them on the economic realities of Independent Uzbekistan.

The cognitive approach to the studied stratum of foreign words allows us to consider the structure of knowledge in the human mind. Consequently, both the process of translating terms and the process of

borrowing seems appropriate to consider from the standpoint of cognitive linguistics, since they represent two aspects of the same phenomenon of language interaction. In this context, terms are understood as cognotypes, and their multi-valued variants, synonyms and homonyms - as variants of the cognotype [8; 9-12] i.e. units of the metalanguage of a certain sphere of use, denoting a special concept that includes the specific field of knowledge of the speaker [3; 25].

Adequate translation of the accounting-auditing terminological system accelerates the process of information exchange between specialists around the world. When translating a lexical unit, it is necessary to take into account the peculiarities of the economic vocabulary as a whole, namely, accuracy of information, lack of emotional coloring, brevity and systematicity [4]. Thus, the translator must correlate the world of the addressing and receiving sides and possess the cognitive apparatus of economics.

The main problem is that a large number of lexical units belonging to the accounting-auditing terminological sphere have several translation options and in most cases, it does not concern all words, but individual words. This fact makes it possible to subdivide economic vocabulary into single-translation and multi-translational. Translating terms are terms that have one equivalent in the language of translation, and translations, respectively, have several equivalents in translation [10]. For example, the term "account" has several translation options:

- 1) an account; account entry;
- 2) report (financial);
- 3) the period while exchange transactions concluded with the closing of the position on the accounting day;
- 4) a broker's record of transactions executed on behalf of a client;
- 5) reporting;
- 6) accounts;
- 7) business books.

Translating terms in most cases are expressions and phrases that have one translation option, but, speaking separately, they can be multi-valued.

In order to overcome different translation while translating accounting-auditing terms from English into Uzbek, it is necessary to take into account the cognitive models that underlie one or another text [9]. Thus, in highly specialized accounting-auditing texts, facts and reports on the state of stock markets are usually given, and reports on companies' profits and losses analyzed.

Results. Popular accounting-auditing texts most often describe people, who have achieved some success in the economic sphere, or unusual projects or ideas. Accounting-auditing terminological texts include features of the above two types, combining various elements. For example:

Across the country, myriad independent contractors and small service firms have sprung up to supply streamlined corporations with skills ranging graphic design to bill collecting and executive recruiting .

In the above example, the term "corporation" has several translation options: 1) association; 2) corporation; 3) joint stock.

In our opinion, in this case it is better to use the equivalent of "corporation", since the article in question is highly specialized, which means that the readers of this publication have basic knowledge on the topic. Thus, while translating such texts, it is best to use equivalent borrowings in the target language, since it is assumed that the readers of this publication are experts in the field of economics. For popular-economic texts, it is best to use metaphors that will help to make economic terminology accessible to a wide range of readers, who have only the most general idea of the meaning of certain accounting-auditing terms.

It is important to mention encouraging submissions that address topics relating to language, culture and translation in accounting, auditing and accountability. The following topics are possible topics for including:

- Limits of equivalence in accounting translation.
- Problems and opportunities of ambiguity in accounting terminology.
- Translation and power: communication, dissemination, legitimization, lobbying, social change

- Ideological, cultural, social, legal and/or political implications of translation and non-translation in accounting
- Cognitive and cultural bias and vested interests in translation.
- English as a lingua franca: cultural dominance, values, identities and ideologies.
- Transformation of accounting systems and cultures, professions, societal and cultural contexts of change.
- Professional socialization in international contexts.
- International accounting education.
- Accounting history across languages and cultures: translation and language change.
- Implications for standard setting, consultation and the IASB due process.
- Implications for implementation of international accounting rules/standards.
- Probability/uncertainty expressions in accounting standards.
- Translations of rules versus principles.
- Economic implications of accounting translation.
- Accounting research across languages and cultures: research instruments, narratives, experiments, surveys, interviews and oral history, theoretical frameworks in translation (Foucault, Bourdieu, Weber, Habermas etc.).
- Implications for translation of the dissemination of research findings in English language academic journals.

Conclusion. Summarizing it can be suggested that while working with accounting-auditing terminological texts, the translator must take into account the peculiarities of the translation inherent in the two types of text described above. It is the basic difficulty of the work, since it is necessary to take into consideration not only the type of text, but also the context, contextual determinants (lexico-syntactic, morphological and lexical-phrasal), as well as the economic and political realities of the country to which readers are oriented edition.

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THEORETICAL BASES OF STUDYING THE TERM FIELD "VITICULTURE AND WINEMAKING" IN MODERN SCIENCE

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Annotatsiya. *Maqolamizda terminologik tarjima muammolarining kichik qismini taqdim etishga harakat qildik. Fransuz va o'zbek tillarida uzumchilik va vinochilik atamalarining tarkibiy-semantik xususiyatlari, ularning farq va o'xshash tomonlari, rus va ingliz tillarida ilmiy-amaliy ahamiyatini o'rganish bo'yicha ixtisoslashtirilgan tadqiqotlar yo'qligi bugungi kunning eng dolzarb muammolaridan biridir.*

Kalit so'zlar: *leksikografik manbalar, tizimli tavsif, maxsus lug'at tarjimasining xususiyatlari, kognitiv lingvistika.*

In the modern world, the main attention of researchers in the field of cognitive linguistics and cultural studies is focused on the study of sections of the national picture of the world. This is confirmed by the studies devoted to the issues of studying the national originality of the linguistic picture of the world and its fragments at the present stage [1]. In the framework of the ongoing research based on French and Russian languages, an attempt is made to substantiate the need for a synthesized approach to the study of the holistic essence of the world picture. In particular, the study considers the term field "Viticulture and winemaking", represented by French and Russian languages as a segment of the world picture, revealing interrelations within the scientific and technical picture of the world and outside it – with the national picture of the world.

Despite a significant number of works in Russian and foreign linguistics devoted to the study of individual thematic groups, the term field "Viticulture and winemaking" has not been the subject of research so far and is insufficiently described in the available lexicographic sources. All this points to the weak study of the term field "Viticulture and winemaking" and the need for its systematic description from the standpoint of the new knowledge paradigm of cognitive linguistics.

The present study is carried out in line with modern trends in cognitive linguistics and terminology, focused on the description of lexico-semantic and word-formation aspects of the formation of special vocabulary.

The communicative aspect and peculiarities of translation of special vocabulary were taken into account in the study of the term field. It is relevant to study the cognitive essence of the process of borrowing foreign-language and inter-branch terms.

The present article research presents the results of a comparative, structural-semantic and functional description of lexical units of English and Russian languages, forming the term field "Viticulture and winemaking". The investigated term field includes names of different types of wines, various forms of the production process; vocabulary related to the practice and theory of winemaking, related aspects of viticulture and winemaking (vine diseases, objects contributing to the consumption of wines; inventors and names of drinks, viticulture and winemaking regions, as well as the history of the industry, etc.).

The term "viticulture and winemaking" is of scientific interest from the point of view of its systemic structure, history of formation and evolution, stability and variability in dynamics, linguocultural component.

Viticulture and winemaking is a branch of agriculture related to the cultivation of grapes and wine production. This term has both lexico-semantic and word-formation aspects in both English and Russian.

The lexico-semantic aspect includes the meanings of the term "viticulture and winemaking" itself and related concepts. In English, the term is translated as "viticulture and winemaking". "Viticulture" means the cultivation of grapes, and "winemaking" means the process of wine production. In Russian, the term "viticulture" refers to the cultivation of grapes, and "winemaking" refers to the process of making wine.

The word-formation aspect includes the process of forming new words and word combinations based on a given term. For example, in English one can find such words as "viticulturist" (grape grower) or

"oenologist" (winemaker). In Russian, one can form the words "виноградник" (place for growing grapes) or "винодельня" (wine production plant).

Thus, the term "viticulture and winemaking" contains both lexico-semantic and word-formation aspects reflecting the specificity of this branch of agriculture in English, French and Russian.

Viticulture and winemaking - these terms in both languages have similar lexico-semantic meanings and are related to the process of wine production. In French, the word "viticulture" is translated as "viticulture" and "winemaking" as "viniculture" or "enology". In Russian, the terms "viticulture" and "winemaking" are used respectively.

The vocabulary aspect of these terms is also interesting. For example, in French the term "enology" is derived from the Greek word "oinos" (wine), while "viniculture" is formed from the Latin word "vinum" (wine). In Russian, the word "viniculture" consists of the root "grape" and the suffix "-arstvo", denoting a type of activity or production.

Thus, the terms "viticulture" and "winemaking" in French and Russian have similar lexical-semantic meanings and are formed based on roots related to wine production. Translation of wine industry terminology can be problematic due to the specificity and complexity of terms related to wine production. Some of them have highly specialized meanings that may be incomprehensible to the average translator.

Additionally, several terms may be unique to a particular region or country, which also complicates the translation process. For example, the specific name of a grape variety or method of wine production may be difficult to translate accurately into another language. To solve this problem, it is advisable to consult wine experts and translators with experience in wine industry terms. It is also useful to use specialized dictionaries and glossaries to facilitate the translation process.

The results of the conducted research have shown that the majority of terminological units of "Viticulture and winemaking" are simple (homogeneous) words. In this regard, micro-nests and macro-nests were identified in English and Russian languages, as well as types of terminal chains were revealed, which is evidence of the high derivational potential of the terminological domain "Viticulture and Wine Industry".

Words constructed with prefixes.

agriculture-mots latins et sens (composants);

viticulture-prefixe

viniculture-prefixe

verjus-prefixe

vinifera-prefixe

porte-greffe- mots construits

vin blanc- mots construits

vin rouge- mots construits

boeuf bourguignon- mots construits

bouillie bordelaise-mots construits

terroir viticole- mots construits

grain blanc- mots construits

vin de table- mots construits

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STYLISTIC DIFFICULTIES OF TRANSLATION IN MODERN ENGLISH

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Аннотация: В статье освещаются стилистические трудности перевода в современном английском языке студентами вузов.

Ключевые слова: задачи в речи, стилистика, грамматическая передача лексического значения, иллюстрация, аллитерация.

Practically, stylistic devices in almost all languages are similar still though their functions in speech vary. Identical stylistic devices are used differently in languages; they perform different functions and have different value in stylistic system of their language what actually explains their necessity when transformations in translation occur. The stylistic changes are as necessary as grammatical or lexical ones. While applying some grammatical or lexical transformation in translation the translator is guided by principle of rendering grammatical or lexical meaning. When rendering stylistic meaning of the source text a translator should be guided by the same principle – to recreate in translation the same impression that might be left by the original text.

A translator should not try to preserve the stylistic device given in the sentence, but reproduce its function in the target language. We should not forget that almost all stylistic devices are multi functional. It is like when polysemantic words in English and Russian languages do not coincide in their lexical-semantic variants and the same is when differ the function of identical stylistic device. Thus when comparing stylistic devices we can easily identify complete correspondence, partial correspondence and even sometimes absence of correspondence and their functions.

To illustration it we can compare alliteration in the English and Russian languages. The function of alliteration coincides in both languages – in this function alliteration is one of the basic devices of poetic speech. However the usage of alliteration for pleasant sounding in prose is more characteristic for the English language, than for Russian. The second function of alliteration is logical. Alliteration emphasizes close relationship between components of the statement. Especially brightly alliteration shows the unity of an epithet with an attributed word. The third function of alliteration in English language – to attract attention of the reader – is widely used in the names of literary works, newspaper headings and often in articles. The use of alliteration is a convincing acknowledgement that various functions of stylistic devices in different languages do not always coincide in usage. Repetition as you know is a more widespread stylistic device in the English language, than in Russian. In some cases repetition as the stylistic device should be necessarily kept in translation, but for the difference in combinability and various semantic structures of polysemantic words or words of wide meaning in English and Russian languages the translator has to change and replace some of elements. The repetition is widely used with stylistic purposes in newspaper publicity. In these cases the translator is compelled to apply stylistic changes, make substitution or omission.

A policy of see no stagnation, hear no stagnation, speak no stagnation has had too long a run for our money.

Слишком долго мы расплачиваемся за политику пол-ного игнорирования и замалчивания застоя в нашей эко-номике.

The triple repetition of no stagnation has been omitted in translation, though is partially compensated by the use of synonymic pair at a word (stagnation), but neutralization is evident in translation. The neutralization happened when translating the phraseological unit to have (too long) a run for our money.

Among stylistic devices used in political literature rather frequent there are synonymic and alliterated pairs. The use of such pairs is traditional for all styles of the English language including business style as well. When translating official documents such pairs are frequently by one word. For example, the just and equitable treatment of all nations from UN Charter is given in Russian as справедливое отношение ко всем нациям, for in Russian there is no absolute synonym for the word just.

Metaphor is used in all emotionally – colored styles of speech. However in style of fiction the metaphor always carries original character, whereas in political literature the original metaphor is used rather seldom and basically – copied metaphors. Sometimes the difficulty of translation of metaphor consists in translating some word combination or a phraseological unit, which does not have figurative equivalent in Russian. Being purely linguistic and stylistic device – metonymy is used more and more in political literature, perhaps, even more than metaphor. Metonymy translation presents one of numerous problems for the use of metonymy significantly differs in English and Russian languages. Due to this fact the translator is often forced to go back to the primary meaning of a word, that is to the meaning that was firstly created by metonymy.

It is a widespread case of metonymy usage – substitution of concrete notion by an abstract one, which can not always be preserved.

"It (the flood) has hurl us a great deal," the Pakistan Prime Minister told correspondents last week as he toured the destruction in the flooded provinces. ("Newsweek") «Наводнение нанесло нам огромный ущерб»,—сказал корреспондентам премьер-министр Пакистана, на прош-лой неделе во время поездки по пострадавшим от навод-нения районам.

Concerning the translation of comparison as a stylistic device, the difficulties arise only if the words of English and Russian languages are various in the semantic structure. We have already considered in the chapter of lexical transformations the question of translation of such terms and now we would like to give the example of stylistic comparison. In order to preserve this playing comparison, the interpreters were forced to apply additional words.

We discussed above the importance of articles in translation and now we should mention once again that they can serve in stylistic purposes.

An expressiveness gets the definite article, before a indefinite pronoun one.

... this is the one way we can achieve success in elections.

...это единственный способ достигнуть победы на выборах.

The given synonyms compensate render the stress contained the original text.

There is another kind of stylistic transformation – actualization – which involves transition of something simple into something unusual, strange. It reveals potential expressiveness put in the lexical morphologic and syntactic means of a language.

Actualization of the passive form often occurs while translating political literature but it is not as colored as in the translations of fiction.

Now from everything that has been discussed above we can infer that the usage of some of stylistic devices in English is peculiar – and bears specific national character, therefore their direct translation in many instances is impossible. Moreover, the impression left by some of stylistic device maybe different in both languages, compare soft panic and тихаяпаника. It can be explained not only by national features of stylistic means and devices of some of the language but by the their multi functioning character also – that do not always coincide – as it was shown on the matter of alliteration. This is the main criteria causing the necessity of stylistic transformations that involve substitution and changes.

In conclusion therefore we should warn the future translators and interpreters that it is not important to classify the device itself but the point is to be able to realize their ongoing effect and to identify the purpose of their application in the translation they are working on.

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TARJIMADA FRAZELOGIZMLARNING EKVIVALENTINI BERISH USULI ("BASANTIY" ROMANI MISOLIDA)

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Tarjimashunoslik va xalqaro jurnalistika kafedrasida o'qituvchisi

Аннотация. В данной статье на примере романа индийского писателя Бхишама Сахни «Басантий» рассмотрены способы перевода на узбекский язык индийских фразеологических оборотов.

Ключевые слова: эквивалентность, фразеологизм, аналогия, транслитерация, коммуникация, трансформация.

Milliy madaniyati urf-odatlarini bilan farq qiluvchi o'ziga xos so'zlarni tarjimada berish tarjimonni jiddiy o'ylantiradigan jarayondir. Negaki, tarjimon buning uchun o'sha xalq milliy madaniyati va odatlaridan xabardor bo'lishi darkor. Bunday xos so'zlarni tarjima qilishning oson yo'li bu-so'zlarni transliteratsiya qilish, ya'ni so'z talaffuzini berish, saqlash maqsadga muvofiq. Bu usuldan kishi ismlarini, joy nomlarini, geografik nomlarni, lavozimlarni, tabaqalar nomlarini va shunga o'xshash atamalar transliteratsiya qilishda keng qo'llaniladi.

Tarjima qilinayotgan tilda frazeologizmlarni tarjima qilishning keyingi yo'li ma'noni yaqinlashtirib tarjima qilish, buni so'z analogiyasi bo'yicha tarjima qilish deb ham yuritish mumkin. Agar tarjima qilinayotgan tilda aslyatda qo'llangan so'zning muqobili bo'lmasa, tarjimada o'sha so'z ma'nosiga o'xshash va yaqin so'z tanlanadi. Masalan, Bhisham Sahniyning "Basantiy" asarida hind jamiyatiga tegishli bo'lgan tabaqalanish, ya'ni kastachilik tizimiga oid so'zlar qo'llaniladiki, tarjimon bu o'rinda to'g'ri yo'l tutib, ularni transliteratsiya orqali beradi.

Transliteratsiya-xalqlar turmush tushunchalarini aks ettiradigan xos so'zlarni tarjimada talqin etishning eng samarali usullari sifatida uning yordamchi aslyatining milliy xususiyati qisqa holda talqin etiladi.

"Basantiy" romanida अहीर (ahiir), राजस्थानी (rajasthani), राजपूत (rajput) पंचायत (panchayat), धोबी (dhobii) kabi tabaka vakillari ko'p uchraydi. Ushbu so'zlar tarjimon tomonidan transliteratsiya yo'li bilan aslyatdagidek o'qilishi bilan tarjima qilgan holda matnda izoh berib o'tiladi. Shu o'rinda aytish joyizki, अहीर (ahiir) ya'ni "Ahiir" Hindistondagi quyi kasta vakillari hisoblanib, "ot boqarlar" deb yuritiladi [1; 165]. Tarjimon bu so'zga "podachilar toifasi" deb matn ostida izohini berib o'tadi. अहीर (ahiir) lar ot boqish-boqmasligidan qat'iy nazar ularning avlod-ajdodlariga tegishli tabaqa vakillari nazarda tutiladi. राजपूत (rajput) tabaqasini esa "rojput" deya transliteratsiyada bergan. Ushbu jummalarni ham tarjimon matn izohida "Rojput" larni imoratsoz va g'isht teruvchilar toifasi deb izoh berib o'tgan. Asarda yana पंचायत (panchayat) so'zi ham ko'p qo'llanilgan. पंचायत (panchayat) so'zi "jamiyat, kengash" ma'nosini bildiradi [2; 11]. Asarda bu so'z mahalliy kengash ma'nosida kelganligiga qaramay, tarjimon buni transliteratsiya orqali "panchayat" deb tarjima qilgan. धोबी (dhobii) kir yuvuchilar toifasi (tabaqasi). राज-मस्त्री (raj mastrii) yoki sinonimi (राजगीर - raajgiir) uy quruvchi, g'isht teruvchilar toifasi. सरदार (sardaar) Sikh mazxabi vakillari ularni Hindistonda "Sardor" deyishadi.

Tarjima jarayonida asarda hindlarning bir nechta tangri xudolarining nomlari ham ko'p uchraydi: "Shiva", "Durga", "Hanuman", "Devi"[2,97], atamalarini izoh talab qiladi. Ushbu tushunchalarni anglamay turib, o'sha davr hind jamiyati haqida to'liq ma'lumotga ega bo'lish mumkin emas. Asarni tahlil qilish jarayonida quyidagi jummalarni ko'rib chiqamiz. भगवान तुम्हारा भला करें (१७०) (Tarjimasi: Hudoyo sizlarni hech narsadan kam qilmasin [2; 137]. Quyidagi misolda भगवान (bhagvaan) so'zi umumiy ma'noda "hudo" deb berilgan. Hindistonda turli din vakillari tilida bu so'z राम (Raam) yoki hindlarning boshqa ko'plab ilohlarining nomi bilan ham beriladi: कोई लड़का बाहर गता हुआ बरामदे में जा रहा था "में क्या करुं राम मुझे बूढ़ा मलि गया!" (६५) (Tarjimasi: Ayvonda bir yigit "Sangam" kinofilmidagi qizning hazil qo'shig'ini hirgoyi qilganicha o'tib borardi. [2,49] So'zma-so'z: Kimdir tashqarida qo'shiq hirgoyi qilib o'tib borardi: "Men nima qilay Ram, menga chol uchragan axir!" Yana bir jumlada: में क्या करुं राम मुझे बूढ़ा मलि गया! shaklda berilgan ram so'zi tushunarli, lekin tarjimon buni so'zma-so'z tarjima qilsa kitobxonga gap

qo'shiq haqida borayotganligini yetkaza olmagan bo'lardi. Shuning uchun tarjimon buni transformasiya usulida bergan. Negaki, bir so'z ikki xil guruh vakillari tomonidan turlicha qabul qilinishi mumkin. Misol uchun: diniy istiloh-tushunchalarda "parvardigor" tushunchasi o'zbek xalqi ongida yagona "Alloh" ma'nosi nazarda tutilsa, hindlarda esa ko'p xudolilik bo'lganligi sababli bu tushuncha ular ongida turlicha tasavvur uyg'otadi. Tarjimon shu o'rinda diniy istiloh-tushunchalarning o'rnini topib, har bir dinga tegishli so'zlarni qo'yib tarjima qilishiga katta mahorat talab etiladi.

Hindlarning milliy liboslarini anglatuvchi bir qator so'zlar tarjimasini ham transliterasiyada berilgan. **साडी** (saariy), so'zi barchaga ma'lumki, hind ayollarining milliy libosi sanaladi. Tarjimada bu "soriy" deb beriladi. **ओरहनी** (aorahni) lug'atda "ayollar yengsiz nimchasi" deb berilgan [1; 285]. Muallif tasvirlagan har bir libosning detallarigacha berilishining asosiy sababi asarni mutoola qilgan kitobxonga kengroq ma'lumot berilganligi seziladi. Bunda tikuvchining rang-barang liboslarni o'z qo'li bilan tayyorlaganligi, muallif tomonidan asar qahramoni bo'lajak to'yiga hozirlik ko'rayotganligini nazarda tutadi. Ma'lumki, hind xalqi to'ylarida sariq libos va rang baranglikning aks etishi ular uchun o'ziga xos marosimdir. asarda yana **बन्दी** (Bindi) so'zi ham keltirilgan. Bu so'zining bir nechta ma'nolari mavjud bo'lib, lug'atda berilgan birinchi ma'nosi "manglayga surtiladigan xol" dir, matoga nisbatan ishlatilgani bois, tarjimon ushbu so'zni kalkalash yo'li bilan muallif ishora qilgan fikrga "xol-xol" so'zini qo'llagan va muallif fikrini to'liq yetkazib bera olgan. Asarda yana **पंडित** (pandit) so'zi keltirilgan, tarjimon tomonidan transliterasiya usulida "hindularning mullasi", matnda izohi berib o'tilgan. **अंगरखा** (angrakha) ushbu libos o'zbeklarning yaktagiga o'xshagan, rang-barang shoyi matodan tikilgan chakmon bo'lib, asosan hindlarning to'ylarda kiyib yuradigan nikoh libosi hisoblanadi. **पगगड़** (paggar) salla bo'lib, uni asosan Rajasthan aholisi boshlariga salla shaklida o'rab oladigan bosh kiyimidir. Tarjimon ushbu salla sikh (bir umr soch-soqolini o'stirib yuradiganlar) erkaklari uzun sochlarining kokillarini berkitish maqsadida kiyib yurishlari haqida izohlab o'tgan. **टोपी** (topii) "do'ppi" bo'lib, bu ham o'zbeklarning do'ppisidan keskin farq qiladigan bosh kiyimi hisoblanadi. Buni asosan hind musulmonlari, yosh bolalar kiyishadi. **बुशशर्ट** (bushshart) erkaklarning yangi kalta ko'ylagidir **धोती** (dhotiy) erkaklarning belidan pastga qarab o'raladigan milliy kiyimi. [4,836] **कुरता** (kurta) ham erkaklarning ko'ylagi hisoblanadi [2; 15]. **पजामा** (pajamaa) shim, ishton. **अंगिया** (anghiya) ayollar sariy kiyimlarini ichidan kiyib yuradigan yangi kalta kofta. **घाघरा** (ghaaghra) ayollar yubkasi. **गाढ़ा** (gaarha)ning lug'atdagi ma'nosi "ip gazlamali mato" (хлопчатобумажная ткань) bo'lib, tarjimada "bo'z mato" deb to'g'ri o'g'irilgan. Bo'z mato-paxta mato bo'lib, qalin va pishiq gazlama turi hisoblanadi. **सलवार** (salvar) keng shalvar turi bo'lib, xuddi o'zbek ayollarining lozimiga o'xshash bo'ladi. Asar qahramonining bunday matodan shalvar kiyishiga sabab, asardagi qahramon tog'lik qishloqdan shaxarga ana shunday libos kiyib kelganligi haqida gap ketmoqda. Bilamizki tog'li rayonlar sovuq bo'lganligi sababli faqat qishloq ayollari ana shunday qalin matodan shalvar kiyib yuradilar. Asarda bundan tashqari milliy taqinchoqlari ham aks ettirilgan. **पजेब** (pazeb) oyoqqa taqib yuradigan ayollar taqinchog'ining bir turi bo'lib, ushbu so'zni leksik ma'nosiga e'tibor beradigan bo'lsak, fors tojik tilidan o'zlashma so'z hisoblanib, "oyoqqa bezak" ma'nosini bildiradi. Bu har ikki tilda ham shakl va ma'no jihatdan ekvivalent milliy xos so'z deya olamiz. Yana asarda **चाय की दुकान** (chay ki dukan) ya'ni tarjimon tomonidan "choyxona" jumlasini ham ko'p qo'llanilgan. Hindlarda ham choyxona so'ziga mos jumla **चाय घर, चायखाना** (chay ghar, chaykhana) sinonimlari bo'lib, bu o'rinda hindlardagi choyxona bilan o'zbeklarning choyxonasi o'rtasida farq bor. O'zbeklarning choyxonasida choy bilan birga yeguliklarni ham uchratish mumkin. Hindlar choyxonasida esa faqat choy yoki sut tortiq etiladi. Ulardagi yengil tamaddi, ovqatlanish joyi ya'ni **चाय पानी** (chay pani) o'zbeklarning choyxonasiga to'g'ri keladi. Bundan tashqari asarda **तंदूर** (tanduur) ya'ni "tandirxona" jumlasini ham kelgan bo'lib, buni o'zbek tandiri yoki nonvoyxonasi bilan Hindistondagi tandirlarining o'rtasida farqi katta ekanligini izohlab ketish muhim. Ularda ham yer tandiri bo'lishiga qaramay, nonlarining shakli va xajmiga ko'ra o'zbeklarnikidan katta farq qiladi.

Demak, yuqorida keltirib o'tilgan milliy o'ziga xos so'zlarning qiziqarli dalili shundaki, tarjimada keng tarqalgan aloqa nuqtalari mavjud ikki xalqning ikki tildagi tahlili turli xalqlar hayotning ko'plab sohalarida tez-tez yaqinlashishi va milliy urf-odatlar, milliy ma'naviyat, madaniy va ma'rifiy, an'analarni xalq ijodining yagona tuzilishiga, birlashtirishiga ham xizmat qilar ekan.

Iboralarni tarjimada adekvat talqin etish tarjima amaliyotining o'ta murakkab va shu bilan birga, juda mas'uliyatli masalalaridan hisoblanadi. Chunki ular nutqning badiiy-tasviriy vositalari sifatida fikrning oddiy, betaraf bayonidan ko'ra ko'proq turli-tuman uslubiy vazifalarni ifoda etishda ishtirok etadi.

III. TARJIMA VA TARJIMASHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MASALALARI SHU'BASI

Ko'pgina tadqiqotchilarning izlanishlaridan ma'lum bo'ldiki, iboralar tilning yaxlit lug'aviy birligi sifatida uni grammatik, semantik, funktsional, xatto sotsiologik jihatdan o'rganish mumkinligi ko'rsatiladi. Bundan tashqari, talay iboralar milliy xususiyatga egadirki, bu hol tarjimonlarga qiyinchiliklar tug'diradi. Har bir til ibora zahirasi tarkibida xalq hayotiga mansub ijtimoiy voqea xodisalar, axloqiy va ma'naviy-madaniy me'yorlar, ruhiy holatlar, diniy tasavvur, milliy an'ana va urf-odatlar o'z aksini topgan bo'ladi.

Tarjimada ekvivalentlikka erishish uchun elementar ma'nolarning yarmi berilishi ham maqsadga muvofiqdir. Tarjimada o'zak ma'nolar ko'payishi kuzatiladi. Agar tarjimada dastlabki matnning xolati o'zgarsa yoki boshqasiga o'zgartirilsa ma'noviy yig'indi ham predmetning dastlabki matnli holatiga qarab o'zgaradi. Ma'lumot mazmuni va tuzilmasiga tegishli bo'lgan semantik va sintaktik darajalarga, ya'ni matn kategoriyalariga kelsak, biz aynan ular nutqiy asarlarning ekvivalentligini belgilab berishini misollar orqali keltirib o'tdik. Milliy xos so'zlar tarjimon tomonidan transliterasiya usuli orqali matn ostida izohlab berilgan. Transliterasiya usulining sharti, asliyatdan ko'chirilgan so'zlarga izoh berishni unutmash kerak, aks holda kitobxonda tushunmovchilik tug'dirishi mumkin.

Tarjimada mutarjim mazmun va ma'hoga aynan mos tushuvchi so'zlarni qo'yib o'girish bilan tarjima ekvivalentligiga erishgan. Tarjimonning ma'naviy bilimlari qanchalik chuqur va keng bo'lsa, badiiy tarjima matnining ekvivalentlik darajasi shunchalik yuqori bo'lishi mumkinligiga amin bo'ldik.

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EFFICIENCY OF DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTION IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada til o'rgatishda differentsiallashtirilgan ta'lim tushunchasi o'rganilib, uning talabalarning o'quv jarayonida faolroq va samarali bo'lishiga yordam berishdagi roli ta'kidlangan. Unda differentsiallashning turli jihatlari, jumladan, uning ta'riflari, ahamiyati, strategiyalari, afzalliklari va kamchiliklari keltirilgan va misollar taqdim etilgan. Ta'kidlangan asosiy fikrlar content differensiyasi, jarayon differensiyasi, o'quv muhiti va talabalar mahsuloti differensiyasini o'z ichiga oladi.

Kalit so'zlar: differentsiatsiya, differentsiallashtirilgan ta'limning muhimligi, differentsiallashtirilgan ko'rsatmalarning turlari va misollari, differentsiallash tarixi, differentsiallashtirilgan ta'limning afzalliklari va kamchiliklari, tarkibni differentsiallashtirish, jarayonni differentsiallashtirish, o'quv muhiti va talabalar mahsulotini differentsiallashtirish.

Introduction. Each student possesses a distinct learning style, just like how every individual has a unique fingerprint. It is likely that students do not all comprehend a subject in the same manner or possess the same level of proficiency as they frequently have diverse backgrounds and varying prior experiences. It might be challenging to educate effectively while attempting to deliver same content and resources to all kind of students simultaneously. So, how can teachers optimize the delivery of their classes to ensure they reach all students in the class? In order to respond to this question, this article aims to provide a summary

of essential practices that enhance effective teaching for English Language Learners (ELLs). It sheds light on the definition, history, strategies, advantages and disadvantages of the differentiated instructions which is essential in language teaching.

Concept of differentiated instructions. Differentiated instruction is a pedagogical approach in which teachers optimize learning outcomes by tailoring instruction and evaluation to individual student characteristics. It entails utilizing a range of instructional methods to exceed the various learning demands of students. Since ELLs have a wide range of prior knowledge, linguistic abilities, and educational experiences, this method to English language teaching (ELT) is beneficial for them. In spite of their specific characteristics, learners are expected to master the same skills, concepts, and theories and it is quite difficult to support all students in their academic success.

Differentiated instruction—also referred to as differentiated learning or, simply, differentiation in the context of education—means tailoring instruction to each student's needs. As a result, the teacher responds to the requirements of the learners by giving them a variety of possibilities for learning. Furthermore, according to Tomlinson and Imbeau (2023), differentiating instruction entails a teacher seeing and comprehending the differences and similarities between each of his or her students before using this knowledge to organize instruction.

According to Hattie (2012), teaching is "demonstrating and assisting someone in learning how to do something, providing instructions, directing the study of something, providing skills, and leading to know or understand." It is advised that teachers modify their lessons in accordance with the demands of their learners to deliver it appropriately. It is based on the idea that every single student who enters a classroom brings with them a variety of cultural, linguistic, intellectual, and life experiences (Gibson and Hasbrouk, 2008). They also have various learning requirements, expectations, and styles. To put it another way, no two learners are likely to have the same skills, life experiences, or needs. Therefore, Dixon et al. (2014) emphasizes that differentiated education requires teachers to consider a variety of strategies when developing lessons, delivering them, and evaluating their students' progress.

The origin of differentiated instructions. The concept of differentiated education emerged when students of varying ages were taught by a single teacher in cramped one-room schoolhouses. Students' identical learning capacities were brought to light as the educational system transitioned to graded schools. However, the implementation of achievement assessments in 1912 led to the discovery of disparities in students' aptitudes across various educational tiers.

Congress enacted the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) in 1975 to ensure that students with disabilities have equal access to public education. To reach this learner group, several educators used tactics for differentiated instruction. Following its successful implementation, No Child Left Behind mandated in 2000 that schools implement more personalized and skill-based curricula. Research by Wilson (1994) highlights the critical need of incorporating diversity into classroom instruction. Among the several methods of training she tested, she discovered that lectures yielded the lowest retention rates (only 5 to 10% after 24 hours). The most effective methods for improving memory retention are taking part in group activities, practicing what you've learned after exposure, and teaching others.

Methods and instances of differentiated instruction. Tomlinson (2001) proposes four key areas—content, method, product, and learning environment—that teachers may use to differentiate education.

Content differentiation. Students who aren't well-versed in a subject may have to settle for less rigorous forms of retention and comprehension when given classwork. Learners who have a basic understanding could be required to implement and analyze the material, while students with advanced proficiency could be tasked with activities related to assessing and developing. Examples of differentiation activities include matching vocabulary words to their definitions.

- Read a section of text and respond to associated inquiries.
- Think about a situation where a story character goes through a different outcome.
- Make a difference in the narrative between facts and views.
- Find the author's position and provide evidence to back up their viewpoint.
- Make sure you outline the lesson in a PowerPoint presentation.

Process differentiation. Each learner possesses a favored style of learning, and effective differentiation

involves presenting the content in various styles: auditory, kinesthetic, visual, and verbal. This approach considers individual student needs for teacher support and enables learners to choose to work in small groups, pairs, or solo. While certain pupils may thrive with individualized attention from the instructor or the classroom assistance, others may excel independently. Educators may boost the learning process by providing tailored assistance according to each student's specific requirements. A few instances differentiating the process:

- Supply textbooks catering to both verbal and visual learners.
- Make audio books accessible to learners who study by hearing.
- Give kinesthetic learners the option to complete an online multimedia assignment.

Product differentiation. The outcome is the culmination of the student's work at the conclusion of the lesson, showcasing their proficiency of the subject matter. Assessment can take the form of examinations, projects, or various other endeavors. Instructors have the ability to allocate tasks to students that showcase their understanding of the subject matter based on their preferred learning method. Illustrations for differentiating the final product:

- Reading and writing: learners are tasked with writing a book report.
- Students with visual impairments make a graphical representation of the story.
- Students that possess Auditory Learning abilities deliver an oral report.
- Kinesthetic learners create a diorama to visually represent the story.

Differentiation of the learning environment.

There are physical and psychological aspects to an optimal learning environment. It is essential to have a flexible classroom design that can accommodate different types of work, including both individual and group projects. Teachers, from a psychological point of view, should use methods of classroom management that foster an environment that is both safe and supportive of student learning. Some examples of environmental differentiation:

- Organize learners into reading groups to engage in a debate regarding the task.
- Offer learners the choice to read autonomously if they desire.
- Establish tranquil environments free from interruptions.

Benefits and drawbacks of differentiated instruction. Implementing differentiation in the classroom offers benefits, but it also results in an increasing workload.

Ford (2009) argues that 70 percent of adolescent learners will benefit from differentiated instruction, regardless of their socioeconomic background—whether they come from middle- or upper-class households, low-income households, families living in poverty, or families with English language learners. Today, too many middle schools assign their kids a curriculum that requires them to study the same texts and do the same tasks. Unfortunately, rather than advancing them, this puts too many students behind. The diversity of the learners in the classroom should therefore be taken into account when formulating instructions to maximize learning for all students. King-Shaver and Hunter (2003) emphasized that the biggest error made by educators over the ages, has been treating every child as if they are different forms of the same person. As a result, teachers have felt justified in teaching all students the same material in the same methods.

In his study, Weselby (2014) emphasizes the efficacy of individualized education in addressing the needs of both high-achieving students and individuals with varying degrees of disability. Moreover, according to Wilson (1994), providing students with additional learning options increases their accountability for their personal development. In support of these assumptions, Smit and Humpert (2012) also state that classrooms where educators implement differentiated classes experience a corresponding increase in student engagement and a decrease in disciplinary issues. Hattie (2012) recommended using differentiated instruction in language classrooms due to the following reasons. First, differentiated education places an emphasis on each student's unique academic demands and learning style. Teachers can adjust the syllabus's material by changing their teaching strategies to better fit their students. Furthermore, it encourages critical thinking in children, provides them a chance to show what they have learned, and creates a feeling of equality for everyone despite any potential learning disabilities. Finally, differentiated learning gives students greater opportunities to excel academically.

However, the idea has drawbacks even though it can make learners study more efficiently since it can take a lot of time, and at its worst, it might even cause them to have lower expectations in the classroom.

Drew (2021) provides some worthy drawbacks of differentiation stating that it is costly in terms of both time and resources. Moreover, he highlights that it is unattainable to differentiate instruction for an entire class of pupils, as they all have different learning preferences. The 35 students in your class cannot have different lessons since there are not enough hours in the day, claims Drew (2021). The most surprising and innovative argument against this assumption was provided by Sisson (2022) who offers teachers to use Artificial Intelligence (AI) in differentiation to save time and resources as well. He shares with some teachers' experiences where they succeeded in utilizing this specific application which could differentiate the content, process and product in seconds according to the requirements provided in chat.

Conclusion. This article focuses on the term and the significance of the differentiated instruction in teaching language providing data about its various definitions, historical background, ways of implementation as well as its pros and cons. Having analyzed and synthesized every aspect of differentiated instruction, it can be concluded that this strategy is an effective 21st-century method of teaching languages in schools, colleges and universities. It aids teachers in considering how to teach in a way that is most effective while also assisting students in overcoming obstacles to learning whether it is about content, process, product or the learning environment differentiation. Despite some barriers that educators can face while implementing this approach, they ought to apply it skillfully finding some innovative ways to overcome.

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